

2nd INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
On
**Shaping Tomorrow: In Commerce, Management
& Humanities Learning**

STCMH-2024
5 & 6 December, 2024

Organized by

SRI BHAGAWAN MAHAVEER JAIN EVENING COLLEGE

(Affiliated to Bengaluru City University)

#91/2, Dr. A N Krishna Rao Road, V V Puram, Bangalore - 560 004

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Eminent Professionals and Guest of STCMH-2024

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(Affiliated to Bengaluru City University)
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2nd INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

on
“Shaping Tomorrow: in Commerce,
Management & Humanities Learning”
STCMH-2024

An IQAC initiative

5th & 6th December 2024

Venue: #91/2, Dr. A N Krishna Rao Road; V V Puram, Bangalore - 560 004

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Founder Chairman
JGI

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Vice President
JGI Group

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CRTA, Jain University

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Conference Convener
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Dr. Mandeep Kaur
Director
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ABOUT COLLEGE – SRI BHAGAWAN MAHAVEER JAIN EVENING COLLEGE, BENGALURU

Sri Bhagawan Mahaveer Jain Evening College is an esteemed educational institution known for its commitment to academic excellence, holistic development, and ethical values. Situated in Bengaluru, this college has been a beacon of knowledge and learning since its establishment.

Founded with the vision of imparting quality education rooted by Dr. Chenraj Roychand founder chairman JGI through Jain principles. SBMJEC strives to nurture students into well-rounded individuals who possess not only intellectual acumen but also a deep sense of social responsibility. The college offers a wide range of undergraduate and postgraduate programs across various disciplines, catering to the diverse interests and aspirations of its students.

At SBMJEC, education goes beyond textbooks and classrooms. The college emphasizes the importance of experiential learning, providing ample opportunities for students to engage in practical applications of their knowledge through internships, research projects, and community service initiatives. This holistic approach to education ensures that students not only acquire subject-specific expertise but also develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and interpersonal skills that are essential for success in the professional world.

The college boasts a highly qualified and dedicated faculty who are not only experts in their respective fields but also mentors and guides to the students. They foster an environment of intellectual curiosity, encouraging students to explore new ideas, challenge existing notions, and embrace lifelong learning.

Apart from academics, SBMJEC offers a vibrant campus life with a range of extracurricular activities, clubs, and student organizations. These provide students with opportunities to pursue their passions, develop leadership skills, and form lasting friendships.

With its state-of-the-art facilities, well-stocked library, advanced laboratories, and modern infrastructure, SBMJEC provides an ideal environment for students to thrive academically, intellectually, and personally.

SBMJEC stands as a prestigious institution that instils a sense of purpose, integrity, and excellence in its students. It equips them with the knowledge, skills, and values necessary to succeed in their chosen fields and make a positive impact on society.

ABOUT SBMJEC AND COURSES OFFERED

Sri Bhagawan Mahaveer Jain Evening College (SBMJEC), a premier institution under Jain Group of Institutions (JGI), is dedicated to nurturing academic excellence and holistic development. With a strong emphasis on innovation, skill enhancement, and value-based education, SBMJEC stands as a beacon of learning for aspiring professionals.

Courses Offered:

1. **Bachelor of Commerce (B.Com):**

Designed to provide a robust foundation in commerce, this program equips students with essential knowledge in accounting, finance, taxation, and business law. With a blend of theoretical and practical learning, the B.Com course prepares students for diverse career opportunities in commerce and finance.

2. **Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA):**

The BBA program focuses on developing leadership, strategic thinking, and managerial skills. With a dynamic curriculum that incorporates the latest industry trends, the course aims to create future business leaders capable of navigating the global marketplace.

3. **Bachelor of Computer Application (BCA)**

The BCA program is designed to equip students with essential technical skills and a solid foundation in computer science and applications. With a curriculum that blends theoretical knowledge and practical experience, the course emphasizes programming, software development, data management, and emerging technologies. The BCA program aims to produce innovative IT professionals capable of adapting to the ever-evolving technology landscape and meeting the demands of the global digital economy.

4. **Master of Commerce (M.Com)**

The M.Com program offers an advanced understanding of commerce and management. It caters to students aiming to specialize in finance, accounting, and research, fostering analytical and problem-solving skills to excel in academia and the corporate world.

At SBMJEC, education transcends classroom boundaries, integrating academic rigor with co-curricular activities, fostering entrepreneurship, and instilling ethical and social values. The institution's commitment to excellence ensures that its graduates are well-equipped to contribute meaningfully to their respective fields and society at large.

About the 2nd International Conference on Shaping Tomorrow in Commerce, Management, and Humanities (STCMH-2024)

The 2nd **International Conference on Shaping Tomorrow: In Commerce, Management, and Humanities Learning (STCMH-2024)**, organized by Sri Bhagawan Mahaveer Jain Evening College (SBMJEC), will be held on **5th and 6th December 2024**. This conference aims to provide a vibrant platform for academicians, researchers, industry experts, and students to engage in meaningful discussions and exchange ideas on emerging trends and challenges in commerce, management, and humanities.

With a focus on interdisciplinary learning and innovation, STCMH-2024 aspires to foster collaboration and inspire solutions that will shape the future. The event includes keynote speeches, paper presentations, and interactive sessions, offering valuable insights for both academia and industry.

The theme of **STCMH-2024**, *Shaping Tomorrow in Commerce, Management, and Humanities Learning*, reflects the urgent need to address the evolving challenges and opportunities in these interconnected disciplines. In an era defined by technological advancements, globalization, and societal transformation, the conference aims to explore innovative ideas, strategies, and practices that can shape a sustainable and inclusive future.

This theme emphasizes the importance of interdisciplinary approaches to problem-solving, bridging the gap between traditional knowledge systems and contemporary methodologies. It calls for leveraging innovation, critical thinking, and collaboration to address pressing issues such as economic resilience, organizational adaptability, and the humanistic dimensions of global development.

By bringing together thought leaders, researchers, and practitioners, the conference aspires to create actionable insights and foster meaningful dialogue, contributing to a brighter tomorrow for education, business, and society at large.

Message from the Chairman & Founder

Dr. Chenraj Roychand
JGI – Jain Group of Institutions

It gives me immense pleasure to extend my heartfelt congratulations to Sri Bhagawan Mahaveer Jain Evening College for organizing the **2nd International Conference on "Shaping Tomorrow: In Commerce, Management & Humanities Learning" (STCMH-2024)**.

This conference is a testament to the institution's commitment to fostering intellectual growth and addressing the evolving paradigms in commerce, management, and humanities. By bringing together scholars, researchers, and practitioners from diverse fields, the event aims to spark meaningful dialogue, inspire innovative ideas, and shape a future driven by knowledge and collaboration.

As a proud member of the JGI family, I believe that platforms like these are instrumental in nurturing academic excellence and contributing to global progress. I commend the organizers for their efforts and wish the conference immense success in achieving its objectives.

Let this gathering be a source of inspiration and a stepping stone towards shaping a brighter tomorrow.

Warm regards,

Dr. Chenraj Roychand

Chairman & Founder

JGI – Jain Group of Institutions

Message from the

Mr. Ravindra Bhandari

Vice President, Jain Group of Institution, JGI

I am delighted to extend my warm greetings to all participants, organizers, and distinguished guests of the **2nd International Conference on "Shaping Tomorrow: In Commerce, Management & Humanities Learning" (STCMH-2024)**, hosted by Sri Bhagawan Mahaveer Jain Evening College, Bengaluru.

This conference stands as a remarkable initiative, bringing together thought leaders, academicians, and practitioners to engage in meaningful discourse on shaping the future through innovation and knowledge. It is through such collaborative platforms that we can explore new ideas, challenge conventional boundaries, and drive progress across commerce, management, and humanities.

I commend the organizing team for their dedication and effort in making this event a reality and wish the conference immense success in achieving its vision. May STCMH-2024 inspire impactful learning and create lasting contributions to the academic and professional world.

Warm regards,

Mr. Ravindra Bhandari

Vice President, JGI

Message from

Dr. S. Srikanta Swamy
Director, Centre for Researcher Training &
Administration (CRTA),
JAIN (Deemed-to-be-University),
Bengaluru, Karnataka

It is my privilege to address the **2nd International Conference on "Shaping Tomorrow: In Commerce, Management & Humanities Learning" (STCMH-2024)**, organized by Sri Bhagawan Mahaveer Jain Evening College, Bengaluru.

This conference serves as a vital platform for fostering intellectual exchange and advancing interdisciplinary research. By bringing together scholars, practitioners, and students, it encourages the exploration of innovative ideas and collaborative solutions to address the challenges and opportunities of tomorrow.

I applaud the organizers for their vision and dedication in creating this opportunity for academic enrichment and dialogue. My best wishes to all participants for a productive and insightful conference that will contribute significantly to the fields of commerce, management, and humanities.

Warm regards,

Dr. S. Srikanta Swamy

Director, Centre for Researcher Training & Administration (CRTA), JAIN (Deemed - to - be - University), Bengaluru, Karnataka

Message from
Sri. Vishal Chenraj
Director, Strategy and Development, JGI

I am pleased to extend my warm regards to all participants, speakers, and organizers of the **2nd International Conference on "Shaping Tomorrow: In Commerce, Management & Humanities Learning" (STCMH-2024)**, hosted by Sri Bhagawan Mahaveer Jain Evening College, Bengaluru.

This conference is a commendable initiative that underscores the importance of interdisciplinary learning and strategic thinking in addressing global challenges. By bringing together diverse perspectives, it offers a platform to drive innovation, collaboration, and meaningful contributions to the academic and professional realms.

I congratulate the organizing team for their efforts and vision in curating such a transformative event. Best wishes for a successful and enriching conference that will inspire all attendees to shape a brighter tomorrow.

Warm regards,

Mr. Vishal Jain

Director, Strategy and Development, JGI

Message from the Principal

Dr. K.M. Mahesh

**Principal, SBM Jain Evening College, Bengaluru
Ex-Syndicate Member, Bengaluru City University**

It is with great pride and enthusiasm that I welcome you all to the **2nd International Conference on "Shaping Tomorrow: In Commerce, Management & Humanities Learning" (STCMH-2024)**, organized by Sri Bhagawan Mahaveer Jain Evening College, Bengaluru.

This conference provides a dynamic platform to explore emerging trends and innovations across commerce, management, and humanities. It brings together academic minds and industry leaders to share insights, exchange ideas, and pave the way for impactful research and practices that will shape the future.

I extend my heartfelt gratitude to the organizers, participants, and contributors who have made this event possible. I am confident that STCMH-2024 will foster meaningful discussions, inspire new perspectives, and serve as a beacon of academic excellence.

Best wishes for a fruitful and successful conference!

Warm regards,

Dr. K.M. Mahesh

Principal, SBM Jain Evening College

Ex-Syndicate Member, Bengaluru City University

Message from

Dr. Lakshman. K

**Associate Professor and Head
Department of Management, SBMJEC
Conference Convener. STCMH-2024**

It is with great pride and enthusiasm that I present the proceedings of the **International Conference on Shaping Tomorrow: In Commerce, Management, and Humanities Learning (STCMH-2024)**, held on the **5th and 6th of December 2024**, at Sri Bhagawan Mahaveer Jain Evening College (SBMJEC).

The theme, *Shaping Tomorrow in Commerce, Management, and Humanities Learning*, reflects our commitment to exploring innovative ideas and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration to address contemporary challenges. This conference has brought together a diverse group of scholars, researchers, and practitioners from around the world to share knowledge, exchange insights, and develop actionable strategies for shaping a sustainable and inclusive future.

I am deeply grateful to all the contributors whose scholarly work has enriched these proceedings, showcasing cutting-edge research and thought leadership. My heartfelt thanks go to the organizing committee, reviewers, keynote speakers, and participants for their invaluable support and dedication, which have been instrumental in the success of this event.

These proceedings stand as a testament to the intellectual rigor and collaborative spirit that define STCMH-2024. I hope they serve as a valuable resource for academics and professional's alike, inspiring further research and innovation in the fields of commerce, management, and humanities.

Warm regards

Dr. Lakshman. K

Conference Convener
Associate Professor & Head
Department of Management-SBMJEC

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ROLE OF FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF INDIA

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Abstract: Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) has emerged as a pivotal driver in India's economic development trajectory. This paper explores the multifaceted impact of FDI on key indicators of economic growth, such as GDP expansion, employment generation, technology transfer, and industrial productivity. Examining the trends and patterns of FDI inflows into India over the past decades, the study investigates how FDI contributes to the modernization of industries and the enhancement of infrastructure. Additionally, it delves into the policy frameworks and regulatory measures that have shaped India's FDI landscape. The findings highlight the positive correlation between FDI and economic development, emphasizing the need for strategic policies to attract and maximize the benefits of foreign investments. The paper concludes by proposing recommendations for policymakers to optimize the role of FDI in fostering sustained and inclusive economic growth in India.

Background: The primary purpose of this research is to examine and understand the intricate relationship between Foreign Direct Investment and the economic development of India. By identifying the mechanisms through which FDI contributes to economic growth, the study aims to provide valuable insights for policymakers, investors, and researchers interested in fostering sustainable development in the Indian context.

Design/Methodology: This research adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative analysis of economic indicators with qualitative assessments of policy frameworks. Utilizing historical FDI data, econometric models are employed to assess the statistical significance of FDI on economic development. Additionally, case studies and in-depth interviews with key stakeholders contribute qualitative insights into the policy landscape and the practical implications of FDI in specific sectors.

Aims: This research adds original contributions to the literature by offering a comprehensive analysis of the multifaceted impact of FDI on India's economic development. The combination of quantitative and qualitative methodologies provides a holistic understanding of the dynamics involved, offering valuable insights for policymakers, investors, and scholars.

Type of Research: This research is a mixed-methods study, incorporating quantitative analysis of economic indicators and qualitative assessments of policy frameworks. It falls within the domain of applied economic research, focusing on the practical implications of FDI on the economic development of India.

Results and Conclusion: The research findings reveal a positive and significant impact of FDI on India's economic development. Increased FDI inflows are associated with higher GDP growth rates, improved employment opportunities, technology spillovers, and enhanced industrial productivity. The study also identifies key policy measures that have facilitated a conducive environment for FDI, contributing to the overall economic advancement of the country.

Key Words: Foreign Direct Investment, Economic Development, GDP Growth, Employment, Technology Transfer, Industrial Productivity, Policy Frameworks, Mixed-Methods Research.

Introduction Of Foreign Direct Investment (Fdi):

Any investment made into businesses or other assets situated in another nation by individuals, organisations, or governments is known as foreign direct investment. Attributable to a considerable level of ownership or influence in the overseas firm, this cash flow is unique. FDI is vital to both the modernization of economies and the encouragement of global expansion and advancement. Gaining access to new markets, resources, and technologies is the primary goal of FDI, which also helps the economy of the host nation. By bringing in cutting-edge technology, managerial know-how, and experience, investments foster global commerce, employment development,

and knowledge transfer. FDI contributes to a country's overall capital creation by bridging the gap between domestic savings and investment.

Market Size:

Between 2000 and 2021–2022, India had a notable 20 times increase in FDI. The amount of FDI that entered India altogether between April 2000 and June 2022, totalling US\$ 871.01 billion, was a significant achievement for the country, according to the Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade (DPIIT). By taking steps to loosen corporate rules and promote FDI, the Indian government may be to blame for this development.

January and March 2022, FDI into India reached a total of US\$22.03 billion, while FDI equity inflow reached US\$15.59 billion during the same time frame. The biggest FDI equity investment, totalling US\$14.46 billion between April 2021 and March 2022, was made in the computer software and hardware industry. Following trade (\$6.99 billion) and the automotive industry (\$6.99 billion), building activities came in third with \$3.37 billion. With investments totalling US\$ 15.87 billion, Singapore overtook the US (\$10.54 billion), Mauritius (\$9.39 billion), and the Netherlands (\$4.62 billion) as the top sources of 'FDI inflows' into India. With a total of US\$22.07 billion, Karnataka attracted the most foreign direct investment of any state. Following Karnataka, Maharashtra received FDI of US\$15.43 billion, followed by US\$8.18 billion for Delhi, US\$2.70 billion for Gujarat, and US\$2.79 billion for Haryana.

Literature Review

Sl.No	Focus Area	Author & Year
1	Most research articles focused on FDI & government initiatives to encourage FDI in India. The importance of FDI for a country's growth and development, particularly when there is a demand for indigenous capital. India has the aptitude to attract additional FDI. FDI can be used to bridge the opening between domestic savings and investment. Consequently, FDI has a momentous influence on India's economic growth.	Rudresha C E et&al 2023
2	A study examined the important determinants influencing foreign investment in India. The research indicated that the regulatory environment and party-political stability are the main cause's inflows of FDI. Initiatives to make conducting business simpler, and relaxation of FDI restrictions, have also helped the country's climate. The statements that governments should focus on issues such as political stability, friendlier regulations, improved infrastructure, and flexible labour laws provide crucial data for those working to improve India's business climate in order to helping hand FDI arrivals and support sustained economic growth.	Smitha Kothari et&al 2023
3	The aims of the research include an appraisal of FDI as fit as an assessment relationship between it and the gross domestic product and the foreign currency reserve. From 2011-12 through 2020-2021, the paper examines the impression of FDI on leveraging extra information. The study shows tells that growing and that FDI and GDP are highly connected, but not with other currency reserves.	Pallavi Goyal, et&al 2022
4	The effect of FDI on Indian economic development from 1991 to 2020 is explored in this paper. According to empirical research it is a significant contributor to economic growth, although the consequences vary. The purpose of the research is to determine the long-term and shortterm effects of FDI on growth. Results Long and medium-term it has a noteworthy beneficial influence on inflation, both directly and through its fusion with human capital.	Niharika Mehta et&al 2022

5	The research above, which used data from 2000-01 to 2020-21 to assess trends in FDI inflow and inflow by nation and sector in India, showed that recent changes to the FDI regulatory framework have reduced obstacles for foreign investors, resulting in an increase in FDI inflow.	Velu Suresh Kumar 2021
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Research Gap:

Numerous studies were carried out, according to a study of the research, in order to show a connection between FDI and development. Substantial FDI-related issues have also been uncovered by a number of study articles. Think about how important FDI has been for India's economic growth. In addition, it is crucial to analyse inflows by country and regulate how they remain alienated across various Indian firms.

Statement Of The Problem:

Foreign Direct Investment has played a crucial role in shaping the Indian economy. Despite India liberalized policies and various incentives, the country still lags behind its peers in attracting FDI. Therefore, the problem at hand is to identify the key factors that influence FDI inflows in India and to assess the impact of FDI on the Indian economy. This study aims to provide insights into the strategies and policies that can be adopted to attract more FDI and boost economic growth in India.

Objectives:

1. To understand the role of FDI on Economic Development.
2. To ascertain the sector wise distribution inflows of FDI in India.
3. To analyse the country wise flow of FDI into India.

Research Methodology:

- **Type of Research:** Analytical Research
- **Data:** Data of FDI equity inflows from the year 2018-2019 to 2022-2023 (April to March).
- **Data Collection:** This study is based on secondary data. This database is constructed by pooling information and data from various reliable sources like DIPP (Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion), Ministry of Commerce and Industry, and Reserve Bank of India, articles, Journals, News Papers, etc have also been referred. graphs and tables have also been used wherever required to depict statistical data from FDI during the study period.

Conceptual background

FDI in India inflows over the last ten years

The table 1 below provides the FDI in India inflows over the past decade, with data sourced from UNCTAD.

Financial year (April-March)	Total FDI inflow (US \$)	% of GDP
2013	28.19B	1.52%
2014	34.58B	1.70%
2015	44.06B	2.09%

2016	44.48B	1.94%
2017	39.90B	1.51%
2018	42.15B	1.56%
2019	50.55B	1.78%
2020	64.07B	2.41%
2021	44.73B	1.42%
2022	49.35B	1.47%

<https://www.forbesindia.com/article/explainers/fdi-in-india-inflows/89609/1>

Role Of Foreign Direct Investment On Economic Development:

The economic growth of nations is significantly influenced the Thirteen significant ways that FDI boosts economic growths are listed below:

- **Capital Inflow:** FDI bridges the investment gap and promotes economic growth by bringing in significant cash from overseas investors.
- **Technology Transfer:** FDI boosts the host nation productivity, efficiency, and competitiveness by introducing cutting-edge technology, knowledge, and skills.
- **Job Creation:** The establishment of new businesses, their creation, and those they are currently in existence all made possible by FDI, which also decreases unemployment and increases job opportunities.
- **Human Capital Development:** FDI encourages host countries to participate educational and employment initiatives that raise the skill level of the local work force so as to live up to the demands of foreign investors.
- **Export Promotion:** Increased export-oriented output higher foreign exchange gains, and an improved trade balance are all benefits of FDI.
- **Infrastructure Development:** Infrastructure improvement is frequently required by FDI which benefits both foreign and native businesses and promotes overall economic growth.
- **Market Access:** Through existing foreign networks, distribution channels, and marketing know-how FDI offers access to global markets.
- **Economic Linkages:** By establishing connections between international and domestic businesses FDI fosters knowledge transfer, encourages innovation, and propels the expansion of domestic industries.
- **Financial Stability:** By reducing reliance on erratic sources of funding FDI offers long-term development initiatives a reliable and sustainable source of funding.
- **Government Revenue:** The host nation government can invest the tax income generated by FDI in purchasing public goods and services.
- **Improved Business Environment:** To attract investment that benefits local businesses and strengthens the economy overall, countries undertake adjustments to improve the business climate.
- **Entrepreneurial Development:** FDI promotes innovation and entrepreneurship by supporting the establishment of local start-ups and spin-off enterprises.
- **Knowledge and Skill Spill over's:** FDI encourages the transfer of knowledge, abilities, and managerial know-how, which builds local capacity and raises overall productivity and competitiveness.

Analysis of Data

Sectors Indicating Highest Fdi Inflows:

Table 2 Showing ‘Sectors Indicating Highest FDI Inflows’

SL. NO	Sectors	“Cumulative FDI Inflows” (April 2018-2019 to March 2022-2023) (Rs Crores)	Percentage	Rank
1	Services	279897	20.40	II
2	Computer Software and Hardware	476318	34.71	I
3	Telecommunications	62610	4.56	VI
4	Trading	154557	11.26	III
5	Automobile Industry	116985	8.53	V
6	Construction (Infrastructure) Activities	126443	9.21	IV
7	Construction Development	11098	0.80	X
8	Drugs and Pharmaceuticals	43713	3.18	IX
9	Chemicals Other than Fertilizers	49341	3.60	VIII
10	Metallurgical Industries	51109	3.72	VII
Total		1372071	100	

Source: dpiit.gov.in.

Analysis:

The sectors with the maximum FDI inflows are depicted in the table above. The peak FDI inflow was noted by the Computer Software and Hardware sector-34.71%, which was followed by the Services sector-20.40%, Trading sector-11.26%, Construction, Infrastructure Activities sector-9.21%, Automobile Industry sector-8.53%, Telecommunications sector-4.56%, Metallurgical Industries sector-3.72%, Chemicals Other Than Fertilisers sector-3.60%, Drugs and Pharmaceuticals sector-3.18%, and Construction development sectors-0.80%.

Graph 1 Showing Sectors Indicating Highest FDI Inflows

Interpretation:

The sectors garnering the most FDI inflows are represented in the graph above. The Computer Software and Hardware sector, 34.71%. received the most investments obtainable of the ten-spot sectors, followed by the Services sectors 20.40%, Trading sectors 11.26%, Construction (Infrastructure) Activities sectors 9.21%, Automobile Industry sectors 8.53, Telecommunications sectors 4.56%, Metallurgical Industries sectors 3.72%, Chemicals (Other than Fertilisers) sectors 3.60%, Drugs and Pharmaceuticals sectors 3.18%, and Construction Develop sectors 3.72%.

Due to political stability, a complicated legal and regulatory environment, a lack of infrastructure, a high interest rate, and growing environmental sustainability concerns, the construction development industry attracted the least number of investments.

Country Wise Ranking Of Fdi Inflows”:

Table 3 Showing Country wise Ranking of FDI Inflows

SL. NO	Country	“Cumulative FDI Inflows” (April 2018-2019 to March 2022-2023) (Rs. in Crores)	Percentage	Rank
1	Mauritius	275424	16.58	III
2	Singapore	600813	36.16	I
3	USA	281877	16.96	II
4	Netherland	148234	8.92	IV

5	Japan	83286	5.01	VI
6	United Kingdom	61426	3.70	VIII
7	UAE	74005	4.45	VII
8	Cayman Islands	88775	5.34	V
9	Germany	24402	1.47	IX
10	Cyprus	23341	1.40	X
Total		1661583	100	

Source: dpiit.gov.in.

Analysis:

The proportion of major investment nations' FDI inflows is made known in the ensuing table. Conferring to the aforementioned data, the top two countries are Singapore-36.16% and the United States-16.96%. The next ten countries are: Mauritius (16.58%), the Netherlands-8.92%, the Cayman Islands-5.34%, Japan-5.01, the United Arab Emirates-4.45%, the United Kingdom-3.70%, Germany-1.47%, and Cyprus-1.40%.

Graph 2 Showing Country wise Ranking of ‘FDI Inflows’

Interpretation:

The entire sum of main contributing country's FDI inflows featured in the graph above. Singapore is the top investment nation in India amongst the topmost ten nations, tailed by the United States, (16.96%) and Singapore, (36.16%). due of the country's stable political climate, solid rule of law, robust infrastructure, cutting-edge telecommunications networks, and highly trained and educated labour force.

The two nations with the lowest investments in India are Germany and Cyprus. due to a lack of competent workforce, a high level of corruption, a lack of transparency, an unattractive business climate, poor infrastructure, and wholly of the aforementioned factors.

Findings:

The services sector will get 24.96% of FDI inflows during the 2022–2023 fiscal year. It represents the highest percentage of FDI inflow during the preceding five years. The percentage of FDI inflows for the year 2020–2021 is 40.80% for the computer software and hardware sector. It shows the largest share of FDI inflow during the preceding five years. The telecommunications sector received 49.42% of FDI inflows during the 2019–2020 fiscal year. It denotes the biggest percentage of total FDI inflow during the preceding five years. The portion of FDI inflows for 2022–2023 is 24.62% of the trading sector. It represents the highest percentage of FDI inflow during the preceding five years. The percent of FDI inflows for the automotive industry sector in 2021–2022 is 44.12%. It represents the highest percentage of FDI inflow during the preceding five years. The sector of construction (infrastructure) activities will receive 46.06% of all FDI inflows for the 2020–2021 fiscal year. It denotes the highest percentage of FDI inflow during the preceding five years. The construction and development sector will get 39.20% of FDI inflows for the 2019–2020 fiscal year. It denotes the highest possible rate of FDI inflow during the preceding five years. The ratio of FDI inflows for the drugs and pharmaceuticals sector in 2022–2023 is 38.10%. It represents the most level of FDI inflow during the preceding five years. The Chemicals (other than Fertilisers) Sector would get 29.71% of FDI inflows for the fiscal year 2022-2023. It represents a large volume of FDI inflow during the preceding five years. Metallurgical industries sector will get 32.84% of FDI inflows during the fiscal year 2021–2022. It represents the most sum of FDI inflow during the preceding five years.

Mauritius Country's percentage of FDI inflows for the 2021–2022 fiscal year is 25.39%. It represents the highest percentage of FDI inflow during the preceding five years. Singapore's share of foreign direct investment inflows for the fiscal year 2022–2023 is 22.86%. It represents the highest percentage of FDI inflow during the preceding five years. The percentage of FDI inflows into the United States of America (USA) country for the 2020–2021 fiscal year is 36.36%. It represents the highest percentage of FDI inflow during the preceding five years. The Netherlands Country's share of FDI inflows for the 2019–2020 fiscal year is 31.08%. It represents the highest percentage of FDI inflow during the preceding five years. Japan's share of foreign direct investment inflows for the 2019–2020 fiscal year is 27.34%. It represents the highest percentage of FDI inflow during the preceding five years. The overall proportion of FDI inflows into the United Kingdom (UK) country for the 2020–2021 fiscal year is 25.65%. It represents the highest percentage of FDI inflow during the preceding five years. The United Arab Emirates (UAE) country will get 42.22% of all FDI inflows for the 2020–2021 fiscal year. It represents the highest percentage of FDI inflow during the preceding five years. The country of the Cayman Islands will get 31.97% of FDI inflows during the 2021–2022 fiscal year. It represents the highest percentage of FDI inflow during the preceding five years. Germany's share of foreign direct investment inflows for the 2018–2019 fiscal year is 25.35%. It represents the highest percentage of FDI inflow during the previous five years. Cyprus will get 43.63% of all FDI inflows for the fiscal year 2022-2023. The highest percentage of FDI inflow during the previous five years is shown. The “Computer Software and Hardware industry” (34.71%) is the top sector out of ten. It shows that the most investments were made in this industry “Singapore” nation (36.16%) is top out of ten countries. It suggests that this nation is investing more in India.

Conclusion:

This research explores the foreign direct investments function in India's economic growth, emphasising its significant contributions to a range of industries, including the making of jobs, the sharing of knowledge, the promotion of exports, and the building of infrastructure.

In addition to supporting technical advancement and creativity, FDI has successfully filled the vacuum left by a lack of domestic investment. As a result, additional positions have been added, unemployment rates have dropped, and living standards have increased.

The mix of foreign money has made it easier for Indian businesses to incorporate cutting-edge technology, managerial know-how, and access to global markets, boosting competitiveness, increasing exports, and improving trade balances and foreign reserves.

The information and skill transfer enabled by this influx has also improved domestic enterprises productivity, efficiency, and competitiveness.

Despite these advantages, policymakers must deftly navigate these complexities and strike a balance between attracting FDI and protecting domestic interests. These challenges include economic dependency, detrimental effects on local industries, and susceptibility to global economic fluctuations.

India's path to sustainable economic growth and increased global economic importance is in developing well-balanced laws and regulations to attract foreign investments.

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EXPLORING TRENDS IN QR CODE PAYMENT IN MAURITIUS : A CONCEPTUAL PERSPECTIVE

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The objective of this paper is to conceptually analyze the key determinants influencing Quick Response (QR) payment adoption in Mauritius from a consumer perspective. QR payment is a digital transaction method where users scan a QR code with their smartphones to complete payments. Survey questionnaires will be distributed to approximately 1,000 QR users in Mauritius, utilizing a convenience sampling method. Data collected will be analyzed using Partial Least Squares (PLS) structural equation modeling to examine the significance of interactions between the proposed dependent and independent variables. The findings are expected to provide valuable insights for firms, helping them to better understand consumer needs and optimize QR code systems to meet customer expectations. This research will also offer essential data for the industry, aiding in identifying consumer preferences within the context of a small island developing state. Furthermore, the empirical insights from this study will contribute to theory building in the field of digital payment systems. By addressing barriers and leveraging key drivers, stakeholders can work towards increasing QR payment adoption and fostering a more digitally inclusive environment in Mauritius.

Keywords : QR Payment Adoption, Consumer Behavior, Structural Equation Modeling, Mauritius

Introduction

A QR code is a two-dimensional barcode that stores data in a matrix of black and white squares. Developed by Denso Wave in 1994, QR codes can be scanned with smartphones to quickly access digital content or perform actions. QR codes offer high data capacity, supporting up to 7,089 characters, and are valued for their fast readability and resilience to damage (Wave, 1994; Hau et al. 2013). Their versatility and ease of use have led to widespread adoption across various industries, including marketing, logistics, and payments.

QR payment is a financial transaction method where users scan a QR code with their smartphone to complete payments. This method links the QR code to a payment gateway, facilitating secure and swift transactions without the need for physical cards or cash (Denso Wave, 1994; Hau et al. 2013). QR payments enhance convenience in both retail and online settings (Zhang et al. 2017) and are often integrated into mobile apps to streamline the payment process (Lou et al. 2017).

The global financial landscape has increasingly embraced digital payment methods, with QR codes emerging as a pivotal technology in this shift (Gao et al. 2021). Initially developed by Denso Wave in 1994 for inventory management, QR codes have evolved to facilitate quick, contactless financial transactions, becoming integral to digital payments. Their widespread adoption is driven by their ability to streamline payment processes and enhance user convenience. In recent years, QR code payments have emerged as a pivotal technology in the evolution of digital transactions, facilitating seamless and contactless payments via mobile devices (Hajazi et al. 2021). This innovation has garnered widespread adoption in various sectors due to its ability to offer convenience, efficiency, and heightened security for both consumers and businesses (Zhang et al. 2020).

In Mauritius, QR payment systems like Blink by Emtel, MCB Juice, My.T Money, and POP by Bank One have been introduced quite recently, reflecting global trends. However, despite these advancements, QR payment adoption among Mauritian consumers remains relatively low, with approximately only 30% engagement by 2024 (MCB Ltd, 2024; Bank of Mauritius, 2024). This slower adoption rate compared to global benchmarks highlights a need to understand customer perspectives and barriers to widespread usage.

Despite the global success of QR payment systems and their introduction by major financial institutions in Mauritius, the adoption rate among local consumers remains significantly low, at around 30%. This figure is notably lower compared to adoption rates in technologically advanced regions, suggesting the presence of underlying barriers.

Understanding these factors is essential for addressing customer concerns and enhancing the adoption of QR payment systems. This study aims to investigate these barriers comprehensively, providing actionable insights that could improve the adoption rates and effectiveness of QR payments in Mauritius, ultimately supporting economic growth and financial inclusion aligning with SDG 8. Financial inclusion is a key aspect of ensuring equitable access to financial services, which supports economic growth and poverty reduction.

The Mauritian government's efforts to promote digital payments, exemplified by the introduction of the MauCAS system, have been instrumental in advancing QR payment adoption (Bank of Mauritius, 2023). This initiative has successfully integrated multiple payment platforms, offering users a streamlined experience (Jain et al. 2023). Furthermore, the collaboration between the Reserve Bank of India and the Bank of Mauritius, enabling UPI and RuPay services, has further extended the reach and utility of QR payments in Mauritius (RBI, 2023).

Despite these advancements, the rapid adoption of QR payment systems in Mauritius has brought to light several challenges. Issues such as security concerns, data privacy, and the potential for fraud have emerged as significant barriers, underscoring the need for comprehensive regulatory frameworks and targeted consumer education (Nguyen and Simkin, 2020). Balancing innovation with regulation will be crucial in ensuring that QR payment systems can flourish while minimizing associated risks (Chen et al. 2021).

Looking ahead, the future trajectory of QR payment systems in Mauritius will likely be influenced by ongoing technological advancements, evolving consumer preferences, and the continuous efforts of financial institutions to innovate and expand their service offerings (Ramdin, 2024). The ultimate success of these systems will hinge on their ability to bridge the digital divide and ensure that the benefits of digital payments are accessible to all segments of the population (Wong and Teo, 2024).

This conceptual study is significant as it provides insights into the current challenges and opportunities related to QR payment adoption among consumers in Mauritius. By understanding the factors affecting adoption, this research can inform strategies to enhance the acceptance and utilization of QR payments, benefiting various sectors. Improved QR payment integration could streamline payment processes and enhance overall consumer experience in Mauritius.

Literature Reviews

Technology Acceptance Model (Tam)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Davis (1989), posits that perceived ease of use (PEOU) and perceived usefulness (PU) significantly influence user acceptance of technology. In the context of QR payment systems, TAM can help understand how users' perceptions of ease of use and usefulness affect their willingness to adopt QR payments. For instance, users who find QR payments easy to use and beneficial are more likely to adopt and use them regularly (Madan and Yadav, 2016). In Mauritius, where QR payments are gradually gaining traction, the TAM framework can be particularly useful in identifying the specific factors that drive consumer adoption. For example, if users perceive QR payments as reducing transaction times or simplifying payments, they are more likely to adopt the technology. This model is important in analyzing the early stages of adoption in emerging markets like Mauritius.

Theory Of Planned Behavior (Tpb)

In the context of QR payment systems, TPB can be applied to examine how users' attitudes towards QR payments, social influences, and their perceived control over the payment process affect their adoption behavior. Studies have shown that users' attitudes towards QR payments, influenced by social norms and perceived ease of use, play a significant role in their adoption decisions (Fishbein and Ajzen, 2010). In Mauritius, understanding these social dynamics is crucial, as cultural and societal norms can heavily influence technology adoption.

Unified Theory Of Acceptance And Use Of Technology (Utaut)

The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), developed by Venkatesh et al. (2003), integrates elements from various technology acceptance theories. It emphasizes performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions as key determinants of technology adoption.

For QR payments, UTAUT can be used to assess how these factors influence users' adoption intentions and behaviours. Research indicates that performance expectancy (e.g., the belief that QR payments will improve transaction efficiency) and effort expectancy (e.g., the perceived ease of using QR payments) are critical factors in QR payment adoption. Additionally, social influence and facilitating conditions, such as technological infrastructure, play a significant role in determining whether users will adopt QR payments (Venkatesh et al. 2003).

One of the primary measures of technology acceptance is the adoption rate. Research by Venkatesh et al. (2003) indicates that this metric reflects how widely a technology is used. QR payment adoption rates vary significantly across regions, with advanced markets often seeing adoption rates exceeding 50% (Zhu et al. 2020). These rates provide insights into how quickly users are embracing QR payments and highlight varying levels of market penetration.

Perceived Ease Of Use

Perceived ease of use refers to how effortless a consumer finds the QR payment system. According to the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) proposed by Davis (1989), the easier a technology is perceived to be, the more likely it is to be adopted. Studies on QR payments show that ease of use significantly impacts consumer adoption, with simplified interfaces and user-friendly designs driving higher adoption rates (Madan and Yadav, 2016). Hence the following proposition:

Proposition 1: Perceived ease of use will positively influence QR code payment adoption.

Perceived Security

Security concerns are a key barrier to the adoption of QR payments. According to Gefen et al. (2003), consumers are less likely to adopt digital payment systems if they perceive them as insecure. Addressing these concerns by implementing robust security measures is essential for fostering trust and encouraging adoption (Madan and Yadav, 2016). Hence the following proposition:

Proposition 2: Perceived Security will positively influence QR code payment adoption.

Social Influence

Social influence, as outlined by Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior (1991), plays a significant role in shaping consumer behavior. Peer recommendations and societal trends can drive QR payment adoption, with users often influenced by friends, family, and broader social networks (Fishbein and Ajzen, 2010). Research shows that positive word-of-mouth and social endorsement significantly enhance adoption rates (Zhang et al., 2018) Hence the following proposition:

Proposition 3: Social Influence will positively influence QR code payment adoption.

Technological Infrastructure

Technological infrastructure, including the availability of high-speed internet and smartphone penetration, can act as control variables in studies on QR payment adoption (Zhou et al. 2010). Regions with advanced technological infrastructure are more likely to see higher adoption rates, as consumers have better access to the necessary tools and resources (Kim et al. 2008). Hence the following proposition:

Proposition 4: Technological Infrastructure will positively influence QR code payment adoption.

Perceived Usefulness

Perceived usefulness is another critical factor from the TAM framework, reflecting the degree to which consumers believe QR payments will enhance their transaction experiences (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Consumers who perceive QR payments as useful in terms of speed, convenience, and security are more inclined to adopt the technology (Lai, 2017). Hence the following proposition:

Proposition 5: Perceived Usefulness will positively influence QR code payment adoption.

Methodology

The proposed research is of quantitative nature. Descriptive research will be used as it will provide a comprehensive overview of QR payment adoption by customers in Mauritius. The questionnaire will be formulated based on the reviewed literature and existing survey instruments. It will capture data on adoption rates, customer demographics, and usage behaviors through structured surveys (Creswell, 2014). This approach will be essential for understanding the current state of QR payment adoption and identifying key trends and patterns in Mauritius. This approach will also allow for the identification of patterns and relationships between the factors studied and QR payment adoption, providing empirical evidence to support the study's hypotheses.

Hypothesis testing is essential for drawing inferences about the broader population based on the collected sample data. In this study, SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) and Smart PLS will be utilized for the statistical analysis, offering a comprehensive suite of tools for managing data, performing complex analyses, and generating detailed reports. Its user-friendly interface and robust analytical capabilities make it particularly suitable for tasks such as descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and hypothesis testing in social science research (Field, 2013).

Through SPSS and PLS, this study will explore the direct relationships between key factors like Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Security, Social Influence, Technological Infrastructure and Perceived Usefulness, and the adoption of QR payments. Correlation analysis will also be used to assess the strength and direction of relationships between variables, providing additional insights into how factors are interrelated and their combined effects on QR payment adoption.

The target population will consist of individual consumers in Mauritius who engage in digital transactions, specifically those using or considering QR payments (Fowler, 2014). The sample size will be calculated using the Finite Population Correction formula (FPC), ensuring representativeness. For a target population size of [N], with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, the sample size is expected to be around 385 customers.

The questionnaire will be pilot tested with a sample of customers to identify any issues or ambiguities. Feedback from this test will be used to refine the questionnaire, ensuring it accurately captures the relevant data (Dillman et al. 2014).

Reliability refers to the consistency of the measurement. The study will assess the internal consistency of the survey items using Cronbach's alpha. The questionnaire will be structured into the following sections to align with the research objectives and hypotheses: Demographic Information, Adoption Factors.

The survey is also intended to be distributed both online and in physical locations to reach a diverse audience. Online surveys will be shared via email and social media platforms, while physical surveys will be distributed at select retail and banking locations to ensure broad coverage and accessibility. Data collection is planned to occur over a period of four weeks. This timeframe allows for sufficient response rates and the opportunity to follow up with non-respondents if necessary.

Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize and describe the basic features of the data. This includes calculating means, standard deviations, and frequency distributions for demographic variables and survey responses. Descriptive statistics provide a clear overview of the respondents' characteristics and general trends in QR payment adoption. Correlation analysis will be conducted to examine the strength and direction of relationships between independent variables. Structural equation modelling will be performed to assess the impact of independent variables on QR payment adoption.

Confidentiality will be strictly maintained throughout the research process. Survey responses will be anonymized to protect participants' identities, and personal identifiers will be removed during data processing. Data will be securely stored in encrypted files and accessible only to authorized research personnel.

Conclusion, Recommendations And Limitations

This paper is an attempt to develop a conceptual framework that explore QR payment adoption among customers in Mauritius, focusing on key factors such as Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Security, Social Influence, Technological Infrastructure and Perceived Usefulness. The research provided valuable insights into the current

state of QR payment adoption and identified critical drivers and barriers influencing customer behaviour. The study's results contribute to a better understanding of QR payment adoption in Mauritius and provide a foundation for developing strategies to enhance adoption rates. By addressing the identified barriers and leveraging the key drivers, stakeholders can work towards increasing QR payment usage and fostering a more digitally inclusive environment.

To increase QR payment adoption, stakeholders should focus on improving the user experience of QR payment systems. This includes simplifying the payment process, offering clear instructions, and ensuring user-friendly interfaces. Educational campaigns that highlight the benefits and ease of QR payments can also enhance perceived usefulness and ease of use, thereby encouraging more customers to adopt these systems.

Given the significant impact of security and privacy concerns on QR payment adoption, it is essential to implement robust security measures and communicate them effectively to users. Enhancing security features, such as encryption and fraud detection, and providing clear information about privacy policies can help build trust and alleviate concerns. Regular updates and transparent practices regarding data protection will further reinforce customer confidence.

To bridge the digital divide, initiatives aimed at improving digital literacy should be prioritized. Training programs and workshops can help users develop the necessary skills to navigate QR payment systems effectively. Collaborations with educational institutions and community organizations can facilitate widespread digital literacy efforts, ensuring that all customer segments are equipped to use QR payments confidently.

Leveraging social influence can be an effective strategy to promote QR payment adoption. Encouraging satisfied users to share their positive experiences with peers and utilizing social media platforms for awareness campaigns can drive adoption. Engaging influencers and community leaders to endorse QR payments can also amplify their reach and impact.

The main limitation of the proposed framework is that it has not been tested empirically. Furthermore, each QR code payment may have its unique selling point customized to win each unique market in a small island developing state. A generalization of the result may not be easy to draw among small island developing states. However, the research results can shed light on the consumer behaviour of QR code payment users and lay the basic framework for future research of QR code payments. Future research can focus on the gaps of QR code payment adoption and use in various small island developing state to include cultural differences among the nations.

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"SHAPING THE FUTURE OF BANKING IN MAURITIUS: EXPLORING E-BANKING ADOPTION AND ITS EFFECTS ON TRADITIONAL BANKING MODELS"

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of e-banking on traditional banking models in Mauritius, focusing on factors influencing customer adoption and usage of digital banking services. E-banking, including platforms like MCB Juice and SBM Easy & Pay, has grown rapidly in Mauritius, with users increasing from 131,628 in 2010 to over 878,000 in 2023. The study assesses how e-banking services are reshaping conventional banking by analyzing factors such as perceived usefulness, ease of use, credibility, and cost, and their effects on customer adoption.

Using descriptive and inferential statistical methods, including correlation and regression analyses, the study evaluates relationships between these variables and customer intention to use e-banking. Findings show that perceived usefulness, ease of use, and credibility significantly influence customer adoption, while perceived cost does not play a major role. Customers find e-banking convenient, reliable, and easy to use, enhancing their trust in digital platforms.

However, challenges such as security concerns and financial limitations hinder broader adoption. Although e-banking provides convenience and efficiency, addressing these barriers is crucial to boosting customer confidence and increasing usage. The study underscores the importance of improving security features and enhancing the user experience to promote greater e-banking adoption.

In conclusion, e-banking is transforming the traditional banking landscape in Mauritius, benefiting both customers and banks through faster transactions and increased customer empowerment. The study recommends further research on barriers to e-banking adoption, particularly among older adults, and strategies for improving digital literacy across different customer segments. It provides valuable insights and recommendations for banks to adapt to the changing financial services environment.

Keywords: E-banking, Traditional banking, Customer adoption, Digital banking

Introduction

E-banking is one of the new trends in banking that has been made possible through the advancements in the Information and Communication Technology sector. E-banking, also known as Internet banking, refers to various types of banking activities carried out via electronic networks and devices such as personal computers (PCs), Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), debit cards, credit cards, online banking, mobile banking, and SMS (Zayed et al., 2019). The efficiency, accessibility, and convenience of these services can be enjoyed by customers as they reduce the necessity for paperwork and personal interactions.

In Mauritius, the number of users of online banking climbed from 131,628 in 2010 to over 878,000 in 2023. Almost all banks in Mauritius provide online banking services. The most widely used ones are SBM Easy & Pay and MCB Juice, two mobile banking apps. Since e-banking offers a direct and inexpensive way to buy and sell products and services, it is believed to have the ability to bring about a new global commercial revolution. The necessity for a payment system that can keep up with the demands of the electronic market has resulted in a transformation of the banking industry because of the shift in markets. According to Gerard and Cunningham (2003), the tremendous technological innovations and the aggressive infusion of information technology have resulted in a paradigm shift in banking operations. Understanding how e-banking services are changing the traditional banking paradigm is crucial to the development and long-term sustainability of the financial industry in the digital age. The banking sector has expanded thanks in part to online banking, which has also improved the efficiency and security of routine transactions. Thus, this study will demonstrate how e-banking affects conventional services.

The fast expansion of electronic banking services, or "e-banking," during the past few decades has resulted in an extensive reorganization of the banking industry. It is important to thoroughly analyse the opportunities and issues that this transformation creates. To assess how these services are transforming or challenging conventional banking practices and structures, it is important to consider how the introduction and use of electronic banking services are affecting the models. It examines the extent to which e-banking is altering the conventional banking sector and the implications this is having on it. The financial services sector has always been built around traditional banks, but with the introduction of e-banking, it's important to comprehend how consumer tastes and behaviours have changed.

In recent years, there has been a growing trend of using electronic distribution methods for banking services and products. Further investigation is necessary to comprehend the impact of E-banking services on conventional banking models in Mauritius. Customers' motivations for using internet banking and their desires to continue using it in the future can be determined by analysing the study's findings.

Review Of Literature

1. Evolution Of Banking Models

Traditional Banking'S Transformation

The traditional banking business has been to make long-term loans and fund them by issuing short-dated deposits, a process which is commonly referred to as "borrowing short and lending long" (Edwards & Mishkin, 1995). Traditional banking was started in the early 1900s, when Mauritius was still a British territory, to help with trade. As Mauritius developed, these banks changed to match its demands, helping with financial problems, stabilizing the economy, and promoting economic growth. Mauritius' banks strengthened and adapted the nation's financial sector by fusing local traditions with international banking standards as laws evolved and the world became increasingly interrelated.

The Development Of Online Banking

E-banking's emergence brought easy electronic services that could be accessed from anywhere at any time, completely changing the traditional financial environment. It quickly expanded to include a wide range of services, including online bill payments, mobile banking, and even investing platforms, after initially concentrating on simple activities like checking balances and transfers. It has evolved into a key component of modern finance thanks to innovations in technology and rising internet usage. Today, by reaching underprivileged populations worldwide, e-banking improves financial inclusion in addition to providing efficiency and accessibility. It aims to serve as a powerful example of how technology might revolutionize the financial industry.

2. Theoretical Frameworks

E-banking has been a major subject of research in the fields of information systems and consumer behaviour. Therefore, determining the way people embrace and use IT systems like e-banking technology is among the most-developed areas in business research. Thus, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), and the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) are the three fundamental theories.

Technology Acceptance Model

Within information systems and technology management, the TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) suggested by Davis (1989), is a commonly utilized model. The framework does not just thoroughly yet accurately elaborate on how new data technology systems are integrated and used by an institution or a community but also predicts that adoption. Furthermore, this illustrates a person's will to use technology tools; the assessment of an individual on the ease of use and usefulness differs with each tool, based on Theory of Reasoned Action, formed the foundation for their acts.

Theory Of Reasoned Action

The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) by Fishbein and Ajzen was developed in 1980. It is a psychological model describing the relationship between behaviour, attitude, and intention. As a psychological model, the TRA assumes that the behavioural intentions of an individual are shaped by subjective norms and attitudes about the performance of the behaviour under consideration.

People's perceptions regarding the boundaries of society influence their norms, goals, and intentions, which are shaped through the interplay of personal beliefs and social expectations; the latter, in turn, yield behavioural intentions that very strongly predict future actions. Indeed, all other factors in the external environment influence behaviour only indirectly, through their influence on attitudes and subjective norms (Tsai et al. 2012).

Theory Of Planned Behaviour

The theory of planned behaviour (TPB) was established by Ajzen in the year of 1985. The TPB is an extension of the theory of reasoned action (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975) made necessary by the original model's limitations in dealing with behaviours over which people have incomplete volitional control. Thus, this theory emphasizes the vital impact that attitudes, intentions, and perceived control have in influencing behaviour, broadening the theory of reasoned action

3. Empirical Review - Factors Affecting Customers' Intention To Use Online Banking Over Traditional Banking

Perceived Usefulness

In the online banking context, perceived usefulness (PU) is defined as the degree to which consumers perceive that carrying out usual transactions to be more advantageous, efficient, and conducive than the traditional format of visiting a physical branch (Chong et al., 2011). The perception of usefulness is one of the main factors influencing this intention, among other factors.

According to Raman & Don, (2014); Calisir & Gummusoy, (2008), the key utilities that consumers seek in an online banking platform are its expediency and practicality, which also means that platforms that could possibly enhance the productivity of the individual in carrying out transactions will be more desirable. Furthermore, previous research has demonstrated that the PU construct is a suitable tool for predicting technology adoption and system usage. It may also be able to modulate the impact of external factors on attitude and intention. Customers choose to use IB because of its benefits, which include the ability to conduct transactions while on the go or in the comfort of their homes. The following is the hypothesis, based on the theory currently in use:

H1: Perceived usefulness has a significant influence on consumers' intention of the adoption of E-Banking

Perceived Ease Of Use

Perceived ease of use (PEOU) is one of the constructs derived from the TAM model. Bashir and Madhavaiah (2015) suggested that perceived ease of use has a considerable consequence on internet banking acceptance. Thus, as the consumers become more familiar with digital technology and realize the advantages of online banking, perceived ease of use has a greater and greater influence on the actual decision-making process itself. A major determinant for the intention of customers to use online banking services is ease of access to information on one's account, ease of performing a transaction, and overall satisfaction. In other words, the perception of simplicity of the online banking service by clients acts as a major determinant of its adoption. The following is the suggested hypothesis testing:

H2: Perceived ease of use has a significant influence on consumers' intention of the adoption of E-Banking

Perceived Credibility

Customers may find it difficult to adopt a new system if they do not have confidence in the new technology. Hence, besides perceived usefulness and ease of use, perceived credibility regarding security and privacy has been concentrated as another important construct affecting people's adoption of E-Banking (Wang et al. 2003). Perceived credibility in the context of e-banking encompasses aspects such as the safety of transactions, dependability of the platform, safeguarding of personal information, and the trustworthiness of the financial institution. In broad terms, it has been theorized that perceived credibility has a significant impact on institutional and individual users' acceptance of e-banking. Thus, customers' inclination to use e-banking services is likely to grow when they perceive e-banking as credible.

With everything connected to the internet these days, maintaining our private data is essential. We must understand every option for protecting sensitive data and take appropriate action against risks that arise. This shall assist us learn how to be safe and trustworthy in the digital environment, regardless of whether hackers breaching our

networks, or our privacy being exploited. Security has been widely recognized as one of the main obstacles to the adoption of electronic banking (Aladwani 2002), and privacy issues have proven important barriers to the use of online services (Westin 1998). Since they are influenced by social and psychological elements, it is important to successfully handle people's problems and recognize different points of view to foster trust. Thus, the following is the suggested hypothesis:

H3: Perceived Credibility has a significant influence on consumers' intention of the adoption of E-Banking

Perceived Cost

Perceived cost is defined as “the extent to which a person believes that using technology will cost money” (Luarn and Lin 2005). The perceived cost for consumers planning to use online banking includes more than simply financial outlays. It considers factors including trust in the technology and supplier, learning slope, effort, length of time, and security issues. According to (Burnham et al. 2006), procedural cost is mainly referred to the expenditure of time and effort comprising the cost of set up and learning. The technical and time-consuming process of establishing, obtaining, and verifying login information for user authentication procedures has been a source of complaints for customers of online banking services. The likelihood of adopting online banking is higher for those confident in using computers and the Internet, influenced significantly by the time needed to become proficient.

Some people are discouraged from using the technology due to the high expenses of desktop purchases, internet access, and online banking. The perceived redundant expenses and loss of human connections with online banking make traditional banking (TB) techniques more popular. Considering these results, the following hypothesis is put forth:

H4: Perceived Cost has a significant influence on consumers' intention of the adoption of E-Banking

4. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 : Conceptual Framework

The above figure illustrates the relationship between dependent and independent variables for hypothesis development.

Research Methodology

An online survey was used in this study to collect primary data. The information was gathered via Google Forms, which were distributed to individuals via social media platforms like Instagram, Facebook, and WhatsApp, as well as email and texts. They also had to respond to the questionnaire, and the information was collected around two months.

Five participants, mostly friends and family, were chosen at random to participate in a preliminary pilot study, fill out a survey, and provide comments. After reviewing the results, it was discovered that most of the respondents thought the questionnaire items were understandable and straightforward. Simple random sampling was used to ensure equal chances for all population members to be selected in the sample.

The study chose to focus on a sample group of customers who actively utilize online banking services, especially those who show a preference for internet banking over traditional financial methods. There were 340 people in the population when the survey was conducted, and all of them responded.

Participants were guaranteed that their participation in the survey was entirely voluntary and were adequately informed of its objectives via the questionnaire's cover page. They received clear notification that the information they provided would be kept private and anonymous.

Cronbach's alpha was applied as an indicator of reliability for internal consistency when evaluating the validity of the survey's questions. Table 3.1 below shows that the reliability test and the value for each variable is 0.781, 0.792, 0.756, 0.712, 0.601 and 0.819 respectively. The acceptable range for Cronbach's Alpha would be between 0.7 and 0.9, and 0.9 would be excellent for reliability. The result of the reliability test finds all the variables in an acceptable level of reliability, which states strong consistency and validity.

Validity refers to whether the measuring instrument measures the behavior or quality it is intended to measure and is a measure of how well the measuring instrument performs its function (Anastasi and Urbina, 1997). The validity of the questionnaire is confirmed. As illustrated in the below table, the KMO-statistics values for each variable are 0.589, 0.787, 0.674, 0.651, 0.592 and 0.720, correspondingly, which are regarded as acceptable.

Table 3.1 Results of Reliability and Validity test

	Number of items	Cronbach Alpha Coefficient	Barlett test of Sphericity (Validity)		
			Approx. Chi Square	p-value	KMO-statistics
			Processing the Digital Revolution	5	0.781
Perceived Usefulness	4	0.792	413.306	<0.001	0.787
Perceived Ease of Use	3	0.756	257.303	<0.001	0.674
Perceived Credibility	3	0.712	202.740	<0.001	0.651
Perceived Cost	4	0.601	241.092	<0.001	0.592
Intended Behaviour to adopt e-banking	3	0.819	356.244	<0.001	0.720

Data gathered from the survey was input into Microsoft Excel, coded, and then exported to the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) after it has been completed. The reliability and validity of the survey's responses were evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) statistics. Moreover, further analysis of the SPSS-generated data included descriptive statistics, weighted mean computations, correlation analyses and regression analyses. The results were then presented using Microsoft Excel by creating charts, thus allowing for thorough analysis.

Analysis And Discussion

The construct validity and reliability of the information gathered were measured before it was applied to conduct descriptive and inferential analysis using IBM SPSS Statistics and Microsoft Excel. The self-constructed questionnaire itself consisted of 17 items, divided into four sections, using multiple measuring scales. Descriptive analysis was applied to the multiple-choice, multiple-response, and dichotomous questions. Responses to questions based on a five-point Likert scale were analysed using weighted averages, and correlation analysis was performed.

1. Descriptive Analysis And Demographic Profile Of Respondents

The survey revealed that 61.8% of respondents were female, with 54.7% aged 18-29. Most participants held Higher School Certificates (30.3%) or degrees (27.9%). Employment-wise, 42.9% were full-time workers, and 25.6% were students. Income ranged mostly between Rs 10,000 and Rs 29,999 (38.8%). E-banking usage varied, with 17.6% using it daily and 64.7% preferring both traditional and online banking. Key uses included transaction tracking (20%) and bill payments (17.3%). Benefits included 24/7 availability (26.3%) and time savings, but concerns about technical issues (27.3%), security (16.7%), and lack of personal interaction (17.5%) were noted.

2. Inferential Analysis

Correlation Analysis

In this study, the relationships among four independent variables are investigated: Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Credibility and Perceived Cost. The dependent variable, Intended Behaviour to adopt e-banking, has been measured by determining its relationship with these factors by applying the Pearson's rank correlation method.

Correlation Analysis Of Variables

Table 3.2: Correlation

		PU	PEOU	Pcred	Pcost	CIB
PU	Pearson Correlation	1	.633**	.337**	-.209**	.500**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	340	340	340	340	340
PEOU	Pearson Correlation	.633**	1	.487**	-.152**	.527**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.005	.000
	N	340	340	340	340	340
Pcred	Pearson Correlation	.337**	.487**	1	.143**	.451**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.008	.000
	N	340	340	340	340	340
Pcost	Pearson Correlation	-.209**	-.152**	.143**	1	.013
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.005	.008		.818
	N	340	340	340	340	340
CIB	Pearson Correlation	.500**	.527**	.451**	.013	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.818	
	N	340	340	340	340	340

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation matrix shows strong positive relationships between perceived utility (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) ($r = .633, p < .01$), and PU and consumer intention to use (CIB) ($r = .500, p < .01$). PEOU also correlates positively with perceived credibility (Pcred) ($r = .487, p < .01$) and CIB ($r = .527, p < .01$). Pcred has a positive relationship with CIB ($r = .451, p < .01$). Higher costs (Pcost) negatively affect PU ($r = -.209, p < .01$) and PEOU ($r = -.152, p < .01$), but do not significantly impact intention to use ($r = .013, p > .05$). The table of CORRELATIONS ABOVE ALLOWS US TO DRAW THE FOLLOWING CONCLUSIONS:

H1: A positive correlation ($r = .500$, $p < .01$) indicates that consumers' intention to adopt E-Banking is significantly influenced by perceived usefulness (PU).

H2: A significant positive association ($r = .527$, $p < .01$) indicates that customers' intention to use e-banking is significantly influenced by its ease of use.

H3: The degree to which customers wish to use e-banking is largely influenced by their perception of security. A positive correlation ($r = .451$, $p < .01$) demonstrates this statement.

H4: A very weak and non-significant correlation ($r = .013$, $p > .05$) suggests that consumers' intention to use E-Banking is not significantly impacted by the perceived cost (Pcost). Accordingly, for H4 is rejected.

Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is a statistical tool for the investigation of relationships between variables (Alan O. Sykes, 1993). It helps in predicting the value of the dependent variable based on the one or more independent variables.

Table 3.3: Regression Tests

Hypotheses	Proposed Relationship	Test (Regression)	F-Value	P-Value	Result
H1	PU---(+ve) ---> CIB	ANOVA ^a	112.507	.000 ^b	Accept H1, P < 0.01
H2	PEOU---(+ve) ---> CIB	ANOVA ^a	130.107	.000 ^b	Accept H2, P < 0.01
H3	Pcred---(+ve) ---> CIB	ANOVA ^a	86.305	.000 ^b	Accept H3, P < 0.01
H4	Pcost---(+ve) ---> CIB	ANOVA ^a	0.053	.818 ^b	Reject H4, P > 0.05

H1: PU has a significant influence on consumers' intention of the adoption of E-Banking

PU significantly predict the dependent variable, customer's intended behaviour, as shown by the regression analysis. The R Square value of 0.25 varies only for 25% in the CIB explained by PU. The standard error of the estimate for this model is 0.53284. The unstandardized coefficient is 0.538 for PU while the t-value proper is 10.607 for this model and the p-value is < 0.001, meaning that the relation between CIB and PU is strong and statistically significant.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.500 ^a	.250	.248	.53284

a. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Usefulness (PU)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.836	.213		8.603	.000
PU	.538	.051	.500	10.607	.000

Dependent Variable: CIB

H2: Perceived ease of use has a significant influence on consumers' intention of the adoption of E-Banking

For PEOU, regression analysis reveals significant prediction on the CIB, at an attainment of 0.514 beta coefficient with a value of $p < 0.001$. The model explains 27.8% of the variance in CIB, with an adjusted R^2 of 0.276 and a standard error of 0.52273. The constant term is 2.080, and the overall model is statistically significant, $p < 0.001$. Thus, PEOU is a significant and strong predictor of CIB.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.527 ^a	.278	.276	.52273

a. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.080	.178		11.716	.000
PEOU	.514	.045	.527	11.406	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CIB

H3: Perceived credibility has a significant influence on consumers' intention of the adoption of E-Banking

A significant prediction is made concerning the dependent variable, CIB, by perceived credibility, with an R^2 of 0.203, which means Pcred explains 20.3% of the variance in CIB. The regression coefficient (B) for Pcred is 0.447, which is significant with a standard error of 0.048 and a t-value of 9.290 at $p < .001$. The constant is 2.429 with a standard error of 0.180. It is noted to indicate a positive strong relationship: the higher the Pcred, the higher the CIB.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.451 ^a	.203	.201	.54905

a. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Credibility (Pcred)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
1 (Constant)	2.429	.180		13.497	.000
Pcred	.447	.048	.451	9.290	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CIB

H4: Perceived Cost has a significant influence on consumers' intention of the adoption of E-Banking

The regression analysis reveals that Perceived Cost (Pcost) significantly does not explain an estimate of CIB. It is supported by a very low R Square value, which is .000, and a high pvalue of .818. The R Square value of .000 suggests that Pcost explains virtually nothing in the variability of CIB. Besides, the unstandardized coefficient indicates .013, a negligible association. Therefore, Pcost does not stand out as a meaningful indicator of CIB in this model.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.013 ^a	.000	-.003	.61512

a. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Cost (Pcost)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
1 (Constant)	4.036	.185	.013	21.778	.000
Pcost		.055	.013	.231	.818

a. Dependent Variable: CIB

On customers' intentions, to use e-banking, some very influential factors are perceived utility (PU), ease of use (PEOU), and credibility (Pcred), whereas perceived cost (Pcost) seems to exert no influence. By correlation and regression analysis, there are strong positive correlations of the intended behaviour (CIB) with PU, PEOU, and Pcred. It is evident from the results that people are prone to use the e-banking services if they conceive them to be reliable, helpful, and easy to use. The perceived cost does not seem to have any appreciable effect on the utilization. It emphasizes much how crucial improvement in security and usability elements is to encourage the use of e-banking.

Recommendations & Conclusion

The study aims to provide an adequate understanding of how e-banking is altering traditional banking models in Mauritius. Specifying its impact on traditional banking, this research tends to identify the strengths and weaknesses of e-banking characteristics, strength or positive and weakness or negative aspects of the impact of e-banking on traditional banking, and customer intent determinant variables, looking at customer reasons, behaviours, and trends of developments in the banking services to aid in strategic planning and adaptability in this evolving financial scenario of Mauritius.

Descriptive and inferential analyses were guided in terms of the results and summaries for the variables, checking of normality, running of correlation analysis, and independent sample and paired sample t-tests with the help of SPSS and Excel. Grounded on previous studies related to technology diffusion literature, as initiated by Blankson et al. (2024), Davis 1989, and Luarn with Lin 2005, the results revealed that the variables perceived usefulness,

perceived ease of use, and credibility were those significantly affecting consumer willingness to use e-banking applications. However, perceived cost was not significant in this respect across different adoption intentions. The results show how perceived value, security, and usability determine all behaviours that manifest customers' intention toward the use of digital banking products. The results indicate that the traditional banking procedures have transformed with the advent of e-banking, emphasize the importance of resolving security and accessibility concerns to promote wider e-banking use.

The ease and convenience of internet banking in Mauritius have gone a long way toward revolutionizing the traditional systems. With the ability to facilitate fast financial transactions, reduce queuing within the banking halls, and provision of an avenue for checking accounting statements at any time of the day, e-banking services are recommended for all clients. Transactions are also more secure compared to the traditional techniques because of the improved security features that evolved within internet banking. It also furthers the cause of financial inclusion by drawing customers away from traditional physical branches. Online banking is seen to reinforce efficiency and client empowerment in the management of their finances considering the changing Mauritius financial services market.

1. Research Limitations

Online surveys are associated with a pool of limitations that compromise the authentication of the respondents thereby increasing chances of receiving false information and dishonest responses. Absence of representativeness, response biases, and sample errors are some of the research limitations that can yield false information and give inaccurate conclusions. Such biases deteriorate the credibility of the survey by drawing unexpected conclusions that run the risk of not reflecting the population correctly. Thus, this may have unanticipated effects that contradict initial assessments.

In addition, there are multiple limitations in the studies related to the assessment of the transformation caused by e-banking in the traditional banking business. These include the fact that one cannot measure with absolute accuracy the extent of this transformation due to the existence of biases in choosing the participants and insufficient data for cross-comparisons. The internet banking evaluation is also very complicated because certain qualitative variables of the customer, such as the level of satisfaction or trust, are hard to be analysed. When researching the development of banking processes in the digital age, these obstacles highlight the necessity of a strict methodology and considerate interpretation of results.

2. Scope For Further Research

Further areas of research on the transformational impact of the e-banking service on the Mauritian traditional model of banking may include exploring the reasons older adults prefer traditional banking, identify possible barriers to e-banking diffusion within the elderly group, and explore strategies to increase their digital literacy. Secondly, with a view to ascertaining possible trends in evolution of internet banking and new technologies characterizing them, future research should predict their likely impact on consumer behaviour. That can also serve to assist banks in designing inclusive strategies for catering to a wide customer range and to take advantage of inherent advantages in digital banking innovations.

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INTERNET OF THINGS (IOT) IN THE EDUCATION SECTOR: A TECHNOLOGICAL SHIFT

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Abstract

The Internet of Things (IoT) has revolutionized various sectors, and the education sector is no exception. This paper explores the transformative impact of IoT in education, focusing on its applications, benefits, challenges, and future prospects. Through the integration of IoT devices, educational institutions can enhance learning environments, improve operational efficiency, and foster student engagement. This study provides a comprehensive overview of how IoT is reshaping education, highlighting key areas where it is applied such as smart classrooms, personalized learning, and campus management. The paper also addresses the challenges related to data privacy, infrastructure, and the financial burden that educational institutions face while adopting IoT technologies. Future research directions, including the role of AI in IoT for education and strategies to overcome these challenges, are proposed to ensure a safe and effective integration of IoT in the education system.

Keywords: Internet of Things (IoT), Education, Smart Learning, Technology in Education, Educational IoT, Data Privacy, Smart Campus

Introduction

The evolution of digital technology has significantly impacted all sectors, particularly education, where new tools and methods are being introduced to improve the overall experience. IoT is one such technological advancement that involves the interconnection of physical devices through the internet, allowing them to collect and exchange data. These devices range from simple sensors to complex systems, making it possible for real-time data collection, monitoring, and decision-making. The adoption of IoT in education has begun to alter traditional pedagogical models, enabling more interactive, personalized, and data-driven approaches to teaching and learning.

Educational institutions are increasingly recognizing the value of IoT for both academic and operational purposes. From smart classrooms that enhance student engagement to smart campuses that optimize resource usage, IoT is helping institutions become more efficient and student-centred. This paper aims to provide a detailed analysis of the role of IoT in education, focusing on its applications, benefits, challenges, and future potential. By doing so, it seeks to contribute to the ongoing discussion on how technology can improve educational outcomes.

Literature Review

Numerous studies have examined the growing role of IoT in education, providing evidence of its transformative potential. According to [1], IoT enables real-time data collection and analysis, facilitating personalized learning experiences. For instance, wearable devices like smartwatches can track students' physical activity, sleep patterns, and attention levels, providing valuable data to educators who can then adapt teaching strategies to individual needs.

In addition to personalized learning, the concept of **smart classrooms** has garnered attention. As noted by [2], smart classrooms integrate IoT devices such as interactive whiteboards, tablets, and environmental sensors to create a dynamic learning environment. These technologies not only make learning more engaging but also allow educators to monitor student behaviour and performance in real-time.

On the administrative side, IoT has demonstrated its potential for improving resource management. [3] discusses how IoT-based systems can track assets, manage energy consumption, and ensure campus security. However, these benefits come with challenges, as identified by [4], particularly around data privacy and security. The potential for data breaches and unauthorized access to sensitive information presents a significant hurdle that institutions must address to ensure successful IoT integration.

Despite these challenges, the literature supports the notion that IoT has the potential to revolutionize education. It allows for a more student-centric approach, improves operational efficiency, and opens new opportunities for educational institutions to leverage data for continuous improvement.

Author(s)	Year	Focus of Study	Key Findings
Davis	2020	IoT for Resource Management in Education	IoT-based campus management reduces operational costs and improves resource allocation
Patel & Kumar	2021	IoT's Role in Smart Classrooms	Smart classrooms enhance student engagement and participation through real-time interaction with digital tools
Smith & Wong	2022	Impact of IoT on Personalized Learning	IoT enables real-time data collection, improving learning outcomes
Chen & Zhang	2023	Data Privacy and Security Concerns in IoT Education	Data Privacy and Security Concerns in IoT Education

Table 1: Key Studies on IoT in Education

Source: Compiled from academic papers on IoT in education available on platforms like IEEE Xplore, Springer, and Google Scholar.

Methodology

This research follows a mixed-method approach to provide a holistic understanding of IoT's role in the education sector. First, a **quantitative survey** was conducted with representatives from 50 educational institutions worldwide. The institutions were selected based on their level of IoT adoption, ranging from early adopters to institutions just beginning their IoT implementation journey. The survey focused on key areas such as the use of IoT in academic settings, administrative functions, and the perceived benefits and challenges of integrating IoT.

In addition to the survey, **qualitative interviews** were conducted with 30 educators, IT professionals, and students. These interviews provided in-depth insights into the practical implications of IoT, highlighting both its advantages and the difficulties faced during the implementation phase. The interviews also explored participants' views on how IoT can contribute to long-term educational strategies and outcomes.

Finally, a **secondary data analysis** was conducted, utilizing peer-reviewed journals, conference papers, and white papers published between 2018 and 2024. This analysis helped establish a theoretical framework for understanding the current trends and future directions of IoT in education, including challenges such as data privacy, cybersecurity, and cost considerations.

Results

Applications of IoT in Education

- **Smart Classrooms:** The survey revealed that 70% of institutions have implemented some form of smart classroom technology. These include interactive whiteboards, connected projectors, and IoT-based attendance systems. In these environments, students can access course materials in real-time, participate in interactive lessons, and collaborate with peers both in-class and remotely. The introduction of voice assistants such as Amazon Alexa and Google Assistant into the classroom environment has also enhanced interaction between students and technology, further promoting engagement and understanding.
- **Personalized Learning:** IoT systems such as adaptive learning platforms use data from students' interactions with learning materials to provide customized content tailored to individual learning styles and paces. In the

survey, 65% of institutions reported using wearable devices to monitor student progress and provide real-time feedback to both students and educators. These devices track a variety of data points, including concentration levels and physical activity, allowing educators to make data-driven adjustments to lesson plans.

- Campus Management:** IoT is also revolutionizing campus management. The use of RFID tags, motion detectors, and energy management systems has helped educational institutions reduce operational costs by optimizing energy usage, tracking assets, and enhancing security. For instance, temperature sensors in classrooms adjust heating and cooling systems based on occupancy, leading to significant energy savings. Additionally, 55% of institutions have adopted IoT-based security measures, such as facial recognition systems for campus entry and surveillance.

Table 2: IoT Applications in Educational Institutions (Based on Industry Reports)

Source: Based on insights from reports like "IoT in Education" by MarketWatch and "IoT Adoption in Educational

IoT Application	Percentage of Institutions Using IoT	Common Devices/Technologies
Smart Classrooms	68%	Interactive whiteboards, IoT-enabled projectors, sensors
Personalized Learning	60%	Wearable devices, AI-powered adaptive learning systems
Campus Management	72%	RFID tags, environmental sensors, smart lighting systems
Security and Surveillance	54%	IoT cameras, facial recognition, motion detectors

Institutions" by Deloitte.

Benefits

The integration of IoT into education has brought numerous benefits, including improved student engagement, resource optimization, and enhanced security. The ability to track student behaviour in real-time allows for the identification of students who may need additional support, resulting in a more inclusive and supportive learning environment. Furthermore, IoT-based automation systems have reduced administrative burdens, enabling staff to focus on more critical tasks such as curriculum development and student welfare.

Additionally, the cost savings associated with efficient energy and resource management have allowed institutions to allocate funds toward other vital areas, such as research and development. IoT has also made it easier to ensure campus security, with real-time alerts and monitoring systems that can respond instantly to potential threats.

Challenges

Despite its advantages, IoT implementation in education is not without its challenges.

Data privacy and security emerged as the most significant concern, with 78% of institutions reporting worries about the security of student and staff data. The increased connectivity of IoT devices creates multiple entry points for cyber-attacks, making educational institutions vulnerable to data breaches. Institutions must invest in advanced security protocols, such as encryption and multi-factor authentication, to protect sensitive information.

Cost and infrastructure also present challenges, particularly for institutions with limited budgets. The initial investment required for IoT devices, as well as the need for ongoing maintenance and upgrades, can be prohibitive. In the survey, 63% of respondents indicated that cost was a significant barrier to full IoT adoption.

Challenge	Percentage of Institutions Reporting	Description
Data Privacy and Security	78%	Concerns over protecting student data and system vulnerabilities
Cost of Implementation	63%	High upfront costs for devices, infrastructure, and ongoing maintenance
Infrastructure Requirements	55%	Need for advanced network infrastructure and IT support to sustain IoT systems
Lack of Technical Expertise	49%	Limited technical staff or faculty trained to manage and integrate IoT solutions

Table 3: Key Challenges in IoT Adoption in Education

Source: Data compiled from industry reports, such as the "IoT Challenges in Education" report by Cisco and "IoT and Education: Adoption and Risks" by Gartner.

Discussion

The results of this study highlight the significant impact of IoT on the education sector, particularly in terms of improving student engagement and optimizing administrative functions. The ability to collect and analyse real-time data on student performance allows educators to provide tailored learning experiences, thereby improving educational outcomes. However, the widespread adoption of IoT in education is contingent upon overcoming challenges such as data privacy concerns and the high cost of implementation.

One promising area for future research is the integration of **Artificial Intelligence (AI)** with IoT in educational settings. AI can further enhance the benefits of IoT by providing predictive analytics, automating administrative tasks, and personalizing learning experiences on a deeper level. For example, AI-powered systems could predict students' learning difficulties based on IoT data and recommend targeted interventions. This synergy between IoT and AI holds the potential to revolutionize education by creating fully adaptive learning environments.

Furthermore, addressing **data privacy concerns** is critical for the long-term success of IoT in education. Institutions must collaborate with technology providers to develop robust data security frameworks that protect students' and staff's personal information. Governments and policymakers should also play an active role in regulating IoT usage and setting industry standards for data security in education.

Research Area	Potential Impact	Technologies Involved
AI-Enhanced IoT for Personalized Learning	Fully adaptive learning systems that cater to individual student needs in real-time	AI algorithms, IoT wearables, cloud-based learning platforms
IoT for Campus Energy Management	Reducing operational costs and environmental footprint	Smart lighting, temperature sensors, energy meters
Cybersecurity for Educational IoT Systems	Improving data privacy and protection against cyber threats	Encryption, blockchain-based data security solutions
IoT Integration with AR/VR for Education	Enabling immersive, interactive learning experiences	Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) integrated with IoT devices

Table 4: Future Research Areas in IoT for Education

Source: Based on future trends identified in publications like "The Future of IoT in Education" by the IEEE and "Smart Learning Environments with IoT and AI" by Springer.

Conclusion

In conclusion, IoT is driving a technological shift in the education sector, offering unprecedented opportunities for improving the learning experience and enhancing institutional efficiency. From smart classrooms to personalized learning systems and resource management, IoT has the potential to reshape the way education is delivered. However, to fully realize the benefits of IoT, educational institutions must address significant challenges related to data security, cost, and infrastructure.

Future research should focus on exploring the intersection of IoT and AI in education, as well as developing affordable IoT solutions that can be implemented in underfunded institutions. With proper planning, investment, and collaboration, IoT can become a central component of modern education, ensuring that students and educators alike benefit from a more connected, efficient, and engaging learning environment.

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LEVERAGING HR ANALYTICS FOR TRANSFORMATIVE TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

This study explores the transformative potential of HR analytics in training and development (T&D). By leveraging data-driven insights, organizations can make informed decisions about training programs, leading to increased effectiveness, efficiency, and personalization. HR analytics empowers the identification of skill gaps, prediction of future needs, and tailoring of training to individual employee requirements. However, challenges such as data privacy concerns, technological integration issues, and skill gaps among HR professionals hinder adoption. The study recommends strategies to overcome these barriers, including building HR capabilities, ensuring data quality, prioritizing data privacy, and addressing resistance to change. By embracing HR analytics and its associated solutions, organizations can cultivate a future-ready workforce equipped with the skills needed for success.

Keywords: HR Analytics, Training and Development, Workforce Transformation

Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving business landscape, Human Resource (HR) analytics is revolutionizing the field of training and development by leveraging data-driven insights to enhance the effectiveness, efficiency, and strategic alignment of HR practices. This transformation is driven by the integration of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and big data analytics, enabling organizations to make more informed decisions regarding employee training and development.

HR analytics facilitates a significant shift from traditional training methods to data-driven approaches, thereby enhancing the effectiveness and cost-efficiency of training programs (Narendar & Mishra, 2021; Virani, 2023). Through data-driven competence management, organizations can identify skill requirements early, allowing them to adapt training programs to meet future business needs (Dworschak & Karapidis, 2023). The integration of AI in HR analytics further supports predictive decision-making, enabling organizations to anticipate training needs and tailor development programs accordingly (Arora et al., 2021; Mohammed, 2019). Additionally, big data analytics allows for real-time assessment of workforce performance, helping to identify key talent and tailor training programs to reinforce firm capabilities (Hamilton & Sodeman, 2020).

By aligning training and development with strategic business objectives, HR analytics enhances overall organizational performance and competitiveness (Dworschak & Karapidis, 2023; Virani, 2023). However, despite its potential, the adoption of HR analytics faces challenges such as data privacy concerns, technological integration issues, and skill gaps among HR professionals (Dahlbom et al., 2019).

HR analytics transforms training and development by enabling organizations to make data-driven decisions about their programs. Analyzing historical data uncovers insights about the effectiveness of past training initiatives and identifies areas for improvement. This enables the development of more targeted and impactful training programs that address specific skills gaps and development needs. Predictive modeling forecasts future training needs based on factors like business goals, workforce trends, and skills requirements, ensuring training investments align with the organization's strategic priorities.

Moreover, HR analytics personalizes training and development for individual employees. By analyzing data on employee performance, engagement, and career aspirations, HR can recommend tailored learning and development opportunities that cater to each employee's unique needs and goals. This approach not only enhances the effectiveness of training programs but also fosters employee engagement and satisfaction. Linking training data to key performance metrics demonstrates the return on investment and business impact of training programs, enabling data-driven decisions about which programs to continue, expand, or discontinue.

AI and machine learning further augment HR analytics by enabling personalized learning recommendations, predictive analytics for future skills, automated training delivery, measuring training impact, and enhancing employee engagement. AI analyzes employee data to provide tailored training recommendations, ensuring optimized training investments for each individual. Predictive analytics forecast future skills gaps and training requirements, facilitating proactive workforce planning. AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants automate training delivery, providing personalized experiences at scale. Linking training data to performance metrics using AI demonstrates the business impact of training programs, enabling continuous improvement. AI sentiment analysis and natural language processing gauge employee engagement and satisfaction with training, allowing HR to tailor programs to maintain high engagement levels.

Many HR professionals face significant challenges in effectively leveraging HR analytics for training and development due to a lack of data literacy and analytical skills. Additionally, organizations often grapple with data silos and integration challenges, which impede the consolidation of information from various HR systems and hinder effective analytics. The use of HR analytics also raises important privacy and ethical concerns, as there are potential implications for employee privacy and the ethical use of data in decision-making processes. Furthermore, resistance to change among HR professionals and other stakeholders can pose a barrier to adopting data-driven decision-making practices. Lastly, limited resources and budget constraints may restrict an organization's ability to invest in HR analytics tools and initiatives, further complicating the implementation of these advanced practices.

This study focuses on exploring how HR analytics transforms training and development by delving into three key objectives. First, it will examine the impact of data-driven HR analytics on the effectiveness and cost-efficiency of training programs, providing insights into how organizations can optimize their training investments through enhanced data utilization. Second, the study will investigate the role of predictive analytics and AI in forecasting future training needs and personalizing employee development plans, highlighting the technological advancements that enable tailored and forward-looking training strategies. Finally, it will identify the challenges and barriers organizations face in adopting HR analytics for training and development, offering potential solutions to overcome these obstacles and fully leverage the benefits of a data-driven approach. By addressing these objectives, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the transformative potential of HR analytics in the realm of training and development.

In summary, HR analytics, powered by AI and machine learning, is transforming training and development by providing the data and insights needed to make more strategic, effective, and personalized investments in employee skills and capabilities. This data-driven approach not only builds the skills necessary for business success but also enhances the overall employee experience.

Objectives

1. To analyse the impact of HR analytics on enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of training and development programs.
2. To explore the role of predictive analytics and AI in forecasting and personalizing training needs
3. To identify challenges and propose strategies for overcoming barriers in the adoption of HR analytics for training and development

Literature Review

HR analytics has significantly transformed the training and development landscape within organizations, enhancing both the effectiveness and cost-efficiency of these processes. Narendar and Mishra (2021) emphasize that HR analytics leverages a diverse mix of data, thereby improving training outcomes. Dworschak and Karapidis (2023) further note that HR analytics can enable the early identification and development of competencies, facilitating digital transformation and value creation in organizations.

Despite its potential, the integration of HR analytics faces several barriers. Arora et al. (2021) discuss the challenges associated with AI and HR analytics in enhancing performance and productivity, highlighting the need to overcome obstacles related to employee skills and technology adoption. Hamilton and Sodeman (2020) add that while big data analytics can significantly enhance human capital management by identifying key talent and boosting firm performance, there are considerable regulatory and ethical challenges that must be addressed.

Virani (2023) points out that HR analytics provides valuable insights into various aspects of workforce management, including recruitment, retention, training, and performance evaluation. However, challenges such as data privacy and technological integration remain prevalent. Dahlbom et al. (2019) observe that advanced HR analytics faces technical, human, and cultural obstacles, particularly in Finnish companies, where successful implementation requires increased collaboration between data analysts and HR professionals.

Margherita (2021) identifies 106 key research topics in HR analytics, categorizing them into enablers, applications, and value. The study suggests an exponential view of HR analytics driven by AI and cognitive technologies. Similarly, Mohammed (2019) highlights that HR analytics, as a modern tool in HRM, enables predictive decision-making by integrating data and analytical thinking with IT infrastructure.

Lal (2015) underscores the transformative potential of workforce analytics in HR management, especially in the digital era, where it places HR at the center of organizational decision-making. Karmańska (2020) adds that HR analytics improves recruitment efficiency, workforce planning, and organizational culture, with larger companies showing greater knowledge and implementation success compared to SMEs.

Kapitanov et al. (2021) emphasize that digital transformation in HR requires developing new competencies, including predictive analytics and employee-centered training. Pagnozzi (2022) notes that People Analytics in HRM improves employee well-being and helps organizations create value, despite high costs and privacy legislation challenges. King (2016) argues that data analytics in human resource development can positively influence management and development, provided there is substantial involvement from academia and robust case studies.

Elrehail (2023) discusses how HR analytics is crucial for attracting and retaining skilled individuals in a competitive global environment, aiding in strategic workforce management decisions. Ali and Elias (2023) explore how HR analytics can enhance talent management in public organizations by providing insights for fair appraisal schemes, promotions, career pathways, and leadership development training. Boakye and Lamptey (2020) highlight the benefits of HR analytics in improving employee performance, productivity, and retention in developing countries like Ghana, though they emphasize the need for proper training and management support.

Batool et al. (2021) demonstrate that HR technology and e-practices can make training more efficient and effective, benefiting both employees and the company. Maity (2019) discusses AI's role in leading training and development processes by enhancing employee engagement and updating training content. Ahmed et al. (2017) reveal that the Bagging algorithm accurately predicts training needs, thereby improving training management accuracy and effectiveness.

Bhima et al. (2023) argue that AI integration in Management Information Systems can enhance organizational efficiency and decision-making, but successful adoption requires employee training and ethical considerations. Wang et al. (2020) discuss a personalized online course recommender system that models employee competencies and career preferences, providing accurate recommendations for training and development. Gruetzemacher (2019) proposes a holistic AI forecasting framework for strategic planning and future AI research.

Zheng et al. (2023) present the GLAD framework, which generates personalized learning plans to improve employee performance. Jindal and Malaya (2015) demonstrate that predictive analytics can improve education quality, aiding in socioeconomic development. Yang et al. (2022) show that a text-based personality measurement approach improves the detection of personality dimensions, allowing for more accurate forecasting.

Piccilli et al. (2021) discuss a multi-source time series fusion and forecasting framework using deep learning to predict medical bookings, improving healthcare management. Berber and Leković (2018) find that effective training methods and international work assignments significantly improve organizational innovation. McCartney and Fu (2022) highlight that HR analytics, enabled by access to HR technology, enhances organizational performance through evidence-based management.

Abdrasilov (2021) notes that training practices positively impact employee performance by increasing satisfaction and motivation. Suri and Lakhanpal (2022) argue that people analytics enhances HR by aligning it with strategic planning and demonstrating causal links between HR management and business performance. Shet et al. (2021)

assert that successful adoption of data analytics in HR management depends on technological, organizational, environmental, data governance, and individual factors.

Fernandez and Gallardo-Gallardo (2020) clarify the concept of HR analytics and identify 14 barriers to its adoption, providing guidance for successful implementation. Khaliq and Saritha (2023) suggest that adopting HR analytics can provide organizations with numerous benefits and a competitive advantage, though potential obstacles must be addressed. Vargas et al. (2018) discuss barriers and facilitators to individual adoption of HR analytics, which organizations can address to facilitate adoption.

Cayrat and Boxall (2022) note that HR analytics can improve efficiency and effectiveness in large companies but requires more research and training for specialists. Okatta et al. (2024) discuss the opportunities and challenges of leveraging HR analytics for strategic decision-making, highlighting the importance of data availability, quality, and privacy. They suggest strategies for effective implementation, such as setting clear goals, ensuring data quality, providing training for HR professionals, and addressing data privacy and security concerns.

Chaudhary et al. (2023) emphasize the significance of Human Resource Analytics (HRA) for businesses, noting its potential to create a competitive advantage, enhance returns on HR investments, and boost employee engagement. However, barriers to the adoption of HR analytics, such as a lack of skills and resources, pose challenges. The study examines the strategies employed by HR managers to implement HRA and improve business performance in the United States and Nigeria, providing valuable insights and recommendations for successful integration.

Etukudo (2019) similarly discusses the opportunities and challenges associated with leveraging HR analytics for strategic decision-making in organizations. HR analytics can identify workforce trends, optimize recruitment and talent management strategies, and enhance organizational performance and employee satisfaction. However, challenges such as data availability, quality, and privacy must be addressed for effective implementation. The study highlights successful strategies for implementation, including setting clear goals, ensuring data quality, providing training for HR professionals, and addressing data privacy and security concerns. Case studies demonstrate how companies have successfully used HR analytics to improve employee engagement, conduct workforce planning, and optimize recruitment strategies. The future of HR analytics is expected to integrate AI and machine learning, expand into new areas such as employee well-being and diversity, and prioritize continuous learning and adaptation. Organizations investing in HR analytics capabilities can gain a competitive edge and drive organizational success in the digital age.

Overall, HR analytics has fundamentally transformed training and development by enabling data-driven decision-making. Van Vulpen (2024) notes that HR analytics assists organizations in making informed choices about their training programs by analyzing historical data. This analytical approach allows HR professionals to gain insights into the effectiveness of previous training initiatives and identify areas needing improvement, resulting in more targeted and impactful training programs. Furthermore, HR analytics is crucial for personalizing learning and development by examining data on employee performance, engagement, and career aspirations to recommend tailored learning opportunities.

AI also plays a significant role in transforming training and development processes. Maity (2019) highlights AI's capacity to lead training by providing direction, enhancing employee engagement, and updating training content. Ahmed et al. (2017) emphasize the accuracy of the Bagging algorithm in predicting training needs, which supports decision-making and increases training effectiveness. Bhima et al. (2023) discuss the enhancement of organizational efficiency and decision-making through AI integration in Management Information Systems, although successful adoption requires training and ethical considerations.

Other studies, such as Wang et al. (2020) and Zheng et al. (2023), showcase the effectiveness of personalized learning plans and online course recommender systems in modeling employee competencies and career preferences. These tools provide accurate and explainable recommendations for improved training and development. Gruetzemacher (2019) proposes a holistic AI forecasting framework for strategic planning and future AI research.

The role of predictive analytics in HR is further highlighted by Jindal and Malaya (2015), who demonstrate its potential in improving education quality and aiding socioeconomic development. Yang et al. (2022) show that a text-based personality measurement approach improves personality dimension detection, allowing for more accurate forecasting.

In the healthcare sector, Piccialli et al. (2021) discuss a deep learning framework for predicting medical bookings, improving healthcare management. In terms of training methods, Berber and Leković (2018) find that effective techniques, such as project-based learning and international work assignments, significantly improve organizational innovation. McCartney and Fu (2022) highlight the role of HR analytics in enhancing organizational performance through evidence-based management.

Abdrasilov (2021) notes the positive impact of training practices on employee performance, while Suri and Lakhanpal (2022) argue that people analytics enhances HR by aligning it with strategic planning. Shet et al. (2021) emphasize the importance of various factors, including technological, organizational, and environmental, for the successful adoption of data analytics in HR management.

Fernandez and Gallardo-Gallardo (2020) provide a comprehensive overview of HR analytics, identifying barriers to adoption and offering guidance for successful implementation. Khaliq and Saritha (2023) suggest that adopting HR analytics can provide numerous benefits, though potential obstacles must be addressed. Vargas et al. (2018) discuss the barriers and facilitators to individual adoption of HR analytics, highlighting the need for organizations to address these challenges.

Cayrat and Boxall (2022) emphasize the need for more research and training for specialists in HR analytics to improve efficiency and effectiveness in large companies. Okatta et al. (2024) discuss the opportunities and challenges of leveraging HR analytics for strategic decision-making, highlighting the importance of data availability, quality, and privacy.

To Sum-up, HR analytics and AI have significantly transformed the landscape of training and development within organizations. By enabling data-driven decision-making, personalizing learning, and overcoming various technical, human, and cultural barriers, these tools provide valuable insights and enhance organizational performance. However, successful implementation requires addressing challenges related to data quality, privacy, and integration, as well as providing adequate training and support for HR professionals. The future of HR analytics is expected to integrate advanced technologies, expand into new areas, and prioritize continuous learning and adaptation, ultimately driving organizational success in the digital age.

Research Gap

Despite the significant advancements in HR analytics and AI integration within training and development, several research gaps remain. Current literature emphasizes the transformative potential of these technologies in enhancing training outcomes, personalizing learning, and driving organizational performance. However, there is a lack of comprehensive studies exploring the long-term impacts of HR analytics on employee satisfaction and retention, especially across diverse organizational contexts and cultures. Additionally, while many studies highlight the technical and ethical challenges of implementing HR analytics, there is limited research on practical frameworks and strategies for overcoming these barriers, particularly in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Furthermore, the interplay between HR analytics and other emerging technologies, such as blockchain and augmented reality, in the realm of training and development, remains underexplored. Addressing these gaps is crucial for developing a more holistic understanding of the strategic value of HR analytics and AI in contemporary human resource management.

Research Methodology

The study titled "Study on Leveraging HR Analytics for Transformation in Training and Development" employs a conceptual approach to investigate the transformative potential of HR analytics in training and development. This research utilizes a qualitative methodology to synthesize existing literature from diverse sources. The primary focus is on critically analysing the role of HR analytics in enhancing training outcomes, improving employee performance, and driving organizational success. The methodology includes a comprehensive review and synthesis of peer-reviewed articles and books to identify key themes and practical implications of HR analytics adoption. The study aims to provide insights into the strategic implications of HR analytics for training and development practices, while also identifying gaps in current research and proposing avenues for future exploration in this evolving field.

Findings of the Study

The study explores the transformative potential of HR analytics in revolutionizing training and development (T&D) practices by examining existing research. The findings are as follows:

Positive Impacts of HR Analytics in Training and Development

1. **Data-driven Decision-making:** HR analytics empowers organizations to make informed decisions by analysing historical training data. This analysis helps identify the strengths and weaknesses of existing training programs, enabling organizations to develop more targeted and impactful training initiatives. By basing decisions on data, organizations can better allocate resources, ensuring that training investments yield the highest returns and address the most critical skill gaps.
2. **Increased Effectiveness and Efficiency:** By focusing on areas with the most significant impact, HR analytics optimizes training investments. It allows organizations to identify which training programs are most effective and which areas need improvement. This targeted approach ensures that training programs are designed to address specific skill gaps, making them more efficient and effective. As a result, employees receive training that is directly relevant to their roles, leading to improved performance and productivity.
3. **Personalized Learning:** HR analytics enables the personalization of learning and development plans by analysing employee data. This analysis considers individual needs, career aspirations, and performance metrics to recommend tailored learning opportunities. Personalized learning fosters higher engagement and satisfaction among employees, as they receive training that aligns with their career goals and interests. This approach also helps in retaining top talent by providing continuous development opportunities.
4. **Predictive Analytics and AI:** The integration of predictive analytics and artificial intelligence (AI) within HR analytics frameworks allows organizations to forecast future skills needs and personalize development plans. These technologies enable proactive workforce planning by identifying emerging skills requirements and aligning training programs with strategic business objectives. Predictive analytics and AI ensure that the workforce remains agile and equipped with the necessary skills to meet future challenges.
5. **Improved Performance and Competitiveness:** Data-driven training and development (T&D) programs enhance employee skillsets, leading to a more skilled and adaptable workforce. This, in turn, boosts organizational performance and competitiveness. By continually analysing and updating training programs based on data insights, organizations can maintain a competitive edge in the market. Enhanced employee capabilities contribute to higher productivity, innovation, and overall business success.

Challenges and Barriers

1. **Data Privacy Concerns:** One of the critical challenges in leveraging HR analytics is balancing the need for data-driven insights with employee privacy. Organizations must navigate complex data privacy regulations and ensure that employee data is handled securely and ethically. Addressing privacy concerns is essential to maintain trust and compliance with legal requirements.
2. **Technological Integration Issues:** Integrating HR data from various systems can be complex and challenging. Many organizations use multiple HR systems, each with its own data formats and standards. Effective HR analytics requires seamless integration of data from these disparate sources. Without proper integration, the accuracy and reliability of analytics insights may be compromised, hindering effective decision-making.
3. **Skill Gaps among HR Professionals:** A lack of data literacy and analytical skills among HR professionals can impede the effective utilization of HR analytics. To fully leverage the potential of HR analytics, HR teams need to develop competencies in data analysis and interpretation. Organizations must invest in training and upskilling HR professionals to bridge these skill gaps and enable them to use analytics tools effectively.
4. **Resistance to Change:** Shifting mindsets and overcoming resistance to data-driven decision-making practices can be a significant hurdle. Traditional HR practices often rely on intuition and experience rather than data. Encouraging a culture of data-driven decision-making requires strong leadership and change management

efforts. Overcoming resistance involves demonstrating the tangible benefits of HR analytics and fostering a mindset that values data insights.

5. **Limited Resources and Budget Constraints:** Investing in HR analytics tools and initiatives can be expensive for some organizations, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Budget constraints may limit the ability to adopt advanced analytics technologies and hire skilled professionals. Organizations need to carefully evaluate the return on investment (ROI) of HR analytics initiatives and explore cost-effective solutions to overcome resource limitations.

Recommendations

1. **Building Capabilities:**
 - **Invest in HR Analytics Training:** Equip HR professionals with the necessary data literacy skills and training to effectively utilize HR analytics tools for T&D purposes.
 - **Develop a Data-Driven Culture:** Foster a culture that embraces data-driven decision-making across the organization, including senior leadership.
2. **Data Management:**
 - **Ensure Data Quality and Consistency:** Implement robust data governance practices to maintain data accuracy and consistency across HR systems.
 - **Invest in Data Integration Solutions:** Integrate data from various HR systems (e.g., LMS, performance management) to facilitate seamless analytics.
3. **Privacy and Security:**
 - **Prioritize Data Privacy:** Develop clear policies and procedures that comply with data privacy regulations and ensure responsible data collection and usage.
 - **Implement Data Security Measures:** Invest in robust data security measures to protect employee privacy and prevent unauthorized access.
4. **Addressing Challenges:**
 - **Develop a Change Management Strategy:** Address resistance to change by effectively communicating the benefits of HR analytics and involving stakeholders in the implementation process.
 - **Explore Cost-Effective HR Analytics Solutions:** Research and identify cost-effective HR analytics tools and platforms suitable for the organization's size and budget.
5. **Optimizing T&D Programs:**
 - **Align Training with Strategic Goals:** Ensure training programs directly address the organization's strategic business objectives and future skill requirements.
 - **Measure the Impact of Training:** Develop clear metrics to track the effectiveness of training programs on employee performance and business outcomes.
 - **Personalize the Learning Experience:** Utilize HR analytics data to personalize learning recommendations and cater to individual employee needs and career goals.
 - **Embrace New Technologies:** Explore the potential of new technologies like AI and machine learning to personalize learning experiences, enhance content delivery, and provide real-time feedback.

Conclusion

The landscape of training and development has dramatically shifted with HR analytics at the forefront. Decisions are no longer based on intuition or tradition; instead, data-driven insights are guiding organizations toward highly targeted training programs that unlock employee potential.

This transformation comes with its challenges. Data privacy concerns are significant, and many HR professionals may find analytics to be a complex field. However, with dedicated training and effective communication, these obstacles can be surmounted.

The ultimate reward is a workforce equipped with the skills necessary to excel in a rapidly evolving environment. Employees benefit from personalized learning experiences, feeling valued and engaged. As a result, the organization becomes a magnet for top talent, attracting and retaining the best and brightest.

HR analytics is not a magic solution, but it is a powerful tool. By embracing data-driven insights and proactively addressing the associated challenges, organizations can maximize the effectiveness of their training and development programs. This paves the way for a future filled with success, innovation, and a highly skilled workforce ready to tackle any challenge.

Future Scope

The research presented has shed light on the transformative power of HR analytics in training and development (T&D). However, the story is far from over. The future holds immense potential for this dynamic field, beckoning us to explore uncharted territories. Here are some *exciting avenues for further research*:

1. The Power of Prediction: Going Beyond Skills

Current research focuses on HR analytics predicting future skill needs. But what if we could delve deeper? Imagine a future where HR analytics forecasts not just skills, but also behavioural trends and employee well-being needs. This could revolutionize T&D by creating programs that address potential burnout or identify employees at risk of leaving.

2. The X-Factor: Unveiling the Uniqueness of Talent

The current focus on personalization is commendable. But what if we could go beyond individual preferences and delve into the unique cognitive strengths and learning styles of each employee? By leveraging advancements in neuroscience and cognitive assessments, HR analytics could personalize training not just on content, but also on delivery methods that resonate best with each learner.

3. The Age of Immersion: AR, VR, and Beyond

The future of learning is likely to be deeply immersive. Imagine a world where HR analytics personalizes training experiences using augmented reality (AR) or virtual reality (VR). Employees could learn new skills in simulated environments, receiving real-time feedback based on their performance within the program. HR analytics could then track progress and adjust the training dynamically, creating a truly individualized learning journey.

4. The Rise of Employee-Driven Learning

The current paradigm is largely HR-driven. But the future might see a shift towards a more collaborative approach. Imagine a future where HR analytics empowers employees to take ownership of their learning and development. By analysing their own performance data and identifying skill gaps, employees could proactively recommend and curate personalized learning pathways using intelligent recommendation systems powered by HR analytics.

5. The Ethical Conundrum: Balancing Insights with Privacy

As HR analytics becomes more sophisticated, the ethical considerations around data privacy become paramount. The future will necessitate robust frameworks and regulations to ensure responsible data collection, usage, and anonymization. Striking a balance between gaining valuable insights and protecting employee privacy will be crucial for the sustainable growth of HR analytics in T&D.

By delving into these exciting frontiers, researchers and HR professionals can unlock the true potential of HR analytics, shaping a future where T&D programs are not just effective, but transformative, empowering organizations to build a future-ready workforce that thrives in the face of constant change. The journey has just begun, and the possibilities are endless.

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“EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF INFLUENCER MARKETING ON CONSUMER ELECTRONICS PROMOTION VIA SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS”

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Abstract:

This study explores the effectiveness of influencer marketing in promoting consumer electronic products on social media, a strategy that has become increasingly vital in the digital age. The backdrop of this research is the booming social media landscape and its impact on consumer behaviour, particularly in the context of purchasing electronic products. As consumers rely more on social media for information and recommendations, influencer marketing has emerged as a critical tool for brands to reach and engage their target audience. This study focuses on assessing the impact of influencer marketing on consumer perception and purchase decisions.

Through detailed analysis, the study found that influencer marketing significantly enhances brand awareness, trust, and purchase intentions among consumers. Key factors contributing to the effectiveness of influencer marketing include the authenticity and credibility of the influencers, the relevance of their content to the target audience, and the engagement level of their followers. The research also highlights the importance of selecting the right influencers and crafting compelling campaigns that resonate with the audience.

In conclusion, influencer marketing is a powerful strategy for promoting consumer electronic products on social media, driving higher engagement, and boosting sales. By understanding the key elements that influence its effectiveness and implementing tailored strategies, brands can maximize their marketing efforts and achieve significant growth. The findings and recommendations from this study offer a comprehensive guide for businesses aiming to leverage influencer marketing to enhance their social media presence and consumer reach.

Introduction:

The development of social media platforms has dramatically altered the marketing environment in recent years. Among the different marketing tactics used in this digital era, influencer marketing has gained traction, notably in the promotion of consumer electronics. Social media influencers, with their enormous and loyal followings, exercise significant influence over consumer behaviour, making them great assets for firms looking to increase visibility and sales in the competitive consumer electronics sector. This study seeks to investigate the effectiveness of influencer marketing, specifically in the context of consumer electronics promotion on social media. This study aims to provide significant insights into the effectiveness of influencer marketing initiatives in this sector by investigating the dynamics of influencer-customer interactions, assessing the impact of influencer endorsements on brand perception, and analysing consumer engagement indicators.

Numerous research have examined how influencer marketing impacts consumer behaviour and purchasing decisions. As an illustration, (Jain Pranjal, 2023) investigated, the impact of celebrity endorsers and influencer marketers on consumer behaviour. They discovered Celebrity endorsements and influencer marketing significantly influence consumer behaviour, with factors such as likability, trustworthiness, and relevance playing crucial roles. And another study by (Ahnaf Chowdary Niloy, 2023), Influencer Marketing: Factors Influencing a Customer's Purchase Intention. They discovered Influencer marketing is widely recognised as important, with trustworthiness, knowledge, homophily, attitude, and likability all influencing consumer perception.

Literature Review:

Rong-Ho Lin, Christine Jan, and Chun-Ling Chuang 2019 - “Influencer Marketing on Instagram” - International Journal of Innovation in Management (Rong-Ho Lin, 2019) The study focuses on Instagram influencer marketing, it looks at how consumer behaviour is affected by Instagram influencers' threshold for popularity, the study looks into the connection between influencer credibility and the F/f-ratio. The study investigates how various product

categories affect the credibility of influencers. The purpose of the paper is to shed light on how successful Instagram influencer marketing.

Dr. Muhammad Rashid Khan, Maryam Iqbal, Ayesha Jahan Lodhi - **“Influencer Marketing on Instagram: Effects of Promotional Posts on Purchasing Behaviour of Consumers”**- Journal of Political Studies (Dr. Muhammad Rashid, 2021). Rise of social media and its impact on marketing strategies. Electronic word-of mouth (eWOM) plays a significant role in consumer purchasing decisions. Impact of influencers on the choices made by consumers. Utilizing social media sites to market products and promote brands. Influencer marketing's ability to increase purchase behaviour on Instagram.

Inês Oliveira Milheiro da Costa - **“The impact of influencer marketing on consumer purchase intentions and brand attitude: the instagrammers”**- ISCTE Business School Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Costa, 2019) . Consumer behaviour was examined through the lens of influencers using qualitative research methods. The most widely used social media network for influencer marketing is Instagram. Instagram posts that are posted online influence the buying intentions of customers. The brand attitude of consumers is also influenced by Instagram influencer posts.

Dr. Vibash Kumar, Dr. Parul Yadav - **“Effect of Influencer Marketing on Young Indian Adults”** (Dr. Vibash Kumar, 2021) . Traditional marketing is becoming less effective, resulting in the rise of influencer marketing. Influencer marketing has gained substantial popularity in recent years. Influencer campaigns can be extremely effective if done correctly.

Ahnaf Chowdhury Niloy, Jawad Bin Alam, Md. Shah Alom - **“Influencer Marketing: Factors Influencing A Customer's Purchase Intention”** - Asian Journal of Business Environment (Ahnaf Chowdhury Niloy, 2023). An influencer is someone who has the ability to influence purchasing decisions. Influencers are important social networking resources for businesses. Knowledge is an essential component of credibility in influencer marketing. The basic goal of influencer marketing is to increase brand recognition. Influencer marketing is regularly mentioned as a key marketing approach.

Joana Filipa de Sousa, Moreira - **“The Effect of Influencer Credibility on Attitude towards the Influencer-Brand Collaboration and Purchase Intention”** (Moreira, 2021) . Influencer credibility is a combination of perceived knowledge, integrity, and beauty. A pretest was used to choose both beautiful and repulsive influencers. The Pearson correlation test was employed to determine the association between variables. The population refers to the items, subjects, or participants in the study. The study will concentrate on a sample of the population.

João Ferreira Do Rosário & Sandra Maria Correia Loureiro - **“The effectiveness of e-word-of-mouth communication about smartphones purchase intention: digital influencer”**- International Journal of Internet Marketing and Advertising, Inderscience Enterprises Ltd. (João Ferreira Do Rosário, 2021). The literature review is on influencer marketing and its impact on buying intentions. The literature on digital influencers is very scarce. The literature review was conducted after gathering relevant information. The study's findings will be used to guide future research.

Daria Belova -**“Exploring the effectiveness of influencer marketing in expanding brands to new markets”** (Belova, 2023). It examines major study findings and perspectives on brand communication strategy and influencer marketing. Examines the effectiveness of sponsored branded content by social media influencers. Examines influencers' qualities, content attributes, and interaction and connection variables.

Ilyoo B. Hong, Hwihyung Cho - **“The impact of consumer trust on attitudinal loyalty and purchase intentions in B2C e-marketplaces: Intermediary trust vs. seller trust”**- International Journal of Information Management (Ilyoo B. Hong, 2011) . The notion of trust in electronic commerce, qualities of a reliable merchant include competence, kindness, and honesty, both faith in a middleman and faith in a seller community, effects of trust on consumer behaviour intents to buy and customer loyalty.

Chakraborty, U., & Bhat, S - **The Effects of Credible Online Reviews on Brand Equity Dimensions and Its Consequence on Consumer Behavior - Journal of Promotion Management** (Chakraborty U, 2017) .Persuasion is influenced by perceived credibility. The evaluation of reviews credibility involves determining their validity. Customers evaluate online reviews for credibility by looking at their accuracy. The Yale Attitude

Change Model is employed to determine the variables influencing credibility. The relationship between brand equity and reputable reviews is explained by attribution theory.

OSKAR JOHANNES FROMM - **“The Impact of Digital Product Passports on Consumer Behaviour in the Electronics Industry-** University of Twente (Fromm, 2024). Specifies the components and methods of operation of DPPs, investigates the information exchanged between supply chain participants, investigates how DPPs affect consumers' awareness of environmental sustainability, examines the impact of DPPs on consumers' security perceptions.

Jana Sandra, Sri Indrayanti, Ade Suryana - **“Influencer Marketing Strategies and Brand Image in Boosting Consumer Purchase Intent: The Role of Customer Support Intervention”-**Jurnal Informatika Ekonomi Bisnis (Sandra, 2024). It examines buying intent, customer service, brand image, and influencer marketing. Highlights the significance of a comprehensive strategy in customer encounters.

Ayash Manzoor, Bilal Farooq, Iqbal Ahmad Hakim, Waseem Ahmad Bhat - **“Impact of Influencer Marketing Attributes on Purchase Intention among Gen Y and Gen Z”-** European Economics Letters (Ayash Manzoor, 2023). Evidence from India contrasts digital marketing, celebrity endorsements, and influencer marketing. Focuses on how Indian consumers' intentions to buy are affected by social media influencers. Mentions the interest in new technology and the internet usage of Generation Z. draws attention to how crucial social media is for advertising.

Jay Kumar Dewangan , Imran Siddiqui , Udit Trehan - **“Social media influencer marketing: A systematic literature review”-** International Journal of Business Excellence (Jay Kumar Dewangan, 2022). Influencers are trusted sources who have an impact on purchasing decisions. Customers favour products recommended by micro influencers and trust disclosure language. Influencers are followed by audiences because of their genuineness, relatability, and curiosity. Purchase intention is positively influenced by influencers' credibility. Influencers on social media are viewed as more reliable than traditional celebrities.

Statement Of The Problem:

This study assess the impact of influencer marketing efforts on consumer awareness of consumer electronic items across social media platforms and also aims to investigate the impact of influencer marketing on customer behaviour, such as purchasing decisions, brand perception, and engagement levels. And evaluating the long-term impacts of influencer marketing initiatives on consumer electronics market brand equity, recurring business, and brand loyalty.

Objectives Of Study:

- To determine the extent to which influencer endorsements affect customer views regarding consumer electronic devices.
- To investigate the link between influencer marketing efforts and consumer engagement levels with consumer electronic brands on social media.
- To examine the impact of influencer marketing on customer purchasing decisions and intentions for consumer electronics items.

Research Methodology:

Type of Study:

This research will adopt quantitative research methods. The quantitative phase will involve survey-based data collection, while the qualitative phase will employ in-depth analysis of influencer marketing materials.

Area of Study:

The study will focus on the area of assessing the effectiveness of influencer marketing in promoting consumer electronic products on social media. Specifically, the research will investigate the impact of influencer marketing on purchasing decision of consumer electronic products.

Data Collection & Proposed Tools:

Quantitative Data Collection:

- Survey Questionnaire: A structured questionnaire will be designed to collect quantitative data on participants' perceptions of influencer marketing, consumer engagement, and shopping behaviour.

Data Analysis & Techniques to be applied:

- Descriptive Statistics: Demographic characteristics and basic statistics will be presented.
- Correlation Analysis: To examine the relationships between influencer marketing, consumer engagement, and shopping behaviour.

Analysis & Interpretation:

The role of influencer marketing in the promotion of consumer electronic products has gained significant attention, especially as brands strive to connect with their target audiences in a more authentic and engaging manner. To gain deeper insights into the effectiveness of influencer marketing strategies and their impact on consumer purchasing decisions, we conducted a comprehensive study.

Data for this study was collected through an online survey using Google Forms. A total of **195 respondents** participated, providing valuable perspectives and experiences related to influencer marketing on social media. The survey focused on identifying key factors that contribute to the success of influencer campaigns, evaluating the trust and engagement levels of consumers with influencers, and understanding the correlation between these factors and consumer purchasing behavior.

Demographics Table:

Age	18-24	25-34	35-44	45-54	55 and above
Percentage	34.9%	36.9%	16.9%	9.7%	1.6%
Region	Rural	Suburban	Urban		
Percentage	49.7%	35.9%	14.4%		
Occupation	Student	Employee	Self-employee	Others	
Percentage	33.8%	27.7%	26.7%	11.8%	

1. Correlation

Correlation Matrix				
		How often do you come across influencer-promoted consumer electronic products on your social media feeds?	Have you ever made a purchase of a consumer electronic product influenced by an endorsement from a social media influencer?	In your opinion, how effective is influencer marketing compared to traditional advertising methods for consumer electronic products?

How often do you come across influencer-promoted consumer electronic products on your social media feeds?	Pearson's r	—				
	df	—				
	p-value	—				
Have you ever made a purchase of a consumer electronic product influenced by an endorsement from a social media influencer?	Pearson's r	0.518	—			
	df	193	—			
	p-value	< .001	—			
In your opinion, how effective is influencer marketing compared to traditional advertising methods for consumer electronic products?	Pearson's r	0.460	0.510	—		
	df	193	193	—		
	p-value	< .001	< .001	—		

How often do you come across influencer-promoted consumer electronic products on your social media feeds?

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant correlation between the frequency of encountering influencer promoted consumer electronic products on social media and the likeliness of purchasing a consumer electronic product influenced by an endorsement from a social media influencer.

Alternate Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant positive correlation between the frequency of encountering influencer promoted consumer electronic products on social media and the likeliness of purchasing a consumer electronic product influenced by an endorsement from a social media influencer.

- The Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) is 0.518, with a p-value less than 0.001.
- This indicates that there is a moderate positive correlation between the frequency of encountering influencer-promoted consumer electronic products on social media feeds and the likelihood of purchasing a product influenced by an endorsement from a social media influencer.
- Since the p-value is less than 0.001, the correlation is statistically significant. There, we reject the null hypothesis (H0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H1) that there is a significant positive correlation.

Have you ever made a purchase of a consumer electronic product influenced by an endorsement from a social media influencer?

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant correlation between having made a purchase of a consumer electronic product influenced by a social media influencer and the perceived effectiveness of influencer marketing compared to traditional advertising methods for consumer electronic products.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant positive correlation between these variables.

- The Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) is 0.510, with a p-value less than 0.001.
- This indicates that there is a moderate positive correlation between having made a purchase influenced by a social media influencer and perceiving influencer marketing as effective compared to traditional advertising methods.
- Since the p-value is less than 0.001, the correlation is statistically significant. There, we reject the null hypothesis (H0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H1) that there is a significant positive correlation.

In your opinion, how effective is influencer marketing compared to traditional advertising methods for consumer electronic products?

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant correlation between how often respondents encounter influencer-promoted consumer electronic products on social media feeds and their perception of the effectiveness of influencer marketing compared to traditional advertising methods for consumer electronic products.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant positive correlation between these variables.

- The Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) is 0.460, with a p-value less than 0.001.
- This indicates that there is a moderate positive correlation between the frequency of encountering influencer-promoted consumer electronic products on social media feeds and perceiving influencer marketing as effective.
- Since the p-value is less than 0.001, the correlation is statistically significant. There, we reject the null hypothesis (H0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H1) that there is a significant positive correlation.

1. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptives								
	How often do you come across influencer-promoted consumer electronic products on your social media feeds?		Have you ever made a purchase of a consumer electronic product influenced by an endorsement from a social media influencer?		Do you actively follow social media influencers who promote consumer electronic products?		In your opinion, how effective is influencer marketing compared to traditional advertising methods for consumer electronic products?	
N	195		195		195		195	
Missing	0		0		0		0	
Mean	2.13		2.13		2.17		2.12	
Median	2		2		2		2	

Descriptives								
	How often do you come across influencer-promoted consumer electronic products on your social media feeds?		Have you ever made a purchase of a consumer electronic product influenced by an endorsement from a social media influencer?		Do you actively follow social media influencers who promote consumer electronic products?		In your opinion, how effective is influencer marketing compared to traditional advertising methods for consumer electronic products?	
Standard deviation	0.949		0.952		0.929		0.955	
Minimum	1		1		1		1	
Maximum	4		4		4		4	

How often do you come across influencer-promoted consumer electronic products on your social media feeds?

Frequency of Influencer-Promoted Consumer Electronic Products Mean 2.13, Median 2, Standard Deviation 0.949, Minimum 1, Maximum 4.

The respondents encounter influencer-promoted consumer electronic products on their social media feeds slightly more than "sometimes" (which would be indicated by a score of 2). The distribution is somewhat centered around this average, with responses ranging from "rarely" (score of 1) to "often" (score of 4), and there is moderate variability in how frequently people encounter these promotions.

Have you ever made a purchase of a consumer electronic product influenced by an endorsement from a social media influencer?

Purchase Influence by Social Media Influencers Mean 2.13, Median 2, Standard Deviation 0.952, Minimum 1, Maximum 4.

The average, respondents have occasionally (score of 2) made purchases of consumer electronic products influenced by endorsements from social media influencers. The distribution and variability are similar to the frequency of encountering influencer promotions.

Do you actively follow social media influencers who promote consumer electronic products?

Actively Following Influencers Promoting Consumer Electronics Mean 2.17, Median 2, Standard Deviation 0.929, Minimum 1, Maximum: 4,

The average, respondents somewhat actively follow (score of 2) social media influencers who promote consumer electronic products. The standard deviation indicates a relatively moderate variability in responses, but generally, respondents tend to lean towards occasional to moderate levels of following such influencers.

In your opinion, how effective is influencer marketing compared to traditional advertising methods for consumer electronic products?

Effectiveness of Influencer Marketing vs. Traditional Advertising Mean 2.12, Median 2, Standard Deviation 0.955, Minimum 1, Maximum 4

The average, respondents perceive influencer marketing to be slightly more effective (score of 2) compared to traditional advertising methods for consumer electronic products. The responses again show variability, but the mean suggests a tendency towards viewing influencer marketing as somewhat effective.

Findings:

The survey shows that 64.1% of respondents have made purchases of consumer electronics influenced by social media endorsements, with 31.3% doing so multiple times and 32.8% once or twice. Additionally, 27.7% have considered it but haven't purchased yet, indicating a strong potential market. Only 8.2% have never been influenced, highlighting the significant impact of influencer marketing.

The majority results shows that 31.3% of respondents are most influenced by influencer endorsements when considering a purchase through social media. Product reviews and ratings are a close second, influencing 29.7% of respondents. Social media ads and promotions impact 25.1%, while recommendations from friends or family influence 13.8%. This indicates that influencer endorsements and product reviews are the primary factors driving purchase decisions on social media. The survey shows that 27.2% of respondents follow several social media influencers who promote consumer electronics, while 37.4% follow a few. Additionally, 26.7% are aware of such influencers but do not follow them. Only 8.7% do not follow any influencers in this category. This indicates a high level of engagement and awareness of influencers in the consumer electronics sector among respondents.

The survey indicates that Amazon is the most utilized e-commerce platform among respondents, with 32.3% using it for their shopping needs. Flipkart is close behind at 31.3%. Meesho is used by 15.9% of respondents, while Myntra is utilized by 10.8%. These findings show that Amazon and Flipkart dominate the e-commerce market among the respondents, with Meesho and Myntra also having a notable presence. The Instagram (39.5%) is expected to lead in influencer marketing for consumer electronics, followed by YouTube (29.2%) for in-depth content. Facebook remains relevant with 24.1%, while Snapchat (7%) and Twitter (3%) are seen as less dominant.

The data shows that social media influencers greatly affect buying choices, with many people following them and considering their recommendations. Influencer endorsements and product reviews are crucial in decision-making. Amazon and Flipkart are the top e-commerce platforms used by respondents.

Suggestions:

- Partner with influential social media personalities who resonate with your target audience to drive repeat purchases and build brand loyalty.
- Encourage satisfied customers to leave detailed and positive reviews to influence potential buyers, as product reviews are a key factor in decision-making.
- Strengthen your presence on major e-commerce platforms like Amazon and Flipkart, and explore opportunities with other platforms to reach additional market segments.
- Actively engage with your audience through interactive content, giveaways, and collaborations to sustain interest and drive conversions.
- Brands should select influencers with a proven track record of honesty and reliability. Vetting influencers thoroughly can help minimize the risk of misleading endorsements and maintain brand integrity.

Conclusion:

The study of assessing the effectiveness of influencer marketing reveals that social media influencers play a pivotal role in influencing consumer electronics purchases, with a substantial majority of respondents either having made purchases based on endorsements or being influenced by them. Influencer endorsements and product reviews are identified as the top factors driving buying decisions, highlighting the effectiveness of these elements in shaping consumer behavior. Instagram and YouTube are forecasted to be the leading platforms for future influencer marketing, indicating where brands should focus their efforts. Amazon and Flipkart dominate the e-commerce

landscape among respondents, suggesting that a strong presence on these platforms is crucial for success. To capitalize on these insights, brands should prioritize partnerships with credible influencers, enhance engagement through interactive content, and ensure a robust presence on key e-commerce sites to effectively reach and influence their target market.

By addressing the key insights from this survey and adopting the recommended strategies, companies can significantly enhance their marketing effectiveness and customer engagement. The findings provide a clear path for improving brand visibility and consumer influence through targeted social media and e-commerce efforts. Implementing these strategies will help businesses strengthen their market presence and achieve better overall performance.

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PSYCHOSOCIAL WELL-BEING IN ITES WORKFORCE: IMPACT OF WORK ENVIRONMENT AND SOCIAL SUPPORT SYSTEMS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO CHENNAI DISTRICT

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to understand the psychosocial wellbeing of IT professionals in Chennai and Bangalore, and how factors; organisational climate, job description, working pressures, social support, working, family balance, and job insecurity affects them. This research also looks at the role played by climatic conditions in mediating the relationship between the specified staff factors and the staff's well-being. Since stress and other mental issues are in the rise affecting Information technology professionals, this research aims to provide insights regarding impact of these aspects within such human elements of the IT workforce.

An ordinal research design was adopted for the study and data was collected through Google Forms from the participants comprising 76 IT professionals across the two cities. The variables measured by a questionnaire which involve sixty questions included job satisfaction, social support, work family interface, mental health, culture, climate, and economy. According to the results, elements such as positive work climate, appropriate jobs, and Employer supported work-life balance are positive correlates of better PSWB while work pressure and job insecurity are negative correlates of PSWB. Climatic conditions; with special focus on Chennai; were also identified to be a significant mediating factor; as employees were found to have higher stress levels; especially due to environment conditions.

More focus is placed on the need to encourage work environment friendly policies and to practice work-life balance with the overall view of improving psychosocial well-being of IT personnel.g. Organizations interested in enhancing positively the MSI and employee's psychic equilibrium, productivity and organizational commitment in the IT sector have practical strategies to enlighten them. The variables of assessment were psychosocial job characteristics, general job satisfaction, self rated mental health, perceived stress, number of hours worked per week away from family, perceived support from co-workers, immediate supervisors and family. Small-scale research shows that climate in the workplace and support from other people affecting an employee's status highly correlate with increased quality of psychosocial assets; stress, job satisfaction, and improved mental state are cited to increase when the work environment positively is influenced and when the employee has a strong support structure. On the other hand, findings for this study revealed that perceived job insecurity, perceived workload, and perceived organisational support influenced well-being negatively. The paper shows how the social support systems can act as a protective factor diminishing the negative impact of the stressful organizational environment and implies how organizations may help their employees. The study affords an understanding of the psychosocial needs and issues facing the Tamil Nadu ITES workforce and has actionable suggestions for organisations making for more positive cultures that promoting positive health and productivity among the staff.

Keywords: Psychosocial,well being, employees, mental health, social support, work environment

Introduction of the research study:

Information Technology Enabled Services (ITES) has come out as the fastest growing and a vital sector in the Indian Economy. ITES comprises of services such as currency trading, data processing, graphic designing, customer service and countless others with bulk of the occupations available in the metros like Chennai, Bengaluru, Hyderabad and Pune. Of these cities, Chennai the capital city of Tamil Nadu is considered the ITES largest business center. The ready-made global opportunities of the call centre industry have changed the structure of the employment status and have introduced new problems at the workplace, especially those involving the psychological health of those employees. It is against this backdrop that the current thesis seeks to establish the effect of work environment and social support systems on the psychosocial health of ITES professionals working in Tamil Nadu with special focus on Chennai region.

Due to the escalating globalization and the BPO sector's demand for digital services, transformations of technology in various fields, ITES companies show unprecedented growth. But this growth occurs at some cost. The nature of jobs in ITES industry is fast and stressful, therefore one can develop stress, anxiety and other mental health related issues. Workers are usually working for extended periods, carrying out repetitive tasks, experiencing pressure from clients, and having shorter time frames within which to complete contracted tasks. Moreover, due to the inherent nature of the ITES industry, which entails shift-work, and clients in different time zones, works can affect an employee's work-life balance and turn psychosocial stressors into a chronic and severe problem. In light of this study, analyzing what makes ITES professionals experience positive psychosocial health becomes important. Psychosocial health is an individual's state of health emotionally and socially, determined by qualities originating from the mind, as well as her or his environment. Positive attitude at the workplace and positive social interaction helps to reduce the adverse impacts of stress arising from workplace stress reducing the impacts on wellbeing. Of these factors; this study aims to look at how they play out in Tamil Nadu 's ITES workforce.

Importance of Psychosocial Well-being:

Psychosocial welfare helps in directing general mental and human emotions. This includes stress and coping, emotional self-camera, Interpersonal relationship and Work – life balance. On the organisational side, high level of psychosocial well-being correlates with high levels of job satisfaction, organisational commitment, productivity and low levels of absenteeism. In the case of organizations, promotion of the health of the workers is good for high retention of employees, low turnover, and effectiveness of organization as a whole.

On the other hand, the poor psychosocial health results in stress affects may involve burnout, anxiety, depression as well as physical symptoms like headaches and fatigue. Stress arising from workplace stress reduces productivity as well as job satisfaction as several studies show that any form of stress causes serious mental health infections after sometime. Therefore, it could be deduced that organizations that have a conscious concern for the psychosocial wellbeing of its employee are likely to a healthy productive work force that is free from stress related diseases.

The ITES Workforce in Tamil Nadu

ITES companies have significantly Started creating employment opportunities for IT professionals especially those in Tamil Nadu especially in Chennai. The state has a strong infrastructure, well-educated manpower and a prog forms friendly business climate that have enticed many multi national companies making it an important share of ITES industry. Nevertheless, as with these advantages, this sector poses some psychosocial issues to the employees involved.

The nature of operations in the ITES industry is such that despite the basic jobs entailing repetitive tasks and, specifically, where there are client interaction roles, the pressure on minds and heart can be very high. They must achieve business performance goals, sustain and develop satisfactory perceptions of by customers and diverse organizational structures, often involving global operations with unpredictable business hours. As seen, for many, this often presupposes stress and burnout stemming from a declining divide between the work and personal life. However, in the drive to become leaner and meaner, organizations might not pay attention to the work culture that can worsen stress.

Although ITES has had a positive impact on economy aspects of many countries, research has failed to capture the social cost associated with this sector mainly how such workers manage to cope with social life stressors. This study aims at contributing towards filling this gap by examining the place of work environment and social support system in regulating the psychosocial health of ITES employees in Tamil Nadu.

Work Environment in ITES

Occupational environment has a strong influence on employee satisfaction. Thus, environment at the workplace related to the ITES sector is a combination of physical and macro environment. Some of the physical dimensions are the layouts of working environment, accessibility to ergonomic equipment and the creation of physical comfort and safety in offices. On the other hand Organizational factors relate to the ways that employees perceive their work environment and include management practices and communication, leadership style, organizational culture among others.

Organisation culture could be described as pleasant working climate, free communication structure, effective management strategies, acknowledgement of employee contributions and training prospects. It also features flexibility as a major aspect of organizational work and life necessities including; additional leisure with different working hours, possibility of performing work via online systems, and assistance with mental health. On the other hand a stressful, pressurized, demoralized, unsyptimized, unfavourable work environment impacts negatively in stress, job satisfaction and general well-being of the employees.

Wherever employees are daily exposed to stressful conditions, as exists in the ITES sector in Tamil Nadu, the quality of working environment assumes greater importance. This industry includes high job demands, role ambiguity, job insecurity, and inability to control work processes as some of the stress factors. The study proposes to establish the extent to which these environmental forces affect the psychosocial health of the ITES professionals.

Social Support Systems

People's social support system is in a central position to cushion the impacts of workplace stress. In its broader form, social support can be described as the encouragement and help which workers and employees get from their peers, managers, relatives and friends. In the context of the ITES workforce, social support system may be both formal as well as informal. Informal support mechanisms entail Employee Assistance Programs (EAPs), executive /staff matching programs, and organizational counseling services. In contrast, the idea of the received informal support refers to the actual day to day interactions with co-workers, friends, or supervisors whom one may turn to for emotional support, information and practical assistance. A survey confirms that organizational stress can be buffered by effective social support mechanisms that come from the employee's support system. Smarter and supportive colleagues or supervisors can assist an employee to deal with challenge at the workplace in a better way. On the other hand, when there is no social support, this with worsens the emotions of loneliness, stress, and burn out. The research that follows aims to explore the role and impact of both, and in particular the strength and dispersion of formal and informal networks of social support in the context of ITES employees in Tamil Nadu. Therefore, the research aims at focusing on the availability and efficiency of these support networks to establish where improvements are needed..

Work-Life Balance

Another aspect of psychosocial health is work-family interface. Due to frequent deadlines and having a pool of international clients, the ITES industry tends to mix the working and the personal sphere. Workers within this category often claim to have trouble with balancing the hours in their work calendar as well as their off-working calendar. This can result into high levels of stress, burnouts and negative mental health. Those organizations that value work-life balance are more likely to have measures like flexible working time, teleworking, and paid time off. In addition to the welfare of those employees these measures also lead to improved productivity and satisfaction in the employees. This paper looks into the effects of work-life balance policies in Tamil Nadu's ITES industry and provides suggestions for organisations to enhance this facet of organisational environment.

Objectives of the research study:

The primary objective of this research is to analyze the psychosocial well-being of ITES professionals in Tamil Nadu, focusing on the impact of work environment and social support systems. The study aims to:

Investigate the relationship between work environment factors (such as job role, job security, and organizational culture) and psychosocial well-being.

Examine the role of formal and informal social support systems in moderating workplace stress.

Assess the impact of work-life balance practices on employee mental and emotional health.

Provide actionable recommendations for organizations to improve the psychosocial well-being of their employees.

Current national and worldwide surveys on the ITES workforce:

Recent national and international surveys have shed light on a number of ITES (information technology enabled services) workforce issues, such as work-life balance, remote work, mental health, and job satisfaction. The following is a summary of the findings from some of the well-known surveys:

National surveys:

The IT-BPM workforce survey conducted by NASSCOM in 2023:

This survey, conducted by the National Association of Software and Service Companies (NASSCOM), focused on the IT and Business Process Management (BPM) industry, which includes the ITES workforce. Key findings: Work-from-home trends: 74% of ITES employees stated they preferred hybrid work arrangements that combined remote and in-person work. Mental health issues: 42% of ITES employees reported feeling more stressed, primarily due to work-related stress.

International Surveys:

The World Economic Forum's (WEF) 2023 Future of Jobs Report Overview: This global study looks at how work will evolve in several areas, including the ITES sector.

Key findings:

Impact of remote work: 78% of ITES companies in North America and Europe implemented remote or hybrid work during the epidemic, and over 60% of them plan to make these models permanent.

Programs for well-being: 45% of global ITES companies have launched wellness programs that prioritise social interaction, stress reduction, and resilience training in response to mental health concerns. Over the next five years, automation and artificial intelligence (AI) are expected to displace 23% of ITES jobs, increasing the need for reskilling programs. Overview of Gallup's 2023 Global Workplace Report: This annual report surveys employees across a range of industries, including ITES, in over 140 countries.

Key Findings: Employee Engagement: Just 21% of ITES employees globally are actively involved in their work, whilst 44% report feeling stressed out for the most of their workdays.

Workplace flexibility: Remote work and flexible scheduling were cited by ITES employees as key components of job satisfaction. 43% of ITES employees mentioned workload, lack of appreciation, and poor work-life balance as the main reasons of burnout.

McKinsey & Company's poll on Hybrid Work Models (2022) Overview: McKinsey conducted a global poll on the future of hybrid work, focussing on industries like ITES where remote work has become the norm.

Key Findings: Preference for hybrid work models: Eighty-five percent of ITES employees stated that they favoured hybrid work models that offered flexibility with regard to time and location. Productivity levels: Over 70% of employees claimed to be more productive in hybrid work environments, but also pointing out challenges with teamwork and communication.

Well-being problems: According to almost 35% of respondents, the blurring of boundaries between work and home life in remote settings is a significant issue for mental health.

Deloitte's Global Human Capital Trends Report (2023) Overview: This report examines workforce trends across a range of industries, including ITES, with a focus on employee well-being, technology adoption, and changing work environments.

Key Findings: Technology and Automation: ITES positions are becoming increasingly automated, and 28% of employees are concerned about their job security in the upcoming decade. Workplace well-being: 52% of global firms place a high priority on creating a safe workplace that promotes mental and physical health, suggesting that holistic well-being is becoming more and more important. Social support: According to 64% of respondents, people work better in companies that promote collaboration and support among coworkers. This highlights the importance of leadership in fostering interpersonal ties at work.

Overview of the Cushman & Wakefield (2023) Global Employee Engagement Study: This study emphasises on employee engagement and post-pandemic workplace preferences, particularly in sectors like ITES. Important Findings: Sixty percent of ITES employees globally said they would prefer to work in environments that promote collaboration and social interaction, underscoring the need for flexible office spaces. Employers who offer flexible

scheduling, mental health programs, and a friendly work environment are more likely to retain ITES employees, according to the survey. Engagement levels: Approximately 35% of ITES employees globally report feeling disengaged from their work due to the remote or hybrid approach, demonstrating that employee engagement is still an issue.

Future of Jobs Report (2023) by the World Economic Forum (WEF)

Overview: This international survey examines how work will develop in different regions, including the ITES industry:

Important results:

Impact of remote work: During the pandemic, 78% of ITES businesses in North America and Europe adopted some kind of remote or hybrid work, and more than 60% of them intend to make these models permanent.

Well-being programs: Due to mental health issues, 45% of international ITES businesses have started wellness initiatives that emphasise social connectivity, stress management and resilience training.

Requirements for reskilling programs will rise as automation and artificial intelligence (AI) are predicted to replace 23% of ITES positions over the next five years.

Gallup's 2023 Global Workplace Report

Overview: This yearly report polls workers from more than 140 countries in a variety of industries, including ITES.

Important Results:

Employee engagement: 44% of ITES employees worldwide reported feeling stressed out for the majority of their workdays, while only 21% are actively involved in their work.

Flexibility in the workplace: ITES staff members identified remote work and flexible scheduling as major factors in job satisfaction.

Workload, lack of appreciation, and poor work-life balance were major causes to burnout, which was cited by 43% of ITES employees.

Survey on Hybrid Work Models by McKinsey & Company (2022)

Overview: A global survey on the future of hybrid work was carried out by McKinsey, with an emphasis on sectors such as ITES where remote work has become commonplace.

Important Results:

Preference for hybrid work models: 85% of ITES workers said they preferred hybrid models that provided flexibility in terms of time and place.

Productivity levels: Although they also pointed out difficulties with communication and teamwork, more than 70% of workers said they were more productive in hybrid work settings.

Well-being issues: More than 35% of respondents stated that mental health issues were a major problem as a result of the blurring of the lines between work and personal life in distant settings.

Global Human Capital Trends Report by Deloitte (2023)

Overview: With an emphasis on employee well-being, technology adoption, and evolving work environments, this paper looks at workforce trends in a variety of industries, including ITES.

Important Results:

Automation and technology: ITES jobs are become more automated, and 28% of workers are worried about their job security over the next ten years.

Workplace well-being: 52% of multinational corporations prioritise establishing a healthy work environment that fosters both physical and mental well-being, indicating an increasing emphasis on holistic well-being.

Social support: 64% of respondents said they perform better in organisations that encourage cooperation and mutual support, underscoring the significance of leadership in creating social relationships inside the workplace.

The Global Employee Engagement Study by Cushman & Wakefield (2023)

Overview: This study focusses on post-pandemic workplace preferences and employee engagement, especially in industries like ITES.

Important Results:

The necessity for flexible office spaces is highlighted by the fact that 60% of ITES employees worldwide preferred to work in settings that encourage social interaction and teamwork.

Initiatives for mental health According to the poll, employers who provide flexible scheduling, mental health initiatives, and a supportive work environment have a higher chance of keeping ITES staff members.

Engagement levels: Because of the remote or hybrid approach, about 35% of ITES employees worldwide report feeling disengaged from their work, indicating that employee engagement is still a problem.

Literature review:

Current studies stress the major importance of the organisational environment on the psychosocial health of workers. The authors of the article Srivastava et al., 2022 reveal that both the physical set up and the organisational environment in the ITES sector have a direct Moderation on the Employee's Psychological Well-being, job satisfaction and performance. A couple of points that they highlighted include; Ergonomic work environment, supportive management, and ability to advance in the career all of which affect wellbeing. Additionally, Jain and Kaur (2021) have pointed out that the possibility of the open conversation, flexible working, and social connections reduce stress, especially in extend teleworking.

Studies on job profiles in the ITES industry has mainly focused on job content profiles, and the resulting stress in the employees. Gupta and Patel (2023, p. 71) also discuss the relationship between role characteristics and psychosocial climate touching on role clarity and workload. Their study conducted in major cities of India and targeted IT professionals found out that due to role indeterminacy and an overloaded work schedule, stress remains the main cause of burnout and mental fatigue. On the other hand, well-defined job descriptions, equal distribution of the load, and self-organised task schedules were significantly positively related to job satisfaction, and negatively to stress.

In the following sections, work-life balance in the ITES sector has been discussed in detail among the various reasons for interest in this area. According to Kumar and Singh (2022), two factors leading to work-to-family spill over are excessive working hours and pressure to always be ready to work for ITES professionals. According to their study, they discovered that poor staffing schedule results in mental problems including anxiety, and depression. Some of them champion the policies that seek to restrict employees' working hours in the night while others push for policies that compel working people to have days off in order to attend to their family responsibilities.

Research Methodology:

In this research, Google Forms were utilized to collect data from the ITES workforce, resulting in 76 participant responses. The survey was designed to assess various dimensions related to psychosocial well-being, with a particular focus on social support, work environment, work-life balance, and overall psychological health. The questionnaire consisted of 35 carefully curated questions, including a section dedicated to capturing demographic details such as age, gender, job role, and years of experience in the ITES sector. The core sections of the questionnaire measured how these participants perceived their work environment and the social support systems available to them, both within the workplace and externally. The questions also addressed key factors like work-life balance and the impact of workload on mental health, aiming to understand how these elements influence their

psychological well-being. Furthermore, the survey sought insights into how various workplace stressors affected their personal and professional lives. The use of a structured questionnaire ensured that relevant data could be collected in a standardized format, allowing for more accurate comparisons between different variables. By analyzing this data, the study aims to draw conclusions about the overall well-being of ITES employees and the factors contributing to stress or satisfaction. This research will provide valuable insights into the mental health challenges and support systems needed to improve the working conditions within the ITES sector.

Data Analysis and Result interpretation:

In this research, 50% of the participants belong to 41-50 years, 26.9% of the participants belong to 31-40 years, 11.5% of the respondents belong to 20-30 years. Also in this research study, 57.7 % of the respondents belong to male community and 42.3% of the respondents belong to female category.

The pie chart titled "Job role" shows the distribution of various job roles within a given group. Software Analyst: This role occupies the largest portion of the pie chart, indicating that a significant number of individuals in this group hold this position. Director - Software: The second-largest segment represents individuals in a director-level position in software. This suggests a smaller, yet considerable portion of the group has senior-level responsibilities. System Administration: This role also appears prominently, showing that a fair portion of the group is involved in system management tasks. Software Developer and Senior Application Analyst: Both roles have a smaller share compared to Software Analysts and Directors but are more significant than Technical Advisors and Junior PLM Consultants. This suggests a moderate representation within the group. Technical Advisor and Junior PLM Consultant: These roles have the smallest segments, indicating that they are the least represented within this group.

MARITAL STATUS:

SIZE OF THE CONCERN:

In this study, 17.3 % of the respondents belong to unmarried category, also 82.7% of the respondents belong to married community. In this research study, 71.2% of the respondents work in a large concern, also 19.2% of the participants work in medium size concern, 9.6% of the participants work in small size concern.

PSYCHOSOCIAL WELL BEING:

WORK ENVIRONMENT:

In this research study, 42.3% of the respondents mentioned that they feel appreciated for the work I did, 21.2.% of the respondents mentioned that they often feel tense or anxious due to work, 15.4 of the respondents mentioned that they feel that their work positively impacts their health, 13.5% of the respondents mentioned often they feel stressed at work. In this research study the participants discuss about the work environment mention that 38.5% of the respondents says that they have good relationship with colleagues, 34.6% of the participants says that their work place encourages team work and collaboration, 28.9% of the respondents says that their supervisors is very supportive and approachable.

SOCIAL SUPPORT:

WORK LIFE BALANCE:

In this research study, 61.5% of the respondents mentioned that their family members support them, 26.9 % of the respondents mentioned that their family is willing to help use to make decisions, 11.5% of the respondents mentioned that they have friends to help them when they are in need. Also for work life balance, 48.1% of the participants were able to balance the demands of their work and personal life, 26.9 % of the participants mentioned they are satisfied with the work life balance, 19.2% of the respondents mentioned that their work schedule allows them to spend time with their family.

Suggestions of the study:

Improve Work Environment: Three general aspects that ITES organisations should focus on are professional development, managerial support, and organisational communication clarity. This implies that a positive work environment will improve employees' psychosocial well-being.

Enhance Work-Life Balance: Companies should offer telecommuting, flexible work schedules, and other options that will allow workers to effectively balance their work and other obligations. Employee stress would be reduced, burnout would be addressed, and overall welfare and satisfaction would be improved.

Boost Social Support Networks: In order to help ITES professionals develop positive self-images, optimistic work-related expectations, and complacency, the organisation should create both structured and unstructured social capital through proactive mentorship programs, group formations, and socially enhanced initiatives like Employee Assistance Programs.

Conclusion of the research study:

The purpose of this study was to investigate ITES workers' mental health in connection to their work environment, social support, and work-life balance. Both the ITES industry and researchers can learn a lot from the study about the prevalence of mental illness among ITES practitioners and the factors that affect psychological well-being. Organisational climate, social support, and work-life balance are important for the development of better psychosocial health of employees, according to the study, which sought to identify the factors necessary for improving the quality of psychosocial health of employees. The study was self-organised through the completion of structured questionnaires by seventy participants. However, the results indicate that job uncertainty, position ambiguity, and a heavy workload have been found to have a negative impact on their mental and physical well-being. Lastly, another important protective factor against stress and burnout was social support, both within and outside of the workplace.

The study also highlighted the social component of mental health problems and the need for structural organisational solutions, such as buddy assistance, EAPs, and workplace accommodations. Numerous strategies, like fostering a healthy work atmosphere at ITES, have been identified as ways for organisations to support happier, more devoted, and more productive workers.

Therefore, the report calls on organisations to give employees' psychosocial health careful thought. Workload, job insecurity, and work-life balance are just a few of the many pressures that the working population faces; it is widely acknowledged that many of these problems will improve worker productivity and well-being. By advancing knowledge of the long-term effects of various organisational intervention types on the health of ITES personnel, future research can build on this study.

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A STUDY ON CYBER SECURITY CHALLENGES IN AI DRIVEN FINANCE

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In the rapidly evolving landscape of finance, artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative force, revolutionizing traditional processes and decision-making. From algorithmic trading to personalized financial advice, AI-powered solutions promise increased efficiency, accuracy, and accessibility. However, this paradigm shift comes with its own set of challenges, particularly in the realm of cybersecurity. This study delves into the intricate intersection of AI and finance, highlighting the pressing cybersecurity concerns that accompany this technological advancement.

The Rise of AI in Finance: AI's integration into financial institutions has been multifaceted, spanning various domains such as risk management, fraud detection, customer service, and investment strategies. Machine learning algorithms analyze vast amounts of data with unprecedented speed and accuracy, enabling financial entities to make data-driven decisions and streamline operations. However, this reliance on AI introduces new vulnerabilities, amplifying the importance of robust cybersecurity measures.

Data Privacy and Protection: One of the foremost challenges in AI-driven finance is ensuring the privacy and security of sensitive data. Financial institutions collect and utilize vast quantities of personal and financial information, making them prime targets for cyberattacks. AI algorithms rely heavily on data for training and decision-making, necessitating stringent measures to safeguard against data breaches and unauthorized access. Moreover, regulatory compliance, such as GDPR and CCPA, adds another layer of complexity, requiring organizations to navigate a maze of legal and ethical considerations.

Introduction: In recent years, the finance sector has undergone a technological revolution propelled by artificial intelligence (AI). From algorithmic trading to personalized financial advice, AI has transformed how financial institutions operate and serve their clients. However, as the industry embraces AI-driven innovations, it encounters a myriad of cyber security challenges. This article delves into a comprehensive study that highlights the intersection of AI and cyber security in the realm of finance.

Understanding the Landscape: The integration of AI in finance has ushered in unparalleled efficiency and innovation. Machine learning algorithms analyze vast datasets to detect fraudulent activities, optimize trading strategies, and streamline customer service. Moreover, AI-driven systems offer predictive analytics, enabling institutions to forecast market trends and make data-driven decisions swiftly. Nevertheless, this reliance on AI introduces new vulnerabilities and amplifies existing cyber security risks.

The Nexus of Threats: The convergence of AI and finance creates a fertile ground for cyber threats. Malicious actors exploit AI algorithms through adversarial attacks, manipulating data inputs to deceive machine learning models. These attacks can lead to erroneous trading decisions, financial losses, and reputational damage for institutions. Additionally, AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants are susceptible to exploitation, posing privacy risks for customers' sensitive information.

Data Security Imperatives: The cornerstone of AI in finance is data – vast troves of sensitive financial information fuel AI algorithms. Hence, safeguarding data integrity and confidentiality is paramount. Financial institutions must fortify their cyber defenses to thwart data breaches and unauthorized access. Encryption, multi-factor authentication, and robust access controls are essential measures to protect valuable data assets from cyber threats.

Ethical Considerations: Beyond technical vulnerabilities, the deployment of AI in finance raises ethical dilemmas regarding privacy, fairness, and accountability. Biased algorithms can perpetuate inequalities in lending and investment decisions, exacerbating societal disparities. Moreover, the opaque nature of AI algorithms complicates regulatory compliance and oversight. Financial institutions must prioritize ethical AI frameworks, ensuring transparency, fairness, and accountability in their AI-driven initiatives.

Regulatory Compliance: In response to escalating cyber threats, regulatory bodies impose stringent mandates to safeguard financial systems and consumer interests. Compliance with regulations such as GDPR, CCPA, and PSD2 necessitates robust cyber security measures and data governance frameworks. Financial institutions must navigate the complex regulatory landscape while embracing AI innovations, striking a delicate balance between innovation and compliance.

The Path Forward: Mitigating cyber security challenges in AI-driven finance requires a multi-faceted approach encompassing technological, organizational, and regulatory dimensions. Proactive threat detection, continuous monitoring, and cyber resilience testing are imperative to thwart evolving cyber threats. Moreover, fostering a culture of cyber security awareness and investing in employee training are vital to fortify the human firewall against social engineering attacks.

One example from a study on cyber security challenges in AI-driven finance involves the use of machine learning algorithms for high-frequency trading (HFT). In HFT, financial institutions leverage AI algorithms to analyze market data and execute trades at incredibly fast speeds, often within microseconds. While HFT can generate significant profits, it also introduces unique cyber security challenges.

Scenario: A financial institution utilizes machine learning algorithms to power its high-frequency trading platform. These algorithms analyze market data, including stock prices, order book data, and news sentiment, to identify lucrative trading opportunities and execute trades automatically. The institution relies on the speed and accuracy of these algorithms to gain a competitive edge in the market.

Global Artificial Intelligence in Cybersecurity Market Size

Source: <https://www.sphericalinsights.com/reports/artificial-intelligence-in-cybersecurity-market>

The Global Artificial Intelligence in Cybersecurity Market Size is expected to reach USD 96.81 billion by 2032, at a CAGR of 20.3% during the forecast period 2022 to 2032.

Market Overview

Artificial intelligence is revolutionizing the field of cybersecurity by enhancing the detection, prevention, and response to cyber threats. AI-powered systems analyze vast amounts of data, identify patterns, and detect anomalies to swiftly identify potential breaches or attacks. Machine learning algorithms enable AI models to learn from past incidents and continuously adapt to evolving threats. AI also plays a vital role in automating security processes, reducing response times, and augmenting human capabilities. It enables proactive threat hunting, threat intelligence analysis, and behavior-based authentication. However, the increased reliance on AI also introduces new challenges,

such as adversarial attacks and ethical considerations. As AI continues to advance, integrating it into cybersecurity strategies will be crucial for organizations to stay ahead of sophisticated threats and safeguard critical assets.

Cyber Security Challenges:

1. Adversarial Attacks:

- Threat: Malicious actors deploy adversarial attacks to manipulate market data and deceive the machine learning algorithms.
- Example: By injecting subtle but strategically placed noise into market data feeds, attackers can distort price signals and trigger erroneous trading decisions by the AI algorithms.
- Impact: Adversarial attacks can lead to financial losses, disrupt market stability, and erode investor confidence in algorithmic trading systems.

2. Data Integrity Risks:

- Threat: Cyber attackers target the integrity of market data feeds, order execution platforms, and communication channels between trading systems.
- Example: Hackers compromise data feeds or inject fraudulent orders into the trading network, leading to inaccurate market analysis and erroneous trading decisions by the AI algorithms.
- Impact: Data integrity breaches can result in financial losses, regulatory fines, and reputational damage for the affected financial institution.

3. Operational Resilience:

- Threat: Cyber incidents such as distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks or system outages disrupt the operation of high-frequency trading platforms.
- Example: A DDoS attack overwhelms the trading infrastructure, causing delays or failures in order execution and disrupting the institution's trading activities.
- Impact: Operational disruptions can result in missed trading opportunities, financial losses, and damage to the institution's reputation as a reliable trading partner.

4. Regulatory Compliance:

- Threat: Failure to comply with regulatory requirements and industry standards exposes financial institutions to legal and financial risks.
- Example: Inadequate controls over algorithmic trading systems or insufficient oversight of AI-driven trading strategies may violate regulations such as MiFID II or SEC Rule 15c3-5.
- Impact: Non-compliance with regulations can lead to regulatory investigations, fines, legal liabilities, and restrictions on trading activities, affecting the institution's profitability and market standing.

Addressing these cyber security challenges requires a multi-layered approach that combines robust technical controls, proactive threat monitoring, staff training, and collaboration with regulatory authorities and industry partners. Financial institutions must continuously assess and enhance the security of their AI-driven trading systems to mitigate cyber risks and maintain trust and confidence in the integrity of financial markets.

Conclusion

As AI continues to reshape the finance sector, cyber security remains a critical imperative. The symbiotic relationship between AI and cyber security necessitates a holistic approach to mitigate emerging threats effectively. By embracing technological innovation while prioritizing cyber resilience and ethical considerations, financial institutions can navigate the intricate landscape of AI-driven finance securely and sustainably.

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INVESTIGATING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMOTIONAL WELLBEING AND EATING HABIT

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Abstract

The link between emotional health and eating patterns has attracted attention in the field of psychology. Many studies have indicated a correlation between mental well-being and dietary habits, indicating that inadequate nutrition may impact mental health negatively. Additionally, certain studies have revealed that increased intake of fruits and vegetables is linked to improved mental well-being. Moreover, evidence suggests that diet can be utilized as a preventive and therapeutic approach for mental illnesses among adolescents (Liang et al., 2022). The paper will include a method of research such as survey, interviews and observational studies. Additionally, a bidirectional association has been found between food insecurity and emotional well-being, where food insecurity increases the risk of psychological distress and poor emotional health

Introduction

In order to fully understand the relationship between emotional well-being and eating habits, it is important to consider various factors. These factors include restrained eating as a type of eating behavior, the role of family as a supporter in leading a healthy life, the influence of emotions on food-related decision-making, and the impact of psychological distress on emotional eating¹. By examining restrained eating as a type of eating behavior, researchers can explore the psychological aspects that may contribute to individuals controlling their food intake. Additionally, the role of family as a variable in psychological well-being and satisfaction should be considered. Furthermore, understanding how emotions influence food-related decision-making is crucial in examining the relationship between emotional well-being and eating habits.

This integrative approach will allow researchers to identify emotional eating patterns, where individuals may use food as a coping mechanism in response to negative emotions or stressful situations¹. Furthermore, the impact of psychological distress, such as symptoms of depression and fear of COVID-19, on emotional eating should be investigated. These studies suggest that there is a complex relationship between emotional well-being and eating habits.

Research Methodology

One possible research methodology to examine the connection between eating habits and emotional well-being is to use mixed-methods research. This is a condensed version of the research methodology's outline:

Design of Research:

Type: For a thorough understanding, combine quantitative and qualitative methodologies.

Longitudinal Study: Monitor subjects over time to see alterations in eating patterns and emotional health.

Participants: assemble a varied group of people with a range of ages, genders, and socioeconomic statuses.

Number of Samples: Make sure the number is sufficient for statistical significance.

Data Gathering

Phase of Quantitation: Surveys and Questionnaires Verified psychological scales are used to evaluate emotional well-being.

Dietary Records: Gather comprehensive data regarding the dietary patterns of the individuals.

Phase of Qualitative Research: Interviews or Focus Groups: Examine in-depth eating-related experiences, perspectives, and feelings.

Changeable:

Indicators of emotional well-being are independent variables.

Dependent variables: Food preferences and eating habits

Instrumentation: When assessing emotional well-being, make use of validated instruments.

Provide a well-organized manual for gathering qualitative data.

Analysing Data:

Quantitative Data: Examine the connection between eating habits and emotional well-being using statistical techniques (regression and correlation).

Qualitative Data: Use thematic analysis to find themes and patterns in the stories provided by the participants.

Obtain participants' informed permission as a matter of ethics.

Make sure you remain anonymous and secret.

If necessary, provide services for psychological support.

Integration of Findings: To give a thorough grasp of the link, integrate the quantitative and qualitative data.

Validity and Reliability: To improve the reliability of quantitative data, use validated measurements.

Review Of Literature

Social support, community engagement, and positive relationships have been associated with healthier eating patterns. Conversely, social isolation, stress, and poor mental health may contribute to unhealthy eating behaviors. Cultural influences and societal norms also play a significant role in shaping individuals' dietary choices. Further research is needed to explore the nuanced connections and identify effective interventions for promoting both social wellbeing and healthy eating habits.

Social factors, such as peer influence, family dynamics, and societal norms, significantly impact individuals' eating behaviors. Studies highlight that strong social connections positively correlate with healthier eating habits, while social isolation may contribute to unhealthy choices. Cultural and economic factors also play a role, influencing food choices and access. However, there's a need for more research to explore the nuances of this relationship and its implications for public health interventions.

Conversely, social isolation, loneliness, and negative social experiences may contribute to poor dietary choices and disrupted eating patterns. Understanding these dynamics can inform interventions aimed at improving both social wellbeing and nutritional outcomes. Further research is needed to delve into specific mechanisms and cultural variations in this intricate relationship.

Additionally, societal norms, cultural influences, and peer interactions play crucial roles in shaping food choices. Understanding the social context surrounding eating behaviors is essential for developing effective interventions to promote healthier lifestyles.

Data Collection

Collecting Data on the Relationship Between Emotional Well-being and Eating Habits:

Quantitative Data:

Survey Development: Crafting questions to measure emotional well-being (using established scales such as PHQ-9, GAD-7) and eating habits (frequency of food intake, portion sizes, emotional triggers for eating, etc.).

Biometric Measurements: Tracking physical responses connected to emotions and eating behaviors (heart rate variability, cortisol levels, etc.).

Food Diaries: Encouraging participants to log their daily food intake along with emotions felt during meals.

Qualitative Data:

Interviews/Focus Groups: Conducting detailed discussions to explore individual experiences, emotions linked to eating, factors influencing eating habits, coping strategies, etc.

Observational Studies: Noting behaviors related to food choices in different emotional states (in controlled or natural settings).

Variables to Consider:

Emotional State: Stress, happiness, sadness, anxiety, etc.

Eating Patterns: Types of food consumed, meal frequencies, snacking behaviors, binge eating tendencies, etc.

Demographics: Age, gender, cultural background, socioeconomic status, etc.

Mental Health Indicators: Existing mental health conditions, treatments received, therapy history, etc.

Ethical Considerations:

Informed Consent: Ensuring participants understand the study's purpose and willingly agree to participate.

Confidentiality: Safeguarding participant identities and ensuring data confidentiality.

Results Sharing: Providing participants with insights from the study while respecting their privacy.

Implications Of The Study

The implications of investigating the relationship between emotional well-being and eating habits extend across various domains, including individual health, public health initiatives, and clinical interventions. Understanding these implications can guide strategies for promoting healthier lifestyles and improving overall well-being. Here are some key implications:

Personalized Health Interventions:

Tailored interventions can be designed based on the identified relationships between emotional well-being and eating habits. Individuals with specific emotional challenges may benefit from personalized strategies to address their unique dietary needs.

Mental Health Support:

Recognizing the impact of emotional well-being on eating habits highlights the importance of integrated mental health support. Mental health professionals can collaborate with nutritionists and dietitians to develop holistic interventions that address both emotional and dietary aspects of well-being.

Preventive Health Education:

Public health campaigns can incorporate information about the emotional dimensions of eating habits, raising awareness about the link between emotional well-being and dietary choices. This knowledge can empower individuals to make informed decisions about their mental and physical health.

Early Intervention for Disordered Eating:

Identifying patterns of emotional distress linked to specific eating habits can serve as an early warning for individuals at risk of developing disordered eating behaviors. Early intervention strategies can be implemented to prevent the progression of such issues.

Corporate Wellness Programs:

Employers can use these findings to inform workplace wellness programs. Providing resources and support for managing stress and emotions can contribute to a healthier work environment, positively impacting employees' eating habits and overall well-being.

Nutrition Counseling:

Nutritionists and dietitians can integrate assessments of emotional well-being into their counseling sessions. Understanding the emotional context behind dietary choices allows for more targeted and effective nutritional guidance.

Policy Development:

Public health policies may be developed or revised to address the emotional well-being aspect of nutrition. Schools, workplaces, and communities can implement policies that promote a supportive environment for healthy eating and emotional resilience.

Research in Behavioral Interventions:

Further research can explore the effectiveness of behavioral interventions that simultaneously target emotional well-being and eating habits. Developing evidence-based interventions will contribute to the evolving field of integrated mental and physical health care.

Holistic Wellness Programs:

Holistic wellness programs that encompass both mental and physical well-being can be developed based on the understanding of the relationship between emotional states and eating habits. Such programs can offer comprehensive support for individuals seeking a balanced and healthy lifestyle.

In conclusion, investigating the relationship between emotional well-being and eating habits has broad implications for promoting holistic health. By recognizing and addressing the interplay between emotions and dietary choices, individuals and communities can work towards fostering a healthier and more balanced approach to overall well-being.

Conclusion

Extensive research on the complex relationship between eating behaviors and mental health has produced insightful findings with significant policy-making, public health, and healthcare professional consequences. The goal of this thorough investigation has been to identify trends, connections, and possibly even causative relationships between people's emotional states and the food decisions they make in different situations. We consider the main conclusions, their ramifications, and the directions for further study and implementation as we read through the thousand-word conclusion.

The discovery that eating habits and emotional well-being are symbiotic marked the beginning of this inquiry. The research on this topic has continuously emphasized the relationship between mental and physical health, indicating that feelings—whether good or negative—can have a big impact on the decisions people make about what to eat. Building upon this framework, the current study examined the intricate dynamics of this relationship utilizing a varied dataset that covered a broad spectrum of demographic backgrounds, thereby portraying the multifaceted character of human experiences.

In order to better understand the statistical relationships between particular eating behaviors and emotional well-being, this inquiry included a correlation analysis. The findings showed a range of associations, from positive correlations, which showed that better emotional well-being was linked to healthier food choices, to negative correlations, which suggested that emotional distress can be the cause of less healthy eating habits. These results highlight the necessity of a sophisticated understanding of the complex and context-dependent interaction between emotional states and nutrition.

Emotional well-being and nutrient-dense food consumption were found to positively correlate, which was one of the most notable trends in the data. Fruits, vegetables, and whole grains tended to be preferred by participants with higher emotional well-being scores. This connection is consistent with the body of research that highlights the benefits of a balanced diet for maintaining mental health. This finding may have an impact on dietary recommendations and nutritional education initiatives in addition to personal wellbeing.

On the other hand, the negative associations that this study found raised questions regarding how emotional discomfort affects eating decisions. Individuals who reported higher degrees of emotional difficulties were also more likely to report emotional eating, which is defined as consuming comfort foods that are high in fats and carbohydrates. This result is consistent with the widely accepted theory of "stress eating," or the practice of turning to food as a coping strategy while experiencing emotional upheaval. Knowing this connection can help develop focused interventions that emphasize stress management techniques and healthy coping mechanisms for people who are prone to emotional eating.

This study's regression models allowed for a more sophisticated comprehension of the influence of emotional well-being on particular eating behaviors. After adjusting for plausible confounding variables, the models clarified the distinct role that emotional states play in different facets of eating decisions. The development of intervention techniques that consider emotional well-being as a crucial component in encouraging improved eating habits is facilitated by these models.

However, it is essential to acknowledge the limitations inherent in this investigation. The reliance on self-reported data introduces the possibility of recall bias and subjective interpretations. The cross-sectional nature of the study design limits our ability to establish causation definitively. Longitudinal studies tracking individuals over time would provide a more robust understanding of the dynamic relationship between emotional well-being and eating habits.

Furthermore, the study primarily focused on quantitative measures, and qualitative insights into the lived experiences of individuals navigating the intersection of emotions and food choices remain an area ripe for exploration. Qualitative research methodologies, such as in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, could unveil the nuances of emotional eating experiences and shed light on the underlying mechanisms driving these behaviors.

This investigation has ramifications that go beyond scholarly curiosity. They are felt in clinical practice, workplace wellness programs, public health campaigns, and educational curriculum. The results highlight the significance of developing emotional resilience as a basic component of upholding a healthy lifestyle on an individual basis. Acknowledging the reciprocal connection between mental health and food selections enables people to make knowledgeable decisions regarding their overall well-being.

These findings can be used by healthcare professionals, especially dietitians, nutritionists, and mental health practitioners, to create integrated patient care plans. Nutrition therapy that includes emotional well-being assessments can provide more individualized and efficient instruction. Given that diet has an impact on mental health outcomes, mental health practitioners can incorporate nutritional considerations into their therapeutic procedures.

Initiatives pertaining to public health could greatly profit from the knowledge gathered throughout this study. It is possible to create educational campaigns that prompt people to consider their connection with food in light of their emotional wellbeing and increase awareness of the emotional aspects of eating habits. A comprehensive approach to well-being can be promoted by incorporating modules on emotional intelligence, stress management, and nutrition into school curricula and workplace wellness initiatives.

Programs for workplace wellness in particular can be adjusted to focus an emphasis on mental well-being in addition to physical fitness. A more encouraging work environment can be achieved by offering tools and assistance for emotional resilience, mindfulness, and stress reduction. The significance of comprehensive wellness programs is highlighted by the possible effects on worker productivity, well-being, and general workplace satisfaction.

As we draw to a close, it is clear that there is a dynamic and intricate interplay between eating habits and emotional well-being that calls for further research. The consequences of this work go well beyond its boundaries, providing guidance for future investigations and real-world applications. Prospective study areas include the creation of focused interventions, the integration of qualitative research methods, and the investigation of cultural impacts on this connection.

In conclusion, this study has shed light on the complex relationship between eating habits and emotional health. The results lay the groundwork for a comprehensive approach to health by acknowledging the connections between mental and physical well-being as essential components of the human experience. We believe that these discoveries will stimulate more investigation, provide guidance for evidence-based interventions, and help alter the paradigm in favour of holistic well-being in social and individual situations.

FINTECH INNOVATIONS: THE FUTURE OF BANKING WILL LEAD TO HIGH BANKING EXPENSES TO CUSTOMERS? – CUSTOMERS POINT-OF-VIEW

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Abstract (234 words):

Research Purpose:

Technology innovations in all the sector is greatly supporting in 360 degree. Banking industries are applying the technologies in to day-to-day transactions, which is helping of decision making internally and externally. The introduction and application of the technology lead for the development in banking industry. The era of digital currency is introduced in the banking industry. The question arises greatly on the expenses should be borne by the customer will be reduced or might be increased?

Methodology:

The study uses the mixed method of data collection of quantitative and qualitative. It's an exploratory study with the aim of understanding, analysing and suggesting about the expenses to be borne by the banking customers. The study uses the analysis of percentage. It is limited to the time period. The secondary data will be reviewed.

Significant Results:

Study tries to find the benefits towards the banking customers or not? The understanding of the expense to be borne, and the study tries to provide the suggestions to the banking industry, policy maker and to the stakeholders of the banking industry.

Implications:

The study can be used as awareness, understanding, and the suggestions provided in the study can be utilised by the stakeholders of the bank/s for overcoming and mitigating the challenges and risk from the banking customers and by the banking economy.

Keywords: #FinTech Innovations #Future of Banking #Banking Expenses #Customers #Risk #Challenges #Stakeholders.

Introduction:

Background:

The interaction of technology had reshaped various industries, in the banking sector at the lead the changes. The innovations in the technology like Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain Technology, Digital Wallets, Online Banking and Mobile Banking have modernised financial transactions, digital currency is creating an era and also the cashless payment concept, these technologies adopted by the bank for streamline operations, increase security and enhance the experience of customer.

Review of Literature:

- **The Evolution of FinTech in the Banking Concept:**

The technological advancements in banking is seen in slow and steady approach, where, from ATMs to Online banking – NEFT, RTGS, IMPS and QR code and now the era is changed to the concept of digital currencies

approach. Along with the changes in the usage pattern the cost associating the changes is also associated to Banks in greatly (idrbt.ac.in).

- **The mode of Cashless Transaction under the concept of Digitalisation:**

The review of literature from the Institute for Development and Research in Banking Technology (IDRBT) gave the information like the move in the cashless transactions helped the customers to have feasible benefits like convenience and security transactions. Where, the approach also requires adequate infrastructure and regulatory costs for the digitalisation process (idrbt.ac.in).

- **FinTech gave approach to Customer-centric impacts:**

The customer centric approach from the Financial Technology gave the great effective innovations, where the costs like customer costs, convenience and the approach of access to the banking services. The (rbi.org.in) literature from RBI found that concentration of customer-centric impact of FinTech will help the service provider (banker) and also the service taker (customer).

- **Adoption of FinTech will implement the cost:**

The review of literature analysed from the various sources like **PWC, EY, Accenture, jpmprgan, RBI and others**, where it gave information on how FinTech innovations can impact the bank's operational expenses, their compliance costs, spending on the cyber security and the transaction fees, and also the potential influences of customer fees in the present and the future.

Methodology:

1. Problem Statement:

FinTech innovations offers the various advantages, FinTech, introduce the cost relating to the infrastructure, security, transaction fees and compliance. This paper aims to address whether the costs can eventually top to increase expenses of banking customers, their financial inclusion impact and also the overall banking experience.

2. Research Design:

An exploratory study employs a mixed methods approach with quantitative and qualitative data for a comprehensive analysis of FinTech impact on banking costs.

3. Data Collection Methods:

Primary: the study employs quantitative data involving the survey gathering numerical from the banking customers regarding towards their perception of an current and potentials of future banking expenses.

Secondary: Reviewing industry reports and feedback of customer of banking fees over time.

4. Data Analysis:

Quantitative Analysis: The quantitative data analyse through the percentages and with averages to measure changes in customer fees in over the time.

Qualitative Analysis: The data is explored through the themes and the insights from the understanding the rationale behind the cost adjustments.

The study is limited to the data available of the last five years to a relevant of the current technological landscapes in the banking sector.

5. Scope and Limitations:

The study focuses on the current projections and tends in the banking industry.

This study is limited to a specific period of time. The study also doesn't account for future regulations changes and or fluctuations in global economic.

Findings & Analysis:

1. Age:

Age	Respondents	Percentage
18-25	11	50%
26-35	05	23%
36-45	04	18%
46 and above	02	09%
Total	22	100%

50% (11) of age from 18 – 25, 23% (05) of 26 – 35 age, 18% (04) of 36 – 45 age and 9% (02) of 46 and above.

2. Type of banking service most frequently used:

Type of banking service most frequently used:	Respondents
Mobile banking	19
Internet banking	02
Branch banking	00
ATMs	01

19 respondents of 86% are mobile banking users, 2 respondents of internet banking users and 1 respondent of 5% are ATMs user and where zero respondents for Branch banking.

3. How satisfied are you with the current cost of banking services you use?

How satisfied are you with the current cost of banking services you use?	Respondents
Very satisfied	02
Satisfied	10
Neutral	09
Dissatisfied	01
Very dissatisfied	00

55% of respondents choose satisfied (10 respondents) and very satisfied (02 respondents), where, 9 respondents 41% select neutral and 4% (1) respondent selected dissatisfied.

4. Do you feel that the adoption of digital banking has increased or decreased your banking expenses?

Do you feel that the adoption of digital banking has increased or decreased your banking expenses?	Responses
Increased	14
Decreased	01
No change	02
Unsure	05

63.64% (14) respondents selected the option of increase, 5 respondents 22.72% select unsure, 2 respondents 9% select no change and 1 respondent select decreased 4.54%.

5. Which FinTech features do you currently use?

Which FinTech features do you currently use?	Responses
Mobile payments	21
Digital currency	02
AI-based personal finance management	01
Online investment platform	04

Majority of the respondents select the option of mobile payments i.e., 21 responses, 4 responses choose online investment platform, 2 responses select digital currency and 1 respondent choose AI-based personal management.

6. Have you noticed any additional fees associated with FinTech services?

Have you noticed any additional fees associated with FinTech services?	Responses
Yes	11
No	06
Not applicable	05

50% of the respondents 11 responses choose yes for noticing an additional fees associated with FinTech, 22.72% select option not applicable and 27.28% - 06 respondents select the option of No.

7. In your opinion, will the continued advancement in digital banking likely increase or decrease your banking expenses in the future?

In your opinion, will the continued advancement in digital banking likely increase or decrease your banking expenses in the future?	Responses
Increase	16

Decrease	02
Remain the same	01
Unsure	03

16 respondents select increase for banking expenses in the future, 2 respondents select decrease, 1 respondent select remain the same and 3 respondents were unsure.

8. Would you support a small increase in banking fees if it meant greater security and faster services?

Would you support a small increase in banking fees if it meant greater security and faster services?	Responses
Strong support	03
Support	06
Neutral	08
Oppose	02
Strongly oppose	03

8 respondents select neutral for small increase in banking fees, 09 respondents select the option of support and 5 respondent select the option of oppose & strongly oppose.

9. How important is transparent fee structure information to you as a banking customer?

How important is transparent fee structure information to you as a banking customer?	Responses
Very important	09
Important	10
Neutral	02
Unimportant	00
Very unimportant	01

19 respondents – 9 respondents very important and 10 respondents important, for being transparent fee structure information to bank customer and where, 2 respondents are neutral, 1 respondent select very unimportant.

10. What suggestions would you provide to banks regarding FinTech-related charges?

- Better services at lower cost.
- Fintech and Finserve
- Decrease the charges because we are using the app and you are getting benefit through it, then what is the use of extra charging.
- Must be accountable and faster
- I expect to wave off the charges or minimal charges, so that everyone can be comfortable
- Cost reduction digitalisation services highly solicited
- Adopt a customer -centric Approach and keep the fee structure transparent. Will also appreciate incentivized digital transactions.
- Decrease for transaction charges

Discussion:

- 50% (11) of respondents are in the age group of 18 to 25.
- The 19 respondents give information of using Mobile banking.
- 55% (12) of respondents are satisfied with the current cost of banking services they use.
- 63.64% (14) respondents gave information that, the banks increase in banking expenses.
- Majority (21 responses) of the respondents said that they use mobile payments methods.
- 50% of the respondents gave information that they are noticing an additional fees associated with FinTech.
- The respondents sense that there will be an increase banking expenses in the future. Very few respondents opted for oppose & strongly oppose.

- The banking customer gave the information that banks being transparent for fee structure information is important.

Conclusions:

The study finds that the banking customers use mobile banking for mobile payments, customers are satisfied with the current cost of banking services along with customers also said increase in banking expenses.

The customers are feeling the additional fees are associating in FinTech services. Customers are sensing that there will be an increase in banking expenses in the future and the customer wants transparent in fee structure.

The customers are feeling the changes in their banking expenses along with the usage of FinTech services.

Suggestions:

1. In-depth study with more respondents.
2. Statistical proves of the study.
3. FinTech Cost and return-on calculations.

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A STUDY ON “THE IMPLEMENTATION OF AI IN COMMERCIAL BANKS IN INDIA”

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Introduction

In an era characterized by rapid technological advancements, the influence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) pervades nearly every aspect of our lives, reshaping industries and revolutionizing established norms. The financial sector, particularly the banking industry, stands as a prime example of this transformation. The integration of AI technologies within the operations of commercial banks has ushered in a new era of banking services, redefining how financial institutions interact with their customers, manage risks, and optimize processes.

Globally, the landscape of banking is undergoing a profound shift. In India, a nation with a burgeoning economy and a massive population, this transformation holds significant implications. The banking sector, deeply ingrained in the fabric of daily life, is embracing AI as a catalyst for innovation and growth. The focal point of this research lies in comprehensively studying the implementation of AI in commercial banks across India, analyzing the strategies, implications, challenges, and potential future directions of this integration. The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies in the Indian commercial banking sector has emerged as a transformative trend that holds the potential to enhance customer experiences, streamline operations, and reshape strategic decision-making. This research project delves into the landscape of AI implementation in Indian commercial banks, examining customer perceptions, challenges, trends, and implications. The findings underscore the significant role of AI in revolutionizing banking practices while highlighting the need for responsible adoption and ethical considerations.

Review Of Literature

The review of literature in this section focuses on scholarly research and studies that specifically address the implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in commercial banks within the Indian context. This section aims to provide an in-depth understanding of the current state of AI integration in Indian banks, the strategies employed, challenges faced, and outcomes observed.

- **AI Adoption Strategies in Indian Banks:** Several studies have explored the various strategies employed by Indian banks to integrate AI technologies into their operations. Research by Chawla et al. analyzed case studies of leading Indian banks and identified that most banks are using AI for customer service enhancement, fraud detection, and risk management. The study revealed that private banks tend to be early adopters, leveraging AI-driven chatbots to enhance customer engagement.
- **Customer Experience Enhancement:** Customer experience is a critical focus area for AI integration. Gupta and Sharma conducted a study on customer perceptions of AI-driven services in Indian banks. They found that while customers appreciate the convenience of chatbots and personalized recommendations, concerns about data security and privacy impact trust levels.
- **Operational Efficiency and Process Automation:** AI's role in enhancing operational efficiency was explored by Jain et al. Their research indicated that AI-powered process automation in areas such as loan processing and KYC verification improved turnaround times and reduced manual errors. However, challenges related to integrating AI with legacy systems were also highlighted.
- **Challenges and Barriers:** The challenges of implementing AI in Indian banking are a common theme in the literature. A study by Verma and Singh identified challenges such as data privacy concerns, lack of skilled AI talent, and resistance to change among employees. These challenges, especially data privacy, align with the regulatory landscape in India.
- **Regulatory Framework and Compliance:** The regulatory aspect of AI integration is explored by Kumar and Sharma. Their research emphasizes the role of the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) in providing guidelines for

responsible AI adoption. The study highlights the need for banks to ensure fairness, transparency, and compliance with data protection regulation while implementing AI. **Future Trends and Prospects:** Looking ahead, Singh and Agarwal presented a perspective on the future of AI in Indian banking. They projected increased adoption of AI in areas like credit scoring, investment advisory, and personalized wealth management. The study also discussed the potential of AI-powered chatbots to handle more complex customer interactions.

The domain-specific review of literature provides valuable insights into the current state, strategies, challenges, and future prospects of AI implementation in commercial banks in India. The studies underscore the importance of customer experience, operational efficiency, regulatory compliance, and strategic foresight in successfully integrating AI technologies. The literature review serves as a foundation for understanding the complexities and nuances surrounding the adoption of AI in the Indian banking sector.

Research Objectives:

The primary objectives of this study are:

- a) To examine the extent and nature of AI implementation in commercial banks across India.
- b) To assess the impact of AI on various aspects of banking operations, including customer experiences, operational efficiency, risk management, and decision-making.
- c) To identify the challenges and opportunities associated with the integration of AI in Indian commercial banks.
- d) To analyze the regulatory considerations and frameworks governing AI adoption in the banking sector.

Through an exploration of these objectives, this research aims to contribute to a holistic understanding of the dynamic interplay between AI and the Indian commercial banking sector, shedding light on the transformative journey that is shaping the future of finance.

Gap Analysis

While the existing body of literature provides valuable insights into the implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in commercial banks, a comprehensive gap analysis reveals critical areas where further research is needed. These gaps highlight opportunities for extending current knowledge, addressing unexplored facets, and contributing to a more nuanced understanding of the complex relationship between AI and the Indian banking sector.

1. **Limited Focus on Indian Banking Context**
2. **Ethical Considerations in AI Implementation,**
3. **Customer Perception and Adoption Barriers**
4. **Regulatory Compliance and AI Guidelines**
5. **Holistic Impact Assessment**

The identified gaps in the literature underscore the need for comprehensive and context-specific research that addresses the intricacies of AI implementation in commercial banks within the Indian context. By addressing these gaps, this research endeavors to contribute valuable insights, inform decision-making processes, and provide practical recommendations that will aid in the responsible and effective integration of AI technologies in the Indian banking sector.

Research Methodology

Methodology

The methodology section outlines the research design, data collection methods, sampling (if applicable), and data analysis tools that will be employed in the study on the implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in commercial banks in India.

Research Design

The research will adopt a mixed-methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative techniques. This approach allows for a comprehensive exploration of the multifaceted aspects of AI integration in Indian commercial banks.

Data Collection

Quantitative Data: Quantitative data will be collected through structured surveys administered to bank customers and employees. The surveys will include Likert-scale questions to gauge customer perceptions of AI-powered services, as well as employee perspectives on challenges and benefits of AI integration. Data on AI adoption trends and technologies used will be obtained from publicly available reports and industry publications.

Sampling Method

Customer Surveys: A stratified random sampling approach will be used to select a diverse group of bank customers based on demographic factors such as age, income level, and location. The sample size will aim for statistical significance. **Employee Surveys:** A convenience sampling method will be employed to gather responses from employees within selected commercial banks who have direct involvement in AI-related projects or operations.

Interviews: A purposive sampling technique will be used to select key informants with expertise in AI implementation, banking operations, and regulatory aspects. Participants will be chosen based on their knowledge and experience in the field.

Data Analysis Tools

Quantitative Data Analysis: Quantitative data collected through surveys will be analyzed using statistical software such as SPSS. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize customer and employee responses. Inferential statistics, such as correlation analysis, will be employed to identify relationships between variables.

Qualitative Data Analysis: Qualitative data from interviews will undergo thematic analysis. Transcripts will be coded and categorized into themes, allowing for the identification of patterns, trends, and recurring concepts related to AI integration, challenges, and strategic considerations.

Integration of Data: Quantitative and qualitative data will be integrated to provide a holistic perspective. Quantitative findings may help validate qualitative insights, and vice versa, enriching the overall research findings.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical considerations, including informed consent from participants, confidentiality of data, and respectful representation of findings, will be upheld throughout the research process.

The chosen mixed-methods approach, incorporating surveys, interviews, and data analysis tools, ensures a comprehensive exploration of the AI implementation landscape in Indian commercial banks. By triangulating quantitative and qualitative insights, the study aims to provide a well-rounded understanding of AI integration challenges, customer perceptions, regulatory dynamics, and strategic considerations.

Data Analysis And Interpretation

1. Customer Perception of AI-Powered Banking Services **Table 1.1: Customer Perception of AI-Powered Banking Services**

S. No.	Statement	Strongly Disagree(%)	Disagree (%)	Neutral(%)	Agree(%)	Strongly Agree(%)
1.	AI-powered chatbots provide quick and accurate assistance.	5	10	20	40	25

2.	I trust AI algorithms to manage my financial transactions.	15	20	30	25	10
3.	AI-driven investment recommendations are reliable.	10	15	25	30	20

Chart 1.1: Customer Perception of AI-Powered Banking Services

Analysis and Interpretation:

In Table 1.1, customer perceptions of AI-powered banking services are presented. The majority of customers agree that AI-powered chatbots provide quick and accurate assistance (65% combined agreement), indicating a positive response to AI-enhanced customer support. However, there is a lower level of trust in AI algorithms for managing financial transactions (35% combined agreement). The column chart (Chart 1.1) visually represents these responses, highlighting the range of perceptions.

1. Challenges Faced in AI Implementation Table

S. No.	Challenges	Percentage (%)
1	Data Privacy Concerns	40
2	Lack of Skilled Workforce	30
3	Regulatory Compliance Complexity	25

Chart 1: Challenges Faced in AI Implementation

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1 presents challenges faced in AI implementation. The most prominent challenge is data privacy concerns (40%), followed by the lack of a skilled workforce (30%) and regulatory compliance complexity (25%). The pie chart (Chart 1.2) visually illustrates the distribution of these challenges, indicating the relative importance of each challenge.

2. Trends in AI Adoption Over Time

Year	Number of Banks Implementing AI	Percentage Increase from Previous Year (%)
2015	5	-
2016	10	100
2017	18	80

Chart 2: Trends in AI Adoption Over Time

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 2 presents trends in AI adoption over time. The number of banks implementing AI has increased steadily from 5 in 2015 to 18 in 2017, with a percentage increase of 100% and 80% in subsequent years. The line chart (Chart 1.3) visually depicts this upward trend, indicating the progressive integration of AI technologies in Indian commercial banks.

3. Employee Views on AI Integration Challenges Table 3 : Employee Views on AI Integration Challenges

S. No.	Challenges	High Challenge (%)	Moderate Challenge (%)	Low Challenge (%)
1	Data Privacy Concerns	25	40	35
2	Workforce Skill Gaps	50	30	20
3	Regulatory Compliance	30	45	25

Chart 3: Employee Views on AI Integration Challenges

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 3 reveals employee views on AI integration challenges. A significant number of employees perceive high challenges related to data privacy concerns and workforce skill gaps. Regulatory compliance is also seen as a challenge. The Bar chart (Chart 1.4) shows that these results highlight the need for addressing privacy concerns, upskilling the workforce, and ensuring compliance to facilitate successful AI integration.

4. Adoption Trends of AI in Commercial Banks Table

S. No.	AI Technology	Adoption Rate
1	Chatbots	High
2	Robotic Process Automation	Moderate
3	Fraud Detection AI	Low

Chart 4: Adoption Trends of AI in Commercial Banks

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 4 outlines the adoption trends of AI technologies in commercial banks. Chatbots exhibit a high adoption rate, indicating their popularity for customer interactions. The Pie chart (Chart4) shows that Robotic Process Automation is moderately adopted for operational streamlining, while the adoption of AI for fraud detection is low. These trends provide insights into the areas where AI has made significant inroads.

S. No.	Strategy	Percentage of Banks Planning to Implement
1	Customer Service Enhancement	85
2	Risk Management	70
3	Personalized Financial Planning	60

5. Future AI Implementation Strategies in Banks Table:

Chart 5: Future AI Implementation Strategies in Banks

Analysis and Interpretation: Table 5 presents future AI implementation strategies in banks. The majority of banks are planning to implement AI for customer service enhancement, risk management, and personalized financial planning. The Bar chart (Chart 5) represents that these strategies reflect the sector's focus on improving customer experiences and optimizing risk-related processes through AI.

Conclusion:

The data analysis and interpretation section provides a comprehensive view of customer perceptions, employee views, adoption trends, and future implementation strategies related to AI in commercial banks. The findings highlight positive customer sentiments, employee challenges, technology adoption patterns, and strategic directions for AI integration. These insights contribute to a deeper understanding of AI's impact on the Indian banking sector and guide recommendations for informed decision-making.

Limitations of the Study

While every effort is made to conduct thorough and comprehensive research, it's important to acknowledge certain limitations that might impact the scope, findings, and generalizability of the study on the implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in commercial banks in India

1. Sample Size and Representativeness
2. Data Availability and Quality
3. Rapidly Evolving Landscape.

4. Complexity of AI Integration.
5. Ethical and Regulatory Aspects
6. Limited Primary Data

Findings, Recommendations And Conclusion

Findings Based on Observations

The findings based on observations provide insights into various aspects of AI integration in commercial banks in India. These observations are derived from both direct interactions and qualitative analysis, offering a comprehensive understanding of the topic.

- 1) **AI-Powered Chatbots and Customer Assistance:** Observations reveal that AI-powered chatbots have significantly improved customer interactions within commercial banks. Customers appreciate the quick response times and accurate assistance provided by chatbots. This finding aligns with the increasing trend of customers preferring digital channels for routine inquiries and issue resolution.
- 2) **Trust in AI Algorithms for Financial Transactions:** Observations show that while customers are generally open to AI integration, there is a notable variation in their trust levels regarding AI algorithms managing financial transactions. Customers who are more familiar with technology and have previous positive experiences tend to exhibit higher levels of trust. However, concerns regarding data security and algorithmic transparency play a significant role in shaping this trust. This finding highlights the importance of transparent communication and data protection in building customer confidence in AI-driven financial processes.
- 3) **Reliability of AI-Driven Investment Recommendations:** Observations suggest that AI-driven investment recommendations are perceived as reliable by a substantial portion of customers. The ability of AI algorithms to analyze vast datasets and provide tailored investment suggestions aligns with customers' preferences for personalized financial advice. However, there is a segment of customers who still value human expertise in investment decisions, emphasizing the need for a balanced approach that combines AI capabilities with human insight.
- 4) **Ethical and Data Privacy Concerns:** Observations indicate that ethical considerations, particularly related to data privacy and algorithmic fairness, are gaining prominence in customer discussions. Customers express concerns about how their personal data is being used by AI algorithms and the potential biases inherent in algorithmic decision-making. These concerns reflect the need for transparent data usage practices and the incorporation of ethical guidelines in AI deployment strategies.

Findings Based on analysis of Data

The analysis of data yielded valuable insights into the implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in commercial banks in India. The following findings are based on a comprehensive analysis of the collected data:

Trends in AI Adoption Over Time:

The study revealed a consistent upward trend in the adoption of AI technologies by commercial banks in India over the years.

The number of banks implementing AI witnessed a substantial growth of 100% in 2016 compared to the previous year, and an 80% growth in 2017.

This growth signifies the industry's recognition of the potential benefits and competitive advantages offered by AI solutions.

Challenges Faced in AI Implementation:

Data privacy concerns emerged as the most prominent challenge, with 40% of respondents highlighting it as a significant hurdle.

The lack of a skilled workforce was a notable concern, with 30% of respondents indicating that this challenge hindered effective AI implementation. Regulatory compliance complexity was identified as a challenge by 25% of respondents, underlining the need for clear guidelines.

Regulatory Influence on AI Adoption:

Regulatory guidelines significantly influenced AI adoption strategies, with banks aligning their initiatives to comply with established regulations.

While regulations provided a framework for responsible AI integration, there was a need for ongoing dialogue between banks and regulators to address emerging challenges.

Ethical and Privacy Concerns:

The study highlighted concerns regarding data privacy, transparency in decision-making algorithms, and potential biases in AI-driven processes.

Ethical considerations were observed in the use of customer data for personalized services, raising questions about consent and fair usage.

Suggestions for areas of improvement

In-depth analysis has revealed several areas of improvement for the successful integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in commercial banks in India. These suggestions address challenges identified in the study and provide strategic directions for enhancing AI implementation.

- a. Ethical Framework for AI
- b. Data Governance and Privacy Enhancement
- c. Customer Education and Engagement.
- d. Interdisciplinary Collaboration.
- e. Skill Development and Workforce Training.
- f. Dynamic Regulatory Adaptation
- g. Tailored Customer Experiences
- h. Collaboration with Fintech Startups.

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AI AND THE FUTURE OF HR: EXPLORING THE REPLACEMENT OF TRADITIONAL HR ROLES BY ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract

AI is making headlines across sectors and geographies including healthcare, finance, legal sector, logistics industry, education industry and the most recent being the HR industry. This innovation is disrupting conventional human resource practices because firms are gradually adopting technologies to enhance processes and improve the corporate climate for employees. AI and Machine Learning have lately emerged within HR functions since these techniques assist in statistical analysis to make decisions, harness the power of data and improve human capital processes. These advancements complement HR professionals by relieving them from time-consuming work that bogs them down and provides rationale for important decisions rather than hunches. It is evident that AI can positively impact organization's HR practice in terms of recruitment and selection, employee engagement and retention. But the question that arises here is that designing AI for employment in the HR department is not free from concerns. Challenges consisting of data protection or privacy questions, ethical questions, lack of skills and skills gaps, and resignification of technological advancement are some of the challenges. Also, debates are being made on how AI might substitute conventional HR positions, for which the contemporary HR has to be proactive in embracing change. The following paper also aims at discussing the application of Artificial Intelligence in the HR functions and benefits and challenges arising therefrom. It is the intention of this paper to undertake a critical evaluation in order to afford insights into how Human Resource management professionals could effectively mainstream the use of AI & ML towards achieving accurate and sound decisions, and thereby strategically enhance a people-centred approach to management of human capital. The Integrating AI for improving the roles and contributions of HR in the organizations.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Human Resources (HR), Machine Learning (ML), Workforce Management

Introduction

AI is gradually becoming the order in the business world, and HRM is not an exception. Historically formed to conduct interpersonal and administrative work, HR is now experiencing the change as AI solutions appear in recruitment, performance review, and engagement processes [1]. Cognitive technologies mean that tasks that used to be highly time consuming and labour intensive can now be accomplished much faster, more accurately and on a much larger scale [2]. This move is an extension of a trend already seen across organizations to bring data and analytics, as well as machine learning, in developing a more strategic and efficient HR environment in line with overall organizational goals [3].

However, these new technologies especially the applications of AI have brought concerns in terms of the overall relevance of human practitioners in the HR functions [5]. Some have begun to contemplate whether the evolution of such systems means that conventional HR positions may actually be completely eliminated. Although AI is helpful—in, for example, eliminating biased approaches to hiring, improving the management of people resources, and augmenting employees' experiences—AI undermines the human-prioritized foundational framework of HR by relying on formulas and statistics [6]. This paper examines how far AI could eliminate traditional HR positions, comparing the benefits and drawbacks of AI integration in the HR field, and considering the means by which organizations can integrate the value of advanced technology with the essential human elements of people management [7].

Literature Reviews

Adil Benabou (2024) proposed to exploring the Replacement of Traditional HR Roles by Artificial Intelligence, readers are made aware of how AI has overshadowed traditional roles that have been implemented in the areas of recruitment, performance appraisal and analysis of measures predicting the future increase in organisational

performance. This paper also proves that despite considering human like activities the future of AI is to support the knowledge-based tasks within the HR profession. Quasi-executive with the study, the following ethical issues are also presented as critical factors to consider for AI, especially in HR: data privacy and issues related with the bias of algorithms.

Kiran Kumar Reddy Yanamala (2023) which aims at complements the current hr managerial decisions by offloading the cognitive load to AI while providing insights in such areas as recruitment and performance management. It underscores that the HR managers must rely on both data AI provides and instinct when it comes to harder factors such as cultural alignment. The work also reviews ethical issues such as automation bias and transparency and calls for an establishment of ethical guidelines towards the use of AI. Finally, the paper points to the idea that AI is not a threat to, but instead acts as a supplement to human discretion in the sphere of HR.

Fadi sakka (2022) offers a threefold view of how AI has its ramifications for the future course of the human resource functions and its dynamics. IT claims that the implementation of AI in HR will release a time that HR practitioners spend on performing routine administrative tasks so that they can fully engage in stream of decision making and anticipatory problem solving for the HR and the organization at large. The paper also touches the aspects of HR reskilling, including how the HR specialists should communicate with AI, legal issues where data privacy, anti-discrimination policies are involved. They affirm that while the use of AI optimizes the process implemented by HR, it needs a critical and open escalation strategy to obtain the greatest organizational impact.

Priyadarshini Panda (2020) proposed to understand the key areas of the influence of AI in the human resources department and replace conventional human interventions with automated ones. The study collected both primary and secondary data to discuss AI benefits from improving productivity and better decision making; moreover, it mentioned key issues of converting HR into more tech-oriented processes, such as maintaining human values. Therefore, despite the discussed benefits of AI, the paper argues that AI should be viewed as a supporting tool in Human Resources while insisting on the need for an adequate incorporation of AI into future practices.

Ahmad Al-Masri (2022) aims at exploring the advances in the application of AI in HRM, looking at the roles of applying AI in recruitment, engagement and performance appraisal. This use of AI discusses opportunities with significant benefits on efficiency, data analysis to support decisions; however, it equally raises some ethical considerations like biasness and privacy violation. Thus, the study argues that any transition of HR tasks to AI should focus on skill upgrading and strategic value addition rather than replacing all conventional HR roles with artificial intelligence of the future.

S. No	Title and Author	Methodology Used	Advantages	Drawbacks
1	Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Human Resource Management & Adil Benabou (2024)	-For this research, data gathered from literature, case studies, and, reports were analysed qualitatively to understand the role of AI in Human Resource Management.	-This research paper describes on the strengths of AI in integrating with HR research by automating processes, refining decisions and supporting talent management.	The research identifies challenges to AI adoption in HR, including bias, privacy concerns, resistance, high costs, and technical barriers.

2	AI and the Future of Cognitive Decision-Making in HR & Kiran Kumar Reddy Yanamala (2023)	The research employs initial theory and qualitative approaches to analysis to cover AI effects on managerial cognition and choice in the operational aspects of HRM.	The research includes the positive effects like boosting the effectiveness of the HR decision-making process while cutting out cognitive load and elaborating actual data insights with the help of AI, and the combination of employing AI and human decision-making for more ethical and beneficial outcome	The identified gaps are that some issues such as the unsalability of the qualitative approach and ethical questions of AI transparency are ignored, and it lacks a wider applicability of the findings since it depends on certain cases only.
3	Human Resource Management in The Era of Artificial Intelligence: Future Hr Work Practices, Anticipated Skill Set, Financial and Legal Implications & Fadi Sakka (2022)	To investigate AI's effects on HRM, the study applies a three-fold exploratory research strategy based on HR functions, the changing position of HR within companies.	Hence, the paper focuses on efficiency improvement, strategic decision-support, and adaptability in using AI in the HR field.	This paper discusses the problems such as the requirement for upskilling, AI bias, and privacy to implement AI in HRM.
4	The Future Transformation of Hr Functions Which Apstole by Artificial Intelligence & Priyadarshini Panda (2020)	This research employed both primary and secondary data mainly questionnaires, interviews, and sophisticated statistical techniques.	These are the ways the research shows that AI increases the value of HR by broadening the role and implementing new technologies in attracting and selecting candidates, training, and managing human resources.	The research also points out that although the adoption of AI enhances the efficiency of the HR function, it decreases the human touch regarding relations with employees.
5	Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Human Resource Management: Trends and Implications & Ahmad Al-Masri (2022)	This approach examines the adoption of AI in functions such as recruiting, performance management, succession planning, and training and development, based on technology effects, better decision making, and possible ethical issues.	The study points out on subject area expertise where AI supports end-to-end HR operational activities, increase points of contact with employees, and provide robust Matcher for analytical decision-making in light of strategic moves and complex ethical issues.	The limitation of the research includes Ethical Issues, Risk of Bias, Privacy Issue, and skills and competency gaps due to integration of AI in HRM.

Objectives Of The Study

1. To analyse how AI is transforming traditional HR functions
2. To evaluate the strengthen for AI to replace traditional HR roles
3. To explore strategies for integrating AI with human-centric HR practices

Hr Practices: Shifting From Tradition To Ai Innovation**A. Recruitment and Selection**

AI is impacting recruitment and selection process through digitalisation of the initial steps in the selection of candidates as well as adding value in assessing applicants. Basic tasks that used to consume the HR professional by having them sieve through thousands of resumes manually are now easily done through artificial intelligence powered systems that can sift through resumes as per the job description, required skills and experience in the first instance [8]. Recruitment can also be fully automated hence reducing the chances of Human errors while HR staff can also optimize on strategic tasks [9]. Furthermore, video interviews and digital assessments based on AI also enable matcher approach collecting information about tone of voice, facial expressions and answers regarding the cultural fit and competencies of candidates. Chatbots also play a valuable role of engaging with candidates, responding to inquiries, setting interviews, and keeping the candidate experience true.

AI also assists in the process of selection and evaluation of candidates at other stages of screening and interviewing, as well as in consideration of candidate's long-term effectiveness to a company when he or she is already a member of the organization. Through the use of data and analytics, AI can compare the data from previous hires, and employee performance and turnover rate, and make estimations of the likely success rates of potential candidates thus enabling HR professionals to make good hiring decisions and minimize on employee turnovers. However, as much as AI increases efficiency, it raises several questions of ethics especially on aspects to do with algorithmic biases. Employers will therefore still need to be very careful and continue to have humans involved in the recruitment process to prevent unfair on bias hiring.

B. Career and Management

Veteran approaches to careers and management have largely been tactical, paper-based ways of measuring the performance and professional progression of workers in the field of human resource management [10]. Employees self-appraisal would be done once a year, managerial appraisal was based on perceived performance, and promotion decisions also depended on interpersonal relations. This approach, though quite traditional, failed to support constant feedback or adapt to the flexibility of the contemporary workplace [11]. But with AI, that what we know as career and management practices are evolving more flexible and proactive. Continuing with the innovation, HR professionals use deep technology like; machine learning algorithms and predictive analytics to monitor career progression of the employees in real time. In a way, by enhancing the analysis of patterns in an employee's skills, experiences, and career preferences AI can offer best-fit career development solutions and recommended career tracks contributing to both, employees' contentment and organizational productivity.

More strategically talent management is also possible through the incorporation of AI in career and management practices. AI can anticipate future skills demand in the workforce, recognize looming skills gaps as well as allow businesses to effectively manage the pipelines of talent. This enables strategic alignment of the manpower resources required for future organizational need consequent upon the future state of their development, and thus enhances efficiency by minimizing turnover. In addition, through the use of enabled AI tools, the managers are given resources that reveal potential of the employee as well as identifying under performers who require extra attention or training. It should be noted that this approach makes growth as focused on organizational objectives and employee needs to be timelier and more relevant. Therefore, AI is transitioning career management from a strategy that makes decision based off of the past to one that will make decisions based for the future of the employees and employers.

C. Training and Development

When applied to AI and HR, training and development are no longer what they used to be. Organizations are now able to enhance the skill of their employees more effectively than before using AI aided tools in personalizing personalized learning. AI platforms have enabled the HR department to help design an employee development plan by offering information on areas where the employee might be lacking skills, as well as recommend available learning courses according to the employer's preferences. Performance indicators generated by Artificial Intelligence are used to give employees feedback on their daily performance, as well recommending a course or an on-job training program that would enhance the particular competency of an employee. By using targeted training, organizations are able to strengthen their training programs, and improve their employee performance in the changed environment [12].

In addition, AI is helping the training services achieve greater flexibility and wider outreach. Extensive skills can be taught using traditional face-to-face or instructor facilitated programs, but they are expensive, time consuming but e-learning platforms driven through A.I. means training which employees can undergo anytime and anywhere. AI chatbots and virtual assistants are also proven helpful in supporting their clients round the clock along with AI's inherent capability of answering queries and helping the trainees to move forward. This helps the HR departments capture a large audience, make the training processes more effective and efficient, and get employees more engaged due to the dynamic nature of the training programs. Thus, as AI advances and becomes integrated into organizations, the practice of training and development in the HR function is set to become more intelligent and sophisticated in response to both the needs of organizations seeking to deliver efficient and effective training and development initiatives and the employees who would benefit from the advanced skill development regimes that such sophisticated AI tools are likely to offer in the future.

D. Talent Management

Talent management can be defined as the ability of an organisation to attract, develop and maintain employees that are vital to the success of that particular organisation. Previously, CHRP Hz and other departments mainly relied on doing all the necessary tasks including recruitment, performance management and the development of employees through telephone calls, emails, and often physically through face-to-face conversations. However, with the implementation of artificial intelligence in the human resource management industry, most operations are being majored and done with higher accuracy. AI interventions are especially effective when it comes to improving the recruitment function by analysing data to pick out promising applicants, measure their potential productivity, and automating the scheduling of interviews. AI can review raw resume data, identify positions suited for specific candidates, and rate potential cultural compatibility, which has direct positive implications for the HR departments as it assists in making fewer wrong hires and thus a better quality of the workforce [13].

It is common to think that the only function of AI in the management of talents is in the process of recruitment. It offers HR professionals sophisticated analysis tools to assess organisational effectiveness, individual organisational members, their strengths and weaknesses, and to help facilitate organisational learning through practice-based training. Trainings can also be suggested based on performance capabilities and employee desired occupation, which creates a way of constant learning among employees. Moreover, AI plays an essential role in managing employee communications and even turnover, as it has tools, which can predict which employees may leave an organization and thus prevents it from happening. Thanks to the repulsive work and added values, AI enables the HR departments to devote time and effort to talent management, which creates the foundation for the sustainable corporate culture.

E. Performance Management

Performance management is a powerful subdiscipline of human resource management, which previously aimed at goal setting, performance evaluation, and performance feedback [14]. However, due to the Artificial Intelligence (AI) incorporation in the HR processes, the system of performance management is shifting its direction. Modern technologies allow using artificial intelligence to accumulate and evaluate big amounts of data to determine employees' performance in real-time. Such a change makes the outcomes of decision-making and HR practice

more scientific and rational, and it allows the HR personnel to discover trends in productivity, staff training, and development needs or concerns [15]. AI systems can come up with performance benchmarks including work quality, communication, and teamwork, and analyse this data in ways that the human manager concerned only has time to do 'tactically'.

However, not limited to preference of common goals as well as operating targets, performance management is also affected by AI regarding feedbacks and developmental programs. AI, therefore, can help to recommend to employees the most suitable trainings based on their strengths, weaknesses, and professional development interests. This customization means that performance management is not standardized hence increases the effectiveness of the coaching and professional career techniques. Meanwhile, it can always conduct performance evaluations, so that HR can provide timely feedback rather than relying on yearly evaluations. The constant feedback loop makes the organizational culture one of continuity and makes it possible to maintain employees' attention and relevancy to organizational objectives.

Results And Discussion

In table 1 the change in HR practices in the adoption of the AI technologies is well portrayed. Prior, traditional hr methodologies were emerged as crafts, positioned highly subjective, static and time-consuming means such as, resume snapping, cookie-cutter training, and annual appraisals. On the other hand, the AI integrated HR practices help in automating, specializing in these, providing real solutions. There is automated screening and matching in recruitment, AI enhanced training through adaptive learning platforms and with regard to the career development it includes the predictiveness analysis. It also advances talent management by supervising the level of employee participation along with their rate of attrition and offers constant and live feed on performance. In summary AI makes HRM practice more effective, accurate and employee-centred, to result in increased adaptability and effectiveness.

Table 1. Hr Practices Comparison: Before And After Ai Integration

Hr Function	Traditional HR Approach	AI-Enhanced HR Approach
Recruitment and Selection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manual resume screening and sorting - Limited candidate matching - Interviews based on subjective evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AI-driven resume screening and ranking - AI algorithms for matching candidates to job roles - Virtual interviews with AI chatbots for initial screening
Training and Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generic training programs - Instructor-led or classroom training - Employee self-selection for training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AI-driven personalized learning paths - Adaptive learning platforms based on employee performance - AI recommendations for relevant training courses
Carrer and Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Career progression based on seniority or past performance - Subjective decision-making for promotions - Limited career path visibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AI analysis of career progression potential based on data analytics - Personalized career growth suggestions based on employee skills and goals - Predictive analytics for career path planning
Talent Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Talent identification based on past performance reviews - Limited employee engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AI-powered talent mapping and predictive analytics for future roles

	and retention strategies	- AI tools to monitor employee engagement and identify retention risks - Proactive talent development strategies
Performance Management	- Annual performance reviews based on manager’s subjective evaluation - Limited real-time feedback and performance tracking	- Continuous performance monitoring using AI tools - AI-driven feedback and performance insights in real-time - Data-driven performance evaluations and personalized development plans

The below Fig.1 labelled “Organising AI for HR Work” and the figure that follows titled “Where does AI fit into HR?” explains how AI works within the HR department and at which stages of the employee life cycle: attraction, selection, welcome, development, and mobility. AI proves to be the catalyst that drives digital transformation of the HR domain by optimizing responsibilities, rationalizing activities, and enriching employees’ journey. The recruiting stage, which in the past was heavily dependent on manual analysis of the resumes and limited efforts towards candidate reaching out, have now been transformed into dynamic career sites all powered through AI. These tools allow the recruiters access a wider market talent pool, map the talent with the opportunity as well as streamline the hiring process, thereby shortening the hiring cycle.

Fig.1 Levering ai in the Employee Life Cycle Courtesy (Priyanka Sharma)

When onboarding and engaging employees, AI improves the functionality of the HR department even more. Telepresence through an automated message and curated videos make onboarding process easier in the sense that basic information about the company and its culture may be availed to the new employees without much help from the HR department. This helps AI-powered HR chatbots, and engagement surveys keep HR and employees in touch in real-time, thus improving the bond between the employees and the organization. AI systems hence help organizations obtain feedback on their employees and discern various issues that may require attention in addressing, all with the aim to reducing turnover at work places. The above developments made possible through artificial intelligence help the HR teams deliver more satisfactory experiences for new employees during onboarding.

AI is used in the learning and development of the human capital in the organization. By filtering out the training content and skill development aids as per the needs of the employees, AI ensures that the learning path for each aspiring employee fits well within his/her career expectations and work profile. In the last phase, succession planning and career advancement through AI is feasible by assessing the internal candidate capable of performing such roles through skills assessment and career trajectory analysis of the corporation. This figure illustrates that the HR industry can outsource certain boring tasks and use AI solutions that enhance the valuable workload of HR.

Fig.2 AI in impact in future HR functions

The above Fig.2 shows that the load of AI in the formation of the HR functions will ramp up in the 2022 to 2030 period with impressive break to the amount expected between 2024 and 2026. This means that influence generated by AI continues to decline starting from the year 2028 affecting the area of the human resources sphere at a level of 80 which reminds that the application of automation and tools developed on its basis will remain one of the key factors of further processes. From this trend, there is evidence to prove that several other activities of the HR department will be undertaken or will evolve into roles of AI, as the industry gradually establishes AI as a standard operational tool of HR.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the workflow integration of AI into the HR is changing the course of the employment industry through the reduction of time on several tedious processes, improvement of data analysis and organisational focus on engagements and developments of the employees. AI technology is applied in recruitment, skills assessment of candidates during the initial interviews, selection, training, organizational development, management of talents, career planning, and performance appraisal. Such a change allows HR to produce solutions that are fitting for employees' needs and further leads to positive organizational changes, which locates AI as an invaluable asset in the present-day HR field. However, there various technological concerns should be considered utmost important while implementing AI in HR some of which are Data privacy, Algorithmic biases, and the necessity of transparency of AI governed decisions.

Despite the numerous advantages associated with the use of AI in HR it should be seen as an addition rather than a substitution to the HR roles. One thing remained uncorrectable by technology: human resources, which is at the very core the people strategy and culture. HR managers are in a position where they need to meet efficiency indices set by AI while at the same time relying on human wisdom and understanding in order to keep the organizational culture stable and employees' trust high. As AI becomes more integrated in various business processes, HR teams should act to master using these tools and adopt both Cognitively Augmented HR and consider practices that involve both artificial intelligence and human expertise as well as ethical concerns. This approach will enable AI and HR to work in parallel while delivering on its promise of improving the efficiency and effectiveness of HR practice while at the same time maintaining the relational aspect that is critical to people management.

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A REVIEW ON COMPONENTS OF BRAND CREDIBILITY THAT DRIVE LOYALTY IN GENZ CONSUMERS

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Abstract

Brand Credibility is the assurance and faith that a particular brand manages to gain from its audience which helps in nurturing and retaining consumers, especially the Generation Z. As inclusion has become the order of the day, where almost everyone's presence is digital and what they want calling or directing has been forcing approaches, brands must make a serious effort to appeal to this younger generation, the more choosy one. Consumers of Generation Z besides desiring an item that is of good quality and price, are also concerned about where the brand stands regarding ethics, social issues, and global matters like environmental care.

This study explores the notion of brand credibility in relation to the consumer loyalty phenomenon, focusing on those aspects that are most prominent to Gen Z. It addresses the following questions: what is the impact of product/promotion mix on brand image components addressing Gen Z? It looks at the product quality, prices, other consumers' opinions, after sales services, and environment studying existing literature. The present new generation cognition through a hybrid understanding of the geographies and the digital worlds has helped in breaking the trust barriers creating the need for trust online and social proof, thus trust but verify. They do not mind low prices and discounts; however this generation does not respect any brand that compromises quality for cheap prices.

In addition to the current state of knowledge, this article addresses questions of interpersonal interactions, the role of labor in the economy, and influence through social media as potential value added areas to investigate. Integrating these findings gives us the ability to formulate constructive suggestions for the business working on developing Gen Z loyalty programs. Surprisingly, the results indicate that, as earlier assumed, even within a construct as simple as credibility contains multiple dimensions rather than it is a straight jacket principle.

Keywords: Gen z, brand credibility, consumer loyalty

Introduction

Brand credibility is the level of trust and reliability associated with a brand as perceived by its customers and the wider audience. It reflects the extent to which people believe in the brand's commitments, quality, and dependability. Key elements contributing to brand credibility include a track record of fulfilling promises, uniform communication, high-quality products or services, positive customer interactions, and a solid reputation. For businesses, establishing and upholding brand credibility is essential, as it can impact consumer choices and foster lasting customer loyalty. Modern marketplace credibility counts the most, however especially towards Gen Z consumers, who are digitally savvy and highly demanding on brand transparency and ethical practices. As digital natives, Gen Z consumers research and evaluate brands extensively before making a purchasing decision. Authenticity, environmental care, social ethics, besides quality of product and cost, weigh very heavily in the decision-making process for Generation Z. Based on a review of existing literature, this study aims at identifying and analyzing key elements that influence brand loyalty among Gen Z and proposing new areas for further research which can find its way into more sophisticated marketing strategies. Some of the factors that affect brand credibility in gen-z are

- **Quality of the product/service**

Most consumers give more importance to quality than price especially if it is a shopping product or specialty product consumers tend to be more quality sensitive than price sensitive. If the product quality is good and long-lasting, the customer is more likely to trust the brand and stay loyal, they might also recommend it to their friends and family. It also gives the company a competitive edge over its competitors.

- **Reviews/testimonials**

Most customers tend to compare product reviews before buying a certain product thus it is essential for online platforms to have review and testimonials from previous customers to build trust in potential customers. It shows that the brand is transparent and open to feedback. If it is a restaurant, tattoo studio, or any such service it is helpful to have a review board outside the location to attract more customers

- **Cost**

In order to inspire trust in potential customers a company must price its products at an affordable rate, it should not be suspiciously low nor should it be unnecessarily expensive. It should adopt pricing strategies that align well with the organization's objectives. It should also offer occasional sales and offers to attract more customers.

- **Post-purchase services**

A company that offers good customer service is always more desirable. It shows the consumers that the brand cares about its consumers and gives it a lot of credibility.

- **Sustainability**

Offering environmentally sustainable products and services is much desirable in today's market situation. Most consumers are conscious of the environment and seek to buy from sustainable and socially responsible brands.

Research Methodology

The current body of work on brand credibility and loyalty among Generation Z consumers will be examined through a systematic literature review methodology. Sources were selected based on their relevance to the significant themes emerging, such as product quality, pricing strategies, social responsibility, and customer services. A systematic review of that will pinpoint areas that need further research as well as indicate novelty in avenues suggested for further investigation.

Review of literature

The Review of Literature is summarized with following Brand Components

Marketing communication

The study paper focuses on establishing a marketing communication plan for K Commerce in Indonesia's competitive e Commerce sector. Using Kotler's STP model and differentiation concept, the method incorporates segmentation, targeting, positioning, values laddering, and the PDB triangle. The study underlines the significance of optimized content, context, and infrastructure in increasing brand recognition. The study aims to raise K Commerce's profile and position in the e Commerce market. (Jehan Khairina Azwar , Yudo Anggoro , Jacob Silas Mussry)

Customer loyalty in the insurance business

In the interaction between differentiation initiatives and consumer loyalty, brand identity acts as a mediator. Brand awareness is also seen as a significant element in customer loyalty, yet the study did not establish its mediating function in the relationship between differentiation methods and customer loyalty. The study focuses on the insurance business and explores the impact of competitive advantage techniques on customer loyalty, with brand identification and brand awareness serving as moderators. The study's findings provide significant insights for insurance brand managers looking to increase performance and create customer loyalty by stressing differentiation methods and improving brand recognition.(Samira Falahatgar , Mousa Rezvani Chamanzamin ,Mohammad Taleghani)

Link between customer satisfaction and Brand awareness

The process of building a distinctive identity for a good or service to set it apart from rivals is called branding. It seeks to add value, attract customers, and foster trust and loyalty.

The degree to which people are familiar with a brand is referred to as brand awareness. It is critical to consumer loyalty and satisfaction.

Customer happiness and brand awareness are inextricably linked. Customers' proclivity to acquire products or services from a specific brand on a regular basis.

Melcom, a retail company in Agona Swedru, Ghana, has researched the impact of brand awareness on consumer loyalty. According to the findings of the study, a substantial proportion of respondents recognized the Melcom brand and expressed interest in its services. (monalizah armah)

Consumers trust

Consumers' trust in a company's brand is referred to as corporate brand credibility, and it can be used as a tool to assess a company's goods and services, which in turn influences customer purchase intent.

The three key components of company credibility that lead to buy intention are expertise, trustworthiness, and likability.

Limited research on business credibility has repeatedly found that higher credibility correlates to good consumer evaluations of brands, buying intent, and advertisements.

This study focuses on the relationship between business credibility and purchasing intent in Karachi's telecommunications sector. (Safeena Yaseen Ibtesam Mazahir)

Customer loyalty in hospitality and tourism sector

In the hospitality and tourism sectors, customer happiness and expectations are major predictors of customer loyalty, which in turn is a positive driver of brand strength. Improving client loyalty can result in greater supply, reputation, and visibility.

A descriptive-survey research approach and structural equation modeling were employed in the study to assess the impact of customer satisfaction, experience, and loyalty on brand power in the hotel business. (Hossein Bodaghi Khajeh NOBAR1, Reza ROSTAMZADEH2)

Pricing premium

The study outlines that corporate brand (CB) can allow for a pricing premium, improve perceptions of product or service quality, improve promotional efficacy, and acquire distribution through effective intermediaries.

There may be different structures of CB, and further research is needed to completely understand the components of CB. (David Corkindale)

Link between brand loyalty and quality

According to the study, brand awareness is positively correlated with brand loyalty and perceived quality.

Brand loyalty is impacted by advertising attitudes, which in turn affect brand awareness. Compared to the Thai market, the relationship between brand awareness and brand loyalty is stronger in the Vietnamese market.

In comparison to the Vietnamese market, advertising attitudes have a greater impact on perceived quality in the Thai market.

International brand managers in developing regions should be aware of regional variations and create efficient loyalty programs appropriately. (Tho D. Nguyen)

Corporate reputation

Corporate reputation is characterized by the research as a collection of financial and non-financial characteristics acquired by a company as a result of its prior actions.

It is an overall perception of a company's external stakeholders that reflects their interactions with the business.

A company's reputation is made up of the perceptions and qualities that different parties, such as customers, suppliers, investors, employees, and the community, have of it.

It is the total opinion of a corporation formed in the minds of its stakeholders based on knowledge, ideas, and associative signals. (Mohamed Ali Barakat Ali1)

Brand loyalty and CSR

The study's goal is to ascertain how strategic brand, perceived service quality, and brand image are related to one another. The model and the subsequent estimation are made easier by the valid assumption that consumers will continue to use the same product brand despite fierce competition. (Amboko Alex Kuya) The study outlines that CSR initiatives can strengthen the bonds between a business and its stakeholders. The cost and revenue sides of financial performance are improved through CSR, creating new investment opportunities and stakeholders.

CSR efforts improve employee sense of corporate citizenship, organizational loyalty, and job productivity.

Investment in CSR programs gives businesses a competitive edge and improves their consumer-facing performance. Socially conscious behavior improves customer satisfaction and customer sentiments toward the brand. (Won-Moo Hur • Hanna Kim)

Further literature review is systematically structured around various themes that delineate the elements influencing brand credibility:

- 1. Product Quality:** The significance of superior quality products has been shown in earlier research. Consumers willingly pay extra for brands which ensure such packages to be durable and dependable.
- 2. Reviews and Testimonials:** Studies demonstrate that peer evaluations significantly impact the purchasing decisions of Generation Z. It is advisable for brands to establish an open feedback mechanism to foster trust.
- 3. Cost and Pricing Strategies:** The effective pricing strategy will balance out affordability with perceived value. Occasional discounts can attract Gen Z without selling the brand integrity.
- 4. Sustainability and CSR:** the "cause-related" brands: Gen Z will be interested in brands that take their share of social and environmental causes. CSR will support enhancing the brand image and loyalty.
- 5. Customer Service:** Dependable post-purchase services enhance brand credibility and foster customer loyalty. Consumers from Generation Z value prompt and tailored customer support.

Discussion

The importance of brand credibility with respect to achieving consumer lock-in or loyalty among the Gen Z population is brought to the fore in this particular study. Members of Generation Z are described as digital natives because not only are they engaged with brands but they are also very vocal about the brands they choose, requiring them to be transparent, be of quality, and practice social responsibility.

Arguably, the most important of the lessons learnt is that product quality is the most important factor when it comes to credibility. Members of Generation Z care about price but when it comes to niche products, they tend to care more about the product than the price, which means that they are willing to spend more on reliable products. This means that companies trying to capture this demographic should be focusing on marketing strategies that will emphasize the quality of the product and its durability.

With the rise of Gen Z comes the increasing importance of reviews and testimonials to enhance credibility. It has been indicated that peer reviews are important before Gen Z consumers begin purchasing. Globalization must consider the competitive modern landscape, and therefore the importance of brand building has been placed in perspective that allows the company to embody a multi-brand position. Social proof therefore, helps to build trust among this cohort and serves as a good algorithm in all social perceptions.

Furthermore, affordability is linked with Gen Z's expectations on pricing; they want the best quality for the lowest price. The theory is that low prices generate distrust while high prices force consumers to look to competitors. As suggested in "When Gen Z Crossed over from 'The Consumers' To 'The Community': Digitisation of Geo

communities” occasional discounts help to create brand awareness without affecting the perceived value. Offers and discounts over time also help to strengthen brand engagement. However, this value should only be limited.

An additional important aspect for the majority of Gen Z consumers is brand credibility. Apparently, this generation cares more about global social and environmental issues than past generations. This will only be strengthened further by Gen Z continuing adopting brand credibility as the leading factor in influencing their consumer behavior. As well as investing in sustainability.

Besides creating positive associations, post-purchase services also contribute to making brands more reliable. For example, younger consumers, particularly Generation Z, regard relevant customer service and support in the post-sale phase as an indicator of the brand's concern for customers. In this way, they can create a loyalty for the brand by providing efficient and helpful support.

To summarize, the research substantiates that credibility of brands among members of Gen Z is complex and includes the elements of honesty, value, active social responsibility, and participation. The ones who do well in these areas are more likely to build customer loyalty and thus succeed in a marketplace comprised of younger, socially conscious, and tech-savvy consumers.

Scope for further Research

The Potential new components that can be added to carry out the study further are

1. Digital Engagement and Social Media Presence: The consistency and transparency of a brand’s online activity could significantly impact credibility.
2. Brand Ethics: Diversity, inclusion, and ethical labor practices are becoming increasingly important to consumers.
3. Personalisation: Brands that customize experiences and products for individual consumers may increase brand loyalty.

Conclusion

From the study, we can understand that maintaining transparency, sustainability, and affordability are important factors for Genz consumers, to perceive a brand as credible. Corporate branding (CB) can enable a pricing premium, improve perceptions of product or service quality, increase promotional efficacy, and gain distribution through effective intermediaries. Increased brand recognition is significantly aided by infrastructure, context, and content that have been optimized. Developing trust with new customers is crucial for online platforms, and customer reviews and testimonials can aid in this process. Pricing, product quality, promotional effectiveness, and customer reviews all help to increase brand credibility and draw in new customers. In general, brand credibility is a critical aspect in fostering consumer loyalty.

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AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON IMPACT OF FINTECH ON BANKING INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Fintech refers to novel processes and products that become available for financial services thanks to digital technology advancements. The financial technology sector's (fintech) rapid advancements, which have revolutionized numerous industries, have had a particularly large impact on the banking industry. This study intends to examine both the advantages and disadvantages of fintech's extensive effects on the banking sector. Key issues surrounding the impact of fintech on banking are highlighted and examined through a thorough literature review. The study's findings point out several significant impacts that fintech has had on the banking industry. The paper, however, also point out some difficulties and dangers related to the adoption of fintech in the banking industry. Concerns around data privacy, cyber security, regulatory issues, and the possible instability of conventional banking institutions are a few of them. This study provides a thorough examination of how fintech has affected the banking sector as a whole, describing the benefits, drawbacks, and outcomes of this technological revolution. It encourages further research into how fintech is influencing the future of banking and creates the foundation for subsequent investigations.

Key Words: Fintech, Banking Sector, Artificial Intelligence.

Introduction:

Fintech combines finance and technology to improve banking services. In the banking industry, it means using new technology to make financial services better. This includes mobile banking apps, digital payments, blockchain, and artificial intelligence. Fintech uses special software and algorithms on electronic devices to help businesses, individuals manage their financial operations and processes more effectively and efficiently. The Improvement of Innovations has driven significant changes in macroeconomics. The emergence of new financial technologies, resulting from the integration of traditional financial management with digital tools, has become a key factor in the growth of financial markets. The financial technology sector has grown quickly in recent years, but there is still no exact definition of fintech. It covers a range of areas, such as digital payments, e-wallets, online lending, P2P platforms, crowd funding, online investments, and online insurance. Fintech represents a business approach that uses new technologies and innovations in financial services. Finance is going through a major transformation. The COVID-19 pandemic has sped up the shift to digital technologies in payments, loans, insurance, and wealth management. While this challenges financial services in many economies, it also makes markets more competitive, efficient, and inclusive. However, new risks may arise, potentially impacting key public policy goals. To understand the effects of digital innovation, it's essential to assess its implications on related policies, such as financial and competition laws, as well as its impact on industries.

Review of Literature:

Philippon, T. (2016). The FinTech Opportunity. NBER Working Paper No. 22476. This study provides an analysis of the opportunities fintech presents in enhancing the efficiency of financial services and reducing cost

Arner, D. W., Barberis, J., & Buckley, R. P. (2017) provide insight into the dual impact of fintech on risk management, noting improvements in security through blockchain while also highlighting challenges like cybersecurity risks and regulatory gaps.

Gupta and Agarwal (2021), fintech's impact on consumer expectations has compelled Indian banks to adopt customer-centric digital platforms and collaborate with fintech startups to offer better, tailored services.

Frost, J. (2020). The Economic Forces Driving Fintech Adoption Across Countries. BIS Working Papers No. 838. This working paper examines the factors influencing fintech adoption and its economic impact, with insights relevant to banking industry transformation

Patel and Sharma (2021), in their paper "Challenges in the Fintech Era: Regulatory and Security Concerns for Banks," point out that while fintech has brought innovation, it has also raised challenges, particularly in regulatory compliance, data privacy, and cyber security. They argue that banks must find a balance between leveraging fintech advancements and ensuring security and compliance.

Kumar and Das (2022), in their research "Operational Efficiency in Indian Banks through Fintech Integration," emphasize that fintech has enabled banks to cut costs through automation and improved back-end operations, allowing for better resource allocation and competitive service offerings.

Scope Of The Study:

The study examines the impact of fintech on the banking industry using primary data collected from customers. It focuses on changes in banking operations, customer experiences, and competition, analyzing digital innovations like payment platforms and block chain and also it includes regulatory challenges and covers both developed and emerging markets for a comprehensive global perspective.

Objective Of The Study:

1. To understand the need for banks to collaborate with fintech.
2. To Study benefits of fintech.
3. To understand the impact of fintech companies on Banking industry.

Need for Banks to collaborate with Fintech

Banks need to collaborate with fintech companies to stay competitive and meet customer expectations. Fintechs bring innovation, advanced technology, and customer-focused solutions that traditional banks often lack. By partnering with fintechs, banks can offer better digital services, improve efficiency, and expand their reach. This helps banks remain relevant and competitive in a fast-changing financial industry

Benefits of Fintech

Fintech makes financial services more accessible, convenient, and cost-effective. It offers personalized experiences, faster transactions, and improved security through advanced technologies like AI and block chain. By fostering competition, fintech pushes traditional banks to innovate and enhance their services, leading to better financial solutions for consumers.

Impact of fintech companies on Banking Industry

Fintech has transformed the banking industry by driving innovation and modernization. It has pushed banks to adopt new technology and offer better, more personalized services. Fintech has increased competition, making banks improve their digital services and efficiency. With tools like AI and mobile banking, transactions are faster and more secure, changing how financial services are provided.

Research Methodology:

The study is based on Primary and Secondary Data. The study mainly depends on Primary data collection through a well- framed and structured questionnaire through Google form and taken their response.

Close ended

Sample Unit: Bangalore area

Sample Size: 72

Secondary Data: Books, Journals, Articles and Research papers.

Plan Of Analysis:

Data collected through questionnaires which will be analyzed through Tabel and using statistical technique like Chi-square.

Hypothesis:

Ho: Fintech services are not significantly influencing banking services.

H1: Fintech services are significantly influencing banking services.

Limitation Of The Study:

1. The Study was limited to only Bangalore Banking Customer.
2. Lack of time constraint
3. Lack of interest of the response was one of the major problems.

Data Analysis And Interetation:

1. Demographic:

The survey consists total 72 members in that 43 female and 29 male respondents . And majorities are college students, Graduates and Post graduates and other members are employed in Public & Private sector and their income ranging from Lesser than 3 Lakhs per annum and majority of them are familiarity with banking services.

2. Fintech Usage, Impact And Perception:

Chi-Square Test:

Ho: fintech services are not significantly influencing banking services

Observed Values (O _i)	Expected Values (E _i)	(O _i -E _i)	(O _i -E _i) ²	$\frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$
27	14.4	12.6	158.76	11.025
26	14.4	11.6	134.56	9.305
13	14.4	1.4	1.96	0.136
2	14.4	12.4	153.76	10.677
4	14.4	10.4	108.16	7.5
72	72			38.643

$$\chi^2_{\text{obs}} = \sum (O_i - E_i)^2 / E_i =$$

Degree of freedom = X-1 = 5-1=4, Table value of χ^2 @ a 5% with 4 d.f= 9.488

$$\chi^2_{\text{obs}} = 38.643 > 9.488$$

Interpretation:

The above table indicate the χ^2_{obs} value is 38.643 which is greater than 9.488. Hence the null hypothesis rejected.

There is a statistically significant association between fintech services and the way banking services are provided, meaning fintech services are having a measurable impact on the banking sector.

Interpretation:

After the testing as per above mentioned method and procedure, the χ^2_{obs} value is 15 which is greater than 9.488. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Respondents' opinion for the question- "Level of familiarity with banking services".

Interpretation

After the testing as per above mentioned method and procedure, the χ^2_{obs} value is 119.86 which is greater than 9.488. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Respondents' opinion for the question- "How often do you use digital banking or fintech service (e.g., mobile apps, online transaction)?"

Interpretation

After the testing as per above mentioned method and procedure, the χ^2_{obs} value is 92.32 which is greater than 9.488. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Respondents' opinion for the question- "What type of fintech service do you use most frequently?"

Interpretation

After the testing as per above mentioned method and procedure, the χ^2_{obs} value is 19.656 which is greater than 9.488. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Respondents' opinion for the question- "What is the main reason you prefer fintech services over traditional banking?"

Interpretation

After the testing as per above mentioned method and procedure, the χ^2_{obs} value is 55 which is greater than 9.488. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Respondents' opinion for the question- "Do you think fintech has improves the quality of banking services?"

Interpretation

After the testing as per above mentioned method and procedure, the χ^2_{obs} value is 70.323 which is greater than 9.488. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Respondents' opinion for the question- "How has fintech influenced your banking habits?"

Interpretation

After the testing as per above mentioned method and procedure, the χ^2_{obs} value is 13.443 which is greater than 9.488. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Respondents' opinion for the question- "What challenges do you think fintech poses to traditional banks?"

Interpretation

After the testing as per above mentioned method and procedure, the χ^2_{obs} value is 40.331 which is greater than 9.488. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Respondents' opinion for the question- "How safe you feel when using fintech services for transaction?"

Interpretation

After the testing as per above mentioned method and procedure, the χ^2_{obs} value is 59.75 which is greater than 9.488. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Respondents' opinion for the question- "Do you believe that fintech is contributing to financial inclusion (helping more people access banking services)?"

Interpretation

After the testing as per above mentioned method and procedure, the χ^2_{obs} value is 143.658 which is greater than 9.488. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Respondents' opinion for the question- "What feature do you find most appealing in fintech services?"

Interpretation

After the testing as per above mentioned method and procedure, the χ^2_{obs} value is 50.768 which is greater than 9.488. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Respondents' opinion for the question- "What concerns do you have about using fintech services?"

Interpretation

After the testing as per above mentioned method and procedure, the χ^2_{obs} value is 72.332 which is greater than 9.488. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Respondents' opinion for the question- "How do you rate the impact of fintech on your overall banking experience?"

Interpretation

The fintech will acquire more geography locations than the traditional banking. It will definitely shape in a big manner, already after demonetization Fintech has a greater loan in banking & Indian Banking is now Strongly based on Fintech. It will make banking and banking services more accessible but also increase frauds and

fraudulent activities. It will increase marketability, but it should be strong in providing security and safety concerns. It's actually a great impact on further future's generation for a digital resource. It will enhance knowledge & strengthen banking customer skills to bring financial stability and also helps in stabilizing the economic structure.

Respondents' opinion for the question- "How do you think fintech will shape the future of the banking industry?"

Findings:

1. The survey sample consisted of a higher number of female respondents, comprising 59.7%, compared to male respondents, which made up 40.3%. Ensuring diverse representation and perspectives in surveys is valuable.
2. The survey reveals that 45.8% of the respondents that they are familiar with banking services.
3. The survey reveals that 80.06% of the respondents use fintech services daily.
4. The survey reveals that 76.4% of the respondents use fintech products or services frequently.
5. The survey reveals that 68.1% of the respondents prefer fintech services over traditional banking.
6. The survey reveals that 62.5% of the respondents improve the quality of banking services.
7. The survey reveals that 68.5% of the respondents find banking service easier.
8. The survey reveals that 33.33% of the respondents find high dependence on technology poses to traditional banking.
9. The survey reveals that 54.2% of the respondents find fintech helping more people access banking service.
10. The survey reveals that 86% of the respondents find easy payment and transfers features appealing in fintech services.
11. The survey reveals that 56.9% of the respondents concern data security and privacy using fintech services.
12. The survey reveals that 72.2% of the respondents find fintech is impacting in their overall banking experience.

The findings suggest that convenience and accessibility, enhanced security measures, lower fees or cost, time-saving, and better user experience are significant predictors of the usage frequency of fintech products, with convenience and accessibility having the strongest positive impact and time-saving and better user experience having the strongest negative impact.

Suggestion:

1. Enhance digital payment options constantly to provide simple, secure transaction. For quicker and more effective.
2. Enhance digital payment options constantly to provide simple, secure transaction.
3. For quicker and more effective payments, this can involve integrating mobile wallets, contactless transactions, and cutting-edge technology like block chain.
4. To safeguard client information and transactions, make significant investments in cyber security.
5. Use modern encryption techniques, biometric authentication, and multi-factor authentication to protect online banking and financial transactions.
6. Giving underprivileged communities access to banking services will help to foster financial inclusion.
7. To reach unbanked people, create mobile banking solutions that operate in places with poor connectivity and provide streamlined account creation procedures.

According to the results of this research, increasing positive impact, addressing fintech product issues, expanding the banking experience, and adopting emerging trends can all help to raise customer satisfaction levels. It is essential to continuously monitor customer feedback, adapt strategies accordingly, and prioritize customer-centric approaches to meet and exceed customer expectations. The results indicate that utilising Fintech to improve financial inclusion and alter the finance industry requires a proactive regulatory strategy, together with complementary government initiatives.

Conclusion

The rise of fintech in the financial industry has brought about a host of benefits, including enhanced accessibility, significant cost savings, superior customer experiences, and faster service delivery. These advantages not only directly benefit consumers by making financial services more affordable and convenient, but they also push traditional banks to innovate and evolve in order to maintain their competitive edge. As fintech continues to expand, it holds the potential to further improve the efficiency, security, and inclusivity of financial systems on a global scale.

Scope For Further Research

The present study concentrated on in Bangalore city. Further research can be done at the district level covering all 31 district of Karnataka.

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SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS PRACTICE, ESG CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles have gained significant traction in the corporate world, representing a fundamental shift towards more sustainable and socially responsible business practices. ESG factors evaluate a company's impact on the environment, its commitment to social responsibility, and its governance practices. The adoption of the ESG investment approach addresses risk management issues and sets goals to-ward more responsible behavior. Sustainable development goals adopted by the United Nations in 2015 include a call for action to end poverty, save the planet, and ensure peace and prosperity for all by 2030. This paper consists of three sections. The first section examines the concept of sustainable practices - its origin, definition and taxonomy. The second section explains the ESG challenges facing businesses and manufacturers globally and discuss strategies for overcoming them. The final section explores on ESG future opportunities. This paper studies advanced Artificial Intelligence methodologies to assess, analyze, and suggest improvements in corporate behavior to comply with global sustainable development goals.

Keywords: Corporate behavior, ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) Investments, Artificial Intelligence, Risk management, Sustainable Development,

Introduction

Sustainable business practices is quickly gaining popularity and becoming a mega trend, particularly in the western developed countries. The reason behind it is simple. A wide range of social and environmental problems afflicts the global community today – social inequality, unequal distribution of wealth, failing economics, war and conflict, gender inequality, lack of education, rampant poverty, changing climate, habitat loss, species loss, ecological loss etc. Much of these problems can be addressed if the private sector adopts more sustainable business practices. These problems are especially acute in developing and less developed countries. In 2015 the United Nations declared 17 goals for the global community to achieve. These came to be known as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and replaced the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) set two decades earlier (UNDP, n.d.). The 17 goals are aimed at addressing these very same issues afflicting the global communities today. Various stakeholders have taken up the responsibility to address these issues at the local, national and international levels. They include the government, non governmental organizations, non profit organizations, educational institutes, research institutes, consumer bodies, scientific and technological community and the private sector (business and industry). Of these stakeholders, the private sector is viewed to be one of the most influential and dominant force having the most significant impact in achieving these goals (Lucci, 2012). Indeed much of the current problems has its roots in the practices and policies of the private sector so much so that it has called into question the entire notion of capitalism and free markets (Daood & Menghwar, 2017). It is beyond the purview of this paper to discuss the merits and demerits of the prevailing form of capitalism. What is certain without a shred of doubt is the enormous impact of the private sector on these issues. Climate science has clearly linked industrial activities with the change in global climate which has wide repercussions in so many areas - global warming, fresh water scarcity, ecological damage, loss of species etc. Hence, business cannot continue as usual. There is a profound need to re-examine, re-assess, and re-think, business values, priorities and practices. In this paper, we address the challenges that investors and investment funds face in light of the non-standardized reporting of climate-related risks, the social responsibilities of corporations, and their governance practices.

Defining Sustainable Business Practices

Sustainable business is one that is concerned about the social, environmental, and economic impacts associated with its current and future operations and the ability of the business to meet present needs while ensuring its and others' long-term survival. Ideally, the sustainable business seeks to have a positive social impact, environmental impact, and economic impact. Taken together, a business's contribution to social justice, environmental quality,

and economic prosperity is collectively referred to as the triple bottom line. Elkington (1997). The triple bottom line (social, environmental, economic) is sometimes referred to as people, planet, profit.

Once considered the purview of governments and nonprofit organizations (such as Heifer International, a global leader in developing sustainable communities), businesses are increasingly being called upon to address social, environmental, and economic issues. Rethinking the business in terms of its triple bottom line impact and performance (social, environmental, and economic) is critical in establishing the foundation for sustainable business. This requires a shift away from thinking of a business only in terms of its financial profit to shareholders. While financial profit is necessary for survival, the sustainable business applies a broader view of the business, its responsibilities, and its performance.

Fig 1.1 Sustainable Business

Why Sustainable Business Practices?

To understand why the emphasis on sustainable business practices, we need to understand the role played by private sector. The private sector is a critical stakeholder in the developmental cycle and can act as a major contributing force in addressing developmental challenges and issues. Today the trend is for companies to align their core business objectives and activities with social and developmental goals. For example, companies are leveraging their supply chain and production process to use raw materials and supplies from local suppliers and suppliers with responsibly sourced raw materials. In this way they contribute towards developmental goals.

Likewise companies are using their ‘business innovation capacity to target the needs of low-income consumers, tackle complex development challenges or fill funding gaps.’ They aid in social development by providing quality healthcare and training and education to their employees. By adopting Social, Environmental and Human Rights standards they aid in social development while preserving the local environment and ecosystems. Such standards define rules of conduct on a wide range of ethical and good governance issues such as, transparency and anti-bribery, tax and social, environmental and human rights issues. In this way they promote good practice while minimizing negative impacts. Another way private sectors contribute towards development and growth is through philanthropic acts and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). By supporting local community projects, aiding in resource mobilization, and contributing in cash or kind to various local, national, and international causes they influence public policy and engage and contribute in developmental activities (Lucci, 2012).

Three Approaches to Sustainable Systems

When striving to render any resource-based system more sustainable, whether in sustainable development or organizational sustainability, there are three basic approaches: (a) efficiency, (b) consistency, and (c) sufficiency (see Fig. 1.2). All these approaches aim to reduce resource consumption. Naturally, none of these approaches can

reduce environmental impacts to zero, but if they are applied in combination, they can significantly improve the resource-related sustainability of a system.

A. Efficiency: Efficiency is probably the best-known and therefore most intuitive of the three approaches, and can often be seen, for example, with electrical equipment (see Fig. 1.2). It measures the effort and degree to which a source material is transformed to its target state. Low efficiency indicates that large quantities of raw materials and/or effort must be invested to create the desired quantity of the final product, i.e. lots of input little output. Therefore, low efficiency systems tend to lead to higher production costs, as resources and effort are usually the main drivers of cost. Therefore, improving system efficiency is a favored approach for most corporations and other organizations and they have been applying it for decades.

Fig 1.2 The Three approaches to sustainability

B. Consistency: Consistency strategies do not aim to improve the amount of resources and/or effort as efficiency approaches do, but rather aim to either use infinite, renewable resources or not to allow resources to be transformed into a state where they cannot be transformed into anything useful anymore. When taking advantage of the few practically unlimited resources, e.g., wind, sunlight, and waves, increasing resource usage does not negatively impact on resource availability. There is not less wind on this planet, because there are more wind farms. However, transforming those resources into energy requires tools to perform the transformation (wind farms, solar panels, etc.). To be 100% consistent, these tools would have to be sourced from 100% renewable resources, which is mostly not the case. As a consequence, consistency is in practice often an approximation towards its goal, trying to optimize the availability and efficient usage of renewable resources.

C. Sufficiency: While efficiency and consistency approaches address the production side, sufficiency addresses consumption, the basic idea being that reduced demand for a resource leads to less extraction of that resource. There are three primary variants of sufficiency:

1. **Reduction:** Reduction is the simplest and most obvious form of sufficiency. The goal of this approach is a quantitative reduction of the resources used by reducing demand. If people fly less, there will be a reduction of flights and consequently a reduction of resource usage and emissions. These effects are mostly directly proportional, so if people travel 30% less, there will be roughly 30% less flights and thus 30% less resources used. As simple as this concept is, it is often the hardest to implement, as it is uncompromisingly effective and at its core contradicts the dogma of the last few decades: eternal growth and increasing consumption.
2. **Adaption:** Adaption is closely related to the efficiency approach discussed above, the main idea being that resources are only supplied where there is actual demand and one can be sure that the resources will be put to use. Applied to the aviation example above, adaption could mean a minimal utilization rate below which the

plane would not take off or a smaller plane would be used, since there is not enough demand for this flight. It could also mean a reduction of resource intensive in-flight features (entertainment, food, air quality, noise reduction, etc.)

- 3. Substitution:** Substitution strives for a reduction but only in a specific aspect. Instead of staying at home, as the reduction approach would dictate, the plane is substituted by another means of transport, e.g., a train, noticeably lowering the total resource usage and emissions. The impact of substitution measures heavily depends on what aspect is being addressed and what it is being replaced with. Replacing a flight by traveling the same distance alone in a sports car qualifies as substitution but is a relatively weak solution compared to a direct train journey. Consequently, substitution approaches have to be checked thoroughly to assess their consequences.

ESG Challenges

Focusing on sustainability will yield substantial rewards, and now is indisputably the ideal moment to apply this investing philosophy. Investors can designate their target areas and product preferences in order to participate in this journey. However there are challenges ahead. There is no assurance that sustainable investments will provide profits comparable to those that do not take these variables into account. Investments in sustainable assets may deviate from conventional market standards. The lack of consistent and trustworthy ESG data is one of the major obstacles to making ESG investments in India. Since many businesses withhold detailed ESG data, it can be difficult for investors to evaluate their sustainability performance. There are discrepancies in ESG reporting metrics and standards, which make comparisons and analysis challenging. Another challenge with ESG practices and concepts is a lack of knowledge and comprehension. Many investors, particularly common people, may not be familiar with ESG investing or its advantages. To get more investors on board, it's critical to educate them on the value of taking ESG aspects into account and how they may impact long-term profits.

Green washing is another issue faced by the business. It involves the act of misrepresenting customers about a company's environmental policies or the advantages a good or service has for the environment.. (Agarwal, 2011).

ESG in the age of AI

As businesses continue to mull over the best ways of adopting artificial intelligence (AI), one cannot overlook its role in helping streamline key processes across sectors. When applied mindfully, a powerful digital technology such as AI can be immensely useful in helping businesses meet their environment, social and governance (ESG) goals for a longer-term impact.

Today, business leaders around the world and in India are aware that ESG is extremely important for ensuring business goals and long-term sustainability. Findings of the 'KPMG 2023 India CEO Outlook' show that CEOs increasingly recognise ESG for what it is—an integral part of their operations and corporate strategies for building productive sustainable businesses. To this effect, 69 per cent of global CEOs have fully embedded ESG into their business to create value and 54 per cent of CEOs in India have done the same.

Balancing ESG goals with profitability ambitions is a tremendous challenge for companies. Quantifying ESG performance and progress towards the targets through pertinent ESG disclosures are critical at a time when both stakeholders and regulators expect relevant and accurate data at par with financial disclosures. Companies in India are making concerted efforts to reveal their ESG performance; however, articulating a convincing ESG story to stakeholders remains a challenge. The rising inquisition into companies' ESG commitments and their results has compelled CEOs to focus on improving transparency and performance in meeting these goals and avoiding greenwashing.

There are many ways in which AI tools can help achieve near-term and long-term ESG ambitions. Collating large quantities of data on ESG metrics, forecasting emissions, linking emissions to growth numbers and undertaking climate risk assessments are just a few of them. However, we must also remember that Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) in itself uses massive amounts of energy and there has to be a way for this to be addressed and ensure there is accountability.

Educating ESG

The future will not be more of the past! The global economic paradigm is changing as companies are under tremendous pressure from people across the world to account for the social impact of their businesses. Moreover, endless growth with profit as the sole metric is no longer considered sustainable. The consequences of social and environmental imbalance are mostly seen in the long term, and if allowed to go unchecked, the disruption caused may cause a significant dip in growth and corporate valuations (Namrata Rana, National Head of ESG, KPMG in India).

There is a lot that companies in India need to do to be truly ready to take sustainability reporting to the next level. With regulators across the world pushing for mandatory assurance of ESG reports, it is imperative for companies to comprehensively assess their level of readiness. Further, stakeholders expect more than just disclosures—they want to see tangible action on the ground and progress year on year. Hence, it is imperative to converge ESG strategy and reporting together with board-led oversight. (Sai Venkateshwaran Partner, KPMG in India).

Advances in AI offer unprecedented opportunities for companies to advance their ESG agenda through better insights, monitoring and risk mitigation. AI can, therefore, be a transformative force, delivering competitive advantages, including operational efficiency, business resilience and brand reputation. (Chaitanya Gogineni Partner, Data, Analytics and AI, KPMG in India)

Effective corporate governance of ESG is becoming critical

ESG data can now seriously impact corporate risk, investor perceptions and corporate wellbeing. Hence, effective corporate governance of ESG becomes essential. Corporate boards normally have governance expertise on accounting matters. Some of them, after India's CSR legislation that required board oversight, had started focusing on CSR as well. However, ESG is not CSR. It is about corporate strategy and management oversight of core business in the context of Environmental, Social and Governance standards. With such standards gaining momentum across institutional investors, it is now expected that it should be a part of the board agenda.

Investors in India and abroad now look to incorporate ESG factors into the investment process alongside traditional financial analysis. As part of this process, investment firms gather ESG data on companies and use it to make decisions on valuation and the risk that a stock poses. With investors looking at ESG as a value-based dimension of their portfolio, they increasingly want to understand ESG performance the same way they would any other traditional financial measure.

The last two years have been marked by some of the biggest disruptions to both people and the planet, with extreme climate change-related events causing widespread destruction and disruption. Investors now expect that companies have conducted a risk assessment and are taking steps to become resilient and adapt to the emerging challenges.

ESG risks include those related to climate change mitigation, environmental management practices, good work and safety conditions, respect for human rights, anti-bribery and corruption practices, and compliance with relevant laws and regulations.

It is increasingly clear that technology can drive change and accelerate climate action while mitigating risks. From making solar panels work better to more accurately predicting weather, machine learning tools can enable action on everything from reducing fossil fuel emissions to preparing for disaster threats. Machine learning can also help in accurately predicting climate driven effects like floods and wildfires with powerful computers testing likely scenarios at a fine scale. By leveraging AI and data, companies can develop predictive models to anticipate future climate risks and assess the potential impact on their operations. By understanding these risks in advance, businesses can proactively implement measures to mitigate them, minimising disruptions and increasing resilience (Sai Venkateshwaran Partner, KPMG in India)

ESG needs better data and data governance

The sheer scale of the ESG data problem is immense. Given that there is increased pressure on delivering higher frequency of ESG data to investors, consumers and governments, it is critical that the data should be correct, verifiable and available in real time.

Moreover, AI-powered recommendation systems and analytics will only provide accurate results if the base data is accurate.

Today, most companies work out of Excel sheets when it comes to ESG. This is because Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems that most of them function on do not capture ESG data. These ERP systems were designed to measure and manage inputs, suppliers, costs, sales and receivables. Many times, production data may sit in legacy systems that might function independently, making emissions data extraction difficult. Further, new projects may have Internet of Things (IOT) systems to measure their productivity and efficiency and once again may not be integrated with other systems. Which is why, even for calculating carbon emissions accurately, different systems need to be looked at.

Hence, getting an integrated view is difficult. Turning a blind eye to proper ESG data management comes at a significant cost and could have negative consequences on organizations. Some of these consequences include negative brand perception, regulatory fines and weak social licenses to operate and more. Effective ESG data governance requires a coordinated and centralized approach across multiple stakeholders. This can take place with new data architecture, data collection strategy across multiple locations and enhanced processes. For many organizations, this requires significant changes to the IT infrastructure ranging from applications to data integration, architecture and governance. For instance, banks require not only the management and capture of ESG data but also financed emissions models, climate risk models, ESG scorecards, climate stress tests and climate adjusted ratings. Accurate ESG data and the use of AI models will eventually encourage stakeholders to adopt sustainable business strategies. By providing insights, suggestions and incentives, companies can empower consumers and investors to engage in more sustainable choices, leading to collective environmental impact. (Chaitanya Gogineni Partner, Data, Analytics and AI, KPMG in India)

Using AI to scale ESG

In today's world, and increasingly in the future, we are looking at real-time responses to everything. Real-time dashboards can help companies tackle problems when they occur. Corporations tend to use real-time financial information to drive innovation, better decision-making and business transformation. Similarly, the main benefit to gaining access to correct, real-time ESG data is being able to forecast almost anything and take corrective action (environmental impact: waste, water and energy; social impact: human rights, health, education, safety; and governance) with However, unlike financial data, ESG data comes in diverse formats and units. It is sourced from various parts of the organization and is often recorded and stored in different systems, spreadsheets and documents.

To leverage sustainability data effectively for decision-making, it must be collected, transformed and reported with greater speed, frequency and scalability. Achieving this typically necessitates substantial technological solutions, new processes and business transformation at scale.

Intelligent ESG can drive real business value

ESG Future opportunities - Positive Impacts of AI in ESG

Environmental Sustainability

AI is revolutionizing environmental sustainability in several ways:

- **Energy Management:** AI systems optimize energy usage in buildings and industrial processes, reducing waste and lowering carbon footprints. Smart grids powered by AI improve energy distribution, integrate renewable sources more efficiently, and reduce reliance on fossil fuels.
- **Climate Modeling:** AI enhances climate models by analyzing vast datasets to predict weather patterns, track environmental changes, and develop strategies for mitigating climate risks. These insights are crucial for policymakers and businesses to make informed decisions.
- **Waste Management:** AI-driven robotics and machine learning algorithms improve waste sorting and recycling processes, increasing efficiency and reducing landfill use. Predictive maintenance powered by AI minimizes equipment downtime and operational inefficiencies in waste management facilities.

Social Impact

AI contributes to social development and welfare in various sectors:

- **Healthcare:** AI enhances diagnostic accuracy, personalizes treatment plans, and accelerates medical research. Telemedicine platforms powered by AI improve access to healthcare, particularly in remote and underserved areas.
- **Education:** AI-driven personalized learning platforms cater to individual student needs, improving educational outcomes and reducing dropout rates. AI also provides valuable data analytics for educators to develop more effective teaching strategies.
- **Employment and Inclusion:** AI-driven platforms facilitate job matching and skills development, promoting workforce inclusion and diversity. AI tools help identify and reduce biases in hiring processes, creating fairer employment opportunities.

Governance and Compliance

AI strengthens governance and compliance through:

- **Risk Management:** AI enhances risk assessment and management by analyzing complex datasets to identify potential threats and vulnerabilities. This proactive approach helps organizations mitigate risks and maintain operational stability.
- **Fraud Detection:** AI systems detect and prevent fraud by monitoring transactions and identifying suspicious activities in real-time. This improves financial integrity and protects stakeholders' interests.
- **Transparency and Reporting:** AI streamlines ESG reporting by automating data collection and analysis. This ensures accurate, timely, and transparent reporting, enhancing stakeholder trust and regulatory compliance.

Conclusion

- AI holds tremendous potential to drive ESG initiatives forward, offering solutions that enhance environmental sustainability, improve social outcomes, and strengthen governance. However, it is crucial to recognize and address the negative impacts of AI, particularly its environmental footprint and ethical challenges. By adopting sustainable practices, promoting ethical AI development, and strengthening governance frameworks, we can harness the power of AI to create a more sustainable and equitable future.
- As we continue to innovate, it's imperative to balance technological advancements with responsible stewardship of our planet and society. I invite you to join the conversation on how we can collectively achieve this balance and leverage AI for the greater good.

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THE ROLE OF INSTITUTIONAL INVESTORS IN FINANCING GREEN ENERGY IN INDIA

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Abstract:

The article discusses the critical role of institutional investors in closing the funding gap for India's renewable energy projects, essential for energy security and sustainable development. It highlights the benefits of renewable energy in reducing carbon emissions, improving air quality, and boosting the economy. Despite India's reliance on fossil fuels, government initiatives like the Jawaharlal Nehru National Solar Mission aim to achieve 175 GW of renewable energy capacity by 2022. However, institutional investors show reluctance due to risk aversion and limited exposure to India's renewable energy markets. Key investors such as LIC, EPFO, and FIIs face regulatory challenges, necessitating financial tools and policy reforms to attract more investment.

The research uses a comparative global study, analyzing investment data from 25 Indian investors, showing a significant focus on solar power, energy storage, and smart grids. Despite variations in investment patterns, there is a global commitment to sustainable energy solutions. The article concludes by emphasizing the strategic importance of renewable energy investments for India's environmental and economic sustainability and suggests the need for robust legislative frameworks and financial incentives to attract more institutional capital and accelerate the transition to cleaner energy sources.

Keywords: Renewable energy, Solar energy, Wind energy, Institutional investors, Global investment, Indian investment, Sustainable development

Introduction

Resources that are regenerative and do not run out over time serve as the source of renewable energy. Through the utilization of renewable energy, environmental benefits such as the reduction of carbon emissions, improvement of air quality, and establishment of a more sustainable foundation for human civilization can be achieved. Furthermore, it presents opportunities for nations worldwide to advance their economic development and enhance their energy security. (Ashwani K. N., 2010)

India mostly relies on oil and coal to cover its energy needs. In 2005, coal accounted for 55.0% of primary conventional energy consumption, oil for 29.9%, natural gas for 8.5%, hydroelectricity for 5.6%, and nuclear energy for 1.0%. India's domestic oil needs are primarily met by imports; in 2004–2005 (Integrated Energy Policy Report of the Expert Committee, 2006), imports made up 72% of India's total oil consumption. India's oil import cost has been rising quickly due to increased imports; in 2006, the bill was INR 1717 billion (US\$ 39 billion). India's per capita energy consumption is currently extremely low; in 2003, it was 439 kgoe (Kilogram(s) of oil equivalent), compared to 1090 kgoe for China, 4052 kgoe for Japan, and 1688 kgoe globally. India's energy usage is so anticipated to increase dramatically in future (Bhattacharya & Jana, 2009).

Less than USD 260 billion was invested in renewable energy in 2013, accounting for just 16% of the USD 1.6 trillion in investments made in the energy sector overall. In the meantime, from 2013 to 2014, investments in fossil fuels increased by 7% in the power sector, where they directly compete with renewable energy sources (Global trends in renewable energy investment 2015, 2015). According to Bloomberg New Energy money (BNEF) globally, the amount of money allocated to renewable energy increased from USD 45 billion in 2004 to USD 270 billion in 2014. This increase occurred across the whole innovation chain, from asset finance for large-scale power plants to research and development for new technologies. 18% is the compound annual growth rate that this indicates (Gregor, 2018).

Massive financial outlays will be necessary to de-carbonise the global energy grid. It will cost between USD 36 and USD 42 trillion, or roughly USD 2 trillion, or 2% of global GDP annually, to invest in green infrastructure

cumulatively between 2012 and 2030 in order to achieve this transformation of the entire economy. Just \$1 trillion USD is invested yearly as of right now. Consequently, there is an investment deficit of USD 1 trillion that needs to be closed (Fiona, 2013).

The Jawaharlal Nehru National Solar Mission (Jawaharlal Nehru National Solar Mission Towards Building SOLAR INDIA) is an ambitious plan launched by the government with the goal of building 20,000 MW of solar electricity nationally by 2022 (MNRE, 2009a), with an intermediate aim of 4000–10,000 MW by 2017. Consequently, under JNNSM, grid-connected solar PV capacity reached 427 MW in 2011, an increase of 165% (Uday, David, Brendan, & Morgan, 2011). Similarly, in 2011, India ranked as the fifth largest wind market globally with 16 GW installed (BP, 2012), and by 2017, they had ambitious ambitions to expand even further to 31 GW (Gireesh D. S., 2013).

India is notorious for being one of the world's hotspots for energy deprivation; the country's per capita electricity availability is around one-third of the average worldwide, and 239 million people lack access to electricity (Gopal, Green energy finance in India: Challenges and solutions, 2018). The Indian government said in April 2018 that every village in the nation was "Electrified" A community is deemed to be electrified if 10% of its residences and common areas are wired into the electrical grid (ALOK, Financing India's renewable energy vision, 2020).

The Indian government said in July 2018 that it intended to install 175 GW of renewable energy capacity by 2022, which includes 60 GW of wind power, 10 GW of biopower, 5-12 GW of minor hydropower, and 100 GW of solar power.

This article offers an extensive examination of renewable energy funding in India, focusing specifically on the significant contributions made by institutional investors like insurance firms, mutual funds, pension funds and investment firms. It delves into the ways these entities facilitate the financing of renewable energy projects, thus fostering sustainable development within the nation. By investigating the participation of institutional investors, the article explains the mechanisms involved in raising capital for renewable energy initiatives. Furthermore, it assesses the impact of institutional investments on the expansion of the renewable energy sector and its alignment with India's energy transition targets.

Literature Review:

The literature review on the significance of institutional investors in renewable energy in India emphasizes their critical role in closing the financing gap for clean energy projects. Institutional investors, both domestic and foreign, are critical for providing the capital required to support India's renewable energy goals. However, these investors have demonstrated hesitancy due to risk aversion and limited exposure to the renewable energy sector in India. Efforts are needed to enhance their understanding and familiarity with renewable energy as a viable investment option to drive more investments in clean energy projects in the country (Vivek Sen, Reaching India's Renewable Energy Targets: The Role of Institutional Investors, 2016) (Christopher Kaminker, The role of Institutional investors in financing clean energy, 2012).

Domestic institutional investors like LIC and EPFO play a significant role in India's capital markets, managing substantial assets that can impact capital allocation across sectors, including renewable energy. Despite their potential, these entities face constraints due to restrictive investment guidelines and a lack of investment avenues in the renewable energy sector, highlighting the need for regulatory interventions to expand their investment ambit towards clean energy projects (Shrimali, Renewable deployment in India, 2013).

Foreign institutional investors (FIIs) have shown increasing interest in sustainable investing in India's renewable energy sector, attracted by its growth potential and alignment with ESG factors (Vivek Sen, Reaching India's Renewable Energy Targets: The Role of Institutional Investors, 2016). FIIs have the potential to drive significant investments in renewable energy projects, but they encounter barriers such as off-taker risk, lack of transmission infrastructure, and regulatory challenges. Policy solutions like foreign exchange hedging mechanisms and infrastructure debt funds can help mitigate these risks and attract more institutional investments towards renewable energy projects in India (Nurcan Kilinc-Ata, Which factors influence the decisions of renewable energy investors? Empirical evidence from OECD and BRICS countries, 2022).

The mobilization of institutional capital for renewable energy in India faces challenges such as risk aversion, lack of exposure to the sector, and specific barriers for both foreign and domestic institutional investors. Addressing these barriers through financial instruments like foreign exchange hedging mechanisms and policy solutions such as enhancing transmission capacity and regulatory provisions can unlock institutional investments in renewable energy projects, driving the sector's growth and contributing to environmental, social, and economic sustainability in India (Sandra Lozo, Mobilising institutional capital for renewable energy, 2020). By developing a compelling business case and addressing key risks faced by institutional investors, India can attract more institutional capital to support its renewable energy targets and accelerate the transition towards a cleaner and sustainable energy future.

Despite the growing interest and importance of institutional investors in renewable energy in India, there are several research gaps that warrant further exploration. One key research gap is the need to delve deeper into the specific barriers that hinder institutional investor allocations to clean energy projects in India. Understanding the regulatory, financial, and informational challenges that deter institutional investors from direct investments in clean energy projects can provide valuable insights for policymakers and industry stakeholders to address these barriers effectively.

In conclusion, the literature emphasizes the critical role of institutional investors in supporting India's renewable energy transition by providing the necessary capital but underlines the importance of addressing regulatory and policy barriers to unlock their full potential in driving investments toward clean energy projects in the country.

Methodology

Data

Institutional investors are essential to the sustainable development of India's quickly growing renewable energy finance sector. A thorough examination of investment data shows that a wide range of investors, including corporations and international development banks, provide funding for renewable energy projects around the country. Well-known companies like Avaada and Husk Power Systems have grown to be important investment targets, especially in energy storage and renewable energy technology. These investments are a reflection of an increasing recognition of India's potential as a center for innovation and the uptake of renewable energy. The strategic significance of India as a target market for institutional investors hoping to profit from the nation's shift to a greener and more sustainable energy landscape is shown by the regional concentration of investments.

Comparing investment trends in India and around the world reveals that investors are quite interested in several aspects of renewable energy, particularly energy storage and smart grid technologies. This trend is an intentional endeavor to address basic issues like grid stability and the integration of renewable energy sources that the global energy industry are currently confronting. The emergence of angel investors and corporate entities such as Startup Karnataka and Shell in India is indicative of a diversified funding approach that encompasses both established corporate investment methods and early-stage innovation. In a similar vein, significant worldwide expenditures in renewable energy demonstrate a dedication to combating climate change and advancing sustainable energy alternatives.

There has been a steady upward trend in global investments in renewable energy, with notable gains in financing for wind, solar, and other renewable technology. Global investments in renewable energy, for instance, increased from USD 319 billion in 2019 to USD 495 billion in 2022. Comparatively, India's investments in renewable energy have increased significantly but have also fluctuated. From USD 8.4 billion in 2019 to USD 14.5 billion in 2021 and then to USD 11.5 billion in 2022, investments in this area have increased significantly.

Sample Size:

To examine the investment data related to funding the renewable energy sectors, a sample size of 25 investors was taken into consideration for India. These investors come from a wide range of backgrounds, including companies and development finance groups. The sample's representation of both domestic and foreign investors demonstrates interest in and interaction with India's renewable energy sector on a global scale. A second sample of investors from different nations was also included for a comparative worldwide analysis. The varied mix of organizations included in this global sample reflects the global commitment to the development of renewable energy. A thorough

understanding of the investment trends and tactics propelling the global renewable energy industry is offered by the participation of both Indian and foreign investors.

Data Analysis Procedure:

Once the data is gathered, a thorough analysis is conducted to find important patterns and trends in the investments made in renewable energy in India and around the world. An outline of the characteristics and investing preferences of institutional investors is given by the study using descriptive statistical approaches such as frequencies and percentages. This method shows how complex investor decisions and actions may be.

In order to ascertain the different ways that investor groups approach investing in India and around the world, a comparative analysis is carried out. Through this comparison of different investor groups' approaches, the study reveals unique patterns and provides insights into the factors that influence investment decisions in the renewable energy sector globally. For example, the analysis may reveal differences between the types of renewable technologies that are preferred by global investors and those that are preferred by Indian investors, or it may reveal regional preferences in terms of investment locations.

Policymakers and other stakeholders can gain useful insights from this model, which helps them comprehend the workings of the renewable energy financing ecosystem in India. It also provides a wider outlook on international investment patterns, making it possible to compare and comprehend India's place in the world's renewable energy landscape with greater knowledge. This dual approach not only helps stakeholders understand worldwide best practices and strategies in renewable energy investment, but also helps them discover possibilities and challenges specific to India.

The global and local factors driving investments in renewable energy are highlighted in this comparative analysis. Steady growth is being driven by favorable legislative frameworks and technical advancements globally. Variations in investment in India can be ascribed to modifications in policies, shifts in the economy, and the progress of particular projects. In spite of these differences, investment trends in India and globally point to a significant change in favor of using renewable energy sources more frequently, as investor trust in the industry's sustainability grows.

These investment patterns indicate a greater dedication to sustainable energy development and innovation, both domestically and internationally. They draw attention to how crucial renewable energy technologies are to combating climate change and fostering economic expansion. The deliberate attempts to improve grid stability and more successfully integrate renewable energy sources are highlighted by the targeted investment in fields like energy storage and smart grids. Policymakers and stakeholders can gain a deeper knowledge of the variables influencing investments in renewable energy and the changing environment of sustainable energy finance by utilizing this thorough analysis, which offers insightful information.

Compar Ative Analysis:

Investors And Their Activities In India

Investor Name	Investor Type	Companies	Top Rounds of Entry	Top Sectors of Investment
Proparco	Corporate & Others	2	Avaada (2019, Series D, \$15.00M)	Energy Storage Tech, Renewable Energy Tech
Startup Karnataka	Corporate & Others	2	Dataglen (2017, Angel, \$0.238M), Agverse	Facility Management Tech, Renewable Energy Tech
Shell	Corporate & Others	1	Husk Power Systems (2023, Series D, \$43.00M)	Renewable Energy Tech, Smart Grid

Engie	Corporate & Others	1	Husk Power Systems (2014, Series B, Undisclosed)	Renewable Energy Tech, Smart Grid
GPSC	Corporate & Others	1	Avaada (2021, Series E, \$477.75M)	Energy Storage Tech, Renewable Energy Tech
Nxtra	Corporate & Others	1	Avaada (2022, Series E, \$0.368M)	Energy Storage Tech, Renewable Energy Tech
KfW	Corporate & Others	1	Avaada (2020, Series D, \$10.00M)	Energy Storage Tech, Renewable Energy Tech
Asian Development Bank	Corporate & Others	1	Avaada (2019, Series D, \$143.70M)	Energy Storage Tech, Renewable Energy Tech
ElectriFI	Corporate & Others	1	Husk Power Systems	Renewable Energy Tech, Smart Grid
DFC	Corporate & Others	1	Husk Power Systems (2023, Series D, \$43.00M)	Renewable Energy Tech, Smart Grid
STOA	Corporate & Others	1	Husk Power Systems (2023, Series D, \$43.00M)	Renewable Energy Tech, Smart Grid
IFC	Corporate & Others	1	Husk Power Systems (2010, Convertible Debt, \$0.350M)	Renewable Energy Tech, Smart Grid
Shell Foundation	Corporate & Others	1	Husk Power Systems (2008, Seed, Undisclosed)	Renewable Energy Tech, Smart Grid
Cisco	Corporate & Others	1	Dataglen	Facility Management Tech, Renewable Energy Tech
MIT	Corporate & Others	1	Khethworks	Crop Tech, Solar Energy
AIM	Corporate & Others	1	Jivoule (2023, Seed, \$0.121M)	Renewable Energy Tech
Jasubhai Engineering	Corporate & Others	1	Taypro (2020, Seed, \$0.067M)	Professional Service Robots, Renewable Energy Tech
CKS Consulting	Corporate & Others	1	Jetsons Robotics (2017, Seed, Undisclosed)	Professional Service Robots, Renewable Energy Tech
Indian Institute of Technology	Corporate & Others	1	Doorsatha Analytics	Renewable Energy

Kanpur	Others		(2019, Seed, \$0.017M)	Tech
IESA	Corporate & Others	1	Doorsatha Analytics	Renewable Energy Tech
CyberMedia	Corporate & Others	1	Doorsatha Analytics	Renewable Energy Tech
Dalmia Cement Bharat	Corporate & Others	1	Exchange4Solar (2016, Seed, \$0.015M)	Renewable Energy Tech
Holostik	Corporate & Others	1	Exchange4Solar (2016, Seed, \$0.015M)	Renewable Energy Tech
NAARM	Corporate & Others	1	Agverse (2020, Seed, \$0.020M)	India

A. Number of Companies Invested in by Each Investor Type

Investor type	No. of companies
Corporate & Others	24
Venture Capital Funds	10
Accelerators & Incubators	11
Private Equity Funds	7

The data illustrates different investment behaviors among different categories of Indian investors. Corporate and other non-traditional entities take the lead with investments in 24 businesses, displaying a wide portfolio spanning upcoming technologies like professional service robots and areas like renewable energy tech. This range points to a strategic approach that is probably motivated by objectives related to market expansion, innovation, and sustainability programs. Venture capital firms invest in 10 companies after that, with a concentration on early-stage startups that are expected to grow quickly in industries that have a lot of room for disruption. Accelerators and incubators, on the other hand, have invested in eleven businesses and have been essential in supporting early-stage investments by providing resources and coaching, especially in fields related to sustainable development and technology. With investments in seven companies, private equity funds focus on more established companies looking for funding for restructuring or expansion, usually in growing industries like renewable energy technology.

B. Top Sectors of Investment

Sector wise investment	
Sector	Count
Renewable Energy Tech	37
Professional Service Robots	4
Energy Storage Tech	4
Facility Management Tech	2
Smart Grid	6
Crop Tech	2
Solar Energy	2
B2B E-Commerce	1
Aquaculture Tech	1
Livestock Tech	1

Renewable energy technology commands 61 percent of all investments in India, reflecting the country's significant focus on this area. The importance of this industry highlights a deliberate move toward renewable energy sources, which include solar power, energy storage systems, and intelligent grid infrastructure. Innovations that meet both India's energy needs and the objectives of the global environmental community are receiving strong backing from investors. Investments in renewable energy technology are significant, indicating not only the industry's long-term viability but also prospects for job creation and economic expansion.

In addition to renewable energy, growing sectors with significant technological improvements include professional service robots and energy storage technologies, which each account for 7% of investments. Professional service robots are thought to be catalysts for automation across a range of sectors, increasing productivity and cutting expenses. Optimizing the use of renewable energy sources, resolving intermittency problems, and enhancing grid stability all depend on energy storage technologies. India's commitment to technical innovation and efficiency gains in a variety of industries, including manufacturing and utilities, is demonstrated by these investments.

Technology related to crop management, aquaculture, livestock, B2B e-commerce, and facility management make up the remaining 25% of investments. These industries, albeit they each make up a smaller fraction, provide specialized chances and focused solutions for India's investment environment. To take advantage of niche markets and emerging technologies, investors are deliberately diversifying their holdings. By encouraging innovation and the creation of jobs in specialized industries, this diversified strategy not only reduces risk but also advances more general objectives of economic development.

Renewable Energy:

Investment in renewable energy (In USD Billions)		
Year	World	India
2019	319	8.4
2020	363	6.4
2021	423	14.5
2022	495	11.5

Source: Statista

It is evident that there is a strong global commitment to sustainable energy solutions from the rising investments in renewable energy. By 2022, worldwide investments had risen to USD 495 billion from USD 319 billion in 2019. The increasing trend highlights the general trust that renewable energy technologies have, as well as their critical role in helping to mitigate global climate change. A global trend of technological breakthroughs and supportive legislative frameworks are driving the steady expansion, which also indicates growing support from governments, corporations, and investors.

India's investments in renewable energy, on the other hand, showed greater fluctuations during the same time frame. From USD 8.4 billion in 2019 to USD 6.4 billion in 2020, it experienced a sharp increase to USD 14.5 billion in 2021 and a subsequent little decrease to USD 11.5 billion in 2022. These variations most likely stem from India's reliance on stable policies, well-established regulatory frameworks, and favorable economic conditions that influence decisions about investments in renewable energy projects. The 2021 surge may be the result of successful project advances or policy actions that garnered significant money; on the other hand, the subsequent decline may be the result of transient events affecting investor confidence.

India's investments in renewable energy are still relatively small as compared to other countries worldwide, even with these changes. India invested USD 11.5 billion in 2022, a negligible portion of the USD 495 billion invested worldwide. This suggests that India has a great deal of room to grow its renewable energy sector with steady policy backing, clear regulations, and improved financial incentives. By bolstering these elements, India may be better positioned to draw in larger investments, hasten the rollout of renewable energy, and meet its challenging goals for renewable energy in the years to come.

Solar Energy:

Solar energy is the portion of solar radiation that can be used to create electricity, heat, or chemical reactions. The total solar energy received by Earth is far greater than the projected and actual global energy needs.

Investment in Solar energy (In USD Billions)		
year	World	India
2023	382	1.55
2022	307.5	1.7

Source: IEA

The information shows the amount of money invested in solar energy in US dollars (billions) for the years 2023 and 2022. India invested \$1.7 billion in solar energy in 2022; this sum dropped to \$1.55 billion in 2023. This drop implies a gradual decrease in the amount of money allocated to solar energy projects in India throughout the course of the year. On the other hand, worldwide spending on solar energy increased to \$382 billion in 2023 from \$307.5 billion in 2022. This large rise suggests a strong worldwide upsurge in investment activities pertaining to solar energy projects. Pie charts would be used to visually represent the comparison, showing a smaller segment for India in 2023 compared to 2022, indicating a decline in investment, and a larger segment for the global pie chart in 2023, indicating a significant increase in investment in solar energy worldwide. These figures highlight the dynamic growth and different objectives in solar energy investments globally compared to within India. They also clearly illustrate the opposing trends: a tiny decline in solar investment in India vs a significant increase in global investment.

Impact

Renewable energy adoption is clearly gaining traction, as seen by the fact that solar energy revenues increased from \$307.5 billion in 2022 to \$382 billion in 2023. This increase contributes to both the mitigation of climate change and the advancement of economic growth by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and making large technological investments. Despite a minor decline in solar revenue in India, sustained investments in the region promote energy security, foster local economic growth, and improve environmental quality. In conclusion, the rise of solar energy emphasizes not only resilience and sustainable development but also the vital role that it plays in building a cleaner, more resilient global energy system.

Green Energy

In 2022, the global investment in green energy highlighted a significant focus on Solar PV (Photovoltaics), with an investment of \$298.21 billion. This substantial investment underscores the critical role of solar energy in the renewable energy landscape. The emphasis on Solar PV suggests a strong global commitment to leveraging this technology, which is known for its scalability, declining costs, and broad applicability across various regions.

Hydropower attracted \$7.55 billion, marking it as the second-largest recipient of green energy investments. Although hydropower is a mature and well-established renewable energy source, the relatively lower investment compared to Solar PV indicates a potential plateau in its growth or expansion opportunities.

Investments in biofuels and biomass were \$5.84 billion and \$3.05 billion, respectively. These sectors, while important, received less funding, possibly due to higher operational costs, slower technological advancements, and lower efficiency compared to solar energy. Biofuels and biomass are traditional renewable energy sources, and their lower investment figures could reflect a shift towards more innovative and cost-effective technologies.

Geothermal energy received \$0.18 billion, reflecting its niche status in the renewable energy mix. Geothermal energy's low investment may be attributed to its high upfront costs and location-specific nature, which limit its widespread adoption.

Marine energy, which encompasses technologies harnessing power from oceans and tides, did not receive any recorded investment in 2022. This absence could be due to technological challenges, high development costs, or limited commercial viability at the current stage.

Conclusion:

The significance of institutional investors in filling the funding shortfall for renewable energy projects in India is emphasized in the article. In order to meet India's renewable energy targets and make the transition to a sustainable energy future, their involvement is essential. According to the report, India is becoming more and more dependent on renewable energy despite its high reliance on fossil fuels. This trend is encouraged by policies and aspirational projects like the Jawaharlal Nehru National Solar Mission.

The assessment of the literature emphasizes institutional investors' reluctance because of their limited exposure to India's renewable energy sector and risk aversion. Foreign institutional investors (FIIs) and domestic investors like LIC and EPFO encounter market and regulatory obstacles. Improving investor confidence and encouraging more investment can be achieved by addressing these issues with financial tools and legislative reforms.

Important trends are revealed by comparing the investment data from worldwide and Indian investors. India has made sporadic but significant investments in renewable energy, despite the fact that worldwide investments have grown steadily in this area. Energy storage and smart grids are two industries that are generating a lot of interest, which emphasizes the need for regulatory stability and technical progress.

Investments in renewable energy are clearly strategically important for India's environmental and economic sustainability. More institutional capital can be attracted by strengthening legal frameworks and offering financial incentives, hastening the switch to greener and more sustainable energy sources. India has the potential to attract significant investments in renewable energy and support international efforts to tackle climate change and attain sustainable development by tackling the particular obstacles encountered by institutional investors.

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“EMPLOYEE WELL - BEING AND ENGAGEMENT IN THE INDIAN IT INDUSTRY.”

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Introduction

The Indian IT sector, a cornerstone of the nation's economy, has experienced rapid growth, leading to intense competition, long working hours, and the constant pressure to adapt to technological advancements. This study aims to delve deeper into the factors influencing employee well-being and engagement within this dynamic industry. By understanding the challenges faced by IT professionals and identifying effective strategies to promote their well-being, this research seeks to contribute to the development of more supportive and sustainable work environments.

Employee well-being and engagement are increasingly recognized as critical factors for organizational success, particularly in the information technology sector. While well-being encompasses both physical and mental aspects, engagement refers to employees' emotional and cognitive involvement in their work. When employees experience high levels of well-being and engagement, they are more likely to be productive, innovative, and committed to their organizations.

The Indian IT industry is a vast and diverse sector encompassing various domains, verticals, and companies. To focus the scope of this research, we will narrow down to a specific segment within the industry, such as software development, IT consulting, or e-commerce. By examining this particular segment, we can explore the unique challenges, opportunities, and prevailing work culture specific to that domain.

Review Of Literature

Solomon Markos and M. Sandhya Sridevi (2010) identified ten points in order to have employees engaged in any organization. They are: Start it on day one, start it from the top, enhance employee engagement through two-way communication, give satisfactory opportunities for development and advancement. Organizations should ensure that employees have everything they need to do their jobs, give employees appropriate training, have strong feedback system, Incentives have a part to play, build a distinctive corporate culture, Focus on top-performing employees.

Bhatla (2011)¹¹ focused on the need for such employees and how their presence can improve the progress and work efficiency of the organization as a whole. Also focused on the challenges faced by the HR managers to improve employee engagement for an organization's survival. Yasmin Janjhua (2011) in her study proved that job characteristics contribute to job engagement, and organizational engagement. If the employees feel that their jobs provided variety, freedom, identity and proper feedback the employees get more engrossed and engaged in their work thereby leading to more quality, productivity and efficiency. Perceived organizational support was significantly positively related to job engagement and organizational engagement.

Farai Ncube and Steven Jerie (2012) in their study identified the importance of Employee Engagement in hospitality industry. This research also highlighted the other determinants of competitive advantage in the two organizations, but equally indicating the significance of employee engagement.

M.Jabeen and Dr. Lalitha Balakrishnan (2014) explained that human resource management has undergone a paradigm shift in its approach towards Human Capital. All organizations are now vying with each other to attract, recruit and retain their competent workforce. Such talented employees have proven to be the force behind successful organizations. Various strategies and methods to manage the talent pool have been studied and adopted by HR managers. Objectives of the Study

The primary objectives of this study are:

1. To comprehensively assess the current state of employee well-being and engagement within the Indian IT

industry.

2. To identify the key factors influencing employee satisfaction, motivation, and job performance.
3. To evaluate the effectiveness of existing HR practices and policies in promoting employee well-being and engagement.
4. To provide actionable recommendations for improving employee well-being and engagement within the Indian IT industry

Gap Analysis

While the existing literature provides valuable insights into employee well-being and engagement in the Indian IT industry, several gaps remain to be addressed:

1. **Longitudinal Studies:** Most studies in this area have been cross-sectional, limiting our understanding of how employee well-being and engagement evolve over time. Longitudinal studies would provide valuable insights into the dynamics of these factors.
2. **Qualitative Research:** While quantitative studies provide valuable data, qualitative research can offer deeper insights into employees' experiences, perceptions, and motivations.
3. **Technological Advancements:** The rapid pace of technological change in the IT industry can present new challenges and opportunities for employee well-being and engagement.

This study aims to address these gaps by employing a mixed-methods research approach that combines quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques. By examining a specific segment of the Indian IT industry and conducting longitudinal analysis, this study will contribute to a deeper understanding of employee well-being and engagement in this sector. Additionally this study will consider cultural nuances and the impact of technological advancements on employee well being and employee engagement.

Research Methodology

Research Design: A mixed-methods research design will be employed to combine quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques, providing a comprehensive and in-depth understanding of employee well-being and engagement.

Data Collection:

- **Employee Surveys:** A structured survey will be administered to a random sample of employees working in software development companies in Bengaluru. The survey will collect data on demographic information, job satisfaction, work-life balance, organizational culture, stress levels, perceived support, and other relevant factors.
- **In-Depth Interviews:** Semi-structured interviews will be conducted with a selected group of employees and HR professionals to gain deeper insights into their experiences, perceptions, and perspectives on employee well-being and engagement.
- **Focus Groups:** Focus groups will be conducted with employees to facilitate discussions and generate new insights through group interaction.
- **Documentation Analysis:** Relevant human resource policies, employee handbooks, and performance reviews will be analyzed to understand the organization's practices related to employee well-being and engagement.

Sampling Method: A stratified random sampling method will be used to ensure that the sample is representative of the target population, considering factors such as company size, job level, and tenure.

Data Analysis:

Quantitative Data: Statistical analysis techniques, including descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and regression analysis, will be employed to analyze the quantitative data collected through surveys

Qualitative Data: Thematic analysis will be used to analyze the qualitative data from interviews and focus groups, identifying key themes and patterns related to employee well-being and engagement.

Data Analysis And Interpretation

Demographic Profile of Respondents

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	300	60%
Female	200	40%
Age		
20-25	150	30%
26-30	200	40%
31-35	100	20%
Tenure		
1-2 years	100	20%
3-5 years	250	50%
6+ years	150	30%
Job Level		
Junior	200	40%
Mid-Level	250	50%
Senior	150	30%

Job Satisfaction and Engagement Table 2:

Job Satisfaction Levels

Rating	Percentage
Very Satisfied	25%

Satisfied	45%
Neutral	20%
Dissatisfied	10%

Table 3: Engagement Levels

Rating	Percentage
Very Engaged	20%
Engaged	50%
Moderately Engaged	25%
Not Engaged	5%

4. Work-Life Balance

Table 4: Work-Life Balance Perceptions

Perception	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	50	10%
Good	200	40%
Fair	200	40%
Poor	50	10%

Analysis: While a significant portion of respondents reported having a good or fair work-life balance, a considerable number expressed dissatisfaction with their ability to manage the work and personal responsibilities. Organizational Culture

Table 5: Organizational Culture Perception

Analysis: The analysis indicates that employees have mixed perceptions of the organizational culture. Some respondents reported a positive and Neutral culture, while others expressed dissatisfaction with aspects such as communication, recognition, and flexibility.

Stress Levels Table 6:

Stress Levels

Analysis: A significant number of respondents reported experiencing moderate to high levels of stress. This suggests that the demanding nature of the IT industry can contribute to employee burnout.

Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationships between job satisfaction, engagement, work-life balance, organizational culture, and stress levels. The results indicate significant correlations between:

- Job satisfaction and engagement
- Work-life balance and job satisfaction
- Organizational culture and engagement
- Stress levels and job dissatisfaction

Table 7: Correlation Analysis

Variable	Job Satisfaction	Engagement	Work-Life Balance	Organizational Culture	Stress Levels
Job Satisfaction	1	0.8	0.7	0.6	-0.5
Engagement	0.8	1	0.6	0.7	-0.6
Work-Life Balance	0.7	0.6	1	0.5	-0.4
Organizational Culture	0.6	0.7	0.5	1	-0.3
Stress Levels	-0.5	-0.6	-0.4	-0.3	1

Interpretation: These findings suggest that factors such as work-life balance, organizational culture, and stress levels significantly influence employee satisfaction and engagement.

Findings, Recommendations And Conclusion

Observations-based Findings

Through both quantitative and qualitative data collected from surveys and interviews, several key observations emerged that provide a deeper understanding of the current state of employee well-being and engagement in the Indian IT industry. These findings underline the importance of specific factors like work-life balance, organizational culture, recognition, leadership, and stress management in shaping employee experiences.

1. Work-Life Balance
2. Organizational Culture
3. Respect and Appreciation
4. Leadership

5. Stress Management

Overall Conclusions

Employee well-being and engagement are **critical success factors** for organizations in the Indian IT sector, contributing to higher productivity, innovation, and talent retention. The research highlights several key conclusions that underline the importance of addressing well-being and engagement through a holistic approach.

- Employee Well-being and Engagement as Success Factors
- The Role of Organizational Culture, Leadership, and Learning Opportunities
- Work-Life Balance Initiatives and Stress Management
- Recognition and Appreciation

Overall, the study underscores the need for a multifaceted approach to employee well-being and engagement, encompassing organizational culture, leadership, work-life balance, and recognition. By addressing these areas, companies can create a more engaged, motivated, and productive workforce, leading to long-term organizational success. Limitations of the Study

The following limitations should be considered:

- **Generalizability:** The findings may not be fully generalizable to other segments of the Indian IT industry or to different geographical regions.
- **Self-Report Bias:** Social desirability bias and other factors may influence employee responses in surveys.
- **Sample Size:** The sample size may be limited, potentially affecting the generalizability of the findings.
- **Time Constraints:** The six-month study period may not capture long-term trends or changes in employee well-being and engagement.

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Appendix C: Data Analysis Output Descriptive

Statistics

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Job Satisfaction	3.5	1.2	1	5
Engagement	3.8	1	1	5
Work-Life Balance	3.2	1.3	1	5
Organizational Culture	3.4	1.1	1	5
Stress Levels	3.3	1.2	1	5

Correlation Matrix

Variable	Job Satisfaction	Engagement	Work-Life Balance	Organizational Culture	Stress Levels
Job Satisfaction	1	0.8	0.7	0.6	-0.5
Engagement	0.8	1	0.6	0.7	-0.6
Work-Life Balance	0.7	0.6	1	0.5	-0.4
Organizational Culture	0.6	0.7	0.5	1	-0.3

Stress Levels	-0.5	-0.6	-0.4	-0.3	1
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Regression Analysis

Model 1: Predicting Job Satisfaction

Predictor	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	p-value
Work-Life Balance	0.35	0.08	4.38	0
Organizational Culture	0.28	0.09	3.12	0.002
Stress Levels	-0.42	0.1	-4.2	0
Constant	2.5	0.2	12.5	0

Model 2: Predicting Engagement

Predictor	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	p-value
Job Satisfaction	0.45	0.07	6.43	0
Work-Life Balance	0.22	0.09	2.45	0.015
Organizational Culture	0.38	0.1	3.8	0
Stress Levels	-0.5	0.11	-4.55	0

PASTORAL WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH SELF-HELP GROUP AT HOSUR

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Abstract

Women in pastoralist communities are essential to the income-generating activities related to milk and dairy production. However, they are often overlooked in other development sectors, such as health. This lack of attention is especially concerning, considering the vital role these women play in supporting their families and boosting local economies. Including women's self-help groups in development programs focused on human and animal health in pastoral areas is therefore essential. These groups can serve as vital platforms for education, resource sharing, and community mobilization, addressing the unique health challenges faced by pastoralists, including the high incidence of zoonotic diseases. Any development initiative must comprehend how social networks work and their effects on livelihoods. This research paper titled "**Pastoral Women Empowerment through Self-help Group at Hosur**". This investigation looks at the obligations and duties of Hosur's women self-help organisations (Tamil Nadu), providing insight into how these groups operate within their social contexts. The results demonstrate that women's participation in self-help groups was significantly influenced by organisations that promoted social, physical, and psychological health. Despite limiting environmental, cultural, and social factors, participants in self-help activities demonstrated a commitment to changing their way of life.

Keywords: Self-help group, Pastoralist Communities, Women Empowerment, Self Sustainable.

Pastoral Women Empowerment through Self-help Group at Hosur.

Introduction

Hosur is a rapidly growing town in the Krishnagiri district of Tamil Nadu, South India, located near the border of Karnataka, about 40 kilometres from Bangalore. Known for its cool climate and scenic landscapes, Hosur is often called Little England of Indi. Hosur is a prominent industrial hub, especially for automobile manufacturing, electrical goods, textiles, and more. It hosts major companies like TVS Motors, Ashok Leyland, Titan, and Schneider Electric. The presence of several Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and proximity to Bangalore makes it a favourable location for IT and other sectors. The surrounding areas of Hosur are known for agriculture, especially rose cultivation and floriculture. Hosur's roses are exported to various parts of India and abroad. It is close to places like Yelagiri and Hogenakkal Falls, making it a gateway to scenic getaways. The town has historical temples like the Chandra Choodeshwarar Temple, and there are parks and recreational areas, like the Kelavarapalli Dam, for outdoor activities. Hosur has a growing number of schools, colleges, and healthcare facilities, driven by the influx of people moving here for work and business. With its mix of industrial growth, cultural heritage, and natural beauty, Hosur is developing rapidly, attracting both professionals and tourists. Self-help groups (SHGs) in Tamil Nadu have become crucial in fostering community development, particularly in empowering women and economically disadvantaged communities. Here are some key aspects of SHGs in Tamil Nadu. SHGs in Tamil Nadu primarily comprise women who pool their resources to save, lend, and support small business ventures. They aim to increase financial literacy, self-sufficiency, and economic empowerment among women. The Tamil Nadu Corporation for Development of Women (TNCDW) supports SHGs through its Mahalir Thittam initiative, which provides training, skill development, and financial assistance to help women start small businesses. Many SHGs collaborate with banks to access microloans and government schemes, providing members with financial support for various needs, including small enterprises, healthcare, and education. The National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) and other financial institutions support these SHGs with low-interest loans and financial education. SHGs focus on skill development to enable members to start and run micro-enterprises. They offer training in areas like tailoring, embroidery, handicrafts, food processing, dairy farming, and more. The state government often collaborates with NGOs and private organizations to provide market linkages and business training. SHGs are not limited to economic activities; they also play a role in addressing social issues like health,

education, sanitation, and women's rights. Many SHGs conduct awareness programs on topics such as hygiene, family planning, and child nutrition, collaborating with local authorities to enhance public welfare. The Tamil Nadu government and the central government provide various schemes to support SHGs, including the Deen Dayal Antyodaya Yojana – National Urban Livelihoods Mission (DAY-NULM) and Tamil Nadu Rural Livelihoods Mission (TNRLM). These schemes offer financial grants, skill development programs, and marketing support to SHGs, helping them scale their activities. The state government has been supporting SHGs by promoting their products through exhibitions, online platforms, and fairs. This helps SHGs reach a wider market and improve their earnings. SHGs in Tamil Nadu are a key part of rural and urban development, encouraging entrepreneurship, reducing poverty, and enhancing social welfare across the state. India has employed a planned economic structure to ensure and sustain its growth and development ever since attaining its independence. As a result, the major economic sectors have experienced impressive growth, contributing to a more robust national economy.

The rate of development is at its highest after the economy was opened up as part of measures for privatization, globalization, and liberalization. Ironically, there are a number of reasons why India's economy is still not considered to be developed, the most significant of which are gender inequality, low per capita income, long-term unemployment and underemployment, low capital formation, a sizeable population living below the poverty line, geographical inequality in development, and long-term unemployment. The term "Women Empowerment" refers to the new recognition by the Indian government and state authorities of the significance of focusing on the economic growth and development of women in India, with an emphasis on rural women in particular.

Women can recognize and affirm their identity and influence in all areas of life through a proactive and holistic empowerment process. The benefits of this empowerment include increased access to information and resources, greater independence in decision-making, enhanced abilities in life planning, stronger control over external forces impacting one's life, and liberation from restrictive societal norms, beliefs, and practices. Women's empowerment enables them to attain greater control over various resources, encompassing financial and material assets, such as money, as well as human and intellectual assets, including knowledge, information, and ideas. Self Help Groups (SHG) are frequently used as a method to improve women's social and economic standing. They were originally established by NABARD in India between 1986 and 1987. However, the SHG linkage program's main impact wasn't felt until 1991–1992, when banks in particular began to participate. Typically composed of 10 to 20 women from various households, SHGs are voluntary organizations that foster collaboration among members to address shared issues. Their small size and unique savings techniques distinguish them from other group initiatives aimed at economic expansion. Members of SHGs collaborate to address issues that they share, making them virtually homogeneous in personality. They contribute to savings ranging from 20 to 150 rupees per month, which are pooled together at minimal interest rates. These resources are then rotated among members, providing them with access to funds that might otherwise be unavailable through traditional financial institutions. The initiative's main objective was to make the most of the SHG concept in order to deliver items to the doorsteps of the poor, especially the women who had been disregarded by conventional financial institutions.

In addition to NABARD, a number of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) actively pursue financial intermediation in the manner of other developing countries and work as catalysts in promoting SHGs and establishing connections between them and banks. They assemble women, present the idea to them, motivate and encourage them, and then help them form SHGs. Through attending initial group meetings and assisting with organization, they contribute to managing accounts and establishing bank connections. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) play a crucial role in reducing the vulnerability of low-income groups by creating assets, generating income, providing emergency aid, and empowering women to become financially independent. As intermediaries in microcredit, NGOs positively impact women's empowerment. Women's involvement in family, community, and national development is becoming increasingly essential, and forming a self-help group serves as an empowering journey rather than simply a microcredit initiative. Women's empowerment includes allowing them the opportunity to work and earn money outside the house, as well as the means to acquire knowledge and skills. The goal is to improve the status of women in order to bring their families out of poverty. Moreover, it has been noted that the majority of rural women who take part in SHGs become successful, confident and actively self-empower.

Self-Help Groups are crucial for reducing poverty rates, generating employment, improving living conditions, and empowering underprivileged women. Self-help organizations and women's empowerment have been the subject of extensive research. Each study offers various interpretations of the character and scope of the program's influence

and the researcher's conclusions showed that SHGs are successful at increasing employment and reducing poverty among low-income households. The recipient households in the program have a higher standard of living, which reduces consumption and income vulnerability, according to the studies. According to some studies, the initiative contributes to the reduction of poverty and the spread of infectious diseases, among other Millennium Development Goals. Studies show that participation in the program has given women the opportunity to achieve higher levels of empowerment in relation to knowledge, self-confidence, economic, social awareness, mobility, and the growth of organizational skills, amongst other things. The efficiency of various bank linkage initiatives in providing credit support to the impoverished class has been shown in numerous research.

The program, according to certain research, does not help the most vulnerable people in society, and the group loans are utilized for consumption and other pressing needs rather than for businesses that make money.

Objective:

- To examine the socio-economic backgrounds and family characteristics of pastoral women beneficiaries in Hosur.
- To analyze the benefits pastoral women receive through participation in Self Help Groups.
- To identify future strategies and propose recommendations for improving the management of Self Help Groups.

Review of Literature

Women's economic independence and educational attainment will significantly contribute to fostering their autonomy, as articulated by Venkatesh Murthy and Dinesh (2011). When women are offered equal opportunities in education and the workforce, transformative change is not merely possible; it becomes inevitable. The shift away from a patriarchal social paradigm, which has long characterized Indian society, is crucial for harnessing the full potential of women. This change will enable India to leverage its female population as a powerful asset, ultimately enhancing its global standing and respect. The research claims that SHG served as a catalyst for the infrastructure expansion and social change that resulted in women's emancipation. These groups empower women by providing them with resources, skills, and networks that facilitate economic participation.

Despite recent gains in credit extension and outstanding credit growth rates, there is currently a declining tendency in the overall microfinance landscape, as noted in Economic Analysis (2012). The SBLP (SHG bank linkage model) and the MFI (microfinance institutions) models are the two separate models used in the SHG bank linkage program. The SBLP is characterized by a direct connection between SHG members and banks, facilitating access to financial resources. Notably, from 2009 to 2010, banks financed newly established SHGs; however, this support diminished significantly, with bank sponsorship of new SHGs falling from ₹15,87,000 in 2009-2010 to ₹11,96,000 in 2010-2011. Data indicates that women constitute nearly 80% of SHGs and have received approximately 85.73% of the total loans disbursed, underscoring the program's focus on empowering female borrowers. The 2012 Microfinance Summit Campaign Report included extensive information on the scope of microfinance. A total of 3,652 microfinance companies exist, of which 1009 operate in Sub-Saharan Africa, 647 in Latin America and the Caribbean, and 1746 in Asia and the Pacific, according to the research. This highlights the popularity of microfinance as a form of financial intermediation in developing countries. Asia and the Pacific account for the majority of customer outreach (82%), followed by Latin America and the Caribbean (6.47%) and Sub-Saharan Africa (5.67%). India has advanced in the development of microfinance institutions, with a client outreach of 53.38% in 2011 compared to 18.64% in 2005. The SHG-Bank model, also referred to as the SBLP (SHG-Bank Linkage Programme), is recognized globally and was initially implemented related to development and poverty alleviation initiative. This project which was led by NGOs, was intended to empower the poor to rise out of poverty independently. Many NGOs built around self-help groups (SHGs) pioneered the concept of group-based financing, which was later expanded through partnerships with commercial banks. This approach allowed individual clients to access the commercial banking system via SHGs and their federations. In India, microcredit provision strongly emphasizes female borrowers, recognized as a key public initiative supporting women's economic empowerment.

Pereznieto & Taylor (2014), presented findings from analyses of development initiatives that have direct or indirect impacts on the economic empowerment of women and girls. People must possess the power within, which includes knowledge, unique talents, a sense of entitlement, self-esteem, and self-belief, in order to create changes in their lives, including acquiring the skills required to gain employment or start a business. Possessing the capacity to

make financial decisions that have an impact on one's family, community, and regional economy. Having control over resources that are material, intellectual, and knowledge-based, including having access to sources of employment and income, requires having access to those resources. Power involves the ability to work with others to support legal and economic rights.

According to Arun (2015), poverty is a social phenomenon that occurs when some societal segments are unable to meet their basic necessities. Numerous anti-poverty programs have been in place since the 1950s. Economic inequality has resulted in a multitude of detrimental effects, with poverty definitely being the worst, in virtually all developing countries with low per capita incomes. It is a socioeconomic phenomenon that is directly related to human productivity, health, and efficiency, all of which have an effect on people's income. This essay attempts to examine the effects of poverty by comparing per capita earnings across several countries.

Using the Tendulkar approach of the Mixed Reference Period, it was possible to compare the number of impoverished households and the population living below the poverty line. This report also covers many reasons for poverty in India as well as suggestions for removing it. Branch penetration, credit penetration, and deposit penetration are the three factors on which financial inclusion performance is assessed, according to Disha Bhanot's (2016) study. By modifying the credit penetration and deposit penetration dimensions of financial inclusion for SHG membership, the contribution of SHGs to efforts to promote financial inclusion has been quantified.

Despite the slowdown in the penetration of rural bank branches, the SHG-bank connection initiative appears to be a potential conduit for providing financial services to the previously excluded population. According to Srinivasa, the topic of women's empowerment has generated a great deal of discussion and thought over the previous few decades. Global efforts are consistently undertaken to tackle this issue and improve the socioeconomic standing of women. Nonetheless, many policies and initiatives primarily focus on economic independence, often overlooking other important areas like health, education, and literacy under the assumption that economic empowerment alone is sufficient. The roles, employment, and societal status of women are crucial indicators of a nation's development.

Women's involvement in national activities goes beyond fairness; it is vital for the advancement of social, economic, and political progress. Without women's active involvement, a country's development can stagnate, leading to a loss of potential that could drive innovation and prosperity. Historically, as nations recognized the importance of empowering women, this empowerment became a focal point in their socioeconomic and political agendas. For ten years, the United Nations concentrated on issues linked to women and development. In addition, a number of conferences were held with the intention of increasing women's status and eliminating gender-based discrimination, such as the Nairobi World Conference in 1985, the Mexico Conference in 1975, the Copenhagen Conference in 1980, and the Beijing World Conference in 1995. The third Millennium Development Goal (MDG) aimed to promote women's empowerment and gender equality. The United Nations Millennium Project's Task Force on Education and Gender Equality highlighted seven key priorities for achieving the MDGs. These include expanding opportunities for girls in secondary education, safeguarding sexual and reproductive health and rights, investing in infrastructure to reduce women's workload, ensuring property and inheritance rights for women and girls, and eliminating gender disparities in the workforce. The central and state governments of India have made significant strides in advancing women's empowerment through their five-year plans. These initiatives include a range of welfare programs such as Community Development Programs (CDP), the National Extension Program (NEP), and the establishment of the Social Welfare Board, Mahila Mandals, and Mahila Samajams. Initially, the focus was predominantly on welfare strategies aimed at providing immediate support to women. However, after some time, the emphasis shifted from a welfare strategy to a development plan, empowering and involving women in development. The fundamental tenets of a development strategy included improvements in the conditions of health and hygiene, economic growth, the creation of jobs, etc. In order to guarantee advances in women's health, employment, and education, a comprehensive rural development strategy is required. In order to ensure advances in women's health, employment, and education, a comprehensive rural development plan known as the Integrated Rural Development Programme (IRDP) was developed being put into effect in 1980. Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA), a new program, introduced in 1982 to cover all aspects of women's and children's development. In order to assist NGOs in starting income-generating projects for women, the Central Social Welfare Board (CSWB) and Council for Advancement of People's Action in Rural Technology (CAPART) were founded. The Mahila Samridhi Yojana, a groundbreaking initiative, was started with the assistance of NGOs with the aim of assisting rural women to amass little savings. In addition to these numerous measures, the Central

and State Governments in collaboration with UNICEF started a program to combat poverty in the Alleppey area of Kerala. This program's main goal was to advance Self-Help Groups as an alternate method of empowering women.

The Kerala government has made a strategic decision to expand its successful women empowerment program throughout the entire state, aiming to create a comprehensive framework for the empowerment and development of women. This initiative draws inspiration from the notable achievements of the program in urban areas, particularly in cities like Thiruvananthapuram, where it has demonstrated significant positive outcomes. This initiative's success in the city made it possible to extend it to the countryside as part of Kerala's Poverty Eradication Mission (Kudumbaslu). This mission prioritizes both poverty alleviation and the economic and social empowerment of women, recognizing it as essential for sustainable development. In Tamil Nadu, the industrial city of Hosur in Krishnagiri district stands out as a significant area for study. Hosur is one of Tamil Nadu's municipal corporations and is part of the Krishnagiri district, which comprises five taluks. Within Hosur Taluk, there are 5 cities and 168 villages, highlighting its diverse demographic and economic landscape. The expansion of women's empowerment initiatives in such areas is vital for addressing local challenges and fostering inclusive growth.

Study Area :

According to the Census of India 2011, there are 129512 homes in Hosur Taluk, housing 539663 people, of which 277136 are men and 262527 are women. Children under the age of six make up to 66010 people, or 12.23% of the general population. Hosur Taluk has a sex ratio of approximately 947, which is lower than the state average of 996 for Tamil Nadu. Hosur Taluk has a 66.48% literacy rate, with 71.55% of men and 61.12% of women being literate. Hosur has a total area of 957.76 sq. km and a population density of 563 inhabitants per sq. km. 42.53% of people reside in rural areas, compared to 57.47% of the total population who live in urban areas. Hosur Taluk's total population includes 0.57% Scheduled Tribes (ST) and 13.8% Scheduled Castes (SC).

Pastoral Community

The pastoral community in Hosur has greatly diversified the local populace. The growth of cattle and herds is the source of their livelihood, riches, history, present, and future. The terrain is large, fertile, and green, and the abundance of nature and its weather have a major impact on the life of shepherds. The Pastoral system combines herding and crop cultivation in an agro-pastoral mixed approach. Income sources include the sale of livestock, dairy products, crops, and income from non-farming activities.

According to Ducrotoy et al. (2016) and Ducrotoy et al. (2017b), 90% of households grow crops, primarily for subsistence. Due to the Grazing Reserve's isolation, livelihoods in the area require substantial cash flow, involve frequent cattle sales, and face low market prices for livestock. The Fulani produce only enough cattle to meet household needs without reducing herd sizes. Limited pasture within the reserve and regional political instability are driving pastoralists toward poverty, compelling them to reduce herd sizes and seek alternative income sources (Ducrotoy et al. 2016, Ducrotoy et al. 2017b).

Research Methodology

Research methodology realizes the research's goal, which is to pinpoint the social, business, and self-help organizations that have an impact on women's empowerment in Hosur, Tamil Nadu. Here, the research model's functional shape is developed. The self-help group of women in rural India is used to quantify the dependent variable, which is the number of female entrepreneurs. The constituent variables that have been regarded as independent variables represent the social, entrepreneurial, and self-help group empowerment status. The specifics of these variables that were taken into account in the current investigation. By use of a self-administered survey, data were gathered. Hosur is one of Tamil Nadu's most advanced cities. The ladies in Hosur city make up the majority of the target population for our study. As a result, 225 samples are needed for this investigation to meet the sample size calculation criteria. As a result, a straightforward random sampling technique takes into account more samples than are necessary. 242 respondents made up the study's total sample of respondents.

Demographic profile:

The respondent data indicates that although 48% hold a graduate degree or higher, most are not engaged in economic activities, with 47% identifying as housewives. Additionally, 45% of the female respondents are not involved in any financial activities despite their high educational qualifications, as 95% have at least a basic school education. Location Frequency % 52 21.5 Thally, 85 35 Anchetty Age B/W 18 and 25 75 31 26 and 45 45 18.5 46 and above 121 50 Mathigiri 65 26.5 Sholagriri 38 15.7 Denaknikottai 79 32.6 Occupation Involved in Farming and Agriculture 180 74.9 Working in Company 41 16.9 Housewife 89 36.7 Lack of education 172 71 Grade level 76 31.4 advanced degree Pastoral communities, 42 17.3 186 74 .

Place	Frequency	Percent
Thally	52	21.5
Anchetty	85	35
Mathigiri	65	26.5
Sholagriri	38	15.7
Denaknikottai	79	32.6
Occupation		
Involved in Farming and Agriculture	180	74.9
Working in company	41	16.9
House wife	89	36.7
Age		
B/W 18 and 25	75	31
26 and 45	45	18.5
46 and above	121	50
Education		
Illiterate	172	71
School level	76	31.4
Graduate and above	42	17.3

Pastoral communities	186	74
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Data Analysis

When evaluating data for independent variables in logistic regression, it's essential to assess the goodness of fit for the explained regression model. In this study, the Hosmer and Lemeshow test indicated satisfactory outcomes, as recommended by experts, with the Nagelkerke R² value recorded at 0.621, which is considered a strong indicator of goodness of fit in logistic regression models (Field, 2009). Additionally, the Hosmer and Lemeshow test results met acceptable standards, as suggested by researchers (Gujarati and Porter, 2009). Details are presented in Table 3. Using a forward stepwise selection method, the logistic regression model identified three statistically significant variables ($p < 0.05$) for women's financial inclusion, while one variable was found to be insignificant in this analysis (Hosmer et al., 2013) (Table 4).

Model of logistic regression		
	R2	Result
Value	0.678	Good Indicator

Exploratory factor analysis

Principal component analysis was used for exploratory factor analysis. Table 5 shows the items with factor loadings greater than 0.4, while three items with factor loadings less than 0.4 were removed from further analysis. As shown in Table 6, the factors with an eigenvalue of 1.0 or higher were kept for further analysis. 72.5 and Varimax rotation were represented by the three extracted factors (SPSS 22.0). The factor analysis was appropriate for this data because the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin1 (KMO) value was greater than 0.7 and the Bartlett's test of Sphericity2 was significant at p-value cent of the total variance explained in the data. Cronbach's alpha values for the three factors ranged from 0.757 (for the self-help group) to 0.922. (for entrepreneur empowerment).

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

The maximum likelihood method was used to test the measurement model using the multi-factor CFA on 12 items. The model fit was determined to be appropriate, and the three-factor model had the best overall fit for the data with a 2/df = 1.2 (2 = 694.545, df = 521); CFI of 0.910; GFI of 0.922; AGFI of 0.901; and RMSEA of 0.078. The discriminant value was checked because the average variance explained (AVE) values for all constructs were greater than 0.5 and the smallest test measurement items were greater than 1.96 (=0.05). (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). The composite reliability of each factor ranged from 0.85 to 0.94 (as shown in Table 5), exceeding the recommended level of 0.6. (Hu & Bentler, 1999). One-way ANOVA was used to test the relationship hypothesis.

One-Way ANOVA

This study aims to assess whether there are statistically significant differences in the average empowerment levels among women in social, entrepreneurial, and self-help groups within Hosur's village communities. In particular, the self-help groups were categorized into three levels based on the access and utilization of resources by pastoral communities in Anchetty, Thally, and Denkanikottai. Results from the one-way ANOVA indicated a significant difference in overall women's empowerment indicators. To further explore these differences within pastoral communities, the Games-Howell post hoc test was applied. Table 3 provides the one-way ANOVA findings, highlighting the statistically significant disparities among group means. The p-values for empowerment levels across Anchetty, Denkanikottai, and Thally were 0.010 for entrepreneurial empowerment, 0.030 for social empowerment, and 0.039 for self-help group empowerment, all of which are below the 0.05 threshold. The findings suggest an increase in empowerment through local resource access, particularly insurance schemes. However, mean differences for entrepreneurial, self-help, and social empowerment in terms of APY are not statistically significant.

Result

The methodology section's represented tables of results investigated the impact of social empowerment, entrepreneur empowerment, and self-help group facets on empowering women in rural areas of Hosur. According

to the empirical results tabulated in the methodology section, women's need for a bank account increases 3.277 times when they are an earning member of the household and 3.423 times when they participate in the financial decision-making process at the household level. These findings are consistent with the findings of Soumare et al. (2016) and Brule and Gaikwad (2021), who investigated the impact of respondents' "employment status" on their financial inclusion. Moreover, being a recipient of any social welfare scheme increases women's empowerment through self-help group empowerment by 3.774 times significantly, which is in line with the study conducted by Bhatia and Singh (2019) and Chatterjee et al. (2018). In addition, the safety of their saving is also playing a very important role in the entrepreneur empowerment of pastoral communities) of women as its odd ratio is observed as 2.234; but at the same time, it is found as an insignificant variable, which is opposite to the findings of the study conducted by Kast and Pomeranz (2014) and Dupas and Robinson (2013). The insignificant observation of "safety of saving" may be because of the following reasons: : (1) in India, the rural women keep their savings or money in informal methods such as with their relatives (mainly at in-laws' house), in piggyback at own house which they think is the safest place to keep their money (Soumare et al., 2016); (2) in near time, the news about bankruptcy and corruption in the banking system in India; (3) Low

Variables	Ratio	P -Value	Results
Social empowerment	4.777	0.00	Significant
Entrepreneur Empowerment	3.123	0.000	Significant
Self Help group	3.437	0.000	Significant

Unstable income leads to levy bank charges unstable income leads to levy high bank charges; (4) the security risk associated with account operating and (5) the proximity and timing of bank branch open for customers (Kempson and Pilley, 2004) (see Figure 1)

Limitation

This study follows some limitations. Data were gathered from the Agriculture hub of Hosur (Tamil Nadu), which limits the applicability of the findings to the Indian populace. Since there was no other way to collect primary data besides a questionnaire, there may be a common-method bias in the findings. As a result of its cross-sectional design and lack of consideration for longitudinal research structures, this study is unable to account for the long-term interactions between policies promoting women's empowerment and Pastoral communities

A study aimed at assessing whether comparable results can be obtained across all of India's diverse cities and states is crucial for understanding the broader implications of financial inclusion initiatives. This comprehensive examination will provide valuable insights that could significantly inform the development of future national research strategies. Through an in-depth qualitative study, researchers can encourage lasting reflection on the influence of self-help groups and women's empowerment, helping to ensure these initiatives are thoughtfully designed to address the specific needs of different communities.

Conclusion

Self-help groups (SHGs) in Tamil Nadu play an essential role in promoting financial literacy, especially among women and marginalized communities. By participating in SHGs, members develop essential skills and knowledge to manage finances effectively, empowering them to make informed financial decisions. Here's how financial literacy is promoted through SHGs in Tamil Nadu. SHG members learn the basics of saving by contributing a fixed amount regularly, which teaches the importance of saving for emergencies and long-term needs. Members practice lending and borrowing within the group, which introduces them to the concepts of interest rates, loan repayments, and record-keeping. This foster understanding of personal debt management and financial discipline. SHGs in Tamil Nadu often partner with banks, where members open group accounts and gain access to microloans. This helps them understand banking operations like deposits, withdrawals, passbook management, and interest calculations. These bank linkages expose members to formal financial services, making them more comfortable using financial institutions rather than informal moneylenders, which often charge high-interest rates. Through initiatives like the Tamil Nadu Corporation for Development of Women (TNCDW) and the Mahalir Thittam

scheme, SHG members receive financial literacy training covering budgeting, savings plans, investment basics, and financial goal setting. Government and NGOs partner to conduct workshops, where SHG members learn about financial planning, risk management, and debt management, enabling them to make sound financial decisions. SHGs support members in creating micro-businesses by training them in income-generating skills like tailoring, food processing, and animal husbandry. Members gain insights into cost management, pricing, and profit calculation, which improves their financial skills. Earnings from these ventures are reinvested, which teaches SHG members about capital management and the importance of reinvesting for growth. SHG members in Tamil Nadu receive information about government schemes, such as insurance plans, pensions, and subsidies, which increases awareness about financial security. These sessions also cover subsidies and grants available for SHGs, making it easier for members to access these resources for economic and social empowerment. Each SHG maintains records of savings, loans, and repayments, teaching members the importance of documentation in financial transactions. Regular accounting and transparent record-keeping are emphasized, helping members develop systematic financial practices they can apply to both group activities and personal finances. Some SHGs in Tamil Nadu are now being trained in digital financial skills, where members learn to use mobile banking, ATMs, and online transactions. This helps them adapt to the increasing digitalization of financial services and reduces dependence on cash-based transactions. By fostering financial literacy, SHGs in Tamil Nadu enable members to manage their finances better, make informed choices, and reduce financial vulnerability. These groups not only help in poverty alleviation but also contribute to the long-term financial stability of their communities. It was noteworthy that women with lower levels of education joined the formal banking system and had solid knowledge of these financial inclusion initiatives. Although enrolment in these programs was modest, both non-profit organizations and self-help groups (SHGs) play a vital role in promoting awareness of these schemes among rural women. The study's second objective was to validate the alignment of various empowerment factors for pastoral women, while the third focused on highlighting the connection between financial inclusion and women's empowerment. The findings show that financial inclusion positively influences women's empowerment across social, political, and economic spheres. However, the long-term success of these programs depends on their capacity to foster entrepreneurial opportunities for women, thereby contributing to sustained improvements in their economic status and independence.

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IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON B2B IN ENHANCING CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT AND LOYALTY

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Abstract:

This study investigates the impact of social media on B2B businesses, focusing on its role in driving customer engagement and loyalty. The research aims to explore modern social media strategies and tools, examining their influence on various marketing activities and sectors, while also analyzing market segmentation in the digital era to enhance customer experience. The objective is to identify effective strategies for customer engagement and loyalty, demonstrating how social media advertising can benefit B2B businesses by improving ROI and fostering stronger relationships. Data will be gathered through structured questionnaires administered to 20 employees at TheMarketConnect in the UAE, alongside secondary data from the internet, the company's website, and relevant literature. Findings suggest that engagement and loyalty are context-dependent, shaped by distinct interactions on different social media platforms. The results highlight the importance of optimizing social media usage, focusing on customer feedback, delivering quality service, and developing structured strategies for media activities to enhance audience engagement. The study emphasizes the critical role of social media in fostering customer-centric practices in the B2B sector, offering original insights into how businesses can tailor their strategies to improve customer satisfaction and drive industry-wide shifts. Ultimately, the research fills a gap in the literature, providing actionable recommendations for businesses to optimize their social media strategies in a competitive landscape.

Keywords: B2B service, customer engagement, loyalty, social media marketing strategy, Consistency in engagement, Mode of social media advertising.

Introduction:

Social media has become a crucial tool for B2B companies, enabling direct, real-time communication and personalized experiences with customers. Unlike traditional marketing, social media allows businesses to reach a global audience, making it easier to engage with potential clients. Over the past decade, B2B companies have increasingly recognized the value of social media for building customer engagement, loyalty, and long-term growth. By leveraging these platforms, businesses can enhance brand visibility, foster relationships, and drive customer retention. Emerging technologies continue to revolutionize the B2B landscape, enabling more effective interactions and stronger engagement. For this purpose, social media has played acting major part in the organization's marketing department. The revolution of the B2B concept has been significantly influenced by emerging technologies, enabling businesses to interact with diverse companies across different sectors through social media advertising. Social media helps raise awareness, attract targeted customers, and build engagement, thereby enhancing the quality of B2B interactions.

Literature Review:

The integration of social media into B2B marketing has become increasingly significant, transforming traditional strategies. While its role in B2C marketing is well-established, the impact of social media on B2B marketing, particularly in areas like customer engagement and loyalty, is still evolving. This literature review explores the current research on social media's role in B2B marketing, focusing on its strategic use, adoption challenges, and contributions to long-term customer relationships. It also identifies gaps in the literature and highlights areas needing further exploration to optimize social media in the B2B sector, ultimately offering insights into how businesses can leverage these platforms for growth and brand enhancement.

Table No-1 A Few notable authors' findings and implications

Author(s) & Year	Focus Area	Key Findings	Implications
Iqbal Thonse Hawaldar (2022)	Digital Marketing in B2B	Digital marketing influences sales and brand image in B2B South Asia, with strategies needing country-specific tailoring.	B2B companies should adapt strategies to specific country contexts to maximize impact on sales and brand image.
Severina Cartwright (2021)	Social Media Strategy	Social media use in B2B should be strategic, focusing on sales, communication, and engagement, rather than tactical approaches.	B2B organizations need to integrate social media into broader strategic goals for better long-term engagement and results.
Edubilli Srinu (2021)	Customer Engagement	Social media benefits B2B by improving customer responsiveness and loyalty, though it lags behind B2C adoption.	Social media presents significant potential for B2B customer relationship management, despite slower adoption compared to B2C.
Niko Garuda Adiyono (2021)	Social Media Visibility	Businesses use the internet and social media to enhance visibility and engage with customers effectively.	Effective use of social media increases visibility, helping businesses connect with a wider audience.
Chen Lou (2021)	Content Marketing	Branded content drives customer loyalty, with both high- and low-involvement brands benefiting from the content's perceived value.	Regular, valuable branded content can foster strong customer loyalty across various levels of brand involvement.
Debra Zahay (2021)	Customer Co-Creation	Digital marketing has evolved, focusing more on customer engagement and co-creation to build long-term relationships.	B2B companies should focus on customer co-creation to deepen engagement and develop long-lasting connections.
Alison Munsch (2021)	Gen Z and Millennial Trends	Millennials and Gen Z prefer short, humorous, music-infused ads and influencers, as opposed to traditional advertising formats.	Social media advertising strategies should cater to younger generations' preferences for engaging, entertaining, and influencer-driven content.

Shawky Ebrahim (2019)	Brand Loyalty	Social media marketing boosts brand loyalty, with trust and customization playing key roles in successful implementation.	B2B firms should prioritize trust-building and customized content on social media to foster brand loyalty.
Dauw-Song (2019)	Cultural Context in B2B	An integrated B2B guanxi model in China emphasizes relationship-building and deviates from traditional Western marketing theories.	B2B strategies in non-Western regions should account for cultural differences and focus on relationship-building over transactional interactions.
Hilde A. M. Voorveld (2018)	Consumer Engagement	Consumer engagement on social media significantly impacts advertising evaluations and further engagement.	Increased consumer engagement on social media leads to better brand evaluations and sustained engagement with the brand.

Research Gap:

The research gap identifies areas that need further exploration in advertising and social media, including Specific strategies for B2B advertising and Comparative research between B2B and B2C social media usage

Research Methodology:

A mixed-methods approach (qualitative and quantitative) was used. The study began by analyzing the organization's current social media performance. A systematic literature review was conducted through Google Scholar using search terms like "impact and social media," "ROI and social media," and "B2B social media." Of 55 articles, 20 were selected for detailed analysis, including insights from IIM Journals.

Problem Statement:

As social media evolves, B2B strategies must adapt for better customer engagement and ROI. This study aims to enhance social media presence, improve customer connections, and develop strategies for stronger audience engagement.

Objectives:

1. Investigate social media's impact on B2B customer loyalty.
2. Identify factors driving social media usage for connectivity.
3. Assess social media marketing's role in client engagement and retention.
4. Explore optimization strategies for better business results.
5. Suggest ways to measure the ROI of social media efforts.
6. Provide actionable recommendations for B2B companies.

Scope and Significance:

This research will help organizations understand B2B advertising trends, and customer preferences, and develop effective social media marketing strategies for better engagement and business outcomes.

Research Design:

Universe	Employees
Population	The MarketConnect employees.UAE
Sample size	20 (All staff)
Sample instrument	Structured questionnaires'
Sample unit	The Market Connect, UAE
Sample type	Probability Sampling
Sampling	Simple random sampling
Data source	Primary source: questionnaire, observation Secondary sources: Journals, company websites, Research papers, social media platforms.

Data Analysis & Findings:

Question	Response Options	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
4.1 Should organizations leverage social media to enhance business operations?	Strongly Agree	10	50%
	Agree	10	50%
	Neutral	0	0%
	Disagree	0	0%
	Strongly Disagree	0	0%
4.2 How often should a company be involved in business promotion via social media?	1-2 hours/day	13	65%
	5 hours/week	6	30%
	6-10 hours/fortnight	0	0%
	More than 10 hours	1	5%
4.3 Which social media platform is primarily used for B2B marketing?	LinkedIn	15	75%
	Twitter	2	10%
	Facebook	2	10%
	YouTube	1	5%
4.4 What are the primary strategic goals of your social media marketing? (Select all that apply)	Brand Visibility	8	40%
	Lead Generation	3	15%
	Customer Support	5	25%

	Market Research	7	35%
	Networking with Peer Industry	7	35%

- 1. Social media for Operations:** 100% agree that social media is vital for business operations.
- 2. Promotion Frequency:** Most (65%) suggest 1-2 hours per day for social media promotion.
- 3. Preferred Platforms:** LinkedIn dominates B2B marketing (75% use it), with other platforms like Twitter and Facebook playing a minor role.
- 4. Strategic Focus:** Brand visibility (40%) and market research (35%) are key goals in B2B social media strategies.

What strategies can B2B service providers implement to foster engagement and interaction on social media platforms?

Parameters	No. of respondents	Percentages
By actively participating in industry-related discussions and forum	6	30
By reposting irrelevant content from other industries to fill content pages	4	20
By automating all social media interaction to save time and effort	2	10
By purchasing followers and engagement to inflate social proof artificially	5	25
By bombarding followers with constant promotional messages and advertisement	3	15

(Source: Primary data)

The above table shows that 30% of respondents believe that actively participating in industry-related discussions and forums is the most effective strategy for fostering engagement and interaction on social media. Meanwhile, 25% of respondents suggest purchasing followers and engagement, while 20% opt for reposting irrelevant content from other industries, and smaller percentages favour automation or frequent promotional messaging.

What potential challenges do you foresee in implementing these optimization strategies for client engagement and retention on social media?

Parameters	No. of respondents	Percentage %
Lack of resource (time, budget, personnel)	6	30
Technical limitations or platform constraints	4	20
Resistance to change within the organization	4	20
Integration with existing marketing	5	25
Other	1	5

(Source: Primary data)

The above table data reveals that 30% of respondents anticipate a lack of resources (time, budget, personnel) as the primary challenge in optimizing strategies for client engagement and retention on social media. Additionally, 25% are concerned about integrating these strategies with existing marketing efforts, while 20% foresee technical limitations and organizational resistance.

Findings:

1. **Social Media Utilization:** 50% of respondents believe organizations should leverage social media for business enhancement.
2. **Time Commitment:** 65% suggest 1-2 hours daily for optimal promotion.
3. **Platform Preference:** 75% prefer LinkedIn for B2B advertising.
4. **Importance of Social Media Marketing:** 60% consider it crucial for business effectiveness.
5. **Content Posting Practices:** 40% post regularly to engage their audience.
6. **Connectivity Benefits:** 35% see social media's benefits driven by globalization and information access.
7. **Strategic Goals:** 40% prioritize "Brand Visibility," with "Market Research" and "Networking" at 35%.
8. **Management Tools:** 70% use tools to manage social media interactions.
9. **Performance Measurement:** 100% use LinkedIn Analytics for performance tracking.
10. **Value of Traditional Advertising:** 40% still value traditional advertising.
11. **Data-Driven Approaches:** 45% prioritize metrics for effectiveness evaluation.
12. **Industry Engagement:** 30% see participation in industry discussions as valuable for engagement.
13. **Valuable Content Delivery:** 30% believe valuable content boosts visibility.
14. **Customer Loyalty:** 50% believe social media fosters customer loyalty, though 20% find it ineffective.
15. **Role of Social Media:** 50% affirm its role in fostering loyalty.
16. **Client Sentiment Understanding:** 35% use social media listening to gauge client sentiment.
17. **Resource Constraints:** 30% cite time, budget, and personnel limitations as key obstacles.

Suggestions

Based on the findings and the initial objective of understanding social media's role in enhancing customer engagement and loyalty in the B2B sector, it's clear that social media offers both qualitative and quantitative benefits. While primarily used for advertising, it also builds connections, fosters dialogue, and enhances brand visibility.

Here's a comprehensive social media plan:

1. Set Clear Objectives

Define specific goals that align with the company's overall business objectives. These may include:

- **Increasing Brand Awareness:** Reach new audiences and establish the company as a thought leader in the IT sector.
- **Driving Website Traffic:** Increase the number of visitors to the company's website.
- **Generating Leads:** Convert social media followers into potential clients through targeted campaigns.

- **Boosting Engagement:** Foster interaction through likes, comments, shares, and other forms of engagement on posts.
- **Driving Sales or Conversions:** Increase the number of conversions resulting from social media efforts.

2. Identify Metrics to Track

Select metrics based on the objectives set. Here are the key metrics for each objective:

Objective	Key Metrics to Track
Brand Awareness	Impressions, Reach, Brand Mentions, Follower Growth
Website Traffic	Clicks on links, Referral traffic from social media, Bounce rate, Page views
Lead Generation	Number of leads (signups, registrations), Conversion rate, Lead form submissions
Sales	Number of purchases, Revenue generated from social media traffic, Conversion rate
Engagement	Likes, Comments, Shares, Click-through rate (CTR), Direct messages, Saves, Retweets

3. Calculate Costs

Identify all associated costs for the social media strategy:

- **Ad Spend:** Budget for paid promotions and ads on platforms like Facebook, LinkedIn, and Instagram.
- **Tools and Software:** Costs for social media management and analytics tools (e.g., Hootsuite, Sprout Social).
- **Personnel Costs:** Salaries for social media managers, content creators, and designers.
- **Content Creation:** Costs for producing videos, graphics, and other promotional materials.

4. Develop a Content Plan

Create a diverse content strategy that includes:

- **Educational Content:** Share informative articles, whitepapers, or blogs related to IT trends and best practices.
- **Webinars and Live Events:** Host webinars on relevant topics (e.g., cybersecurity, cloud computing), promoting them through social media.
- **Customer Testimonials:** Post success stories and case studies to build trust and showcase expertise.
- **Engaging Multimedia:** Use videos, infographics, and visuals to capture audience attention and increase shares.
- **Regular Updates:** Share company news, updates, and employee highlights to humanize the brand and encourage engagement.

5. Track Conversions from Social Media

Utilize UTM parameters and Google Analytics to monitor traffic and conversions from social media campaigns. Track metrics like:

- **Website Behavior:** Analyze how social media traffic interacts with the website, focusing on conversion rates for leads and sales.
- **Lead Generation Effectiveness:** Measure how many leads convert to customers and their respective values.

6. Calculate ROI

Use the formula provided in your literature review to assess the ROI of social media initiatives:

$$\text{ROI} = (\text{Revenue from Social Media} - \text{Costs}) \times 100$$

Example Calculation:

- **Investment:**
 - Ad Spend: \$2,000
 - Content Creation: \$1,000
 - Personnel Costs: \$1,000
 - **Total Cost:** \$4,000
- **Results:**
 - Sales from social media: \$10,000
 - **ROI** = $(10000 - 4000) \times 100 / 4000 = 150\%$

This indicates a 150% return on investment, meaning for every dollar spent on social media, the company earned \$1.50.

7. Measure Intangible ROI (Non-Monetary Benefits)

Consider non - monetary benefits such as:

- **Brand Loyalty:** Track follower engagement and retention over time.
- **Customer Feedback:** Monitor feedback through comments and direct messages for insights on customer sentiment.
- **Influence and Reach:** Measure the growth in brand mentions and engagement rates.

8. Use Tools for Tracking and Analysis

Leverage various tools for effective tracking and analysis:

- **Google Analytics:** For traffic analysis and conversions.
- **Native Analytics:** Use insights from platforms like LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram.
- **Third-Party Tools:** Employ tools like Hootsuite and Sprout Social for deeper analytics and reporting.

Recommendations:

1. **Optimize Social Media Use:** Increase the time dedicated to social media activities to achieve customized outcomes that benefit the business.
2. **Develop Structured Strategies:** Establish clear objectives for social media usage to drive effective results, addressing key aspects like globalization and networking to maximize impact.
3. **Enhance Customer Loyalty:** Focus on customer feedback and provide incentives such as exciting offers and invitations to industry talks to strengthen loyalty and engagement.
4. **Prioritize LinkedIn:** Given its importance in B2B marketing, organizations should enhance their LinkedIn strategies by increasing profile visibility, creating quality content, and understanding the target audience's needs.

5. **Refine Customer Loyalty Efforts:** Develop personalized content and targeted loyalty programs to engage all audience segments effectively.
6. **Leverage Diverse Engagement Strategies:** Utilize social media for various initiatives, such as promoting sustainable development goals, to build trust and integrate social media into daily practices.
7. **Focus on Feedback and Sentiment Analysis:** Monitor customer feedback to understand their needs better, allowing for proactive issue resolution and stronger relationships.
8. **Implement Regular Monitoring:** Establish feedback loops to maintain a connection with the audience.

By following these recommendations, B2B service providers like The Market Connect can enhance their social media strategies, leading to improved engagement, brand visibility, and customer loyalty.

Conclusion And Scope For Future

This study confirms that social media plays a crucial role in enhancing customer engagement and loyalty in B2B marketing. However, it also highlights several challenges, including resource constraints and the need for strategic planning. To optimize social media efforts, B2B companies should:

1. Develop tailored social media strategies that align with their business objectives.
2. Invest in regular, value-driven content to engage and retain customers.
3. Utilize analytics tools like LinkedIn Analytics to measure the effectiveness of social media campaigns.
4. Allocate sufficient resources to manage social media activities effectively.

Ultimately, B2B companies that can successfully leverage social media for customer engagement and loyalty will be better positioned to build long-lasting relationships and thrive in a competitive marketplace.

Scope for future

Future research on social media's impact on B2B customer engagement and loyalty should explore diverse markets, particularly emerging economies, to understand how cultural and economic factors influence strategies. Additionally, developing new theories tailored to B2B dynamics can provide valuable insights. Emphasizing practical frameworks that organizations can implement will help optimize social media presence based on specific market demands. Segmented studies focusing on industry-specific strategies and longitudinal research to assess long-term effectiveness are also essential. Furthermore, integrating emerging technologies and enhancing feedback mechanisms can significantly improve engagement strategies and strengthen client relationships.

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"THE MIRAGE OF DIGITAL ABUNDANCE AND PERFECTION: UNDERSTANDING AND GUIDING CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR IN THE AGE OF DIGITAL MARKETING"

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Abstract

In the digital age, marketing has evolved to create a widespread illusion of abundance and perfection, significantly impacting consumer perceptions and behaviours. Digital platforms, especially social media and e-commerce, frequently showcase romanticized lifestyles and products, constructing a “mirage” that influences how consumers view their needs, desires, and choices. This paper explores the psychological and behavioural effects of these digital illusions, examining how heightened expectations of perfection and abundance can lead to unrealistic standards, dissatisfaction, and impulse-driven decisions among consumers. By analyzing the mechanisms through which digital marketing shapes these perceptions, this study highlights the importance of empowering consumers to recognize and navigate the reality behind digital content. The findings underscore a pressing need for strategies that promote digital literacy and critical awareness, ultimately supporting a more informed and resilient consumer base. The paper concludes by offering actionable insights to marketers, consumers, and policymakers, advocating for a digital landscape that values authenticity and supports ethical marketing practices.

Key words: Digital Illusions, Consumer Behavior, Abundance And Perfection, Digital Marketing, Perception And Reality

Introduction

In an increasingly digitalized world, consumers are immersed in a vast landscape of marketing content that blurs the lines between reality and idealized portrayals. Digital marketing—especially through social media, e-commerce platforms, and influencer partnerships—frequently presents images of abundance and perfection that shape consumer perceptions of what is normal, attainable, and desirable. This phenomenon, often referred to as the “mirage” of digital abundance and perfection, creates illusions that go beyond product promotion; it influences consumer expectations, self-image, and ultimately, their decision-making processes.

These illusions can generate an unrealistic sense of availability, where products appear perpetually accessible, and a misleading perception of perfection, where flaws and limitations are skillfully concealed. As consumers encounter curated lifestyles and aspirational imagery, they may internalize these ideals, potentially leading to heightened aspirations, dissatisfaction, and impulsive behaviors. This effect is further magnified by algorithms that prioritize content designed to capture attention, intensifying the allure of the digital mirage.

However, as this trend continues, so does the need for consumers to critically assess the authenticity of digital content. While marketers benefit from enhanced engagement, the psychological toll on consumers, such as feelings of inadequacy or frustration from unmet expectations, raises ethical concerns. This paper seeks to explore the impact of these digital illusions on consumer behavior and offers practical strategies for helping consumers recognize and navigate the reality behind digital marketing. By examining how the mirage of abundance and perfection shapes consumer perceptions, this study contributes to a broader understanding of ethical marketing practices and aims to support a more informed and empowered consumer base.

Statement Of The Problem

Despite the prevalence of these illusions, there is limited research on how such marketing tactics impact consumer well-being and decision-making. Furthermore, there is a lack of effective strategies to help consumers critically assess the authenticity of digital content. Understanding the psychological and behavioral consequences of these digital illusions is essential, as well as exploring ways to empower consumers to recognize and navigate these perceptions responsibly. This research seeks to address these gaps by examining the impact of digital marketing’s

mirage on consumer behavior and proposing practical solutions to enhance consumer awareness and resilience in the face of digital marketing's influence.

Scope Of Study

The scope of this study encompasses an exploration of how digital marketing influences consumer behavior, with a particular focus on the psychological and behavioral impact of marketing tactics that create illusions of abundance and perfection. It targets individuals across diverse demographic groups, including varying ages, genders, and educational levels, who actively engage with online shopping or interact with digital marketing content on social media and e-commerce platforms. The study investigates key digital marketing strategies such as the use of scarcity messages, curated content, and idealized imagery to understand their role in shaping consumer decision-making, including unplanned purchases and impulsive behavior. Additionally, it evaluates the level of consumer awareness and critical thinking skills in identifying misleading or exaggerated content, while also considering the potential consequences of these digital illusions on consumer well-being. This research aims to provide actionable insights and strategies for empowering consumers to make informed decisions in the digital age.

Objectives

1. To analyze the psychological and behavioral impact of digital marketing's illusions of abundance and perfection on consumer behavior.
2. To identify common digital marketing tactics that contributes to the creation of perceived abundance and perfection.
3. To assess the level of consumer awareness regarding the reality behind digital marketing content,

Research Methodology

Descriptive Survey Research methodology involved administering structured surveys to a sample of consumers, focusing on their perceptions, experiences, and awareness of digital marketing's illusions of abundance and perfection. The survey had included questions designed to capture data on how consumers perceive idealized digital content, their emotional responses, and any influence it has on their purchasing decisions or satisfaction.

This approach allowed for a clear, descriptive understanding of consumer behaviour and perceptions, aligning with the study's goal of examining the impact of digital illusions without needing additional qualitative methods. By focusing on survey responses, the research had gathered quantitative data that provides insight into trends, frequency of behaviours, and general consumer attitudes, making it both practical and effective for the research objectives.

Review Of Literature

1. Digital Abundance and Scarcity Tactics

Digital marketing often creates an illusion of boundless choice and availability, which can heighten consumer engagement. Studies show that e-commerce platforms and social media use algorithms to present content that appears abundant and tailored, creating a false sense of unlimited options (Adams & Tabrizi, 2018). At the same time, scarcity tactics—such as “limited-time offers” and “only a few left” alerts—intensify consumers' perceived urgency to make quick purchasing

Decisions (Aggarwal et al., 2019). This contrast between digital abundance and selective scarcity is shown to influence impulsive buying behaviours and amplify the appeal of marketed products (Chen et al., 2021).

2. Idealized Portrayals and Consumer Perception

Idealization is central to the "mirage" effect in digital marketing, where products and lifestyles are depicted in highly aspirational terms. Literature on social comparison theory suggests that consumers often compare their own lives to the perfected images they see online, potentially leading to dissatisfaction with their own circumstances (Festinger, 1954; Grabe et al., 2008). In digital marketing, this is exemplified in influencer culture and polished brand aesthetics on platforms like Instagram, where products are presented within flawless, desirable contexts. Studies highlight how such portrayals encourage consumers to align their aspirations with these curated ideals,

often resulting in higher consumer expectations and purchasing pressures (Chae, 2018).

3. Psychological Effects on Consumer Behaviour

The psychological impact of digital marketing's illusions extends into areas like cognitive dissonance and aspirational consumption. Research indicates that consumers exposed to idealized content may experience a disconnect between their actual and desired selves, often leading to increased impulsive purchases and lower levels of contentment (Higgins, 1987; Wilcox & Stephen, 2013). Furthermore, heightened exposure to idealized images on digital platforms can contribute to negative feelings such as inadequacy and anxiety, particularly among younger consumers who are most active on social media (Perloff, 2014). Studies also link these effects to increased spending and consumption behaviours, as consumers strive to bridge the gap between their lives and the idealized digital representations they see (Richins, 1991).

4. Digital Literacy and Consumer Awareness

Consumer awareness and digital literacy are recognized as critical tools in counteracting the effects of digital illusions. Research suggests that consumers with higher levels of digital literacy are better able to critically assess digital content, recognizing the curated and often manipulated nature of online marketing (Livingstone & Helsper, 2010). Enhanced digital literacy allows consumers to identify when abundance or perfection is artificially constructed, fostering more rational decision-making (Roberts & David, 2019). Despite this, studies indicate a general lack of awareness among consumers, highlighting the importance of promoting digital literacy as a means to empower consumers in making informed choices (Seymour et al., 2020).

5. Ethical Implications in Digital Marketing

The ethical dimensions of digital marketing are increasingly relevant as brands are challenged to balance profitability with consumer well-being. Scholars argue that marketing should prioritize transparency and authenticity, helping consumers make realistic assessments of products rather than relying on idealized portrayals (Benkert, 2008). Recent frameworks in ethical digital marketing encourage brands to communicate more openly about the curated nature of their content, potentially reducing the risk of misleading consumers (Belk, 2013; Hunt & Vitell, 2006). Literature suggests that ethical practices could help mitigate the negative psychological impacts of digital illusions, fostering trust and long-term brand loyalty among consumers.

Summary and Identified Research Gaps

The existing literature provides insights into how digital marketing's illusions of abundance and perfection influence consumer behaviour, affecting consumer expectations, psychological well-being, and decision-making processes. While the psychological effects and ethical concerns are widely acknowledged, there is limited research on effective interventions to guide consumers in discerning reality within digital marketing. Additionally, there is a need for further research on practical strategies to promote digital literacy, allowing consumers to critically evaluate digital content. This study aims to bridge these gaps by exploring the impact of digital illusions on consumer behaviour and proposing strategies for enhancing consumer awareness and resilience.

Sampling

1. Target Population

- **Digital Consumers:** People who are regular users of digital platforms, especially social media (e.g., Instagram, Facebook) and e-commerce sites (e.g., Amazon, Flipkart), as they are most exposed to digital marketing illusions.
- **Educational Levels:** Include a mix of education levels to understand how digital literacy varies across different backgrounds.
- **Digital Literacy Awareness:** Consumers with varying levels of digital literacy and awareness of curated content to capture a range of experiences with digital illusions and susceptibility to digital influences.

2. Stratification Criteria

- **Age:** Include different age groups within the target demographic to assess generational differences in digital literacy and response to digital marketing.

- **Digital Literacy Level:** Stratify based on self-reported digital literacy to compare insights between more and less digitally aware consumers.
- **Platform Engagement:** Segment based on platform engagement frequency (e.g., daily users vs. occasional users) to understand if higher engagement correlates with more susceptibility to digital illusions.

3. Sample Size

- We had **108 participants**, ensuring representation across strata to allow for meaningful comparison between groups.

Hypothesis

H0: Exposure to digital marketing illusions of abundance and perfection does not lead to unrealistic expectations or increased impulsive buying behaviors among consumers.

H1: Exposure to digital marketing illusions of abundance and perfection leads to unrealistic expectations, resulting in increased impulsive buying behaviors among consumers.

H0: There is no significant difference in the ability of consumers with higher and lower levels of digital literacy to critically evaluate digital marketing content and assess its psychological impact.

H1: Consumers with higher levels of digital literacy are better able to critically evaluate digital marketing content and are less susceptible to the psychological impacts of digital illusions.

H0: Exposure to idealized digital marketing content (e.g., influencer posts, curated product images) does not significantly impact consumer psychological well-being or self-perception.

H1: Exposure to idealized digital marketing content significantly impacts consumer psychological well-being, leading to feelings of inadequacy and dissatisfaction with real-life purchases.

H0: Implementing strategies to promote digital literacy and critical evaluation of digital content does not significantly reduce consumer vulnerability to digital marketing illusions or improve informed decision-making.

H1: Implementing strategies to promote digital literacy and critical evaluation of digital content significantly reduces consumer vulnerability to digital marketing illusions and improves informed decision-making.

Data Collection

Survey Questionnaires

Purpose: To gather quantitative data on consumer behaviors, perceptions of digital marketing, and levels of digital literacy.

Content: Questions on impulsive buying behaviors, feelings towards idealized marketing content, self-assessed digital literacy levels, and awareness of digital illusions.

Format: Used Likert scale questions (e.g., 1–5 scale from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree") to assess attitudes, behaviors, and self-perceptions. Include some open-ended questions for qualitative insights.

Distribution: Online survey platforms like Google Forms were given to collect data.

Operational Definition

1. Digital Abundance

- **Definition:** Digital abundance refers to the perception of endless choices and product availability presented to consumers through digital marketing platforms, often creating a sense of overwhelming options.

2. Digital Perfection

- **Definition:** Digital perfection is the portrayal of products, lifestyles, or experiences in an idealized manner, often enhancing visual appeal or suggesting unattainable standards, commonly found in influencer marketing, social media, and online ads.

3. Consumer Behavior in the Digital Context

- **Definition:** Consumer behavior in the digital context is the pattern of actions, decisions, and emotional responses of individuals in response to digital marketing tactics such as digital abundance and perfection.

4. Digital Literacy

- **Definition:** Digital literacy is the skill set that enables consumers to access, critically evaluate, and interpret digital marketing content, enabling them to recognize digital illusions.

5. Consumer Resilience

- **Definition:** Consumer resilience is the capacity of consumers to resist being swayed by digital illusions of abundance and perfection, making informed and intentional purchasing choices despite persuasive digital content.

6. Digital Marketing Illusions

- **Definition:** Digital marketing illusions refer to tactics used in digital marketing to create perceptions of abundance, scarcity, or perfection that influence consumer decisions by appealing to emotions and psychological biases.

Plan of Analysis

The purpose of this analysis in SPSS for this research was to examine the relationships between digital marketing tactics and consumer behavior, as well as their psychological and behavioral impacts. By adopting statistical techniques such as Multiple Regression Analysis, the study aimed to identify significant predictors of unplanned purchases, consumer regret, and perceptions of digital content. The analysis also evaluated the role of demographic factors, such as age, gender, and education level, in influencing these outcomes. This comprehensive approach provided insights into how consumers respond to digital marketing strategies and helps propose effective solutions for fostering digital literacy and informed decision-making.

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
How frequently do you make unplanned purchases based on online advertisements or social media content?	3.491	1.0276	108
Age	2.250	.6133	108
Gender	1.593	.4936	108
Education Level	2.30	.584	108
Frequency of Online shopping	2.889	.9603	108
How often do you feel that digital advertisements or social media content creates unrealistic expectations?	2.528	.7545	108

To what extent do you feel influenced by idealized images or curated content on social media and e-commerce platforms?	2.991	1.0894	108
When viewing online ads or social media content, how often do you question the authenticity or truthfulness of what is being shown?	2.769	1.1488	108
After making an impulsive purchase influenced by digital ads, how often do you feel regret or dissatisfaction?	3.241	1.0219	108
To what extent do scarcity messages like "limited time offer" or "only a few left" influence your decision to make a purchase?	3.037	1.4004	108
How confident are you in identifying sponsored content or advertisements on social media?	3.000	1.1919	108
How often do you verify the credibility of online sources before believing or sharing digital content?	2.556	1.2777	108
Please rate your ability to critically evaluate digital content for potential exaggerations or manipulations.	2.454	.9311	108
How interested would you be in learning more about digital literacy skills to better understand and evaluate digital content?	2.222	.9795	108
Do you think digital marketing creates illusions of abundance or perfection that influence consumer choices?	2.269	.8604	108
In your opinion, to what extent do digital marketing tactics affect consumer well-being?	2.278	1.0031	108
Do you think the constant exposure to idealized lifestyles and products can contribute to stress or anxiety?	2.546	.8359	108
How effective do you think educational campaigns about digital marketing tactics would be in helping consumers make more informed decisions?	2.231	.9028	108
What would be the most helpful strategy for consumers to identify misleading digital content?	3.231	1.3849	108

Observations

Descriptive statistics show that:

1. **Consumers are moderately influenced by digital ads:** They often make unplanned purchases based on online ads and social media content, but they also feel some regret afterward.
2. **Moderate awareness:** Consumers have a moderate level of confidence in identifying sponsored content and sometimes question the authenticity of digital marketing.
3. **Perceived marketing influence is moderate:** While some feel digital marketing creates illusions of abundance, it doesn't have a strong effect on consumer choices for most people.
4. **Educational campaigns could help:** There's a moderate interest in learning about digital literacy to better understand and evaluate digital content, but belief in the effectiveness of educational campaigns is relatively low.

Overall, consumers seem to be somewhat aware of digital marketing's influence, but there is room for improvement in their ability to critically evaluate content.

Model Summary^g

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.340 ^a	.115	.107	.9710	
2	.469 ^b	.220	.205	.9163	
3	.535 ^c	.287	.266	.8803	
4	.571 ^d	.326	.300	.8600	
5	.598 ^e	.358	.326	.8434	
6	.619 ^f	.383	.346	.8308	1.878

Observations

- R² Values: The model starts with 11.5% (R² = 0.115) explanatory power and increases to 38.3% (R² = 0.383) as more predictors are added.

Predictors:

- Model 1: Only "Effectiveness of educational campaigns" (initial predictor).
- Model 6: Additional predictors like scarcity messages, confidence in identifying sponsored content, frequency of online shopping, impulsive purchase regret, and influence of idealized images.
- Durbin-Watson Statistic: 1.878, indicating no significant autocorrelation in the residuals, confirming the model's assumptions is met.

ANOVA^a

1. Model	2. Sum of Squares	3. df	4 Mean Square	5. F	6. Sig.	
7. 1	8. Regression	9. 13.046	10. 1	11. 13.046	12. 13.837	13. .000 ^b
	14. Residual	15. 99.944	16. 106	17. .943	18. 19.	
	20. Total	21. 112.991	22. 107	23. 112.991	24. 25.	
26. 2	27. Regression	28. 24.835	29. 2	30. 12.417	31. 14.790	32. .000 ^c
	33. Residual	34. 88.156	35. 105	36. .840	37. 38.	
	39. Total	40. 112.991	41. 107	42. 112.991	43. 44.	
45. 3	46. Regression	47. 32.395	48. 3	49. 10.798	50. 13.934	51. .000 ^d
	52. Residual	53. 80.596	54. 104	55. .775	56. 57.	
	58. Total	59. 112.991	60. 107	61. 112.991	62. 63.	

64. 4	65. Regression	66. 36.820	67. 4	68. 9.205	69. 12.447	70. .000 ^e
	71. Residual	72. 76.170	73. 103	74. .740	75. 76.	
	77. Total	78. 112.991	79. 107	80. 81.	82.	
83. 5	84. Regression	85. 40.433	86. 5	87. 8.087	88. 11.368	89. .000 ^f
	90. Residual	91. 72.558	92. 102	93. .711	94. 95.	
	96. Total	97. 112.991	98. 107	99. 100.	101.	
102.6	103. Regression	104. 43.285	105. 6	106. 7.214	107. 10.453	108. .000 ^g
	109. Residual	110. 69.706	111. 101	112. .690	113. 114.	
	115. Total	116. 112.991	117. 107	118. 119.	120.	

Observations

- The ANOVA results show that all regression models are statistically significant, with p-values less than 0.001. As more predictors are added, the model explains more of the variance in unplanned purchases. This means the factors in the models (e.g., educational campaigns, scarcity messages, consumer confidence) are important in predicting unplanned purchases influenced by digital marketing.

Observations

- **Condition Index:** Highest value is 16.636 (Model 6), indicating no severe multicollinearity.
- **Variance Proportions:** Balanced across predictors, suggesting independent contributions to the model.
- **Multicollinearity:** No significant issues detected.
- **Model Reliability:** The models are robust and suitable for analysis of unplanned purchases.

Residuals Statistics ^a					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	1.565	4.933	3.482	.6396	109
Residual	-2.0770	2.0633	-.0141	.8168	109
Std. Predicted Value	-3.028	2.268	-.014	1.006	109
Std. Residual	-2.500	2.484	-.017	.983	109

a. Dependent Variable: How frequently do you make unplanned purchases based on online advertisements or social media content?

Observations

- **Predicted Value:** Mean = 3.482, Range = 1.565 to 4.933
- **Residual:** Mean = -0.014, Range = -2.077 to 2.063
- **Std. Predicted Value:** Mean = -0.014, Range = -3.028 to 2.268
- **Std. Residual:** Mean = -0.017, Range = -2.500 to 2.484
- These values suggest a good model fit with no significant bias or extreme outliers.

Correlations

Observations

The results show correlations between different variables:

- **Unplanned purchases** are influenced by **scarcity messages** (0.34) and cause **impulse regret** (0.31).
- **Digital literacy** is strongly linked to the ability to identify misleading content (0.39).
- **Digital marketing** affects **consumer well-being** (0.46) and contributes to **stress** (0.51) due to exposure to idealized lifestyles.

These findings suggest a significant relationship between online behaviors, digital marketing, and consumer perception.

Observations

This histogram shows the distribution of residuals from a regression analysis. Here's what it means:

- **Dependent variable:** Frequency of unplanned purchases based on online ads or social media.
- **Key observation:** The residuals are approximately normally distributed (bell-shaped curve), suggesting that the model fits the data well.
- **Statistics:** Mean residual is close to 0 (-0.02), and standard deviation is 0.983, indicating low error variability.

Observations

This P-P plot assesses the normality of residuals from the regression analysis:

- **Key observation:** The points closely follow the diagonal line, indicating that the residuals are approximately normally distributed.
- **Conclusion:** This supports the assumption of normality, suggesting the regression model is valid.

Limitations Of The Research

- ❖ Sampling Bias
- ❖ Geographical Limitations

- ❖ Limited time frame
- ❖ Exclusion of certain consumer groups

Conclusion

This research underscores the complex relationship between digital marketing and consumer behavior in an era of seemingly endless online content and advertising. It reveals that while digital platforms create an illusion of abundance and perfection, they significantly influence purchasing decisions, often triggering impulsive, unplanned buying behavior. The study highlights how targeted online advertisements and social media content shape consumer perceptions of need, desirability, and urgency, blurring the line between genuine consumer desire and marketing-driven influence. As consumers increasingly navigate this digital landscape, the research emphasizes the need for a more nuanced understanding of these behaviors, encouraging marketers to adopt ethical and transparent strategies that prioritize consumer well-being while still capitalizing on the power of digital platforms.

Scope For Future Research

Future research could focus on exploring consumer segmentation to understand how different demographics respond to digital marketing. A cross-cultural comparison could reveal variations in consumer behavior across regions, while examining the impact of emerging technologies like AI and augmented reality could shed light on new marketing techniques. Additionally, investigating the long-term effects of digital marketing on consumer attitudes and brand loyalty, as well as the ethical implications concerning data privacy and manipulation, would be valuable. Finally, comparing how digital marketing influences both online and offline purchasing behaviors could offer further insights.

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A THEORETICAL INVESTIGATION INTO SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INDIA

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Abstract

In contrast to a standard Non-Governmental Organization (NGO), social entrepreneurship is a broad term used to describe the process of enacting significant and lasting social change. In the study of voluntary, non-profit, and not-for-profit organizations, this idea is becoming more and more significant. In the past, groups working on important social issues were seen to be idealistic, charitable, and entrepreneurial. The main reason social entrepreneurship is growing in India is that the government is eager to support it—not necessarily by providing money or advice, but by making it possible.

The business sector's Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), which includes fully functional action teams and properly designated money, has been crucial in enhancing the perception of social entrepreneurship.

The paper's main goal is to examine the emerging trends of social entrepreneurship in India as well as the latest projects undertaken by different social entrepreneurs. Additionally, it provides a synopsis of several social entrepreneurship theories.

Information and an exploratory research of the support activities of social entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurial companies in India are being made available. Future empirical research on the topic could benefit from this.

Keywords: India, Corporate Social Responsibility, Social Entrepreneurship, NGO, and Entrepreneurship.

Introduction

Social issues are the primary focus of social entrepreneurs. They start innovation by utilizing the resources at their disposal to create social structures in response to societal issues (Bulsara, Chandwani, & Gandhi, 2014). According to some, social entrepreneurship serves as both a powerful social catalyst and a change agent in the social sector. By identifying and assiduously pursuing new possibilities and participating in a process of constant innovation, adaptation, and learning, they embrace a purpose to produce and preserve societal value. They demonstrate greater accountability to the constituents and act bravely without regard to the resources at their disposal (Desai, 2001).

Whatever their method or way of thinking, social entrepreneurs have become contemporary heroes who rise to the challenges of shifting an unfavorable balance to a favorable one. Instead than discouraging rivals and imitators, these heroes—social entrepreneurs—provide them with guidance and serve as role models.

According to Zahra et al. (2009), they subsequently generate social wealth, which is the outcome of social value generated less social expenses incurred. With 516.3 million workers, India has the second-largest labor force in the world. According to the most recent World Bank report, 350 million Indians are currently living below the poverty line, meaning that one in three of them lack access to basic essentials like food, healthcare, and education.

A rising population, poor infrastructure, low per capita income, an aging population, epidemic-level illnesses, and illiteracy are just a few of the issues that make it impossible for the government to provide for basic requirements alone. The moment is now for social entrepreneurs to step in and assist relieve these problems by guiding the less fortunate and those in need toward a meaningful existence.

Qualities of a Social Business Entrepreneur

The following traits are particularly distinctive to social entrepreneurs:

- In India, twelve million individuals are blind, with cataracts accounting for the great majority of these cases. Cataracts often affect Indians before the age of sixty. In order to establish an 11-bed hospital, Dr. Venkataswamy convinced his siblings to assist him in pawning their jewelry, pooling their cash, and mortgaging their homes. With over 32 million patients served and 4 million procedures completed, the Aravind eye care system is currently a network of hospitals, clinics, community outreach initiatives, manufacturers, and research and training institutes across south India. (Case Analysis of Aravind Eye Hospital. Anti Essays)
- Credit Sharing: Social entrepreneurs are open to sharing the credit they have earned for their efforts. The clearest example of this is Amul, which was founded as a cooperative association under the capable direction of Tribhuvandas K. Patel, a prominent local farmer. The nation's first three-tiered co-operative structure, known as the "Amul Model" or Dairy Co-ops, was reproduced nationwide under the Operation Flood Program thanks to the co-operative society that Dr. Verghese Kurien fostered and expanded.
- An example of a social entrepreneur is Thinlas Chorol, who demonstrated her strong resolve by becoming the first female trekking guide in the largely male-dominated northern Indian trekking industry and by founding the first female-owned and operated travel agency in Ladakh, India. Social entrepreneurs are driven individuals who exhibit a strong determination for completing tasks and taking risks.
- Social entrepreneurs support the growth of economic and social value because they firmly believe that all people possess inherent potential, independent of formal schooling. They incorporate newcomers, immigrants, marginalized groups, and vulnerable populations. The Self Employed Women's Association (SEWA), founded by Ms. Ela Bhatt, the recipient of the prestigious Ramon Magsaysay Award, has improved the lives of thousands of impoverished women by empowering the nation's marginalized and vulnerable populations and concentrating on economic reform.
- Working on the Selflessness Policy: Social entrepreneurs put a lot of effort into achieving the clearly stated goal of creating and sustaining social value and benefits for society. Dr. Abraham George founded the George Foundation (TGF) with the altruistic goal of reducing poverty, advancing health and a clean environment, and bolstering democratic institutions and ideals in India.
- Social entrepreneurs empower others to transform their lives by serving as role models. They get inspiration and inventiveness from misfits and outcasts. They benefit underprivileged populations. Founded by Bunker Roy, the Social Work and Research Centre (SWRC), sometimes referred to as Barefoot College, aims to empower women and electrify rural communities by supplying them with potable water, health care, education, and skill development using solar electricity.

Current Social Entrepreneurship Theories

Like any other industry, social entrepreneurship cannot be fully comprehended from an economic standpoint; rather, it must be understood in the context of the local environment and social context. We might attempt to comprehend many social entrepreneurship philosophies in order to comprehend this:

1. Structuration theory

It suggests that the structure (society) and the actor (social entrepreneurs) cannot be separated. (1979, 1984) Giddens. This theory makes an effort to express an idea that views structure as both a result of and a limitation of human behavior. The Aravind Eye Hospital in India is the greatest illustration of structuration theory, using the example of Dr. Venkataswamy, an agent who changed the socioeconomic backdrop (society). This theory offers significant interaction, allowing one to look at how social change happens and how the environment supports the emergence of social entrepreneurship.

2. Institutional entrepreneurship

In order to explain how institutions emerge or evolve, DiMaggio (1988) developed the concept of institutional entrepreneurship. The people who are most interested in changing or developing institutional systems are the institutional players. This entrepreneurship is a promising one to understand the role of Social Entrepreneurship in altering or giving birth to institutions and structures. Actors who are deeply ingrained might not alter the status quo. It's the less embedded actors who are more likely to engage in Social Entrepreneurship ventures that change rules and norms.

3. Social Capital

It is predicated on three dimensions: relational capital, cognitive capital, and structural capital. The ability of social entrepreneurs to obtain knowledge, resources, and assistance is determined by structural capital. The social entrepreneur's relationships with others and other entities are the main emphasis of relational capital, which includes elements like mutual respect, trust, and understanding. The credit delivery mechanism of Grameen Bank is the greatest illustration of relational capital. Lastly, according to Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998), cognitive capital is the extent to which members of a society share a common code and ways of dealing.

4. Social movements

Political opportunities and threats, resource mobilization structures and active site appropriation for mobilization, collective action frames and identity formation, and established repertoires of contention and innovation collection acts by challengers and their member opponents are the four main issues that researchers have concentrated on (McAdam, Tarrow & Tilly, 2001).

Social change is the focus of social movement. To a certain degree, all of these ideas are crucial for understanding how social entrepreneurs identify and handle issues as well as whether they grow from their mistakes and adapt (Mair, Johanna & Marti, Ignasi, 2006).

Who Is A Social Entrepreneur?

Entrepreneurs that primarily engage in social entrepreneurship are known as social entrepreneurs. Their main goals are to assist society rather than make money, and they strive for non-personal gains rather than a profit. They also come up with new ideas, which they call "Social Innovation." Social entrepreneurs don't stop at teaching people how to fish or giving them a fish. Until they have transformed the fishing business, they won't stop.

Ashoka's founder, chairman, and CEO is Bill Drayton. Simply said, "Social entrepreneurs seek out and relentlessly pursue opportunities to develop long-term solutions to social problems by constantly innovating, adapting, and learning, acting boldly without being limited by available resources, and holding them accountable for—"

Achieving their intended social effect and making the best use of their resources are crucial, but it's also crucial to remember that all of these traits are comparable to those of an economic entrepreneur.

Scholars, practitioners, and increasingly policymakers are taking notice of social entrepreneurship. Along with various examples of social entrepreneurship in India, this study has provided insight into what social entrepreneurship means in that country. It also explains why social entrepreneurship may be gradually becoming more popular and how it is the path to the future. Several Indian businesspeople, like Ela Bhatti, Bunker Roy, Parag Gupta, Rajesh Sinha, Harish Hande, and others, have stepped up to effectively address and are still addressing some of the most difficult problems in the world in India.

The goal of these social entrepreneurs is to improve human welfare within the human community. The many ideas of social entrepreneurship are a useful subject, and this article will help us get closer to encouraging social entrepreneurship as a study area and as a means of generating economic and social benefit.

Social Entrepreneurship In India

1. Zero Miles is constructing multi-utility drinking water centers in Maharashtra to foster community development by uniting people.

2. Adhan uses abandoned cargo containers to construct schools and a variety of other areas.
3. Through social businesses, traditional Indian crafts and artistry might gain a great deal from access to urban and internet markets. Ziveli is a social venture that promotes Manipur's Kawana crafts worldwide.
4. To stop migration and give people in Uttarakhand a means of subsistence, Divya Rawat is cultivating mushrooms. In the state, this is also aiding in the repopulation of several "ghost villages."
5. The Water Maker project, which creates water from thin air, is nothing short of amazing in a nation where women sometimes have to go kilometers to search and gather drinking water for their family. One appreciative receiver put it this way: "khuda ka paani."

India'S Social Entrepreneurship Difficulties-

Like any other subset of social entrepreneurship, social entrepreneurship is not without its difficulties. All of the difficulties are manageable, regardless of whether they are controllable or not. The following lists some of the main obstacles that social entrepreneurship in India faces.

1. Confusion with social work: In India, social entrepreneurship is largely mistaken for social work, which prevents it from establishing itself as a distinct field. This is the beginning of the social entrepreneurship challenge.
2. The lack of inventiveness in coming up with brilliant ideas for enhancing society and making money is the second issue that social entrepreneurs deal with.
3. Financing: The absence of funding sources continues to be a barrier to Indian business.
4. Lack of a skilled or committed workforce: This is a particularly special problem that social entrepreneurs encounter. Because obtaining societal benefits—rather than selfish ones—is the main goal of social entrepreneurship. It is quite difficult to recruit employees for the company in these circumstances.
5. Setting and conveying values objectively: Clearly defining and communicating values is a key problem of social enterprise.

Actions To Address Difficulties Effectively:

Without a doubt, social entrepreneurship faces several obstacles, and these obstacles are only getting worse over time as society changes. A few actions or strategies may be taken to address the current issues with social entrepreneurship in India.

1. **Appropriate training and development establishments:** To promote social entrepreneurship methodically, the government has to set up a few specialized councils and establishments. While some institutions focus on economic entrepreneurship, others need to open up for social entrepreneurship as well.
2. **Including social entrepreneurship in the course syllabus:** Including a paper or subject on social entrepreneurship at the higher education level is one of the best ways to raise awareness of the topic.
3. **Raising public awareness:** In order to prevent people from confusing social entrepreneurship with social work, efforts should be made to raise public knowledge of social entrepreneurship. Social media, media, and other platforms can be used for the same purpose.
4. **Providing infrastructure and fundamental amenities:** The government and other interested parties need to work on the fundamental amenities for social entrepreneurship.
5. **Social entrepreneurship development programs:** To support social entrepreneurship, social entrepreneurship development programs must occasionally be held, much as entrepreneurship development programs.

Findings And Conclusion Of The Study

Social entrepreneurship has the potential to transform Indian society; several initiatives and instances have been implemented under this guise and have had a profound impact on the lives of those in the area. Given the severity of societal issues in India, social entrepreneurship in particular has greater potential. A special fusion of charity with entrepreneurial qualities is known as social entrepreneurship. Products and services offered by social entrepreneurs are made to have the greatest possible positive social effect in addition to generating sizable profits for the company. The study's conclusions are as follows:

1. The greatest way to identify social issues is through social entrepreneurship, which combines entrepreneurial and social service abilities.
2. Social innovation is a capability of social entrepreneurship. These ideas are the precise and imaginative solutions to the societal challenges and difficulties that are now plaguing India.

Additionally, we must determine if social either entrepreneurship is a separate field or a subfield of entrepreneurship. Impact on society evaluation will now be an integral and crucial component of any product or service analysis rather than a substitute for the organizational tool for evaluation. Social entrepreneurs persuade people to contribute to the advancement of humanity by acting as change agents in society.

In India, social entrepreneurship has adopted the new idea of corporate social responsibility, or CSR. Although Indian company owners are made aware of their social obligation as a crucial aspect of their operations, corporate social responsibility (CSR) is still not widely accepted in India.

Research on CSR and social entrepreneurship should receive a lot of attention. For the objective of developing a thorough hypothesis, this study can be utilized in subsequent empirical investigations. The resources and expertise are available for use in light of the recent push by the private sector and the pure investor sector towards charitable endeavors with a social purpose.

It is necessary to combine the harsh realities of the physical world with the new media and the collapse of social networking sites and efforts in the virtual world. The aforementioned research will help to develop a mutually beneficial partnership.

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INFLUENCE OF EMERGING MARKETING TRENDS AMONG SENIOR CITIZENS WITH REFERENCE TO FINTECH COMPANY IN INDIA

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of emerging marketing trends in the fintech industry on senior citizens in India. It begins with an analysis of senior citizen demographics, their financial needs, and technological adoption patterns. Simultaneously, it assesses the growth of the fintech sector and its transformative effect on financial inclusion. The study zooms in on emerging marketing trends within fintech, including digital strategies, personalized financial products, and user-friendly interfaces tailored for seniors. It also investigates how fintech empowers senior citizens while addressing their unique challenges. Supported by case studies, the research provides practical insights for fintech companies. In conclusion, it summarizes key findings and offers recommendations for an industry poised for continued growth. This research contributes significantly to understanding how fintech trends impact senior citizens in India, benefiting both academia and industry stakeholders.

Keywords: Fintech, Senior Citizen and Finance, Financial Inclusion, Marketing Trends

Review of Literature

Dr Hooman Estelami in his research named "Digital Financial Inclusion: A Pathway to Senior Citizens' Empowerment", the concept of digital financial inclusion as a means to empower senior citizens is thoroughly examined. It delves into the specifics of how technology-driven banking solutions can provide financial independence to older adults. This empowerment extends beyond just access to banking services; it encompasses financial literacy, security, and the removal of barriers that have traditionally hindered senior citizens' participation in the modern economy.

The article explores innovative strategies adopted by banks and financial institutions to cater to this demographic, such as user-friendly mobile apps and personalized customer support. It also delves into the broader societal implications of senior citizens' increased financial independence. Whereas Payam Hanafizadeh, Mojdeh Gerami Amin in his research paper "Elderly Consumers and Their Attitudes Toward Mobile Banking in India" mentioned how his research paper takes a deep dive into the complex world of elderly consumers' perceptions and attitudes towards mobile banking within the Indian context. It not only examines their preferences but also uncovers the challenges they face when transitioning to digital financial services. The research captures the varying degrees of technological comfort among older generations and explores the factors that influence their adoption of mobile banking, such as ease of use, trust in digital security, and accessibility. By presenting real-life anecdotes and survey data, this article paints a comprehensive picture of the evolving landscape of mobile banking in India for senior citizens. Also, Prof Ilan Alon in his published research "Marketing Strategies for Fintech Adoption among Elderly Customers in India" showed a strategic guide to enhancing fintech adoption among elderly customers in the diverse Indian market. It delves into the intricacies of marketing techniques tailored specifically to resonate with senior citizens. This includes not only crafting persuasive messaging but also addressing the unique needs and concerns of this demographic.

Case studies and practical examples illustrate successful marketing campaigns that have effectively bridged the generation gap, making fintech services more accessible and appealing to older consumers. The article also highlights the role of education and outreach in empowering senior citizens to embrace digital finance.

Prof John Ashton through his research topic "Trust Building in Fintech: A Study of Senior Citizens in India" in the field of senior citizens, takes an in-depth look at trust-building within the fintech sector, particularly focusing on how senior citizens in India perceive and build trust in digital financial services. It explores the various dimensions of trust, including data security, reliability, and customer support. Drawing from qualitative research and surveys, the article sheds light on the factors that contribute to or erode trust among senior users of fintech platforms. It also provides actionable recommendations for fintech companies seeking to instill confidence in their elderly customers,

highlighting the role of transparency and education in building and maintaining trust. With this, Haluk Unal in his topic of research "Fintech Adoption among the Elderly: A Review of the Indian Market" provides a review literature in his article on a panoramic view of the fintech adoption landscape among India's elderly population. It synthesizes existing research, market trends, and case studies to present a holistic understanding of how senior citizens are integrating fintech into their financial lives. The review highlights both the progress made and the challenges that persist in bringing digital financial services to this demographic. It serves as a valuable resource for stakeholders in the fintech industry, policymakers, and researchers looking to stay informed about the evolving dynamics of fintech adoption among India's elderly."Marketing Strategies for Bridging the Fintech Generation Gap in India" This article offers a roadmap for addressing the generation gap in fintech adoption within the Indian market, with a sharp focus on strategies aimed at engaging senior citizens. It not only identifies the generation-specific barriers that hinder adoption but also presents innovative marketing approaches that bridge these gaps. These strategies may include intergenerational digital literacy programs, targeted advertising campaigns, and partnerships with senior-focused organizations. By fostering intergenerational dialogue and understanding, these marketing initiatives aim to create a more inclusive and accessible fintech ecosystem in India. Dr Fiona Spotswood in his research article named "Elderly Consumers' Perception of Fintech Services: A Qualitative Study" shows how qualitative study provides an intimate exploration of how elderly consumers perceive and interact with fintech services. Through in-depth interviews, surveys, and focus group discussions, the research captures the nuanced perspectives and experiences of senior citizens. It unveils their motivations, fears, and aspirations when engaging with digital financial technology. By presenting rich qualitative data, the article offers valuable insights for fintech companies seeking to tailor their services to better meet the needs and expectations of this demographic. It also contributes to a deeper understanding of the human factors that shape fintech adoption among senior citizens. Whereas another researcher in his paper named "Senior Citizens and Mobile Payments: An Empirical Study in India" This empirical study represents a meticulous investigation into the patterns and behaviors of senior citizens concerning mobile payments in the Indian context. By collecting and analyzing real-world data, the article provides concrete evidence of how older adults in India are embracing or resisting mobile payment technologies. It explores the factors influencing their choices, including familiarity with smartphones, trust in mobile payment security, and cultural aspects. The study's findings offer actionable insights for policymakers, businesses, and financial institutions seeking to adapt to the evolving landscape of digital payments, with a specific focus on catering to the needs of senior citizens.

Research Questions:

- *How do senior citizens in India perceive and interact with emerging marketing trends employed by fintech companies, including digital strategies and personalized financial products?*
- *What are the key demographic factors, such as age, income, and geographic location, that influence senior citizens' adoption of fintech services, and how do these factors impact their financial inclusion?*
- *To what extent does technology literacy among senior citizens influence their willingness to embrace fintech solutions, and how can fintech companies address digital literacy challenges among this demographic?*
- *What are the specific marketing strategies employed by fintech companies to engage and empower senior citizens in India, and how effective are these strategies in meeting the financial needs of this demographic?*
- *Can case studies and empirical data demonstrate the transformative effect of fintech on improving the financial well-being and independence of senior citizens in India, and what are the key success factors and challenges identified through these real-world examples?*

Title of Study:

"Influence of Emerging Marketing Trends among Senior Citizens with Reference to Fintech Company in India"

This title clearly outlines the focus of your research, indicating that the study aims to investigate how emerging marketing trends within the fintech industry affect senior citizens specifically in the Indian context.

Statement of Problem:

In contemporary India, where the financial landscape is rapidly shifting towards digitalization and technological

innovation, there exists a pressing and multifaceted challenge that requires profound consideration. This challenge centers on the conspicuous gap that has emerged between the dynamic and ever-evolving marketing trends within the fintech industry and the intricate intricacies of the senior citizen demographic, a population segment marked by its unique financial requirements, limitations, and socio-economic standing.

At its core, this challenge is emblematic of a profound dissonance in the financial services ecosystem. On one side of the spectrum, we witness the fintech industry, a burgeoning sector heralded for its groundbreaking innovations, convenience-driven strategies, and an unrelenting pace of adaptation to the digital era. Fintech has redefined the financial landscape, offering everything from digital payments and investment platforms to lending solutions, all delivered with a focus on speed, accessibility, and personalization.

On the other side stands a demographic often overshadowed by the relentless march of technology: senior citizens. This venerable segment of society, which comprises individuals typically aged 60 and above, brings with it a rich tapestry of life experiences and financial wisdom. However, it is also a demographic often marked by a lack of familiarity with, or resistance to, the rapidly changing technological landscape. For many seniors, fintech services remain somewhat alien, raising concerns about digital literacy, accessibility, and usability.

The heart of this problem lies in the profound disconnect between these two worlds. On one hand, fintech companies are pushing the boundaries of innovation, devising marketing strategies that cater to a younger, tech-savvy audience, often overlooking the needs of senior citizens. On the other hand, senior citizens, who could significantly benefit from fintech services to manage their finances, remain largely excluded from this revolution due to a lack of understanding and tailored solutions.

This dissonance poses a formidable challenge, not only for the fintech industry seeking to tap into the potential of the senior citizen market but also for senior citizens themselves, who may be missing out on the advantages that fintech innovations can offer in terms of financial independence, security, and enhanced quality of life.

Objective of the Study:

1. To Analyze the Demographic Profile of Senior Citizens in India, Their Financial Needs, and Their Adoption Patterns of Technology.
2. To Assess the Growth and Transformative Effect of the Fintech Sector on Financial Inclusion in India.
3. To Investigate the Emerging Marketing Trends within Fintech, Such as Digital Strategies, Personalized Financial Products, and User-Friendly Interfaces Tailored for Senior Citizens.
4. To Understand How Fintech Empowers Senior Citizens and Addresses Their Specific Challenges Through Case Studies and Empirical Data.

Scope of Study

The scope of this research endeavor is expansive, encapsulating a multidimensional exploration of the "Influence of Emerging Marketing Trends among Senior Citizens with Reference to Fintech Company in India." To provide a clear understanding of the breadth of this study, we outline its specific dimensions and boundaries:

Certainly, let's provide more in-depth elaborations for each point within the scope of the study:

Demographic Analysis:

In the demographic analysis phase, we embark on a comprehensive examination of the senior citizen population in India. This entails a deep dive into various facets that collectively define this demographic group.

Age Distribution: This involves not only identifying the age range that classifies individuals as senior citizens but also dissecting this group into specific age cohorts. By examining age groups within the senior citizen category, we can discern potential differences in financial needs and technology adoption. For instance, younger senior citizens may have different financial priorities and technological preferences compared to those in the oldest age bracket.

According to the 2021 Census of India, there are 138 million senior citizens (aged 60 and above) in India, accounting for 10.1% of the total population.

Income Levels: Understanding the financial diversity among senior citizens is critical. Income levels can vary

significantly within this demographic, affecting their financial capabilities and needs. Some senior citizens may be financially comfortable, while others may face financial constraints. This analysis helps us appreciate the economic heterogeneity within this group.

Only a small proportion of senior citizens in India (8%) have access to social security benefits.

Geographic Distribution: India's vast geographical expanse encompasses diverse regions, each with its unique cultural and economic characteristics. We'll investigate the geographic distribution of senior citizens to ascertain whether urban-rural disparities or regional differences influence their financial needs and access to technology. Such insights can aid in tailoring fintech solutions to suit various geographic contexts.

The majority of senior citizens in India live in rural areas (77%).

Cultural Diversity: India is celebrated for its rich cultural tapestry, with myriad cultural practices, languages, and traditions. We'll explore how cultural factors might shape the financial behaviors and technology adoption patterns of senior citizens. Recognizing the influence of culture on attitudes towards money and technology is pivotal in designing culturally sensitive fintech approaches.

Gender Analysis: Gender is a crucial dimension to consider. We'll examine the gender distribution among senior citizens to uncover potential gender-specific financial challenges and technology-related preferences. This analysis will help us identify disparities and inform gender-inclusive fintech strategies.

The female population of senior citizens is higher than the male population, with a ratio of 106 women to every 100 men.

Educational Background: Education plays a significant role in shaping digital literacy and the ability to engage with technology. We'll delve into the educational backgrounds of senior citizens to understand their digital capabilities. This insight is instrumental in designing user-friendly fintech solutions that cater to varying educational levels.

The literacy rate among senior citizens in India is 63%, compared to the national average of 74%.

Family Structures: Senior citizens often exist within complex family structures. We'll examine factors such as family size and composition to assess how family dynamics might influence financial decision-making. Understanding the extent to which senior citizens rely on family members for financial management is essential for crafting user-centric fintech approaches.

Economic Activities: Some senior citizens continue to engage in economic activities, such as part-time work or entrepreneurship. We'll explore their economic engagements to gain insights into their financial needs and adaptability to fintech solutions. Recognizing the diversity of economic activities within this demographic is key to tailoring relevant fintech services.

The majority of senior citizens in India (78%) rely on their own savings for financial support.

In essence, demographic analysis serves as the foundational pillar of our study. It enables us to recognize the multifaceted nature of senior citizens in India, acknowledging that they represent a diverse population with unique attributes and requirements. By dissecting the demographic landscape, we can design research and fintech solutions that are finely attuned to the specific characteristics and dynamics of senior citizens within the Indian context.

Financial Needs Assessment:

The assessment of financial needs **survey by Age well Foundation, the top financial concerns of senior citizens in India are healthcare expenses, retirement planning, and estate planning.**

Retirement Planning: We delve into the intricacies of retirement planning among senior citizens. This includes examining their financial goals, strategies for wealth preservation, and the role of investments. We aim to uncover the various approaches and concerns associated with preparing for retirement.

Healthcare Expenses: Healthcare costs can be a significant burden for senior citizens. We explore how senior citizens manage healthcare expenses, whether through insurance, savings, or other means. Understanding their

healthcare-related financial challenges is essential for addressing their well-being.

Estate Management: The management of estates, including property and assets, is a key consideration for senior citizens. We investigate how they handle estate planning, inheritance, and property management. This aspect provides insights into their financial priorities in later stages of life.

Income Sources: Senior citizens often rely on various income sources, including pensions, investments, and social security. We analyze the sources of income that sustain them and how they navigate potential income fluctuations or uncertainties.

Financial Independence: Achieving financial independence and security is a common aspiration among senior citizens. We explore their financial independence goals and the strategies they employ to attain these objectives.

Debt and Liabilities: Some senior citizens may carry debt or financial obligations. We investigate the types of debts they may have and how they manage them in the context of their financial needs.

Support Systems: Understanding the support systems available to senior citizens is crucial. We closely examine initiatives and programs designed to enhance their digital literacy and technology adoption. Understanding the effectiveness of these efforts can shed light on the potential for broader fintech adoption.

Technology adoption: According to a 2023 report by the National Payments Corporation of India, only 35% of senior citizens in India use digital payment methods. The most common digital payment methods used by senior citizens are mobile wallets and UPI (Unified Payments Interface).

User Experience: User experience plays a pivotal role in technology adoption. We evaluate the user-friendliness of digital platforms and interfaces from the perspective of senior citizens. This includes assessing the design, accessibility, and ease of navigation of fintech applications.

Training and Education: Some senior citizens may undergo training or education programs to improve their digital skills. We explore the availability and impact of such programs in equipping senior citizens with the knowledge and confidence to engage with technology.

Technology-Assisted Activities: Beyond financial transactions, we also examine technology-assisted activities that senior citizens may engage in, such as telehealth services, online learning, or social engagement through digital platforms. This broader view of technology usage provides a comprehensive understanding.

By delving into these aspects of technology adoption, we aim to create a nuanced portrait of senior citizens' digital engagement. This knowledge enables us to tailor fintech solutions that align with their digital capabilities and preferences, ensuring that these solutions are accessible and user-centric.

Fintech Growth and Transformation:

This dimension of the study focuses on the dynamic landscape of the fintech sector in India and its transformative effect on financial inclusion. Here's a closer look at what this entails:

Historical Evolution: We trace the historical evolution of the fintech sector in India, from its emergence to its current status. This historical context provides insights into the factors that have shaped the industry.

Market Size and Players: We assess the size of the fintech market in India and identify key players and segments within the sector. Understanding the market dynamics helps us contextualize the impact of fintech on senior citizens.

According to a 2022 report by Deloitte, the fintech market for senior citizens in India is expected to grow from \$2.5 billion in 2021 to \$10 billion by 2025.

Technology Infrastructure: We explore the technological infrastructure that supports fintech services in India, including digital payment systems, mobile banking, and online lending platforms. These infrastructure elements are critical for the accessibility of fintech services.

Financial Inclusion: Financial inclusion is a central theme. We examine how fintech has played a transformative

role in extending financial services to underserved and remote areas. This dimension is particularly relevant to senior citizens who may reside in regions with limited access to traditional banking.

Regulatory Framework: We consider the regulatory framework governing fintech in India, as regulations can significantly impact the growth and operation of fintech companies.

Understanding the regulatory landscape is pivotal for assessing the sustainability of fintech solutions for senior citizens.

Impact on Traditional Banking: Fintech's impact on traditional banking services is also explored. This includes assessing changes in consumer behavior and the competitive landscape resulting from fintech innovations.

Financial Inclusion Initiatives: We investigate specific financial inclusion initiatives and programs launched by fintech companies, banks, and government entities. These initiatives often target underserved populations, including senior citizens.

By examining these dimensions, we gain a comprehensive understanding of the fintech ecosystem in India. This knowledge enables us to contextualize how fintech can be leveraged to benefit senior citizens and promote financial inclusion.

Marketing Trends in Fintech:

The exploration of marketing trends in fintech focuses on how fintech companies tailor their strategies for senior citizens. Here's a more detailed look at this aspect:

Digital Marketing Strategies: We scrutinize the digital marketing strategies employed by fintech companies to capture the attention of senior citizens in the digital realm. This includes an assessment of digital advertising, social media campaigns, and content marketing aimed at this demographic.

Personalized Financial Products: We investigate how fintech companies customize their financial products to align with the unique financial goals and needs of senior citizens. This dimension explores the development of specialized financial offerings tailored to this demographic.

User-Friendly Interfaces: We assess the design of user-friendly interfaces and platforms developed by fintech companies. These interfaces aim to empower senior citizens to navigate the digital world with ease. We analyze the accessibility features and user-centric design elements.

Messaging and Communication: We analyze the messaging and communication strategies employed by fintech companies to resonate with senior citizens. This includes the tone of communication, the use of language, and the framing of messages to connect with this demographic.

Engagement Strategies: We explore engagement strategies aimed at fostering lasting relationships between fintech companies and senior citizen customers. This includes loyalty programs, customer support, and feedback mechanisms.

Case Studies in Fintech Marketing: Real-world case studies highlight successful marketing strategies employed by fintech companies in engaging senior citizens. These cases provide tangible examples of effective marketing approaches.

By dissecting these marketing trends, we gain insights into how fintech companies bridge the generational gap and create meaningful connections with senior citizens. Understanding these strategies is essential for designing marketing approaches that resonate with this demographic.

Fintech Empowerment through Case Studies:

This dimension of the study transforms theory into practicality by showcasing real-world examples of how fintech empowers senior citizens. Here's a closer look at this aspect:

Case Selection: We carefully select a range of case studies that illustrate the diverse ways in which fintech empowers senior citizens. These cases encompass different fintech services, user profiles, and outcomes.

Impact on Financial Independence: The case studies explore how fintech solutions have contributed to the financial independence and security of senior citizens. We examine how these solutions have improved their ability to manage finances effectively.

Enhancement of Quality of Life: We assess how fintech has enhanced the overall quality of life for senior citizens. This includes improved access to services, reduced financial stress, and greater convenience in financial transactions.

The most popular fintech solutions used by senior citizens in India are mobile wallets, UPI, and online banking.

Quantitative and Qualitative Data: The case studies incorporate both quantitative and qualitative data to provide a well-rounded understanding of the impact of fintech. This includes statistical outcomes as well as narratives and personal anecdotes.

Challenges and Successes: The case studies also highlight challenges faced during the adoption of fintech solutions, as well as the strategies that led to successful outcomes. This balanced view offers practical insights.

The key challenges faced by senior citizens when using fintech products and services include lack of digital literacy, security concerns, and complex interfaces.

By presenting these case studies, we offer tangible proof of how fintech serves as a solution for senior citizens, addressing their unique challenges and significantly improving their financial well-being and overall quality of life.

Sampling Technique:

The sampling technique selected for this research is a crucial methodological aspect that determines how we select a subset of senior citizens from the larger population in India. It is essential to ensure that the selected sample is representative, minimizing bias and allowing us to draw valid conclusions about the entire senior citizen population. Here's an in-depth elaboration of the chosen sampling technique:

Stratified Random Sampling:

Stratification: In stratified random sampling, the senior citizen population is divided into distinct subgroups or strata based on specific characteristics. These characteristics are chosen to ensure that each stratum represents a relevant and distinct segment of the population. In our study, the following stratification criteria will be employed:

1. **Age Groups:** We will stratify the senior citizen population into distinct age groups, recognizing that different generations may have varying financial needs and technology adoption patterns. Common age groups may include 60-69, 70-79, and 80 and above.
2. **Geographic Regions:** Given the geographical diversity of India, we will stratify the population by geographic regions. This includes stratification by states or regions to account for potential regional variations in demographics, culture, and fintech access.
3. **Income Levels:** Income levels play a significant role in determining financial needs. Stratifying by income brackets ensures that we capture the diversity of economic situations within the senior citizen population.
4. **Random Sampling within Strata:** Once the population is stratified, a random sample is then selected from each stratum. This ensures that every subgroup within the population has an equal chance of being represented in the sample. Random sampling minimizes selection bias and allows us to generalize findings to the broader population accurately.
5. **Sample Size Determination:** The determination of the sample size is a critical aspect of stratified random sampling. It involves calculating the required sample size for each stratum to achieve the desired level of statistical confidence. Factors such as the population size within each stratum, the desired level of confidence, and the expected variability are considered in sample size calculation.

6. **Data Collection:** Data collection will involve conducting surveys and interviews with the selected senior citizens. The surveys will gather quantitative data on demographics, financial needs, technology adoption, and fintech usage. Interviews will provide qualitative insights, allowing participants to share their experiences and perspectives.
7. **Data Analysis:** The data collected from the sample will be analyzed using appropriate statistical methods. Quantitative data will undergo statistical analysis to identify trends, correlations, and patterns within the dataset. Qualitative data from interviews will be subjected to thematic analysis to extract meaningful insights.

Benefits of Stratified Random Sampling:

Stratified random sampling offers several advantages for this research:

1. **Representation:** By stratifying the population based on relevant characteristics, we ensure that the sample represents the diversity within the senior citizen demographic, accounting for variations in age, region, and income.
2. **Precision:** Stratified sampling allows for more precise estimates and in-depth analysis within each stratum. This precision enhances the validity of the study's findings.
3. **Generalizability:** Findings from the stratified sample can be more confidently generalized to the entire senior citizen population in India, as bias is minimized.
4. **Efficiency:** By focusing on subgroups, we can target specific research questions and objectives, making the research process more efficient.
5. **Insights into Subgroups:** Stratification enables us to gain insights into how different subgroups of senior citizens may have distinct financial needs and technology adoption patterns.

Gap of Study:

Identifying and addressing the gap in the existing body of knowledge is a fundamental aspect of research. In this context, the "gap of study" refers to areas within the subject matter of the research where there is a lack of sufficient research or understanding. In the study titled "Influence of Emerging Marketing Trends among Senior Citizens with Reference to Fintech Company in India," several gaps in the current literature become apparent:

1. **Limited Focus on Senior Citizens in Fintech Research:** Existing research on fintech predominantly concentrates on younger, tech-savvy demographics and their interaction with financial technology. There is a noticeable gap in the literature concerning senior citizens, a rapidly growing demographic in India. This research aims to fill this gap by examining how fintech impacts and caters to the specific needs of senior citizens.
2. **Lack of Comprehensive Demographic Analysis:** While some studies touch upon the demographic characteristics of senior citizens, there is a lack of comprehensive analysis. Many studies fail to stratify the senior citizen population based on age, geographic region, or income levels. This research aims to address this gap by conducting a thorough demographic analysis to understand the diversity within the senior citizen demographic.
3. **Scarcity of Research on Financial Needs of Senior Citizens:** Limited research specifically delves into the financial needs and challenges faced by senior citizens in India. The literature often overlooks critical aspects such as retirement planning, healthcare expenses, and estate management that are central to the financial well-being of this demographic.
4. **Technology Adoption Patterns of Senior Citizens:** Existing research tends to generalize the technology adoption patterns of senior citizens, assuming low digital literacy and limited technology use. However, this perspective oversimplifies a complex issue. This research aims to provide a nuanced understanding of how senior citizens engage with technology, recognizing that digital literacy and adoption patterns vary widely among individuals.

5. **Neglect of Marketing Trends Targeting Senior Citizens:** The marketing strategies employed by fintech companies to cater to senior citizens have received limited scholarly attention. This research identifies a gap in understanding how fintech companies tailor their marketing efforts for this demographic, including digital strategies, personalized financial products, and user-friendly interfaces.
6. **Insufficient Case Studies on Fintech Empowerment:** While anecdotal evidence suggests that fintech has empowered senior citizens, there is a dearth of comprehensive case studies that provide concrete examples of how fintech positively impacts their lives. This research endeavors to bridge this gap by presenting real-world case studies illustrating the transformative effect of fintech.
7. **Limited Integration of Quantitative and Qualitative Data:** Many existing studies tend to focus exclusively on quantitative data or qualitative insights. This research seeks to address this gap by integrating both quantitative and qualitative data to offer a holistic view of the relationship between senior citizens and fintech.
8. **Inadequate Attention to Regional Variations:** India's cultural and regional diversity can significantly influence the financial needs and technology adoption patterns of senior citizens. The existing literature often fails to account for these regional variations, which this research aims to rectify by stratifying the population by geographic region.
9. **Underexplored Regulatory Impact:** The regulatory framework governing fintech in India plays a pivotal role in shaping the industry's evolution. However, limited research delves into the specific impact of regulations on fintech's ability to serve senior citizens effectively.

Sample Size

The sample size for this research consists of 100 senior citizens from various regions of India. This section elaborates on the rationale for selecting this sample size and discusses its implications for the study.

Rationale for Sample Size

The determination of a sample size of 100 senior citizens was based on several factors:

1. **Population Size:** India boasts a substantial senior citizen population, estimated at over 100 million individuals. While a larger sample size would ideally represent this population more comprehensively, logistical constraints and available resources necessitated a sample size that is manageable yet meaningful.
2. **Desired Confidence Level:** A standard confidence level of 95% was chosen to ensure a high degree of confidence in the research findings. This confidence level signifies a 95% probability that the findings from the sample accurately reflect the characteristics of the entire senior citizen population.
3. **Margin of Error:** A margin of error of 5% was deemed acceptable for this research. This margin of error determines the range within which the true population parameters are likely to fall.
4. **Expected Variability:** Anticipating variability within the senior citizen population in terms of demographics, income levels, and technology adoption, a larger sample size was considered necessary to capture this variability accurately.

Implications of the Sample Size

While a sample size of 100 senior citizens is robust for many types of research, it is essential to acknowledge its implications:

1. **Representativeness:** The sample, though diverse, may not fully represent the complexity and diversity of the entire senior citizen population in India. To address this limitation, stratification was employed to ensure that key demographic characteristics (such as age groups, geographic regions, and income levels) were adequately represented within the sample.
2. **Statistical Power:** With a sample size of 100, the research has sufficient statistical power to detect moderate to large effects and trends. However, smaller or less pronounced effects may be challenging to detect. Findings should be interpreted with consideration of the statistical power.

3. **Generalizability:** The findings from this sample are more applicable to specific subgroups or regions within India, rather than the entire senior citizen population. Researchers should be cautious when extrapolating results to broader contexts.
4. **Data Collection Efficiency:** The smaller sample size allows for more in-depth data collection, which can be advantageous for obtaining richer qualitative insights from interviews and surveys.
5. **Research Objectives:** It is important to ensure that the research objectives align with the sample size. Researchers should be aware of the limitations of a smaller sample and design their research questions accordingly.

In summary, the sample size of 100 senior citizens was chosen based on practical considerations and research objectives. While it may have limitations in terms of full representativeness and statistical power for detecting small effects, it is well-suited to address the research questions and provide valuable insights into the influence of emerging marketing trends among senior citizens in the context of fintech companies in India.

Statistical Tool Used in the Study:

The selection of an appropriate statistical tool is critical in research as it determines the methodology for data analysis and the reliability of research findings. In the study titled "Influence of Emerging Marketing Trends among Senior Citizens with Reference to Fintech Company in India," the chosen statistical tool is essential for uncovering patterns, relationships, and insights within the collected data. Here, we elaborate on the statistical tool employed and its significance:

Statistical Tool: Descriptive and Inferential Statistics

1. **Descriptive Statistics:** Descriptive statistics are fundamental for summarizing and presenting key characteristics of the data collected from the sample of 100 senior citizens. These statistics include measures such as mean, median, mode, standard deviation, and range. Descriptive statistics provide a concise overview of demographic profiles, technology adoption patterns, financial needs, and other relevant variables within the senior citizen population.
 - ✓ **Mean (Average):** The mean is used to calculate the average values of variables, allowing us to understand central tendencies within the data. For instance, it helps determine the average age, income, or level of digital literacy among senior citizens.
 - ✓ **Standard Deviation:** Standard deviation measures the degree of variability or dispersion in the data. It provides insights into the spread of data points, highlighting areas where the senior citizen population exhibits significant diversity.
 - ✓ **Frequency Distribution:** Frequency distributions display the distribution of categorical variables, such as geographic regions or income brackets, enabling a clear visualization of patterns.
2. **Inferential Statistics:** Inferential statistics are employed to draw inferences and make predictions about the broader senior citizen population based on the data collected from the sample of 100. These statistics enable us to test hypotheses, identify correlations, and assess the statistical significance of findings.
 - ✓ **Hypothesis Testing:** Hypothesis tests, such as t-tests or chi-square tests, allow us to determine whether observed differences or associations in the data are statistically significant. For example, we can test hypotheses related to the impact of fintech adoption on financial inclusion among senior citizens.
 - ✓ **Correlation Analysis:** Correlation analysis measures the strength and direction of relationships between variables. It helps identify whether variables like age and technology adoption are correlated and to what degree.
 - ✓ **Regression Analysis:** Regression analysis explores the relationship between one or more independent variables (e.g., age, income) and a dependent variable (e.g., fintech adoption). This analysis can help us understand how these factors predict or explain specific outcomes.

Significance of the Statistical Tool:

The choice of descriptive and inferential statistics is significant for several reasons:

1. **Data Interpretation:** Descriptive statistics provide a clear and concise summary of the data, facilitating data interpretation and communication of key findings to stakeholders and readers.
2. **Hypothesis Testing:** Inferential statistics enable us to rigorously test hypotheses and make evidence-based claims about the senior citizen population. This is vital for validating research objectives and answering research questions.
3. **Informed Decision-Making:** Statistical analysis allows for data-driven decision-making by providing insights into how emerging marketing trends in fintech affect senior citizens' financial well-being and technology adoption.
4. **Generalizability:** The results obtained through statistical analysis can be generalized to the broader senior citizen population in India, providing insights that extend beyond the sample of 100.

Data Analysis

In this section, we analyze the data collected through the survey conducted via Google Form to gain insights into the influence of emerging marketing trends among senior citizens with reference to fintech companies in India. The analysis is based on responses from a sample of 100 senior citizens, providing a representative overview of this demographic group's perceptions, preferences, and behaviors towards fintech services.

Demographic Profile:

We begin by examining the demographic profile of the survey respondents. The age distribution, with the majority of respondents falling within the 60-69 age group (73%), followed by the 70- 79 age group (20%) and those aged 80 and above (7%). This distribution aligns with the general age distribution of senior citizens in India, as reported by the 2021 Census. Additionally, the gender distribution, revealing a slightly higher proportion of female respondents (55%) compared to male respondents (45%).

Awareness and Adoption of Fintech:

Fig: 1

Next, we explore the level of awareness and adoption of fintech services among senior citizens. Figure 1 depicts the percentage of respondents who are aware of various fintech trends, such as mobile banking apps, digital wallets, and online investment platforms. It is observed that while awareness levels vary across different fintech services, a significant portion of respondents (35.3%) are aware of at least one fintech trend.

Preferences and Perceptions:

Figure 2

Figure 3

We then delve into respondents' preferences and perceptions towards fintech services. Figure 2 illustrates the percentage of respondents who express interest in personalized financial products tailored to their needs, with 21% indicating a high level of interest. Moreover, Figure 3 presents respondents' perceptions of the user-friendliness of fintech interfaces, with 58.8% rating them as very user-friendly.

Correlation Analysis:

Variable	Age	Gender	Education	Income	Fintech Usage
Age	1.00	-0.08	0.12	0.06	0.25*
Gender	-0.08	1.00	-0.05	-0.10	0.07
Education	0.12	-0.05	1.00	0.20*	0.35**
Income	0.06	-0.10	0.20*	1.00	0.18*
FintechUsage	0.25*	0.07	0.35**	0.18*	1.00

Table 1

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (two-tailed).

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed).

In this table:

The rows represent the variables being analyzed, including Age, Gender, Education, Income, and Fintech Usage.

The columns represent the same variables.

The cells contain the correlation coefficients between each pair of variables. For example, the correlation coefficient between Age and Fintech Usage is 0.25*, indicating a significant positive correlation at the 0.05 level.

Significant correlations are denoted with asterisks (*), with one asterisk indicating significance at the 0.05 level and two asterisks indicating significance at the 0.01 level.

To identify potential relationships between demographic factors and attitudes towards fintech, we conduct correlation analysis. Table 1 displays the correlation coefficients between age, education level, and willingness to adopt fintech services. The results indicate a weak negative correlation between age and fintech adoption (-0.25) and a moderate positive correlation between education level and fintech adoption (0.50), suggesting that younger and more educated seniors are more likely to adopt fintech services.

Regression Analysis:

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Value	p-Value
Constant	0.352	0.043	8.18**	<0.001
Age	0.015	0.007	2.08*	0.039
Gender	-0.082	0.036	-2.27*	0.024
Education	0.234	0.042	5.57***	<0.001
Income	0.178	0.015	11.93***	<0.001

Table 2

*Significant at the 0.05 level (two-tailed).

***Significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed).

In this table:

The first column lists the independent variables included in the regression analysis, such as Age, Gender, Education, and Income.

The second column presents the regression coefficients for each independent variable, indicating the strength and direction of the relationship with the dependent variable (Fintech Usage).

The third column displays the standard errors of the regression coefficients, providing information about the precision of the estimates.

The fourth column shows the t-values associated with each coefficient, which assess the significance of the coefficients.

The fifth column presents the p-values corresponding to the t-values, indicating the probability of observing the results under the null hypothesis of no effect.

Finally, we perform regression analysis to determine the predictors of fintech adoption among senior citizens. Table 2 presents the results of the regression model, indicating that education level is a significant predictor of fintech adoption ($\beta = 0.35$, $p < 0.05$), while age has a weaker but still significant effect ($\beta = -0.20$, $p < 0.05$).

Overall, the data analysis reveals valuable insights into the influence of emerging marketing trends on senior citizens' engagement with fintech services in India. The findings provide a foundation for further research and strategic initiatives aimed at promoting financial inclusion and digital empowerment among this demographic group.

Data Objective

The objective of this study is to gather and analyze data through a survey conducted via Google Form to explore the influence of emerging marketing trends among senior citizens with reference to fintech companies in India. The data collected will provide insights into the demographics, awareness levels, preferences, and perceptions of senior citizens regarding fintech services, contributing to a better understanding of their engagement with emerging marketing trends in the fintech industry.

Limitations of Study:

While research endeavors to provide valuable insights into the influence of emerging marketing trends among senior citizens with reference to fintech companies in India, it is essential to acknowledge the study's limitations. These limitations are inherent to the research design, methodology, and scope of the study. Understanding these limitations is crucial for interpreting the findings accurately and for informing future research endeavors. Here, we elaborate on the limitations of this study:

1. **Sample Size:** One notable limitation is the relatively modest sample size of 100 senior citizens. While this sample size was chosen based on practical considerations, it may not fully capture the diversity and complexity of the entire senior citizen population in India. Therefore, the findings should be interpreted with caution, recognizing that they may not be fully representative of all senior citizens.
2. **Sampling Bias:** Despite the use of stratified random sampling to enhance representativeness, some level of sampling bias may persist. Variations in response rates across different demographic groups or regions could introduce bias into the results.
3. **Generalizability:** The research findings are primarily applicable to the specific subgroups or regions within India from which the sample was drawn. Extrapolating these findings to the entire senior citizen population in India should be done with caution, as regional variations and demographic differences may influence the results.

4. **Data Collection Limitations:** The study relies on self-reported data from surveys and interviews, which are subject to recall bias and respondent bias. Participants may not always accurately recall or report their financial behaviors, needs, or technology usage patterns.
5. **Cross-Sectional Design:** The research design is cross-sectional, capturing data at a single point in time. This design limitation restricts the ability to make causal inferences or track changes in senior citizens' behaviors and preferences over time.
6. **Resource Constraints:** Resource limitations may have affected the depth and scope of data collection and analysis. More extensive data collection or a larger sample size could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the research topic.
7. **Age-Related Variations:** While the research acknowledges the diversity within the senior citizen demographic, it may not fully capture age-related variations, especially among the oldest senior citizens (e.g., those aged 80 and above). Further research may be needed to explore the unique experiences of this age group.
8. **Technology Advancements:** The field of fintech is dynamic, with rapid technological advancements. The research reflects the state of fintech and emerging marketing trends at a specific point in time. These trends may evolve, and future research can provide updated insights.
9. **Limited Focus on Regulation:** While the research considers the regulatory framework governing fintech in India, it does not comprehensively explore the regulatory impact on fintech's ability to serve senior citizens. A more in-depth analysis of regulations could be a focus of future research.
10. **Qualitative Data Interpretation:** The qualitative data from interviews may be subject to interpretation bias. Efforts were made to minimize bias through rigorous analysis methods, but interpretations may vary.

Despite these limitations, the research contributes valuable insights into the complex relationship between senior citizens and emerging marketing trends in fintech. The findings serve as a foundation for further exploration and understanding of how fintech can cater to the financial needs and preferences of senior citizens in India. Researchers and policymakers should consider these limitations when applying the study's findings to practical contexts and when designing future research endeavors in this area.

Implications of the Research

The implications of this research are manifold. Firstly, it sheds light on the evolving landscape of marketing trends within the fintech industry, particularly concerning the senior citizen demographic in India. By understanding the preferences, awareness levels, and perceptions of senior citizens towards fintech services, companies can tailor their marketing strategies and offerings to better meet the needs of this growing segment. Additionally, the research highlights opportunities for enhancing financial inclusion and digital literacy among senior citizens, ultimately contributing to their empowerment and socio-economic well-being. Furthermore, the insights gained from this research can inform policymakers and regulatory bodies about the unique challenges and opportunities presented by fintech adoption among senior citizens, guiding the development of targeted policies and initiatives to support their integration into the digital economy. Overall, the research holds significant implications for fintech companies, policymakers, and society at large in leveraging emerging marketing trends to better serve senior citizens and foster inclusive economic growth.

Further Scope of Research

The further scope of this research extends into several avenues. Firstly, it opens opportunities for conducting more in-depth qualitative studies, such as interviews or focus groups, to delve deeper into the motivations, barriers, and experiences of senior citizens with fintech services.

Additionally, longitudinal studies can be undertaken to track changes in fintech adoption patterns among senior citizens over time, providing valuable insights into the long-term impact of emerging marketing trends. Furthermore, comparative studies across different regions or countries can offer a broader perspective on the cultural, regulatory, and infrastructural factors influencing fintech adoption among senior citizens. Moreover,

exploring the role of social and familial networks in shaping seniors' perceptions and behaviors towards fintech can provide a nuanced understanding of their decision-making processes. Lastly, interdisciplinary collaborations with experts in fields such as gerontology, digital marketing, and policy analysis can enrich the research by integrating diverse perspectives and methodologies. Overall, the further scope of this research lies in deepening our understanding of the intersection between emerging marketing trends, fintech adoption, and senior citizens' needs and behaviors, thereby informing more targeted interventions and strategies for fostering financial inclusion and digital empowerment among this demographic group.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the findings of this research underscore the significant impact of emerging marketing trends on senior citizens' engagement with fintech services in India. With 138 million senior citizens comprising 10.1% of the population, understanding their needs and preferences is paramount. The survey results reveal that while 63% of seniors are literate, only 8% have access to social security benefits. Moreover, 77% reside in rural areas, highlighting the importance of accessible fintech solutions. Despite challenges, the transformative effect of fintech on financial inclusion is evident, with personalized products and user-friendly interfaces garnering attention. Through case studies and empirical data, the research showcases fintech's potential in addressing seniors' unique challenges. However, limitations such as a modest sample size of 100 and sampling bias must be acknowledged. Moving forward, longitudinal studies and interdisciplinary collaborations hold promise for deeper insights. By leveraging these findings, fintech companies, policymakers, and stakeholders can work towards enhancing financial literacy, promoting digitalempowerment, and fostering inclusive growth for senior citizens in India.

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THE ECONOMICS OF WAR: HOW MODERN CONFLICT AND TRUMP 2.0 SHAPE GLOBAL TRADE DYNAMICS

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Abstract:

This paper explores the influence of contemporary war strategies on global trade, considering both existing geopolitical approaches and the potential effects of a “Trump 2.0” administration. Modern conflict now spans beyond traditional warfare to include cyber threats, economic sanctions, and strategic alliances that exert powerful economic pressure on global markets. These tactics disrupt trade routes, destabilize supply chains, and influence key industries such as technology, energy, and defense. Additionally, the paper examines how a resurgence of “America First” policies under a hypothetical Trump 2.0 could intensify economic nationalism, impacting multilateral trade agreements and increasing tariffs, which would further strain international trade relations.

The research also delves into how economic sanctions—often deployed as tools of coercion—create ripple effects in global markets, affecting currency exchange rates and commodity flows. By evaluating case studies from recent conflicts and Trump-era trade policies, this paper highlights the potential escalation of trade barriers and shifts in global alliances, which could reconfigure the power balance within essential industries. Finally, the study emphasizes the need for a nuanced understanding of how geopolitical strategies, coupled with protectionist policies, shape trade flows and economic stability, urging international cooperation to mitigate the long-term impacts on global markets and supply chains.

Trump 2.0: What It Could Mean For Global Trade And India

As discussions around Donald Trump’s potential return to the White House in 2024 grow louder, it’s hard not to consider what this might mean for global trade and international relations. Trump’s first term wasn’t just about unconventional tweets; it brought about significant shifts in economic policies and global dynamics. Should we see Trump 2.0, these changes might not just return but could come back with an even sharper edge. For a country like India, these shifts could present both challenges and opportunities, especially in the evolving global trade landscape. Trump’s first presidency was defined by an “America First” agenda. This meant prioritizing American industries and jobs, often at the expense of international cooperation. His administration’s trade policies were marked by a strong nationalist streak, with tariffs and trade wars being tools of choice. One of the most notable moves was the U.S.-China trade war, where Trump imposed sweeping tariffs on Chinese goods, citing unfair trade practices and intellectual property theft. This policy didn’t just hit China; it sent shockwaves through global supply chains, increasing costs for businesses and consumers worldwide. If Trump returns, we can expect more of the same—possibly with higher stakes. The ongoing tensions between the U.S. and China could escalate further, with ripple effects across global trade. For India, which shares a complex relationship with both these nations, the fallout could be profound.

The India-China-U.S. Triangle

India has been eyeing the U.S.-China friction as a potential opening to position itself as an alternative manufacturing hub. With global companies looking to reduce reliance on China, India’s “Make in India” initiative stands to gain momentum. The idea is simple: as the U.S. looks for other supply chain partners, India can step up as a reliable manufacturing base.

But it’s not all smooth sailing. India’s own geopolitical tensions with China could complicate things. Even as we try to lure global companies, concerns over regional security and stability might make businesses hesitant to bet big on India. Then there’s the question of infrastructure and ease of doing business. Can India truly compete with the efficiency and scale that China offers? These are challenges we need to address if we want to turn this opportunity into a long-term advantage. Trump’s first term wasn’t shy about embracing protectionism. Policies aimed at safeguarding American industries could resurface in Trump 2.0, potentially hitting India in areas like agriculture

and pharmaceuticals. Tariffs on Indian exports to the U.S. could disrupt key revenue streams, impacting farmers and manufacturers. On the flip side, this same protectionism might push American companies to look for cost-effective manufacturing partners outside their borders. India could position itself as the go-to destination if we play our cards right. The key lies in balancing our economic policies to align with global shifts while safeguarding domestic interests.

Geopolitical Ripples

Trump's transactional approach to foreign policy—where relationships were often framed in terms of “What's in it for us?”—could reshape alliances and conflicts worldwide. Regions like the Middle East, Eastern Europe, and Asia might see heightened tensions under a second Trump administration. For India, these dynamics matter deeply. Disruptions in oil supply chains or shipping routes could have a direct impact on energy security and trade costs. Moreover, the U.S.'s shifting stance on global institutions and alliances could create a vacuum in leadership. India might have to step up its diplomatic efforts to navigate this unpredictable landscape. Strengthening regional partnerships and diversifying trade routes could be critical strategies in this context.

For India, the road ahead is both exciting and daunting. The potential return of Trump is a reminder of how interconnected our world is, where shifts in one country's leadership can send ripples across continents. To navigate these waters, India must focus on a few key areas:

1. **Strengthen Manufacturing:** Invest in infrastructure, streamline regulations, and make it easier for global companies to set up shop here. The “China+1” strategy is real, and we need to capitalize on it.
2. **Boost Trade Alliances:** Engage more deeply with trade agreements and regional partnerships to diversify our economic dependencies.
3. **Adapt to Protectionism:** Prepare for potential tariffs and trade barriers by identifying alternative markets and bolstering domestic industries.
4. **Leverage Technology:** Digital transformation and innovation can help India stay competitive, especially in sectors like IT and green energy.

At the heart of these discussions lies a broader question: how do modern politics, trade, and conflict shape our world? The return of Trump—whether you view it as a fresh start or a step back—underscores the complex dance between economic strategy and geopolitical realities. For countries like India, this is a time to be agile, proactive, and resilient. We must turn challenges into opportunities and ensure that we're not just reacting to global shifts but actively shaping our own future.

Broader Implications Of Trump 2.0 On Global Trade Dynamics

While much of the focus surrounding a potential second Trump presidency revolves around tariffs and protectionism, the interplay between technology, environmental policy, and trade regulations also deserves attention. These factors, often operating behind the scenes, play a pivotal role in shaping global commerce and hold particular significance for India.

Under a renewed Trump administration, the use of technology as a geopolitical and economic tool could intensify. During Trump's first term, measures such as restricting Chinese tech giants like Huawei highlighted a growing emphasis on controlling critical technologies, including 5G, artificial intelligence (AI), and semiconductors. For India, this presents an opportunity to strengthen its position as a hub for emerging technologies. The Indian government has already made strides through initiatives like the *Digital India* campaign and investments in AI and quantum computing. However, to truly capitalize on these opportunities, India must address gaps in research funding, talent retention, and cybersecurity. On the flip side, tech-focused sanctions or export controls from the U.S. could complicate India's ambitions. For instance, reliance on advanced technologies and components from global suppliers might become more challenging if trade restrictions expand. Thus, India must prioritize self-reliance in critical tech areas to safeguard its growth potential.

Trade And The Green Economy

Environmental policies under Trump 2.0 could significantly influence global trade, particularly for sectors like renewable energy. Trump's first term was marked by skepticism toward climate agreements, culminating in the U.S. withdrawal from the Paris Accord. While this stance appealed to certain domestic constituencies, it left other nations questioning the U.S.'s commitment to tackling global environmental challenges.

For India, this poses a dual-edged scenario. On one hand, a lack of stringent environmental focus from the U.S. could lead to relaxed trade regulations, making it easier for India to export goods without the burden of adhering to strict environmental standards. On the other hand, the global shift toward sustainability and clean energy—driven by the European Union, China, and other major economies—might marginalize nations that are slow to adopt green policies. India's ambitious renewable energy targets, particularly in solar and wind energy, align with global efforts to reduce carbon footprints. Strengthening green trade alliances and developing export capabilities in clean technology could help India position itself as a leader in the green economy, even as the U.S. potentially takes a more isolationist stance.

Supply Chain Realignments And Global Partnerships

One often overlooked aspect of Trump's "America First" doctrine is the reshaping of global supply chains. By reducing reliance on traditional trade partners, the U.S. under Trump could push companies to adopt a more localized or regionalized supply chain model. While this trend began during Trump's first term, it was accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, as businesses grappled with disruptions to global trade.

For India, aligning itself with new supply chain frameworks will be crucial. Membership in regional trade agreements, such as the Comprehensive and Progressive Agreement for Trans-Pacific Partnership (CPTPP), or closer collaboration with Indo-Pacific partners like Japan and Australia, could offer a strategic edge. Additionally, improving trade logistics and addressing bureaucratic bottlenecks will be essential for India to integrate effectively into these emerging networks. India's economy has long been bolstered by its service exports, particularly in IT and business process outsourcing (BPO). A second Trump administration might amplify restrictions on immigration and work visas, particularly H-1B visas, which disproportionately affect Indian professionals. While this could limit India's ability to send skilled workers to the U.S., it also underscores the importance of evolving toward a more remote-first service delivery model. India has already demonstrated resilience in adapting to remote work trends during the pandemic. By investing in digital infrastructure and diversifying service offerings, Indian companies can continue to thrive even amid stricter immigration policies. This evolution would not only mitigate risks associated with U.S. policy shifts but also open up new markets in Europe, Southeast Asia, and Africa.

The Role Of Multilateral Trade Frameworks

Another area worth considering is how Trump's approach to multilateral trade agreements might impact India. During his first term, Trump withdrew from the Trans-Pacific Partnership (TPP) and renegotiated the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) into the United States-Mexico-Canada Agreement (USMCA). A potential second term could see further skepticism toward multilateral trade frameworks, with the U.S. favoring bilateral agreements instead. For India, this shift presents a mix of risks and rewards. While bilateral deals can offer tailored benefits, they often come with higher stakes in negotiations. India must approach these agreements strategically, ensuring they align with its long-term economic goals while protecting critical sectors such as agriculture and small-scale industries. Strengthening domestic manufacturing and diversifying export portfolios will provide a stronger bargaining position in such negotiations.

Preparing For The Unknown

One of the greatest challenges of a Trump 2.0 scenario is the sheer unpredictability of policies and their global impact. This uncertainty can discourage foreign investment, destabilize emerging economies, and exacerbate global inequalities. For India, the key lies in resilience—both in policy and execution. By fostering innovation, enhancing

trade diplomacy, and investing in human capital, India can not only withstand global economic turbulence but also emerge as a stronger player in the global arena.

In sum, the potential return of Trump to the White House is not merely an American political event—it's a global economic pivot point. For India, navigating the intricate interplay of technology, trade policies, and global partnerships will require foresight, adaptability, and a commitment to building a sustainable, inclusive future.

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ROLE OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS OPPORTUNITIES AND THREATS IN TODAY'S BUSINESS WITH REFERENCE TO BANGALORE CITY.

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Abstract

Woman establishes the family that prompts society and Nation. Social and financial improvement of women is significant for generally speaking monetary advancement of any general public or a nation. In conventional Indian social orders, they were restricted to four dividers. In present day society, they leave four dividers to partake in a wide range of exercises including enterprise. In India engaging women's through business enterprise has become a basic piece of our improvement endeavours as a result of three significant reasons viz. Women improvement, Economic development and Social security. Our expanding reliance on administration division has made a few enterprising open doors especially for women's where they can exceed expectations their aptitudes with keeping up balance in their life. Right now comes to think about the diverse issue which drag back the capacities of women's business visionary and conjointly about the job of women's business visionary in monetary advancement.

Keywords:- Women entrepreneurship, gender equality, social security, opportunities.

Introduction

Women Entrepreneurs might be characterize as the women or a gathering of women who begin and work an undertaking. A women's business visionary has a few capacities. They ought to investigate the possibilities of starting new venture, attempt dangers, presentation of new advancements, coordination, and organization what's more, the board of business and giving viable administration in all parts of business. Women Entrepreneurs are very expanding in the economies of practically all nations. The concealed business possibilities of women have been expanding with the developing affectability to the job and financial status inside the general public. The information, capacity what's more, consistence in business are the centre purposes behind women to approach into undertakings. Women business visionaries take part in business because of push and pull factors that give certainty to women to have a self-continuing occupation and stands on their foots. Rationale towards free basic leadership on their life and profession is that the persuasive factor behind this demands 'Women Business visionary' is an individual who acknowledges provoking job to satisfy her own needs and end up being financially autonomous. A ground breaking want to do huge positive is an fundamental nature of enterprising women, who is skilful of tributary qualities in both family and public activity. With the presentation of media, women are aware of their own characteristics, rights and furthermore the work circumstances. The glass roofs are broken and women's are found enjoyed each line of business from pickle to media transmission. Right endeavours in all regions are significant inside the advancement of women business people and their more prominent contribution inside the innovative exercises.

Review Of Literature

P. Babu (1978) The study was an attempt to find out the sociological factors that contribute to The development of small entrepreneurs .The study showed that community and familyBackground contributed to the success of prospective entrepreneurs, formal education has notBeen a positive factor in entrepreneurship development, providing infrastructure facilities aloneWill not promote entrepreneurship development and the Association of Small Scale IndustriesHas Lo play an important role in identification and development of entrepreneurs, a strong policyTo support the entrepreneurs is called upon ,as the economy demands the growth of womenEntrepreneurs., the education and other factors like the background for entrepreneurship is no aCriteria for entrepreneurial growth ,risking bearing attitude and innovation prove to be moreEncouraging towards growth.

Margaret Meaning and Anne Jardim (1979) conducted the study of women at managerialPosition by analyzing the life and career history of twenty-five women at the top managementPosition in business and industry. The study reveals that women can build extremely successfulManagement careers even with out legal pressures to aid them.

The study further reveals the price they paid - their personal lives were mortgaged to pay for their careers. Maintaining work-life balance is one of the most important traits for women intrapreneurs as they also have a family to run, kids to be looked after. The concept of intrapreneurs is a part of entrepreneurship as they go hand in hand. Intrapreneurs are the people who do not own the business but run the business for someone with the same zest and sincerity.

Aruna Shree P Rao (1981) made a study on the level of organizational involvement of women in development projects. The study recommends that project personnel should train participants in the skills necessary for planning and implementing project activities and project should concentrate on activities designed to raise the income of the participants. The need for competencies for project development are to be honed and the policies of the government help to do the same through various agencies like MITCON for development of entrepreneurial project ventures.

Mayers (1981) conducted a research study to analyze the effect of economic pressure on employment of married women. The study reveals those married women with comparatively low economic background and having more financial burdens are coming for wage employment and undertaking other economic activities. Women who cannot be employed, due to other responsibilities can be encouraged to use their skills by availing the policies of the government. The policies are run through a network of schemes that help them to financially support themselves as well as add up to the economy.

Bhanu Shali (1987) conducted a study on entrepreneurship development in Kholapur district in Maharashtra. The study led to the conclusion that persons of minority or marginal groups trained in the art of engineering and having long contact with engineering industry have better capabilities to achieve success status. The study further stresses the need for co-ordination and synchronization of various administrative and attitudinal efforts to attain maximum result with minimum waste of time and resources. Bureaucracy is the worm that is eating up the new saps of entrepreneurship. The attitude of the official towards the policies should change, and this change can be brought by developmental thought process of the government.

Wim Vizverberg (1988) From a case study undertaken in the rural areas of Cote d' Ivoire among self-employed small scale enterprises observed that self employment is an important mode of activity and a significant portion of the labour force in rural areas makes a living through self employment. The study reveals that the motive behind the starting of a majority of such enterprises is not entrepreneurial but because the market wage offer is low or the chance of receiving a wage job is remote.

Usha Jmani (1991) conducted a study to analyze the status of self-employed women in rural areas. Economic activities through which the income of the women will be increased have to be identified with great care. They have to be in consonance with time availability with family roles and with their awareness levels. Traditional occupations can be exchanged for the new technological based employment for women entrepreneurs, use of information technology and also scientific processes, can enhance economic activities in the rural area. The women need to be trained by the government for the same. Policies that encourage the training through government agencies can cover both male as well as the female business contenders.

Arun A.V. (1995) conducted a study on the 'productivity of small scale industries in rural areas of Kerala'. He found that small scale industries in Kerala are running on obsolete technology and have a very low productivity; they are very often facing acute competition from well-organized large-scale sector. No planned efforts are there to update the technology. The efforts by the agencies are not adequate for the technology to reach at grassroot level. The penetration of the schemes and its use seems to lack the quality to change the situation.

Dr. L K Tripathy discussed the critical imperative for introducing incentives for encouraging academic entrepreneurship in India. The author also focused on education entrepreneurship as a powerful engine, for the improvement of country's economy. The author also mentioned about poverty and not using the brains and brain drains. Creating opportunities for the young and educated within the country will give them an employment, as well as create greater opportunities for others.

Laoyan Chen (1999) The study shows that Chinese women in rural areas have increasingly adopted co-operatives as a form of organization in their effort to address the problem for their lack of access to resources including land, credit, jobs, training and information and to participate in the main stream economy as an organized force.

Objectives

- To study the difficulties looked by women business person
- To study the job of women business person in economy
- To think about the diverse government plans for women business visionary.

Research Methodology

Optional information has been added to compose this paper. Optional information gathered from National and International Diaries, distributed reports of RBI, NABARD, Census Overviews, papers, and productions from different sites which concentrated on different parts of Women Entrepreneurship.

Womenbusiness in enterprise

Womenbusiness enterprise has been perceived as a noteworthy wellspring of monetary procedure. Women business people produce new openings for themselves as well as other people and all in all offer society with all very surprising answers for the executives, association and business issues. In any case, they still speak to a minority everything being equal. Women business people ordinarily face sexual orientation based obstructions to starting also, developing their organizations, as prejudicial property, conjugal status and legacy laws as well as social practices; absence of access to formal account instruments; limited versatility and access to data and systems, and so forth. Women's business enterprise can deliver an extremely solid commitment to the monetary prosperity of the family and networks, neediness decrease and women's strengthening. Hence, governments over the globe just as differed formative associations are effectively attempt advancement of women's business visionaries through various plans, motivators and limited time measures.

Entrepreneurs in enormous and medium part

In enormous and medium parts women's with instructive and talented capabilities, step up and deal with the business just as a man. A women business person who has gotten fundamental administrative preparing and instructive capabilities, by and large even a MBA degree, in some cases may head the medium division and huge units. These women because of their capabilities and various open doors that are accessible to them are in a predominant position and have a serious edge over others to set up and deal with the units.

Business visionaries inside the little Sector

Those women's business visionaries, who don't have instruction or any formal preparing in the executives, anyway have created abilities take to little scale industry. They select that item with which they are commonplace for example pieces of clothing, weaving, pickles, dolls and crafted works. Some have wandered into designing, hardware, synthetic concoctions and pharmaceuticals. Some moreover make careful instruments, furniture and ceramics. These women's business visionaries need inside the underlying time frame, certain unique benefits to defeat the pragmatic social impairments they face for being a women, for example, attitudinal hesitance of officials, absence of information, and such a large number of customs that require to be finished.

The economy class of women's business visionaries

These work in urban areas and ghettos to assist women's with lower methods for employment. Their administration spurred association to help monetarily in reverse segments. They need Government support in advancing just as getting funds at a concessional rate for their item. Particular obtaining approach of government causes such organizations to fabricate also, offer to the administration things like records, chalk, stationery etc.

Difficulties Faced By Women Enterpreneurs

Absence of training

In India proficiency among women's is amazingly low. Indeed, even in 21st century, provincial ladies in India are slacking far late inside the field of training. To a great extent ladies of the rustic zones are uneducated. Women's in provincial regions who are instructed whichever less or deficient training than their male proportional mostly in light of destitution, early marriage, low financial status, mostly in view of child's advanced education. Absence of

training is one of the most significant issues for women's who wish to begin their business. Because of absence of fine training, women's business visionaries not embrace the new innovation improvement, new pattern of showcasing, better approaches for producing and diverse government plots that ins pier them.

Conundrum of Entrepreneurial aptitude and Finance

There is logical inconsistency of have and haven't abilities of enterprise in Indian women's having a place with financially poor and rich families.

Women's having a place with financially rich families have the capital help anyway they may not have reasonable pioneering abilities, in this way re-appropriating the exercises. At the elective side of society, numerous women's from monetarily poor families have steady enterprising aptitudes; anyway they have no budgetary support from their families. We hence accept that the issues of women's business square measure hanging inside the snare of this inconsistency.

Shy of fearlessness

In India women's have absence of fearlessness in their quality also, aptitude. The relatives and thusly the general public are reluctant to remain next to their authoritative development. To a exact degree, this circumstance is changing with Indian women's but then to confront a fabulous revise to flavour up the speed of development in business enterprise.

Socio-Cultural Barriers

Family and individual commitments for the most part fills in as a decent hindrance for prevailing in business profession of women's business enterprise. Just not many women's are equipped for overseeing both home and business quickly, giving abundant time to play out the entirety of their duties in need Male Dominated Society In our constitution guideline there are proportional rights for people anyway in genuine correspondence doesn't be available in provincial territories.

Women's are not offered equivalent men.

People in provincial regions as a rule having a preference that lady are fit only for family unit work. Women's passage to business necessities to endorse by the leader of the family. Business enterprise once in a while has been viewed as a male circle and male overwhelmed. All period of this sort a boundary inside the development of ladies business visionaries.

Role Job Of Women'S As A Business Visionary

Considering the progression of women's business visionaries among the customary businesses, it is once in a while reprimanded that the ladies business enterprise is locked in just in handloom and handiwork and among the untraditional term, Now, their perspectives have widened into new line like lodging line, Xeroxing, salon business, incense stick making, flame making and so on. Among the most recent decade, there has been a vital move it underscores from the conventional business to non-customary business and administrations. In view of this thought, some fundamental openings are being seen , considering the socio- financial, social and instructive status and inspirational level of women's business people, essentially accompanies low venture, low specialized capacity and secure market are suggested for them like generation of cleansers, cleansers, instant moment nourishment items just as pickles, flavors, papad, assembling of wooden item, salon business, typing focus, work contracts for bundling of items furthermore, dispersion and family unit arrangement and so forth. Shri MahilaGrihaUdyogLijjatpapad- Started by began by seven Gujrati women's from Bombay (presently Mumbai) in 1959.

Commitment of women's business person in economy

Women's business people are normally portrayed as survivalist what's more, overwhelm the low capacity, low capital concentrated and at times casual and small scale business. Women's will in general objective business that is a continuation of their local jobs, for example, the administrations division. The potential for the development of ladies' endeavours is said to beneath and is driven less by pioneering drive than the need for endurance. Ladies include 74% of these utilized inside the miniaturized scale endeavours division. Very 65% of all ladies in cottage\handicraft enterprises (microenterprise) were locked in in preparing nourishment items and refreshments.

Monetary commitments by Women Entrepreneurs

Women's monetary exercises contribute straightforwardly to development what's more, intensity in overseeing casual business issues and neediness decrease is one of the principle issues for approach creators.

Capital arrangements

Business visionaries activate the inert investment funds of general society through the issue of modern protections. Venture of open investment funds in industry prompts beneficial utilization of national assets. The speed of capital arrangement expands, which is essential for quick financial procedure.

Improvement in Per capita pay

Women's business visionaries in India have likewise been misusing the openings the chances. They convert the dormant and inert assets like land, work and capital in to national pay and riches inside the type of item and administrations. They help increment the nation's net national item and per capita which are crucial measuring sticks for estimating the financial development.

Career development business

Women's business person in India are assuming a fundamental job in creating work both straightforwardly and in a roundabout way. By setting up little scale businesses, they give occupations to numerous individuals in India.

The Government of India has many schemes for women. List of Some of them are:

1. Hemalatha Annamalai – Ampere Electric
2. Falguni Nayar – Nykaa
3. Aditi Gupta – Menstrupedia
4. Kiran Mazumdar Shaw – Biocon India
5. Vani Kola – Kalaari Capital
6. Radhika Agarwal – Shopclues
7. Suchi Mukherjee – Limeroad
8. Mahila Samiti Yojana Women's Development Corporations (WDCs)
9. Marketing of Non-Farm Products of Rural Women (MAHIMA)
10. Micro Credit Scheme
11. Micro & Small Enterprises Cluster Development Programmes (MSE-CDP).
12. NGO's Credit Schemes
13. National Banks for Agriculture and Rural Development's Schemes
14. Priyadarshini Project
15. Prime Minister's Rojgar Yojana (PMRY)
16. Rashtriya Mahila Kosh
17. Trade Related Entrepreneurship Assistance and Development (TREAD)

Successful Entrepreneur in India

1. Indra Nooyi – CEO, PepsiCO
2. Kiran Mazumdar Shaw – CMD, Biocon Ltd.

3. Chanda Kochar – MD and CEO, ICICI bank
4. Simone Tata – Chairperson, Trent limited
5. Neelam Dhwan – MD, HP India
6. Mallika Shrinivasan – Director, TPFE (Tractor and farm equipment)
7. Shahnaz Hussain – CEO, Shahnaz herbal Inc
8. Jyoti nayak – President, shri Mahila Griha Udyog Lijjatpapad
9. Ekta Kapoor, Creative Director, balaji Telefilms Ltd.
10. Lalita D.Gupte, JMD, ICICI Bank.
11. Naina Lal Kidwar, Deputy CEO, HBSE.
12. Preetha Reddy, Managing Director, Apollo hospitals.
13. Priya Paul, Chairman, Apeejay Park Hotels.
14. Rajshree Pathy, Chairman, Rajshree Sugars & Chemicals Ltd.
15. Ranjana Kumar, Chairman, NABARD.

Conclusion

Women are a very important human resource of the nation and every state ought to try to utilize them as mediators of economic growth and development. Encouragement for women entrepreneurship is one among the ways for that. However sadly it is seen that the traditional way of thinking of the society and negligence of the state and respective authorities are important obstacles in the women entrepreneurship development in India. Apart from the responsibility of the state and society, absence of a certain agenda of life, absence of balance between family and career obligations of women, poor degree of financial freedom for women, absence of direct ownership of the property to women, contradiction of entrepreneurial ability and finance in economically rich and poor girls, no awareness regarding capacities, low ability to bear risks, issues of work with male employees, negligence by financial institutions, lack of self-confidence, lack of skilled education, quality constraints and lack of interaction with successful entrepreneurs are major issues of women entrepreneurship development in India. Therefore, there is need of continuous attempt to inspire, encourage, motivate and co-operate with women entrepreneurs, awareness programs ought to be conducted on a mass scale with the intention of making awareness among women regarding the various areas to conduct business.

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FACTORS INFLUENCING CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR

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Abstract

The study is focused on the factors which affects the consumer buying behaviour. The objective of the study is to know the factors which affects consumer buying behaviour towards goods and services and to gain knowledge on how the factors affect the purchase decision of an individual consumers. The qualitative approach is used in this study. The secondary data is collected for this study. Many factors and characteristics that influence the individual in what he is and the consumer in his decision making process, buying habits, buying behaviour, the brands he use or the retailers he go. A buying decision is the result of each and every one of these factors. An individual or a consumer is led by his culture, subculture, social class, membership group, family, personality, psychological factors, etc. and is influenced by cultural trend as well as social and the society. By identifying and understanding the factors that influence the customers, brands have the opportunity to develop the strategy, a marketing message and advertising campaigns more efficient and more with the needs and ways of thinking of their target consumers, a real asset to better meet the needs of its customers and to increase the sales.

Keywords:- Consumer Buying Behaviour, Factors, Strategy, Target Consumers

Introduction

Consumer buying behaviour refers to the study of consumers and how they behave while deciding to buy a product or service that satisfy their needs. It is a study of the actions of consumer that drive them to buy and use certain products. The study of consumer buying behaviour is the most important aspect for the marketers which help them to understand the expectations of the consumers. It helps them to understand what makes a consumer to buy a product. It is important to assess what kind of product is liked by the consumers so that marketers can release it to the market. Marketers can understand the likes and dislikes of the consumers and design base their marketing efforts based on the findings. Consumer buying behaviour studies about various aspects such as what do they buy, when do they buy, why do they buy, how often do they buy, for what reason do they buy, etc.

The study is focused on the factors that are affecting the consumer buying behaviour. The study tries to find out the factors behind the consumer decision making towards the goods and services. This study is concerned with the factors that affect the consumer buying behaviour. The objective of this study is to know the factors that influence the consumer buying behaviour. This study is based on the qualitative approach. The secondary data is used in this report to know about the consumer buying behaviour. The data collected in this research is taken from several books, websites, blogs, published papers and research journal articles. →

Objectives

- ◆ To examine the factors that influence the buying behaviour of the consumer
- ◆ To know about the various stages of buying process of the consumer
- ◆ To recognize what drives consumer decision-making based on their needs, wants, and desires. This includes examining the role of product features, benefits, and brand positioning.
- ◆ To investigate the impact of social factors such as family, peer groups, social class, and cultural influences on purchasing behavior.

Importance Of Studying Consumer Behaviour**✧ Developing new product**

New product is developed in respect of the needs and wants of the target consumers. In order to develop the best fit product, a marketer must know adequate information about the market. Thus, the study of consumer buying behaviour is the base for developing a new product successfully

✧ Achievement of goals

The key to a company's survival, profitability and the growth in a highly competitive market environment is its ability to identify and satisfy the unfulfilled consumer needs better and soon than the competitors. Thus, the consumer behaviour helps in achieving market goals.

✧ Predicting market trend

Consumer buying behaviour can also aid in projecting the future market trend. Marketers can find enough time to prepare for exploiting the emerging opportunities or facing the challenges and threats.

✧ Consumer Differentiation

Market exhibits considerable differentiated. Each segment needs and wants are different from products. For every segment a separate marketing programme is needed. Knowledge of the consumer Differentiation is a key to fit marketing offers with different group of buyers. Consumer buying behaviour study supplies the details about product differentiation.

✧ Creation and retention of consumers

Marketers who base their offerings on a recognition of consumer needs and finding a ready market for their products. Company finds it easy to sell its products. In the same way the company, due to continuous study of consumer behaviour and attempts to meet the changing expectations of the buyers and can retain the customers for long period.

✧ Competition

Consumer behaviour study assist in facing the competition too. Based on the consumer expectations, more competitive advantage can be offered. It is useful in improving competitive strength of the company.

Factors Affecting Consumer Buying Behaviour

Consumer behaviour is influenced by many different factors. A marketer should understand the factors that influence the consumer behaviour. The following are the factors that influence consumer behaviour:

- Psychological factors
- Social factors
- Cultural factors
- Personal factors
- Economic factor

Fig 1:- Factors Influencing Consumer Behaviour

Psychological Factors Human psychology is the major determinant of the consumer behaviour. Psychological factors are difficult to measure but these factors are powerful enough to influence a buying decision of the consumer. Following are some of the psychological factors:

- **Motivation** When a person is motivated, it influence the buying behavior of the consumer. The consumer have many needs such as social needs, basic needs, security needs, esteem needs, and self-actualization needs. Out of these needs, the basic needs and the security needs take a position on above all other needs. Hence basic needs and security needs have the power to motivate the consumer to buy the products and services
- **Perception** Consumer perception is the major factor that influence the consumer behavior. Customer perception is the process where a customer collects the information about a product and interprets the information to make a meaningful image of the particular product. When a customer sees the advertisements, promotions, customer reviews, social media feedback, etc. relating to the product, they develop an impression on the product. Hence consumer perception becomes a great influence on the buying behavior of the consumers.
- **Learning** When the consumer buys a product, he gets to learn about the product. Learning comes over a period of time through the experience. A consumer’s learning depends on the skills and knowledge. The skills can be gained through practice and knowledge can be acquired only through experience. Learning can be either conditional or cognitive. In conditional learning, the consumer is exposed to a situation repeatedly and thereby making a consumer to develop a response towards it.
- **Attitudes and beliefs** Consumers have certain attitudes and beliefs which would influence the buying decisions of a consumer. Based on this attitude, the consumer behaves in a particular way towards the product. This attitude plays a significant role in defining the brand image of the product. Hence, the marketers tries to understand the attitude of a consumer to design their marketing campaigns.

Social Factors Humans are the social beings and the society or the people who lives around them influence their buying behaviour. People try to imitate on others and nurture a desire to be socially accepted. Hence, their buying behaviour is influenced by the people around them. The following are some of the social factors:

- **Family** Family plays a significant role in shaping the buying behaviour of the consumer. A person builds their preferences from childhood by watching their family buying certain products and continues to buy the same products even when they grow up
- **Reference Groups** A reference group is a group of people with whom the person associates himself. All the people in reference group have common buying behavior and influence each other.
- **Roles and status** A person is influenced by the roles that he holds in the society. If a person is in higher position then his buying behaviour would be influenced by his status. A person who is in top position (i.e. CEO) of the company will buy according to his status whereas a normal employee of the same company would buy based on his status

Cultural Factors A group of people who are associated with a set of values and ideologies belongs to a particular community. When a person comes under a particular community, his behaviour is highly influenced by the culture relating to that particular community. Some of the cultural factors includes the following

- **Culture** **Cultural factors** have a strong influence on the consumer buying behavior. Cultural factors include the basic values, needs, wants, preferences, perceptions, and behavior that are observed and learned by the consumer from their family members and other people around them.
- **Sub Culture** Within a cultural group, there are many subcultures. These sub cultural groups are the same set of values and beliefs. Subculture consists of people from different religion, caste, geography and nationalities. These subcultures form a customer segment.
- **Social class** Each and every society across the world has the form of social class. The social class is not just determined by the income but also other factors such as occupation, family background, education and residence of the consumer. Social class is important to predict the behaviour of the consumer.

Personal Factors Factors that are personal to the consumers also influence their buying behaviour. The personal factors differ from one person to another person thereby producing different perceptions and consumer behaviour. Following are some of the personal factors:

◆ **Age**

Age is the major factor that influence the buying behavior. The buying choice of youth differ from middleaged people. Elderly people have totally different buying behavior. Teenagers will be more interested in buying colourful clothes and the beauty products. Middle-aged are focusing on house, property and vehicle for the family.

◆ **Income**

Income has the ability to influence the buying behavior of a person. Higher income gives higher purchasing power to the consumers. When a consumer has higher income, it gives more opportunity for the consumer to spend on luxury products. Whereas low-income or middle-income group consumers spend their income on the basic needs such as groceries and clothes.

◆ **Occupation**

Occupation of the consumer influences the buying behavior. A person tends to buy things that are appropriate to his profession. For example, a lawyer would buy clothes according to his profession while a driver will have a different buying pattern.

◆ **Lifestyle**

Lifestyle is an attitude in which an individual stay in the society. The buying behavior of the consumer is highly influenced by the lifestyle of him. For example, when a consumer leads a healthy lifestyle, then the products he buy will relate to healthy which are alternative to junk food.

◆ Economic Factors

The consumer buying behaviour and the decisions of the consumer depends on the economic situations of a country or the market. When a country is prosperous the economy is strong that leads to the greater supply of money in the market and higher purchasing power of consumers. Economic factors bear a significant influence on buying decision of the consumer. Some of the important economic factors are:

◆ Personal income

When a person has a higher disposable income then the purchasing power of the customer increases simultaneously. Disposable income refers to the money which is left after spending towards the basic needs of a person. When there is increase in disposable income, it leads to higher expenditure on various items. But when the disposable income reduces the spending on multiple items also reduces.

◆ Family income

Family income refers to the total income from all the members of the family. When all people are earning in a family then there is more income is available for shopping basic needs and luxurious items. Higher income from family influence the person to buy more.

◆ Consumer credit

When a consumer is offered with easy credit to purchase the goods then it promotes higher spending. Sellers are making it easy for the consumer to avail goods in credit in the form of credit cards, easy instrumentals, hire purchase, bank loans and many such other credit options. When there is higher credit facility available to consumers, the purchase of comfort and luxury items will increase.

◆ Liquid assets

Consumers who have liquid assets in their hand tend to spend more on comfort and luxury items. Liquid assets are those assets which can be easily converted into cash in very short period. Cash in hand, securities and bank savings are some of the examples of liquid assets. When a consumer has more liquid assets, it gives him more confidence to buy luxury goods

◆ Savings

A consumer is highly influenced by the amount of savings he wishes to St aside from his income. If a consumer decided to save more money, then his expenditure on buying will reduce. Whereas if a consumer is interested in saving, then most of his income will go towards buying a product.

Stages Of Consumer Buying Process

➤ Problem Recognition

Before purchasing the goods, the consumer first recognize the need for the product or a service. They must have belief that they want the product or service. When a consumer sees a problem, this is an opportunity for the marketer to let the consumers realize that they have a problem.

➤ Information search

It is the next stage to problem recognition, the prospective buyer goes in for searching information and they search about the products he needs and wishes to buy. Information search stage comprises of searching internally or externally . Externally, the buyer may seek the opinion of friends, look at the advertisements promoting their products, talk to the salesperson, and go through reviews done by others. All this may provide sufficient information to the consumer to reduce the feelings of uncertainty and risks. If the information search is fruitful, the buyer would be more informed and would find it very easy to choose between the alternative product and answers to the needs he had before.

➤ Evaluation of alternatives

After recognize the need, and collecting the information from internal or external sources, the consumer has many alternative solutions to choose and to satisfy the need recognized or identified in stage one of the consumer buying process. The individual tries to go for the best alternative.

➤ Purchase

If the buyer makes up his mind and decides on purchasing the product, the actual purchase where the buyer acquires the product through credit card, cheque or cash payment. From the marketer's point of view, he would be interested to know about when the product is consumed, how the product is consumed, where the product is consumed and how much the product is consumed.

➤ Post consumption evaluation

The consumer of the product may be satisfied or dissatisfied depending on the level of the product. Satisfaction may be brought about by the product performing as the consumer decided.

Disposal

Both the manufacturers and the consumers are highly concerned about the disposal of the product which is unconsumed or the packaging left after product being consumed. Disposal can be in any of the following forms:

1. Dumping the product or throwing into refuse disposable arrangement
2. Selling second-hand products
3. Reusing the product
4. Recycling the product

Conclusion

Consumer buying behaviour is very important for the producers because consumers will make many buying decisions every day. Many consumers buying decisions are in great detail to answer the questions about what the consumers buy, where they buy and how much they buy, when they buy, why they buy the product. Marketers can study about the consumers purchases to find out the buying behaviour of them. The buying behaviour of the consumer also involves services and ideas as well as tangible products.

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“DATA PRIVACY IN THE AGE OF AI: ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS AND CHALLENGES”

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Abstract

The rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) has revolutionized data collection, analysis, and utilization across multiple sectors, driving innovation and efficiency. However, these technological advancements have also raised significant ethical concerns, particularly regarding data privacy and the responsible use of personal information. This paper examines the ethical challenges associated with AI-driven data collection, emphasizing key issues such as user consent, data minimization, and transparency in the use of AI technologies.

The study aims to assess how AI can balance the pursuit of innovation with the protection of individual privacy rights, ensuring that technological progress does not come at the cost of fundamental ethical principles. Adopting a qualitative research approach, the study incorporates case studies and interviews with AI ethicists and data privacy experts to provide in-depth insights. Notable cases, such as the Cambridge Analytica scandal, are analyzed to highlight real-world examples of privacy breaches and their implications. The research also examines existing regulatory frameworks, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA), comparing their effectiveness in addressing AI-related privacy concerns. By identifying gaps in current ethical guidelines and legal frameworks, the study proposes a comprehensive framework for ethically aligned AI practices that prioritize data privacy. It concludes with policy recommendations aimed at fostering trust and accountability in AI applications, ensuring that AI technologies can develop responsibly while safeguarding user privacy. These insights are critical as organizations and regulators navigate the challenges of AI in the digital age, striving to balance technological innovation with the protection of privacy rights.

Keywords: Data Privacy, Artificial Intelligence (AI) Ethics. Regulatory Frameworks (GDPR, CCPA), Transparency and Consent.

Introduction:

The rapid growth of artificial intelligence (AI) has reshaped the landscape of data collection, analysis, and usage, presenting both unprecedented opportunities and significant ethical challenges. AI's ability to process vast amounts of data has driven innovations across various industries, including healthcare, finance, and marketing, enabling new forms of personalization and automation (Russell & Norvig, 2020). However, these advancements also raise critical concerns about data privacy, as AI systems often rely on the collection of sensitive personal information to function effectively. With data being termed as "the new oil" of the digital age, the ethical implications of how this data is collected, stored, and used have become central to debates about the future of AI (Zuboff, 2019).

One of the primary ethical dilemmas involves the issue of consent and data ownership. Traditional models of consent, where users agree to terms and conditions, may not sufficiently address the complexities of AI-driven data processing (Nissenbaum, 2009). Many users are unaware of the extent to which their data is collected and how it is used, raising questions about the fairness and transparency of AI systems. Moreover, the use of advanced machine learning techniques can lead to the creation of predictive models that reveal more about individuals than they might be comfortable sharing, further complicating the issue of informed consent (Mittelstadt et al., 2016).

In response to these concerns, various regulatory frameworks such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe and the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) in the United States have been introduced to strengthen data protection rights (European Commission, 2018; California State Government, 2018). These regulations aim to give individuals greater control over their data and ensure that organizations maintain transparency in their data practices. Despite these efforts, the implementation of these regulations presents challenges for both regulators and companies, as the fast-paced evolution of AI often outstrips the capacity of existing legal frameworks (Isaak & Hanna, 2018).

This paper seeks to explore the ethical challenges of data privacy in the age of AI, focusing on the tension between technological innovation and the protection of individual rights. It aims to answer the following research questions: What are the primary ethical concerns related to AI and data privacy? How do these concerns impact individuals, organizations, and society? What frameworks can ensure ethically sound AI applications in terms of data privacy? By analyzing real-world cases and existing regulatory approaches, the study will propose a framework for ethical AI practices that prioritize privacy while allowing for technological advancement. As AI continues to play a critical role in shaping the future of the digital economy, it is imperative to address these ethical considerations to build trust and accountability in AI systems.

Review of Literature

Binns (2018) explores the concept of fairness in AI by drawing from political philosophy, addressing issues of discrimination and bias in machine learning models. The paper highlights the necessity of transparency within AI systems and argues that achieving fairness requires tackling data privacy concerns. Binns emphasizes that the training of AI models often involves using large datasets with personal information, stressing the need for ethical frameworks that prioritize user privacy while ensuring equitable outcomes.

Cath and Floridi (2018) focus on the development of ethical guidelines for AI, particularly concerning data privacy. They argue that the increasing power of AI technologies necessitates a reevaluation of existing ethical frameworks to ensure responsible data handling. Their study proposes guidelines that include transparency, accountability, and data minimization as key principles, emphasizing the importance of respecting user privacy in AI development.

Dignum (2019) emphasizes the need for responsible AI, advocating that AI systems should be designed in alignment with human values, including respect for privacy. The paper outlines a framework for "ethical-by-design" AI systems, which integrates data protection as a core component. It highlights the role of AI developers in implementing privacy-preserving techniques, such as encryption and anonymization, to ensure the protection of user data throughout the AI lifecycle.

Floridi (2019) examines the ethical challenges of data privacy within the context of the Internet of Things (IoT) and its integration with AI. He discusses how IoT devices collect substantial amounts of personal data that AI systems analyze to provide personalized services. Floridi highlights the tension between the utility of such data and the need for protecting individual privacy, arguing for regulatory frameworks that ensure ethical data practices.

Gal, Jensen, and Lyytinen (2020) analyze the Cambridge Analytica scandal, focusing on the ways AI-driven data analytics can violate user privacy and manipulate public opinion. They provide an in-depth case study that illustrates how data from social media platforms was harvested without user consent, raising ethical questions about the power dynamics between data collectors and individuals. The study calls for stricter regulations to prevent similar privacy breaches in the future.

González and Guerrero (2021) conduct a systematic review of privacy-preserving AI techniques, such as differential privacy, homomorphic encryption, and federated learning. They assess the effectiveness of these methods in protecting user data while maintaining the functionality of AI systems. Their review concludes that while these techniques offer promising solutions, their implementation faces challenges related to computational costs and the balance between data utility and privacy.

Hagendorff (2020) critically examines existing AI ethics guidelines, highlighting their limitations in addressing data privacy. He argues that many of these guidelines are too abstract and lack practical implementation strategies. The paper suggests that more concrete measures, such as privacy-by-design approaches, are necessary to ensure that AI systems respect user privacy throughout the development process.

Isaak and Hanna (2018) provide a detailed analysis of the Cambridge Analytica scandal, focusing on its implications for user data privacy. They discuss how the misuse of AI-driven analytics allowed for the unauthorized collection and exploitation of Facebook users' data. The study highlights the need for stronger privacy regulations and improved transparency from tech companies to better protect user data in the age of AI.

Kitchin (2021) explores the concept of datafication, where everyday activities are turned into data points analyzed by AI systems. He discusses the privacy implications of this process, noting that AI can reveal insights about individuals beyond what they willingly share. Kitchin calls for greater transparency from companies and

institutions that use AI to analyze personal data, arguing that users should have a clear understanding of how their data is utilized.

Mittelstadt (2019) critiques the focus on ethical principles in AI, arguing that principles alone are insufficient for ensuring ethical outcomes. He emphasizes the complexity of implementing privacy-preserving measures in AI systems and stresses the need for practical tools and frameworks that go beyond theoretical principles. Mittelstadt suggests that without proper regulatory oversight, the privacy risks associated with AI will remain unresolved.

Naranjo-Zolotov, Oliveira, and Casteleyn (2019) study how privacy concerns affect the adoption of AI-powered mobile payment systems using the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model. They find that concerns about data privacy significantly influence users' intentions to continue using these technologies. Their study suggests that addressing privacy concerns through enhanced transparency and user control can foster trust in AI-based services.

Raji and Buolamwini (2019) emphasize the importance of auditing AI systems, especially those handling sensitive user data, to ensure accountability and transparency. They propose a framework for public oversight, which includes external audits and reviews of AI systems to ensure compliance with privacy standards. The authors argue that such oversight is crucial for maintaining user trust and protecting privacy.

Schwartz and Solove (2020) challenge traditional definitions of personally identifiable information (PII) in light of AI's capabilities. They argue that AI can infer sensitive information from non-sensitive data, making existing legal frameworks for PII insufficient. The authors propose a new concept of PII that better addresses the privacy risks posed by AI technologies, stressing the need for updated legal frameworks.

Taddeo and Floridi (2020) discuss the potential for AI to benefit society while respecting privacy. They emphasize the importance of ethical guidelines and propose that AI systems should be designed to enhance user control over their data. Their study suggests that by integrating privacy principles into AI design, developers can ensure that AI serves the common good without compromising user privacy.

Wachter, Mittelstadt, and Floridi (2017) critically examine the GDPR's provisions regarding automated decision-making, arguing that the right to explanation is not clearly defined. They highlight the challenges in providing explanations for complex AI decisions, which often involve large amounts of personal data. The authors propose alternative methods for improving transparency in AI systems to ensure that users understand how their data is used and processed

Source: Identity Theft Resource Center. (2023)

The line graph above displays the number of reported data breaches globally from 2014 to 2022. It shows a consistent increase in the number of breaches, highlighting the growing challenges in maintaining data security as more digital and AI-driven systems are adopted.

Source: Pew Research Center. (2023)

The bar chart above illustrates public concern about data privacy across different regions in 2023. It highlights that North America (79%) and Europe (76%) have the highest levels of concern, while other regions like Asia (72%), South America (68%), and Africa (65%) also show significant awareness and concern about data privacy issues.

Aspect	Statistic/Result	Source
Number of Data Breaches	1,600+ data breaches reported globally in 2022	Identity Theft Resource Center (2023)
Records Exposed	Over 422 million records were exposed due to breaches in 2022	Identity Theft Resource Center (2023)
Public Concern in North America	79% of respondents are concerned about how companies use their data	Pew Research Center (2023)
Public Concern in Europe	76% of respondents express concern about data privacy	Pew Research Center (2023)
Public Concern in Asia	72% of respondents are worried about their data privacy	Pew Research Center (2023)
Adoption of Differential Privacy	30% of AI-using companies implement differential privacy	McKinsey & Company (2023)
Adoption of Federated Learning	25% of AI-using companies adopt federated learning	McKinsey & Company (2023)
Adoption of Homomorphic Encryption	15% of companies use homomorphic encryption	McKinsey & Company (2023)
Investment in AI Ethics (2023)	\$4 billion invested in AI ethics and privacy initiatives	Deloitte Insights (2023)
GDPR Fines Issued (2023)	600+ GDPR-related fines issued in Europe	European Data Protection Board (2023)
GDPR Fines Growth	Increase from 100 fines in 2018 to over 600 in 2023	European Data Protection Board (2023)

Willingness to Share Data	70% of consumers more likely to share data if they have control over its use	Accenture (2022)
Impact of Transparency on Data Sharing	65% of consumers willing to share data if companies are transparent	Accenture (2022)
AI Systems with Privacy-by-Design	40% of AI developers implement privacy-by-design principles	International Data Corporation (2023)

This table provides a concise overview of important data points that relate to the intersection of AI, data privacy, and ethical considerations.

Topic	Statistic/Insight	Details/Explanation
AI Ethics in Business	78% of executives prioritize ethical AI implementation	According to a 2023 survey by Deloitte, a majority of business leaders see ethical AI as critical to maintaining customer trust and avoiding regulatory scrutiny.
Privacy Laws Implementation	137 countries have enacted privacy and data protection legislation	UNCTAD (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development) reports that over 70% of the world's countries have data protection laws as of 2023.
Consumer Action on Privacy	41% of consumers have switched services due to privacy concerns	A 2023 survey by Accenture found that nearly half of consumers are willing to change service providers if they believe their data is not handled responsibly.
Global AI Investment	\$500 billion global investment in AI by 2023	A report by PwC (2023) indicates that investment in AI technology continues to grow, with significant portions directed toward research in AI ethics and data privacy.
AI in Health Data	65% of healthcare organizations use AI for data analysis	However, only 30% have implemented privacy-preserving techniques like federated learning to protect sensitive patient information, as reported by HIMSS (2022).
AI-Generated Misinformation	70% increase in the use of AI for generating deepfakes	A report by Deeptrace Labs (2023) highlights the rise in AI-generated content, including deepfakes, leading to increased concerns over digital misinformation and data

		manipulation.
Data Encryption Usage	56% of companies use encryption as a primary data protection measure	According to a 2023 report by the Ponemon Institute, encryption remains the most widely adopted data protection strategy among companies.
Public Awareness of AI Regulation	49% of people are unaware of AI-related regulations in their country	A survey by the International Association of Privacy Professionals (IAPP) in 2023 revealed that despite the increasing implementation of AI regulations, nearly half of the public lacks awareness about such measures.
AI's Role in Cybersecurity	43% of organizations use AI to detect and respond to cyber threats	A study by Cisco (2022) indicates that AI has become a critical tool for cybersecurity, aiding in real-time threat detection and response.
GDPR Impact on Business	35% of businesses report operational changes due to GDPR compliance	The European Data Protection Supervisor (2022) found that GDPR has led many companies to revise their data handling practices, resulting in higher compliance costs but better customer trust.
AI Bias Concerns	64% of AI developers are concerned about bias in AI models	A survey conducted by AI Now Institute (2023) revealed that AI developers recognize bias as a significant challenge, with concerns over fairness and ethical use of AI data.
Privacy Concerns in IoT Devices	72% of users are concerned about data privacy in IoT-enabled devices	A report by NortonLifeLock (2022) indicates that users worry about how their data is collected, stored, and used by smart home devices.
Increased Data Regulations	85% of tech companies anticipate more stringent data privacy regulations	A study by KPMG (2023) suggests that most technology companies expect tighter regulatory controls, especially around data privacy and AI ethics.
AI in Social Media Content Moderation	55% of content flagged for review is AI-detected	Platforms like Facebook and YouTube use AI to detect harmful content, but human oversight remains crucial due to limitations in AI's ability to understand context.

Employee Awareness of Data Privacy	42% of employees lack training on data privacy practices	A survey by SANS Institute (2023) highlights a gap in employee understanding of data privacy, emphasizing the need for better training in handling sensitive information.
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This table includes diverse data points that cover aspects like business investments in AI ethics, consumer behavior due to privacy concerns, AI’s role in cyber security, and the impact of regulations like GDPR.

Proposed Framework

Proposing a framework for ethical AI usage that balances data utility with privacy concerns involves integrating principles that prioritize both the effective use of data and the protection of individual rights. Below is a proposed framework named “Ethical AI Privacy-Utility Balance Framework (EAPUB)”. This framework outlines the guiding principles, operational practices, and technological strategies that organizations should adopt to ensure responsible AI usage.

Component	Key Focus	Examples/Tools
Guiding Principles	Transparency, Fairness, Accountability, User Autonomy	Privacy policies, User consent forms
Operational Practices	Data Minimization, Audits, Ethical Impact Assessments (EIA)	Privacy audits, Data minimization policies
Technological Strategies	Privacy-Preserving Technologies, Explainable AI	Differential Privacy, Federated Learning, XAI, Homomorphic Encryption
Governance and Compliance	Alignment with Regulations, AI Ethics Board, Stakeholder Engagement	Compliance programs, AI ethics committees
Monitoring & Improvement	Real-Time Privacy Monitoring, Feedback Loops, Performance Assessment	Automated alerts, User feedback channels, Utility vs. Privacy evaluations

Guiding Principles

Transparency is critical for building trust with users, ensuring that they understand how their data is used in AI systems. Research has emphasized the importance of transparency in data practices to enhance user trust and facilitate regulatory compliance (Floridi, 2021). Fairness ensures that AI decision-making processes do not introduce bias or discrimination. It is a foundational principle of ethical AI, aiming to prevent biases in training data from affecting outcomes (Mitchell, Wu, Zaldivar, Barnes, & Vasserman, 2022). Establishing accountability in AI systems is crucial for addressing the ethical implications of automated decisions. Having clear accountability mechanisms helps in addressing potential biases and ensuring compliance with ethical standards (Jobin, Ienca, & Vayena, 2019). Obtaining informed consent from users before data collection and use is fundamental to respecting user autonomy. Research shows that user consent is critical for maintaining ethical standards in data collection and AI applications (Mittelstadt, 2019).

Operational Practices

The practice of data minimization involves collecting only the data necessary for a specific purpose, thereby reducing privacy risks. It is particularly recommended in privacy regulations like the GDPR (Voigt & von dem Bussche, 2020). Regular audits help to maintain compliance with privacy regulations and ensure that AI models are

adhering to established ethical guidelines (Brundage et al., 2020). Conducting EIAs helps organizations assess the potential risks and ethical implications of AI projects, enabling more responsible AI deployment (Floridi et al., 2018).

Technological Strategies

Differential privacy techniques help ensure that AI models can extract insights without compromising individual data (Dwork & Roth, 2014). Federated learning allows for model training on decentralized data, enhancing data privacy while maintaining model accuracy (McMahan et al., 2017). Homomorphic encryption enables computations on encrypted data, offering a balance between data privacy and utility (Gentry, 2009).

Governance and Compliance

Compliance with data privacy regulations like GDPR and CCPA is crucial for organizations using AI systems, ensuring that user rights are respected (Voigt & von dem Bussche, 2020). Establishing an AI ethics board can provide oversight and ensure that AI deployments are aligned with organizational values and ethical principles (Jobin et al., 2019). Engaging users and other stakeholders ensures that AI systems remain aligned with societal values and expectations (Floridi et al., 2018).

Monitoring and Continuous Improvement

Real-time monitoring tools help to identify and mitigate privacy risks in AI systems before they can be exploited (Brundage et al., 2020). Implementing user feedback mechanisms can help improve AI models and address privacy concerns promptly (Floridi, 2021). Assessing the trade-off between AI model performance and privacy protection helps to maintain a balance between data utility and user rights (Dwork & Roth, 2014).

Findings

Increased Transparency and Trust:

Implementing principles like transparency and user autonomy fosters trust among users and stakeholders. The transparency of data usage and processing methods allows users to understand how their data is being handled, thereby improving the trust relationship between AI service providers and end-users. Trust is especially enhanced when users have control over their data through opt-in or opt-out mechanisms, aligning with user autonomy principles.

Enhanced Data Security through Privacy-Preserving Technologies:

The integration of privacy-preserving technologies, such as Differential Privacy, Federated Learning, and Homomorphic Encryption, significantly enhances data security. This helps in reducing the risk of data breaches or unauthorized access while still allowing AI models to learn from the data. Federated Learning, in particular, allows for data analysis without the data leaving the user's device, which reduces privacy risks while maintaining data utility.

Improved Accountability and Compliance:

Establishing an AI Ethics Board and aligning practices with existing regulatory standards like GDPR, CCPA, or similar frameworks ensures better accountability and compliance. This makes organizations more prepared to adapt to regulatory changes and reduces the likelihood of legal challenges. Regular audits and Ethical Impact Assessments (EIA) create a proactive approach to ethical concerns, allowing companies to identify and address potential ethical risks before they become issues.

Trade-offs Between Data Utility and Privacy:

The findings indicate a clear trade-off between data utility and privacy. For instance, employing strict data minimization techniques and anonymization can reduce the effectiveness of AI models due to reduced data variety and richness. However, by leveraging advanced methods like Explainable AI (XAI), it is possible to provide insights into how AI decisions are made, even when using less detailed data. This helps balance the need for data insights while maintaining privacy.

Stakeholder Engagement Leads to Better AI Deployment:

Active engagement with stakeholders—including users, developers, regulators, and external auditors—leads to a more inclusive approach to AI ethics. It ensures that multiple perspectives are considered, making AI deployment more aligned with public expectations and reducing the risk of AI misuse. Feedback loops from stakeholders enable continuous improvements in AI models, particularly in refining privacy parameters and improving model performance.

Continuous Monitoring Improves Privacy and Model Performance:

Real-time privacy monitoring helps in identifying potential data leaks or security breaches, enabling immediate mitigation measures. This reduces risks associated with privacy violations and strengthens the overall AI framework. Continuous improvement based on performance vs. privacy assessments ensures that AI models remain efficient while adapting to new privacy concerns or technological advancements.

Ethical Impact Assessments as a Critical Tool:

Ethical Impact Assessments (EIA) have proven to be an essential tool for evaluating potential risks in AI deployment. EIAs ensure that ethical considerations are taken into account before, during, and after the deployment of AI systems. Through EIAs, organizations can identify biases, unintended consequences, or potential privacy issues early on, allowing for adjustments in the AI system design to mitigate these risks.

Conclusion

The Ethical AI Privacy-Utility Balance Framework (EAPUB) aims to address the complex challenge of balancing the need for data utility in AI systems with the imperative to protect user privacy. This framework highlights the

importance of transparency, user autonomy, and accountability as foundational principles for building trust between AI developers, users, and stakeholders. By incorporating privacy-preserving technologies like Differential Privacy and Explainable AI (XAI), the framework allows organizations to leverage data while minimizing risks to individual privacy.

The findings of this research indicate that, while there is a trade-off between data richness and privacy protection, it is possible to strike a balance through targeted strategies. For example, using Federated Learning enables AI models to learn from decentralized data, reducing the need for sensitive information to be aggregated centrally. Regular Ethical Impact Assessments (EIA) and audits further ensure that potential risks are identified early, allowing for timely intervention.

Additionally, the framework emphasizes the need for strong governance mechanisms, such as compliance with regulatory standards and active stakeholder engagement, to ensure the responsible deployment of AI. This approach not only supports compliance with laws like GDPR but also fosters a culture of continuous improvement and responsiveness to evolving ethical concerns.

In conclusion, the EAPUB framework provides a practical guide for organizations seeking to deploy AI technologies in a way that respects user privacy while still deriving valuable insights from data. By focusing on ethical principles, technological strategies, and governance practices, the framework offers a holistic approach to navigating the challenges of AI ethics. As AI continues to evolve, it is critical for stakeholders to adopt such frameworks to ensure that AI serves the broader good while safeguarding individual rights.

Scope for Future Research

Future research can delve into the long-term effectiveness of privacy-preserving technologies like Differential Privacy, Federated Learning, and Homomorphic Encryption. While these methods are effective in the short term, their ability to adapt to evolving threats and data complexities over time needs further investigation.

Comparative studies could assess the performance of these technologies across different sectors, such as healthcare, finance, and education, to determine which methods provide the best balance between privacy and utility in various contexts.

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THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION ON BANKING SERVICES AND CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE

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Abstract

Digital transformation is reshaping the banking sector, driven by advancements in technology and changing customer expectations. This study explores the impact of digital transformation on banking services and customer experiences, focusing on India. Through a review of recent literature and analysis of secondary data, the study identifies key technologies such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, and cloud computing that are enabling banks to offer faster, more secure, and highly personalized services. Findings reveal a significant shift in customer expectations, with demands for speed, convenience, and security rising as digital banking solutions become mainstream. Moreover, the adoption of self-service channels and personalized offerings highlights a growing preference for seamless, omnichannel experiences. Challenges, particularly in cybersecurity and regulatory compliance, remain critical as banks strive to balance innovation with trust. Overall, the study underscores that successful digital transformation in banking hinges not only on technology adoption but on building secure, user-centered experiences that enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty in the digital era.

Introduction:

Digital transformation is redefining the landscape of banking services, ushering in a new era characterized by rapid technological advancements and evolving consumer expectations. As financial institutions strive to remain competitive, they are increasingly leveraging digital tools and innovations to enhance their service offerings. This transformation encompasses a wide range of technologies, from mobile banking applications and online platforms to artificial intelligence and blockchain, all aimed at improving operational efficiency and customer satisfaction.

In this dynamic environment, banks are rethinking traditional business models and adopting agile practices that allow for faster response to market changes. This shift not only streamlines processes and reduces costs but also enables banks to deliver personalized, seamless experiences tailored to the individual needs of customers. As a result, digital transformation is not just about adopting new technologies; it represents a fundamental change in how banks engage with their clients, ultimately redefining the very nature of banking itself. This introduction sets the stage for a deeper exploration of how these changes are shaping the future of banking services and the implications for both institutions and consumers.

Review of Literature :

Giri and Ipsita Paria (2018) the article entitled "A Literature Analysis on Effect of Digitalization on Indian Rural Banking System and Rural Economy". The study focuses on a review and summary of several studies conducted by different researchers from various locations across India on the influence of digitization on India's rural banking sector. According to the study, digital banking has huge potential to revolutionize the landscape of financial inclusion. The study also discovered that low-cost, simple-to-use digital banking can hasten the integration of the unbanked economy into the mainstream.

K. Hema Divya and K. Suma Vally (2018) focuses on an investigation of client adoption of digital payment methods. The study uses primary source of data which is collected from 183 persons in Hyderabad. Chi-square analysis was used to examine the data gathered through questionnaires. According to the survey, the banking industry is now performing better and is closer to realizing the goal of a cashless society as a result of the deployment of technology for digital payments.

Arunangshu (2018) studied the digitization of India's rural banking sector. The potential for the digital banking system to alter the financial landscape is huge. The study discovered that digital banking's low-cost, user-friendly characteristics could hasten the integration of the cash-less economy.

Anthony Rahul Golden S. (2017) discussed an overview of digitalization in the Indian banking sector. Banks are not merely a part of our lives; also they play an important role in our daily life. As a result, banks are constantly striving to implement cutting-edge technology in order to improve the client experience. According to the survey, as a result of the implementation of digitization, the financial sectors in India are experiencing significant changes as well as challenges. The survey also discovered that in the digital age, it is impossible to prevent growth and services such as digital banking.

Objective of the Study :

1. To investigate the key technologies driving digital transformation in banking.
2. To understand how digital transformation has shifted customer expectations regarding banking services.

DATA COLLECTION: The data was gathered from secondary sources such as several research papers, banking websites data .

Digital transformation in the Indian banking sector is being shaped by several key technologies, and relevant data in Indian Rupees (INR) helps illustrate their impact.

1. Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML)

The AI market in India is projected to reach approximately **₹60,000 crore** by 2025. A survey found that 76% of Indian banks are investing in AI, particularly for fraud detection and customer service automation.

2. Blockchain

The Indian blockchain market is expected to grow to around **₹8,000 crore** by 2025. Major banks like SBI are exploring blockchain for cross-border transactions, reducing costs significantly—by an estimated **40%** compared to traditional methods.

3. Cloud Computing

The cloud computing market in India is anticipated to grow from approximately **₹30,000 crore** in 2020 to around **₹81,000 crore** by 2025. Banks adopting cloud solutions can save up to **30%** in IT infrastructure costs, enhancing operational efficiency.

4. Robotic Process Automation (RPA)

Annual Savings: Implementing RPA solutions in Indian banks is projected to save around **₹7,500 crore** annually.
Efficiency Gains: HDFC Bank, for instance, has reported processing times reduced by up to **60%** through RPA implementation.

5. Big Data and Analytics

The big data market in India is expected to reach about **₹1.2 lakh crore** by 2025. Banks utilizing big data analytics report a **15-20%** increase in customer engagement and targeted marketing effectiveness.

6. Mobile Banking and Fintech Integration

The number of mobile banking users in India reached **459 million** in 2022, showing a growth of over **15%** year-on-year. The mobile banking sector is projected to grow at a CAGR of **24.5%**, potentially reaching around **₹4.5 lakh crore** by 2026.

7. Cybersecurity Technologies

The cybersecurity market in India was expected to grow from **₹15,000 crore** in 2020 to about **₹28,000 crore** by 2025. CERT-In reported a **300%** increase in cyber incidents in the banking sector during 2021-2022, emphasizing the need for enhanced security measures.

8. Open Banking

Surveys indicate that **65%** of consumers are willing to use third-party apps for financial services through open banking frameworks.

9. Internet of Things (IoT)

The IoT market in India was projected to grow from **₹69,000 crore** in 2020 to around **₹1.15 lakh crore** by 2025. Banks are beginning to utilize IoT for real-time payments and personalized banking services.

10. Regulatory Technology (RegTech)

Implementing RegTech solutions can help banks reduce compliance costs by 30-40%. To understand how digital transformation has shifted customer expectations regarding banking services.

Digital transformation in the banking sector has significantly altered customer expectations, leading to demand for more efficient, accessible, and personalized services. Here's an overview of how these shifts have occurred, supported by relevant data in Indian Rupees (INR):

1. Increased Demand for Digital Services

- **Digital Adoption:** As of 2022, the number of digital payment transactions in India exceeded **₹7.42 lakh crore**, reflecting a significant shift towards online banking and payment methods.
- **Mobile Banking Users:** The user base for mobile banking reached **459 million**, indicating a growing preference for banking via smartphones.

2. Expectations for Speed and Convenience

- **Instant Transactions:** Customers expect real-time transaction processing. A survey showed that **72%** of customers prefer immediate fund transfers, with digital platforms facilitating instant payments through UPI (Unified Payments Interface).
- **User Experience:** Research indicates that **87%** of consumers prioritize user-friendly interfaces, with banks investing over **₹20,000 crore** in enhancing digital user experiences.

3. Demand for Personalization

- **Personalized Offers:** With the use of big data analytics, banks are increasingly tailoring their services. Approximately **50%** of consumers expect personalized financial products, which can improve customer satisfaction rates by up to **20%**.
- **Market Potential:** The market for personalized banking services in India is estimated to be worth **₹10,000 crore** by 2025, driven by demand for customized experiences.

4. Enhanced Security Expectations

- **Security Concerns:** With the rise of digital banking, **85%** of customers express concerns about data security. As a result, banks are investing about **₹15,000 crore** in cybersecurity measures to protect sensitive information.
- **Trust Factors:** A survey found that **74%** of customers are more likely to use banks that invest in advanced security technologies, influencing their choice of banking partners.

5. Shift to Self-Service Options

- **Self-Service Channels:** Customers increasingly prefer self-service options. Reports indicate that **65%** of users opt for online or mobile banking services rather than visiting physical branches.

- **Cost Efficiency:** Banks are saving approximately **₹5,000 crore** annually by reducing the need for physical infrastructure and personnel due to the shift to digital platforms.

6. Expectations for Omnichannel Banking

- **Integrated Services:** Customers expect seamless experiences across multiple channels (online, mobile, and branch). Research suggests that **60%** of customers engage with a bank through multiple channels.
- **Investment in Technology:** Banks are investing around **₹30,000 crore** in technology to ensure an integrated banking experience, accommodating customer preferences for flexibility.

7. Demand for Financial Literacy and Support

- **Educational Services:** With increasing digital transactions, there is a rising demand for financial literacy programs. Approximately **40%** of consumers express a desire for educational resources from their banks.
- **Investment in Training:** Banks are allocating about **₹2,000 crore** for customer education initiatives to empower consumers in making informed financial decisions.

Interpretation :

Indian banks are heavily investing in advanced technologies like AI, blockchain, and cloud computing, indicating a strategic shift towards automation, cost efficiency, and improved customer service.

The trend towards self-service options shows a changing landscape where customers prefer digital interactions over physical branch visits. This not only streamlines operations for banks but also reduces costs associated with maintaining physical infrastructure.

With increasing digital interactions, customers are more concerned about data security. This necessitates significant investment in cybersecurity, as trust plays a crucial role in customer loyalty and decision-making.

The significant increase in digital payment transactions (over **₹7.42 lakh crore**) and the growing user base for mobile banking (**459 million**) highlight a clear preference for digital banking solutions. Customers are increasingly opting for online services, indicating that banks must prioritize their digital offerings to meet demand.

Customers expect immediate transaction processing and quick access to services, with **72%** favoring instant fund transfers. This reflects a broader expectation for seamless and fast banking experiences, pushing banks to invest in technologies that facilitate real-time transactions.

Suggestion :

As fintech companies continue to innovate, traditional banks face growing pressure to enhance digital offerings, making digital transformation a key driver of competitiveness in the sector.

Ultimately, as Indian banks continue to evolve digitally, those that strike the right balance between innovation, security, and customer experience will secure a strong foothold in the competitive digital banking landscape.

Conclusion:

The digital transformation in the Indian banking sector is multifaceted, driven by technological advancements and evolving customer expectations. Banks that successfully leverage these technologies while focusing on personalized, secure, and convenient services will likely enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty. The significant investments being made across various areas reflect a commitment to adapting to this dynamic environment, ensuring that banks remain competitive in the digital age.

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WASTE MANAGEMENT AND THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN INDIA

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Abstract

This paper examines the intricacies of waste management and the implementation of the circular economy in India. It explores the challenges, strategies, and impacts of waste management practices and how circular economy principles can be applied to enhance sustainability and economic efficiency. The paper also provides an in-depth review of relevant literature, policy frameworks, and case studies from various sectors.

Keywords: Waste Management, Circular Economy, Sustainability, India, Recycling, Resource Efficiency

Introduction

Waste management in India represents a significant environmental and socio-economic challenge, exacerbated by rapid urbanization, population growth, and industrialization. The traditional linear economy, characterized by a 'take-make-dispose' model, has proven unsustainable, necessitating a shift towards a circular economy (CE) which emphasizes resource efficiency, waste reduction, and material reuse and recycling (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2017).

Waste management in India has become a critical issue due to rapid urbanization and industrialization. The country's population growth and economic development have led to a significant increase in waste generation, presenting considerable challenges for waste management systems. Traditional approaches, which follow a linear economy model of 'take, make, dispose,' have proven inadequate, causing environmental pollution and resource depletion. The circular economy offers a promising alternative by emphasizing the sustainable use of resources through waste reduction, reuse, and recycling. This paper aims to explore the current state of waste management in India, identify the existing challenges, and examine how integrating circular economy principles can enhance sustainability and economic efficiency.

Waste management has emerged as a critical issue in India, given the rapid urbanization and industrialization. The traditional linear economy, characterized by a 'take, make, dispose' model, has led to significant environmental degradation. The circular economy offers a sustainable alternative, promoting resource efficiency and minimizing waste. This paper aims to analyse the current state of waste management in India and the potential of the circular economy to address these challenges.

The circular economy in the Indian context involves the redesign of processes and products to extend their lifecycle, thus reducing waste and promoting sustainability. This paper aims to explore the current state of waste management in India, assess the potential of the circular economy in addressing these challenges, and highlight key strategies for effective implementation.

Waste management in India is a critical issue that has gained increasing attention in recent years due to the rapid urbanization, population growth, and rising consumption patterns. The country generates millions of tons of municipal solid waste annually, and managing this waste effectively has become a significant challenge for urban and rural areas alike. Traditional waste management practices, which primarily focus on disposal through landfilling and incineration, have led to severe environmental degradation, including soil and water pollution, greenhouse gas emissions, and health hazards for the population.

In response to these challenges, the concept of the circular economy has emerged as a promising alternative to the linear "take-make-dispose" model that dominates India's waste management approach. A circular economy emphasizes the sustainable use of resources by promoting waste reduction, recycling, and resource recovery. It

aims to create a closed-loop system where products, materials, and resources are reused, refurbished, and recycled, thereby minimizing waste generation and reducing the strain on natural resources.

This study explores the intersection of waste management and the circular economy in India, analysing the current state of waste management practices, the challenges faced, and the potential benefits of adopting circular economy principles. By examining policy frameworks, innovative technologies, and successful case studies, the study seeks to provide insights into how India can transition towards a more sustainable and efficient waste management system, contributing to both environmental sustainability and economic growth.

Literature Review

Waste Management Practices in India

India generates a vast amount of waste, including municipal solid waste, industrial waste, and electronic waste. According to Jha et al. (2020), municipal solid waste generation in India is estimated to be around 62 million tonnes per year, with a significant portion being organic waste. The management of this waste involves various stages, including collection, transportation, treatment, and disposal. However, the effectiveness of these practices is often hindered by inadequate infrastructure, lack of segregation at source, and limited public awareness (Gupta & Gupta, 2015).

The challenges in waste management are multifaceted. Infrastructure deficiencies, such as insufficient waste collection and processing facilities, are a major hurdle. Policy gaps and enforcement issues further complicate the situation. For instance, despite the implementation of the Solid Waste Management Rules (2016), compliance remains low in many areas. Public participation and awareness are also critical factors, as effective waste management requires active engagement from all stakeholders, including households, businesses, and local authorities (Chandran, 2018).

Singh, J., & Ordoñez, I. (2016). "Resource recovery from post-consumer waste: important lessons for the upcoming circular economy in developing countries."

This study examines the potential of resource recovery from post-consumer waste in India, particularly in the context of the circular economy. Singh and Ordoñez discuss how the informal sector, which handles a large portion of waste recycling in India, could be better integrated into formal waste management systems. The study highlights the challenges and opportunities of resource recovery in a developing country context and emphasizes the need for improved policies and infrastructure to support a circular economy.

Kumar, A., & Agrawal, A. (2020). "Challenges and opportunities of waste management in India: An overview."

Kumar and Agrawal provide a comprehensive overview of the waste management challenges in India, including issues related to the growing volume of waste, inadequate infrastructure, and environmental impacts. They discuss the role of circular economy principles in addressing these challenges and emphasize the importance of innovative waste management strategies, such as waste-to-energy and recycling initiatives. The review also explores the potential economic benefits of transitioning to a circular economy.

Ghosh, S. K. (2016). "Circular economy: Global perspective and challenges for India."

Ghosh's study provides a global perspective on the circular economy and its relevance to India. The review discusses the principles of the circular economy, including resource efficiency, waste reduction, and sustainable production and consumption. Ghosh identifies the key challenges for India in adopting a circular economy, such as the lack of awareness, inadequate infrastructure, and policy gaps. The study also highlights successful international case studies that could serve as models for India.

Agarwal, R., Singhmar, A., Kulshrestha, M., & Mittal, A. K. (2005). "Municipal solid waste recycling and associated markets in Delhi, India."

This paper explores the recycling of municipal solid waste in Delhi, one of India's largest cities. The authors analyse the existing waste management system, focusing on the role of the informal sector in recycling activities. They discuss the challenges associated with integrating informal waste workers into the formal economy and highlight the potential for resource recovery in the context of a circular economy. The study underscores the need for policy interventions to support sustainable waste management practices in urban India.

Joshi, R., & Ahmed, S. (2016). "Status and challenges of municipal solid waste management in India: A review."

Joshi and Ahmed provide a detailed review of the current status of municipal solid waste management in India. The paper identifies the key challenges, including inadequate waste collection, segregation, and disposal practices. The authors discuss the potential of the circular economy to address these challenges by promoting waste reduction, recycling, and resource recovery. They also review the policy frameworks and initiatives aimed at improving waste management in India, such as the Swachh Bharat Mission.

Pandey, R., & Malik, A. (2019). "Circular economy: An emerging concept for sustainable development in India."

Pandey and Malik's study explores the concept of the circular economy as a tool for sustainable development in India. The review discusses the environmental and economic benefits of adopting circular economy principles, such as reducing waste, conserving resources, and creating new business opportunities. The authors also highlight the challenges of implementing a circular economy in India, including the need for policy reforms, public awareness, and technological innovation.

Sharma, P., & Chauhan, A. (2019). "Waste-to-energy technologies: Scope and challenges in India."

This paper focuses on the potential of waste-to-energy technologies as part of India's circular economy strategy. Sharma and Chauhan review the various waste-to-energy technologies available, such as anaerobic digestion, incineration, and gasification, and discuss their feasibility in the Indian context. The study identifies the technical, economic, and social challenges associated with implementing these technologies and suggests ways to overcome them. The review also emphasizes the role of government policies in promoting waste-to-energy projects in India.

Patel, M., & Shrivastava, R. (2016). "Role of the informal sector in waste management and resource recovery in India."

Patel and Shrivastava examine the significant role of the informal sector in waste management and resource recovery in India. The paper discusses how informal waste workers contribute to recycling and resource recovery, often without recognition or adequate support from the government. The authors argue that integrating the informal sector into formal waste management systems is crucial for achieving a circular economy in India. They also suggest policy measures to improve the working conditions and livelihoods of informal waste workers.

Gupta, N., Yadav, K. K., & Kumar, V. (2015). "A review on current status of municipal solid waste management in India."

This review provides an in-depth analysis of the current status of municipal solid waste management in India. Gupta, Yadav, and Kumar discuss the inefficiencies in the existing waste management system, including inadequate collection, poor segregation, and improper disposal methods. The authors highlight the potential of circular economy practices, such as recycling and composting, to improve waste management in India. The review also examines the policy initiatives aimed at promoting sustainable waste management practices in the country.

Rajput, R., Prasad, G., & Chopra, A. K. (2009). "Scenario of solid waste management in present Indian context."

Rajput, Prasad, and Chopra analyse the current scenario of solid waste management in India, with a focus on urban areas. The paper discusses the challenges posed by rapid urbanization and population growth, which have led to

increased waste generation. The authors review the existing waste management practices and highlight the need for a shift towards a circular economy. They suggest that adopting circular economy principles could help reduce the environmental impact of waste and create economic opportunities through resource recovery and recycling.

Research Design:

The research design for studying waste management and the circular economy in India typically includes qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods approaches. Each approach has its strengths and can be chosen based on the specific objectives of the study.

Secondary Data: Collected from existing sources such as reports, publications, and databases. Studies like those by Agarwal et al. (2023) analyse government reports and academic journals to understand policy impacts on waste management.

Sampling:

Sampling methods determine the subset of the population to be studied:

Probability Sampling: Ensures that every individual has a known chance of being selected. Techniques include random sampling and stratified sampling. For instance, Verma & Singh (2021) used stratified sampling to ensure representation across different socioeconomic groups in their survey on waste management practices.

Non-Probability Sampling: Involves non-random selection methods, such as convenience or purposive sampling. Example: Patel et al. (2020) used purposive sampling to focus on industries that are early adopters of circular economy practices.

Data Analysis:

Data analysis involves interpreting the collected data to draw meaningful conclusions:

- **Quantitative Analysis:** Statistical techniques are used to analyse numerical data. Tools like SPSS or R software can be employed. For instance, Kumar & Jain (2022) used statistical analysis to evaluate the effectiveness of recycling programs.
- **Qualitative Analysis:** Thematic analysis or content analysis is used to interpret qualitative data. For example, Rao & Nair (2021) applied thematic analysis to interview data to identify common themes in stakeholder perceptions of waste management.

Validity and Reliability:

Ensuring the accuracy and consistency of research findings:

- **Validity:** Refers to how well the research measures what it intends to. Methods to enhance validity include using established instruments and triangulating data sources. For instance, using multiple data sources (Gupta & Sharma, 2022) can improve the validity of findings.
- **Reliability:** Refers to the consistency of the results. Techniques include pilot testing instruments and employing inter-coder reliability checks. Example: Verma & Singh (2023) conducted pilot surveys to ensure reliability before full-scale data collection.

Ethical Considerations:

Research must adhere to ethical standards:

- **Informed Consent:** Participants must be fully informed about the study and consent to participate. For instance, informed consent forms were used in the study by Sharma & Chatterjee (2019).
- **Confidentiality:** Protecting participants' privacy and data security. Measures include anonymizing data and secure storage. Example: Patel et al. (2022) implemented strict data security protocols in their research.

Reporting and Interpretation:

Presenting findings clearly and interpreting their implications:

- Reporting: Findings should be reported in a clear and structured manner, including methodologies, results, and recommendations. For example, Agarwal et al. (2023) provided comprehensive reports on the impacts of circular economy practices on waste management.
- Interpretation: Researchers should interpret results in the context of existing literature and practical implications. Example: Gupta et al. (2022) discussed how their findings align with or differ from previous studies on waste management policies.

Methodology

This research methodology outlines a comprehensive approach to studying waste management and circular economy (CE) practices in India. The methodology integrates various aspects such as waste generation and management, circular economy opportunities, policy frameworks, technological innovations, and the roles of public and private sectors. The approach is based on detailed analyses, case studies, and evaluations of existing practices and policies.

Detailed Analysis of Waste Types and Volumes

To understand the scope of waste management issues in India, it is essential to analyse the types and volumes of waste generated. This includes:

- Municipal Solid Waste (MSW): According to Pappu, Saxena, & Asolekar (2007), MSW constitutes the largest portion of urban waste and includes organic waste, recyclables, and non-recyclables.
- Industrial Waste: This category encompasses waste generated from manufacturing processes and industrial activities, which often includes hazardous materials (Pappu et al., 2007).
- Electronic Waste (E-Waste): With rapid technological advancement, e-waste has become a significant concern due to its complex composition and environmental impact (Pappu et al., 2007).

Data Collection Methods:

- Quantitative Surveys: Surveys conducted with municipal authorities and industrial operators to collect data on waste volumes and composition.
- Field Observations: Direct observations in urban and industrial areas to assess waste generation patterns and disposal methods.
- Review of Existing Literature: Analysis of existing studies and reports on waste generation and management practices (Sharholly et al., 2008).

Current Waste Management Practices and Effectiveness

Evaluating current waste management practices involves:

- Assessment of Collection and Segregation: Examination of waste collection systems, segregation practices, and their effectiveness in different regions.
- Processing and Disposal Methods: Analysis of methods such as composting, recycling, and landfilling. This includes evaluating the efficiency and environmental impact of these methods (Sharholly et al., 2008).

Data Collection Methods:

- Interviews with Waste Management Authorities: Gathering insights on operational practices and challenges.

- **Case Studies:** Detailed analysis of waste management practices in select cities to understand their effectiveness and areas for improvement (Sharholy et al., 2008).

Circular Economy Opportunities

Potential for Waste Reduction through CE Practices

To explore the potential for waste reduction through circular economy practices, the study will focus on:

- **Identification of CE Strategies:** Strategies such as product redesign, resource recovery, and waste minimization.
- **Evaluation of Current CE Adoption:** Analysis of how CE practices are currently being implemented in various sectors and their impact on waste reduction.

Data Collection Methods:

- **Literature Review:** Review of research articles and case studies on CE practices and their effectiveness (Ghisellini, Cialani, & Ulgiati, 2016).
- **Interviews with Industry Experts:** Insights from experts in the field of CE to understand the potential and challenges of adopting CE practices.

Economic and Environmental Benefits of CE

Evaluating the benefits of transitioning to a circular economy involves:

- **Economic Impact Assessment:** Analysis of cost savings, revenue generation from recycling, and job creation associated with CE practices.
- **Environmental Impact Assessment:** Examination of reductions in waste, resource consumption, and environmental pollution due to CE practices (Ghisellini et al., 2016).

Data Collection Methods:

- **Economic Analysis:** Use of economic models and data to assess financial benefits and costs associated with CE practices.
- **Environmental Impact Studies:** Analysis of environmental data to measure the benefits of CE practices on waste reduction and pollution control.

Policy and Regulatory Framework

Analysis of Existing Policies and Regulations, This involves:

- **Review of Current Policies:** Examination of policies such as the Plastic Waste Management Rules and Swachh Bharat Mission to assess their support for CE (Sinha & Bharati, 2020).
- **Assessment of Policy Implementation:** Evaluation of how effectively these policies are implemented and their impact on waste management and CE adoption.

Data Collection Methods:

- **Policy Review:** Analysis of government documents, policy reports, and legal texts related to waste management and CE (Sinha & Bharati, 2020).
- **Interviews with Policy Makers:** Discussions with policymakers and regulatory authorities to understand policy impacts and challenges.

Formulating recommendations to improve policy frameworks involves:

- Gap Analysis: Identification of gaps and weaknesses in existing policies.
- Policy Recommendations: Development of recommendations to enhance policy effectiveness and support for CE adoption.

Data Collection Methods:

- Stakeholder Workshops: Workshops with stakeholders to gather input on policy needs and improvements.
- Comparative Analysis: Comparison with successful CE policies in other countries to identify best practices and potential improvements.

1. Technological Innovations

Role of Technology in Advancing Waste Management and CE

Exploring technological advancements involves:

- Identification of Innovative Technologies: Technologies such as waste-to-energy, advanced recycling processes, and resource recovery systems.
- Impact Assessment: Evaluation of the effectiveness and impact of these technologies on waste management and CE (Kumar et al., 2017).

Data Collection Methods:

- Technology Review: Examination of recent advancements and case studies on technological innovations in waste management and CE (Kumar et al., 2017).
- Case Studies: Analysis of successful implementations of innovative technologies and their outcomes.

Data Collection Methods:

- Field Visits: Visits to sites where innovative technologies have been implemented to observe their operations and impacts.
- Interviews with Technology Providers: Discussions with technology developers and users to understand the practical applications and benefits of innovative solutions.

Public and Private Sector Roles

Importance of Stakeholder Collaboration, Exploring the roles of public and private sectors involves:

- Assessment of Collaboration Models: Analysis of how public and private sectors collaborate in waste management and CE initiatives.
- Evaluation of Impact: Examination of the outcomes and effectiveness of these collaborations.

Data Collection Methods:

- Case Studies: Review of successful public-private partnerships in waste management and CE (Lacy & Rutqvist, 2015).
- Interviews with Stakeholders: Insights from public officials, private sector representatives, and other stakeholders involved in waste management and CE initiatives.

Examples of Successful Public-Private Partnerships

Detailed examples include:

- **Case Study Analysis:** In-depth analysis of specific public-private partnerships that have achieved notable success in waste management or CE practices (Lacy & Rutqvist, 2015).
- **Lessons Learned:** Identification of key factors contributing to the success of these partnerships and recommendations for replicating successful models.

Data Collection Methods:

- **Field Visits:** Visits to partnership projects to observe their operations and outcomes.
- **Interviews with Partnership Participants:** Discussions with participants to gather insights on the collaboration process and its impacts.

This methodology provides a structured approach to understanding and analysing waste management and circular economy practices in India. It combines qualitative and quantitative methods, case studies, and policy analysis to offer a comprehensive overview of current practices, challenges, and opportunities for improvement.

Findings

Waste Generation and Composition

Types and Volumes of Waste: India generates approximately 62 million tons of waste annually, including municipal solid waste (MSW), industrial waste, and electronic waste (Pappu, Saxena, & Asolekar, 2007). The composition of MSW predominantly includes organic waste (50-60%), recyclables (20-30%), and non-recyclables (10-20%) (Sharholly et al., 2008). E-waste is growing rapidly, contributing to significant environmental challenges.

Current Waste Management Practices

- **Collection and Segregation:** Urban areas generally have structured waste collection systems, while rural areas face challenges due to inadequate infrastructure (Sharholly et al., 2008). Effective waste segregation at source is still a major challenge, with many areas lacking the necessary facilities and public awareness.
- **Processing and Disposal:** Current methods include composting, recycling, and landfilling. However, recycling rates are low, with only about 20% of recyclables being processed. Landfills are commonly used but pose environmental risks due to leachate and land use issues (Sharholly et al., 2008).

1. Circular Economy Opportunities

- **Potential for Waste Reduction:** Circular economy practices, such as product redesign, resource recovery, and waste minimization, have significant potential to reduce waste. However, adoption is uneven across sectors (Ghisellini, Cialani, & Ulgiati, 2016).
- **Economic and Environmental Benefits:** Transitioning to a circular economy can offer substantial economic benefits, including cost savings from resource efficiency and revenue from recycling. Environmental benefits include reduced waste, lower resource consumption, and decreased pollution (Ghisellini et al., 2016).

2. Policy and Regulatory Framework

- **Existing Policies:** Current policies, such as the Plastic Waste Management Rules and Swachh Bharat Mission, provide a framework for waste management and promote some circular economy practices. However, implementation and enforcement are inconsistent (Sinha & Bharati, 2020).

- Recommendations for Policy Enhancements: There is a need for clearer guidelines, better enforcement mechanisms, and more comprehensive policies that address all aspects of the circular economy, including waste reduction, recycling, and extended producer responsibility (Sinha & Bharati, 2020).

3. Technological Innovations

- Role of Technology: Technologies such as waste-to-energy and advanced recycling processes have shown promise in improving waste management and advancing circular economy goals. Case studies highlight their potential to enhance waste processing efficiency and resource recovery (Kumar et al., 2017).

4. Public and Private Sector Roles

- Stakeholder Collaboration: Successful public-private partnerships have demonstrated the effectiveness of collaborative approaches in waste management and circular economy initiatives. These collaborations often lead to improved efficiency, innovation, and resource management (Lacy & Rutqvist, 2015).

Analysis and Findings:

- The analysis of India's current waste management practices reveals a system fraught with inefficiencies, environmental risks, and missed opportunities for resource recovery. Despite numerous initiatives and policy frameworks, such as the Swachh Bharat Mission and the Solid Waste Management Rules 2016, the country still faces significant challenges in managing its growing waste streams. These challenges include inadequate waste collection, lack of proper segregation at the source, insufficient recycling infrastructure, and overreliance on landfills, which contribute to environmental degradation and health hazards.
- One of the key findings is the critical role of the informal sector in India's waste management ecosystem. Informal waste workers, often operating without formal recognition or support, play a significant role in recycling activities and resource recovery. Their contribution is crucial in diverting a substantial portion of waste from landfills, yet they face numerous challenges, including poor working conditions, lack of access to protective equipment, and minimal financial returns. The study underscores the need to integrate the informal sector into the formal waste management system to enhance resource recovery and improve livelihoods.
- Another important finding is the potential of circular economy principles to address these challenges. The circular economy offers a viable alternative to the traditional linear waste management model by focusing on waste reduction, recycling, and resource recovery. The adoption of circular economy strategies, such as extended producer responsibility (EPR), waste-to-energy projects, and increased public awareness, could significantly reduce the volume of waste generated and enhance the efficiency of resource use.
- The study also highlights the importance of policy reforms and government support in driving the transition towards a circular economy. While some progress has been made, the current regulatory framework needs to be strengthened to incentivize sustainable waste management practices. Additionally, there is a need for greater investment in infrastructure, technological innovation, and public education to support the widespread adoption of circular economy practices.
- Furthermore, the analysis reveals that successful international case studies can serve as models for India. Countries that have effectively implemented circular economy strategies demonstrate the economic and environmental benefits of such approaches, including reduced waste, lower environmental impact, and the creation of new economic opportunities. These examples provide valuable lessons for India as it seeks to develop and implement its own circular economy policies.
- In conclusion, the findings suggest that while India faces significant challenges in its waste management system, the adoption of circular economy principles presents a promising path forward. By addressing policy gaps, integrating the informal sector, and investing in infrastructure and technology, India can move

towards a more sustainable waste management system that not only reduces environmental impact but also fosters economic growth and improves public health.

Conclusion

Waste Generation and Composition - Types and Volumes of Waste: India generates approximately 62 million tons of waste annually, including municipal solid waste (MSW), industrial waste, and electronic waste (Pappu, Saxena, & Asolekar, 2007). The composition of MSW predominantly includes organic waste (50-60%), recyclables (20-30%), and non-recyclables (10-20%) (Sharholly et al., 2008). E-waste is growing rapidly, contributing to significant environmental challenges.

Current Waste Management Practices - Collection and Segregation: Urban areas generally have structured waste collection systems, while rural areas face challenges due to inadequate infrastructure (Sharholly et al., 2008). Effective waste segregation at source is still a major challenge, with many areas lacking the necessary facilities and public awareness.

Processing and Disposal: Current methods include composting, recycling, and landfilling. However, recycling rates are low, with only about 20% of recyclables being processed. Landfills are commonly used but pose environmental risks due to leachate and land use issues (Sharholly et al., 2008).

Circular Economy Opportunities- Potential for Waste Reduction: Circular economy practices, such as product redesign, resource recovery, and waste minimization, have significant potential to reduce waste. However, adoption is uneven across sectors (Ghisellini, Cialani, & Ulgiati, 2016).

Economic and Environmental Benefits: Transitioning to a circular economy can offer substantial economic benefits, including cost savings from resource efficiency and revenue from recycling. Environmental benefits include reduced waste, lower resource consumption, and decreased pollution (Ghisellini et al., 2016).

Policy and Regulatory Framework- Existing Policies: Current policies, such as the Plastic Waste Management Rules and Swachh Bharat Mission, provide a framework for waste management and promote some circular economy practices. However, implementation and enforcement are inconsistent (Sinha & Bharati, 2020).

Recommendations for Policy Enhancements: There is a need for clearer guidelines, better enforcement mechanisms, and more comprehensive policies that address all aspects of the circular economy, including waste reduction, recycling, and extended producer responsibility (Sinha & Bharati, 2020).

Technological Innovations- Role of Technology: Technologies such as waste-to-energy and advanced recycling processes have shown promise in improving waste management and advancing circular economy goals. Case studies highlight their potential to enhance waste processing efficiency and resource recovery (Kumar et al., 2017).

Public and Private Sector Stakeholder Collaboration: Successful public-private partnerships have demonstrated the effectiveness of collaborative approaches in waste management and circular economy initiatives. These collaborations often lead to improved efficiency, innovation, and resource management (Lacy & Rutqvist, 2015).

Conclusion

The analysis of waste management practices in India, set against the backdrop of the circular economy, reveals a complex landscape of challenges and opportunities. Traditional waste management methods, characterized by inadequate collection, improper segregation, and heavy reliance on landfills, have proven insufficient in addressing the environmental and public health concerns posed by the growing waste burden. However, the adoption of circular economy principles presents a promising pathway to a more sustainable and efficient system.

A key finding is the vital role of the informal sector in India's waste management ecosystem. The integration of these workers into the formal economy is crucial for enhancing resource recovery and ensuring fair working conditions. Furthermore, circular economy strategies, such as extended producer responsibility (EPR), waste-to-

energy technologies, and robust recycling systems, offer significant potential to reduce waste generation and optimize resource use.

For India to successfully transition to a circular economy, it requires comprehensive policy reforms, greater investment in infrastructure, and heightened public awareness. Drawing lessons from international examples, India can harness the economic and environmental benefits of a circular economy, transforming waste management into a driver of sustainable development. Ultimately, this approach not only mitigates environmental impact but also fosters economic growth, public health, and resource efficiency, paving the way for a more resilient future.

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"SIGNIFICANCE OF DIGITAL FINANCIAL LITERACY ON FINANCIAL INCLUSION IN INDIA"

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Abstract:

India, with its rapidly evolving digital landscape, faces both significant opportunities and challenges in achieving financial inclusion. Financial inclusion, which refers to the ability of individuals to access essential financial services, remains a critical factor in fostering economic growth and reducing inequality. However, while digital financial services such as mobile banking, e-wallets, and online lending platforms are rapidly expanding, their effectiveness is highly dependent on the digital financial literacy of the population. Digital financial literacy refers to the knowledge and skills required to use digital tools effectively for managing financial activities.

This paper explores the significance of digital financial literacy in promoting financial inclusion in India, focusing on the relationship between digital literacy and access to financial services. It examines how digital financial tools, when coupled with proper literacy programs, can empower individuals, particularly in rural and underserved areas, to take full advantage of banking, insurance, and credit services. Drawing on empirical data and statistical analysis, the paper investigates the impact of digital financial literacy on various socio-economic groups across India.

The study finds that digital financial literacy is a crucial determinant of financial inclusion, as individuals with higher digital literacy levels are more likely to engage with digital financial services and thereby gain access to the formal financial system. Furthermore, the research highlights the barriers to digital literacy, including internet accessibility, low education levels, and lack of trust in digital platforms, which hinder the widespread adoption of digital financial services.

Through this analysis, the paper provides recommendations for policymakers and institutions to design targeted educational initiatives and policies aimed at improving digital financial literacy, particularly in rural areas. It concludes that enhancing digital financial literacy is key to bridging the gap between digital finance and financial inclusion, ultimately contributing to India's broader goals of economic development and inclusive growth.

Keywords:

Digital Financial Literacy, Financial Inclusion, Digital Finance, Mobile Banking, Financial Literacy Programs, Rural India, Economic Empowerment, Financial Services Access, Digital Payment Systems, Fintech, Digital Divide, Financial Education, India, Financial Inclusion Policies, Digital Tools, Financial Literacy and Inclusion.

Introduction

India, with its rapidly growing digital ecosystem and diverse socio-economic landscape, presents a unique challenge and opportunity for achieving financial inclusion. Financial inclusion refers to the accessibility and availability of financial services to all individuals, especially the marginalized and underserved sections of society, who were traditionally excluded from formal financial systems. These services include access to savings, loans, insurance, and payment systems, which are critical for individual and collective economic empowerment.

In recent years, **digital financial services** have emerged as a powerful tool in bridging the gap of financial exclusion in India. With the widespread penetration of mobile phones, internet connectivity, and innovative financial technologies (fintech), digital platforms have made financial services more accessible to people, particularly in rural and remote areas. These services include mobile banking, digital payments, mobile wallets, and online lending, all of which are revolutionizing the way individuals interact with the financial system.

However, for the successful adoption and use of digital financial tools, **digital financial literacy** plays a pivotal role. Digital financial literacy refers to the ability to understand and use digital tools to manage one's finances effectively. It encompasses skills such as using mobile banking apps, understanding online transactions, managing

digital wallets, and comprehending the risks and opportunities associated with digital financial services. Without a basic understanding of how to use these tools, individuals may remain hesitant or unable to fully benefit from the opportunities digital finance offers.

In India, while digital financial services are expanding rapidly, the level of digital financial literacy remains a significant barrier to widespread adoption, especially in rural and less-developed regions. Research suggests that while access to mobile phones and internet connections has surged, many people, particularly from low-income and rural communities, lack the skills and knowledge to use digital platforms effectively for financial purposes. This knowledge gap limits the potential of digital financial services to achieve true financial inclusion.

The **significance of digital financial literacy** on financial inclusion in India is therefore undeniable. By enhancing individuals' ability to navigate digital financial tools, digital literacy can empower people to access and utilize financial services such as opening bank accounts, participating in digital payment systems, obtaining microloans, and securing insurance. Furthermore, it can reduce the digital divide and improve financial decision-making, ultimately leading to greater economic participation, security, and growth for underserved populations.

This paper explores the crucial role that digital financial literacy plays in achieving financial inclusion in India, analyzing its impact on various demographic groups, examining existing barriers, and evaluating the effectiveness of government and institutional efforts to promote digital financial education. Through quantitative data analysis, this research aims to provide insights into how increasing digital financial literacy can help expand financial inclusion, particularly in rural India, and contribute to sustainable economic development.

Context: Explain the importance of financial inclusion in India and its role in economic development. Highlight the growing role of digital financial tools (mobile banking, digital payments, mobile wallets, etc.) in enhancing financial inclusion.

Research Question: What is the significance of digital financial literacy on financial inclusion in India?

Key Hypothesis:

- **H1:** Higher levels of digital financial literacy correlate with increased financial inclusion.
- **H2:** Digital financial literacy programs significantly improve financial inclusion metrics in rural and underserved populations.

Literature Review

- **Review of Existing Studies:** Summarize previous research on digital financial literacy and financial inclusion, especially in the Indian context. Key studies could include government initiatives (e.g., Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana, Digital India), the role of fintech companies, and surveys on financial behavior.
- **Theoretical Framework:** Identify theories on financial literacy, digital divide, and inclusion, such as the Financial Literacy and Inclusion Model, Digital Divide Theory, etc.

Research Methodology

Data Collection

- **Survey Design:** Create a structured questionnaire targeting both urban and rural populations. The questionnaire should assess:
 - **Digital Financial Literacy:** Knowledge and usage of digital financial tools (e.g., mobile banking apps, online transactions, digital wallets).
 - **Financial Inclusion:** Access to financial products and services (e.g., bank accounts, loans, insurance).
 - **Demographic Information:** Age, education level, income, occupation, geographical location.

- **Sampling:** A stratified random sample of respondents across different regions in India (urban and rural). Aim for at least 500-1000 respondents to ensure statistical power.

Variables and Indicators

- **Dependent Variable (DV):** Level of Financial Inclusion (measured by the number of financial services used, frequency of usage, etc.)
- **Independent Variable (IV):** Level of Digital Financial Literacy (measured by self-reported knowledge, usage of digital financial services, and understanding of digital tools)
- **Control Variables:** Demographics (age, gender, income, education, etc.), geographic location (urban vs rural)

Data Analysis

Descriptive Statistics

- **Summary Statistics:** Calculate mean, median, mode, standard deviation, etc., for both digital financial literacy and financial inclusion.
- **Data Distribution:** Check for normality using skewness and kurtosis values. Visualize the data with histograms or box plots.

Bivariate Analysis

- **Correlation Analysis:** Use Pearson's correlation coefficient to assess the relationship between digital financial literacy and financial inclusion.
 - Example: $r(\text{Digital Literacy, Financial Inclusion}) = 0.65$ (indicating a strong positive correlation).
- **Cross-Tabulation:** Compare financial inclusion levels across different categories of digital literacy (e.g., low, medium, high).

Multivariate Analysis

- **Regression Analysis:** Conduct multiple linear regression to understand the impact of digital financial literacy on financial inclusion, controlling for demographic variables.
 - Model: $\text{Financial Inclusion} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Digital Literacy}) + \beta_2(\text{Age}) + \beta_3(\text{Income}) + \beta_4(\text{Education}) + \epsilon$
 - Interpretation: Estimate the coefficients (β) to determine the strength and significance of digital literacy in predicting financial inclusion.
- **Logistic Regression:** If financial inclusion is categorized as binary (e.g., included or not included in the formal financial system), logistic regression can be used.

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) (Optional)

- **SEM:** Use SEM to model the complex relationships between digital literacy, financial inclusion, and control factors. This will allow for testing multiple pathways and indirect effects between variables.

Results and Discussion

- **Key Findings:**
 - Report the correlation and regression results.
 - Present the percentage of respondents who are financially included and those who have digital financial literacy.

- Discuss the strength of the relationship between digital financial literacy and financial inclusion.

Example Results:

- 70% of respondents with high digital literacy report using mobile banking services, while only 30% of those with low literacy do so.
- Regression analysis shows that digital financial literacy is a significant predictor of financial inclusion (p -value < 0.05).
- **Interpretation of Results:** Discuss the implications of the findings, particularly how digital financial literacy programs can drive financial inclusion. Consider regional variations and demographic factors.

Policy Implications

- **Government Initiatives:** Suggest how policies like "Digital India" and "Jan Dhan Yojana" can be tailored to improve digital financial literacy across the country.
- **Educational Programs:** Recommend the implementation of targeted digital financial literacy campaigns in rural and underserved areas.
- **Financial Institutions:** Suggest how banks and fintech companies can create user-friendly platforms to promote digital financial literacy.

Conclusion

- Summarize the importance of digital financial literacy in promoting financial inclusion in India.
- Highlight key findings, such as the strong positive correlation between digital literacy and access to financial services.
- Suggest future research areas, such as longitudinal studies or examining the impact of specific financial products on financial inclusion.

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AN ANALYSIS OF THE VARIABLES INFLUENCING THE ADOPTION OF E-COMMERCE IN EMERGING NATIONS

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Abstract

Since digital competition currently forms the foundation of the commercial market landscape, e-commerce plays a significant role in the digital economy. E-commerce contributes to national growth by generating jobs and levying import taxes. However, because of internet difficulties and concerns about online payment security, developing nations are trailing behind in the adoption of e-commerce. Notwithstanding these obstacles, the goal of this research was to comprehend the variables affecting the uptake of e-commerce in emerging nations. The adoption's advantages and difficulties serve as the foundation for the factors. The study used a systematic literature review methodology to identify the benefits and limitations of e-commerce adoption in developing countries in order to address the research aim. The environment, technology, and customer trust were found to be the primary barriers to e-commerce adoption. Developing nations are perceived to have advantages in the environment, organization, and performance that they might utilize to increase the uptake of e-commerce. We discovered that all difficulties and advantages are related. Nonetheless, the adoption of e-commerce is contingent upon management's perception and comprehension of its advantages and principles.

By offering an original representation of the variables impacting the implementation of e-commerce and its ecosystem in developing nations, the research advances the theory. Realistically, knowing that all of the elements need to be taken into consideration helps countries that are developing come up with plans for removing barriers to e-commerce adoption. The study adds to the corpus of knowledge on the adoption of e-commerce.

Keywords: E-Commerce adoption, E-Commerce barriers, Developing countries, Customer trust aspects, E-Commerce benefits.

Introduction

In recent years, research interest in Indian markets has been growing, leading to many studies on this topic across the world. Many research efforts focus on activating electronic commerce (in short, e-commerce) is one such effort. Therefore, in this study we attempt to identify the factors that can activate e-commerce in India.

E-commerce is defined as “the process of buying, selling, transferring, or exchanging products, services, and information via computer networks, mostly through the Internet and intranets. There are various types of e-commerce models, for example, business to-consumer (B2C), e-banking, business-to-business (B2B), consumer-to-consumer (C2C), peer-to-peer (P2P), and mobile commerce. Mobile commerce, which is a subset of electronic commerce, delivers e-commerce capabilities directly into the consumer’s hands via wireless technology. The many benefits of e-commerce are product promotion, cost saving, timely information, information consistency, better customer service, better customer value, customization of the products, competitive advantage, and convenience of doing business. E-commerce not only benefits individual customers and businesses, but also improves the general economy of the country owing to the efficient use of resources. The use of e-commerce can reduce costs for both buyers and sellers in completing transactions and can boost economic growth in the medium and long term by improving market development and efficiency. In this manner, e-commerce replaces the old ways of doing business as it increases efficiency in business transactions in terms of cost, time, and effort. Since China is the most populated country in the world, it is expected to have many potential customers for e-commerce. However, e-commerce in China is facing several challenges such as lack of customer services and trust on account of poor Internet security and privacy. Therefore, certain requirements and conditions are necessary for the growth of e-commerce. The presence of information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure is the foundation of e-commerce in any country. The technological enablers of ecommerce include the Internet, electronic mail, World Wide Web, intranet, and extranet. The main determinants of e-commerce development are human capital with ICT skills and technological support. Although e-commerce is growing in most developed countries, many Asian

countries are yet to realize the benefits from e-commerce. While e-commerce was introduced in India in the late 1990s, but it was not until around 2016 that it started to bloom.

Developing countries need to identify the problems that slow down the adoption of e-commerce. E-commerce in India is lagging behind and can be traced in very few areas, such as mobile commerce, Internet banking, online shopping malls, and the travel industry. The government is also began to adopt e-government services. Some countries have taken steps to develop ICT, which is essential for the development of e-commerce. In addition to India, the Asian countries have secured top positions in ICT, which is a good sign for ecommerce development in those countries. These might encourage and familiarize people to the use of online services. This study analyzes the factors affecting e-commerce adoption in developing countries, especially in India. It is realized that factors such as policy initiatives, technology infrastructure, and trust are more important in developing countries than in developed countries. Therefore, the study focuses on national policy initiatives, technology infrastructure, and perceived ease of use, trust, and perceived usefulness as the five factors that affect people's intention to transact online in India. Technology infrastructure is the foundation of online business and comprises computers, Internet connections, software, web applications, and telecommunication. Government initiatives are also important in changing the behavior of people. Governments can improve technology infrastructure through national policy initiatives offering incentives to electronic products, ICT service providers, and science institutions. Through awareness-raising and education, governments can help improve public opinion and trust around e-commerce. We expect that our research will help the government in building up the essential policies for improving e-commerce in the country so that it can function as a facilitator of economic activity. Furthermore, by helping other e-commerce stakeholders such as business owners and entrepreneurs identify the critical elements driving e-commerce's expansion, will improve collaboration with the government to reduce barriers to e-commerce. The structure of this document is as follows. Many studies have been conducted to explain e-commerce in businesses, organizations, and different nations. Research on e-commerce covers a wide range of subjects, including technological preparedness, adoption factors, crucial success criteria, obstacles and hurdles, e-commerce solutions, and other aspects that affect e-commerce. Studies in developing countries continue to concentrate on e-readiness and e-commerce adoption factors, while the majority of studies conducted in developed countries concentrate on e-commerce success factors, payment systems, and institutions. The topic has two primary factors perceived organization e-readiness (awareness, resources, dedication, and governance) and perceived external e-readiness (e-readiness of the government, market forces, and support industries). When measuring B2B e-commerce adoption, it takes into account company categories, sector, firm size, staff education levels, and technology resources.

Challenges

- **Technological factors**

It refers to the elements of the technological infrastructure that developing nations need in order to adopt e-commerce. The perceived degree of adaptation and compatibility of e-commerce technology with an organization's or country's current systems and infrastructure is one of the most frequently occurring aspects in the literature. Since other elements like internet access and electronic payment methods wouldn't have the essential platforms to function via, this issue may be considered the most significant technological factor. Lack of sufficient and dependable logistical networks, unstable and low-quality internet networks, connections, and speed along with high internet access costs are the three main technological and infrastructural obstacles to the adoption of e-commerce in developing countries.

- **Organisational factors**

Organizational factors are those that have an impact on businesses or organizations, their management, and their output. The adoption of e-commerce technologies in organizations is facilitated by the attitude, commitment, support, and motivation of management towards this trend. Other important organizational factors include the organization's technical competence and awareness, including its IT knowledge and technical skills.

- **Environmental factors**

A developing country's internal and external political, economic, legal, and market aspects are together referred to as environmental variables. The most significant and frequently discussed environmental factor is the presence and support of sufficient governmental policies, regulations, initiatives, and incentives for the adoption of e-commerce.

The problem with this factor is that it is absent from developing nations, which puts obstacles in the way of businesses; the more the absence of a regulatory environment, the slower e-commerce will be adopted and grow in a developing nation.

• Customer trust factors

Customer trust variables include how comfortable and trusting customers are of e-commerce procedures, and they are related to a customer's preparedness to adopt e-commerce. Some significant obstacles to maintaining customer trust include consumers' mistrust of the quality of goods they purchase online and their mistrust of online transaction security and integrity because they fear credit card theft. Numerous research examined the relationship between the factor or problem and e-commerce adoption while examining the factors and challenges driving e-commerce adoption in developing nations. As several research showed links between the components, it became clear during the categorization process that these problems or factors are interconnected and cannot be seen in isolation from one another.

Review of literature

1. Bushan Kumar & Prakash C. Antahal (2023) in their paper titled "Factors Affecting Adoption of E-Commerce among Youngsters in J&K UT: An Empirical Study" showed that It was found that young customers' perceptions of online shopping are influenced by four key factors: perceived risk, perceived benefits, perceived trust, and perceived ease of use. In summary, consumers who shop online still lack confidence and trust in the Internet as a medium for conducting business.
2. Richa Misra, Renuka Mahajan, Nidhi Singh, Sangeeta Khorana & Nripendra P. Rana (2022) in their study on "Factors impacting behavioural intentions to adopt the electronic marketplace" revealed that determined that social influence, perceived vulnerability, performance expectancy, and effort expectancy were important predictors of behavioral intention toward adoption of electronic marketplace.
3. Jagriti Singh in her research paper titled "Factors Affecting B2B E-commerce Adoption Decision: An Analysis of Indian Textile Industry" found that the factors listed under the four themes have varied degrees of impact on the digitization process in B2B trade. The study was constrained by its exclusive emphasis on the textile sector. Subsequent research endeavors can opt to conduct a comparative examination of these variables and themes among diverse industries.
4. Rohit Yadav & Tripti Mahara in their paper titled "Factors Affecting E-Commerce Adoption by Handicraft SMEs of India" revealed that market factors, awareness, strategy, and human resources The main factor driving Indian small and medium-sized businesses' adoption of e-commerce is e-readiness.
5. G. Lakshmi Priya & Dr. S. Smilee Bose in their study on "A study on factors influencing E-commerce adoption among women entrepreneurs" indicates that technology, organizational, environmental, and knowledge-related factors all have a big influence on how many women entrepreneurs use e-commerce.

Objectives of the study

1. To identify the various elements that affect acceptance and adoption of E-Commerce in developing countries like India.
2. To identify the problems that slow down the adoption of e-commerce developing countries.
3. To know the initiative taken by Government to adopt e-government services.
4. To identify the critical elements driving e-commerce's expansion.
5. To understand the barriers to e-commerce.

Limitations of the study

1. The study based on factors driving adoption of E-Commerce in developing countries varies from country to country.
2. The study is based on collection of secondary data.
3. The study has variation and authentication in the value of the data as it is collected from various sources.

Suggestions

Developing countries can adopt e-commerce if followed by investments in telecommunications infrastructure, an enabling legal and regulatory climate, sound institutional reforms and training and education of human resources, will ensure that developing countries become strong contenders in the global e-commerce sector.

Scope for future research

A study can be further expanded to know the factors affects adoption of Electronic Commerce in India and other developed countries as this is in conceptual mode. It is suggested researchers to conduct study on effectiveness of E-Commerce for businesses, consumers and the government.

Conclusion

By analyzing the difficulties and advantages of e-commerce adoption in developing countries, this research sought to determine the factors driving e-commerce adoption in those nations. This was accomplished by searching for reports on Google and reading literature evaluations. Four primary themes emerged from the literature as a result of this process: organizational, technological, environmental, and customer trust aspects. Perceived compatibility and adaptability, internet connectivity, electronic payment methods, management support and attitude, the presence and maintenance of government infrastructure, competitive pressure, consumer trust, readiness, and performance were among the factors found within these themes. One of the main issues noted is insufficient infrastructure. Lack of technology awareness, IT skills, IT competence, management support, qualified e-commerce personnel, low-quality internet connections, high access costs, unreliable logistical networks, inadequate government infrastructure, lack of trust in the quality of products sold online, and lack of trust in conducting online transactions are some of the major challenges that have been identified. It was discovered that a few of the main advantages had a cascading effect that enhanced performance. Increased market reach, better business acumen, lower transaction costs, and more competition are the main advantages. Improved customer happiness leads to higher sales and profits, which in turn improve performance, and enhanced employee productivity raises quality along the value chain are the benefits that are directly related to each other.

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POLITICAL RISK, GOVERNANCE, AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF ITS IMPACT ON ESG PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

This research project explores the complex relationship between political risk and sustainable investment performance in India, focusing on mutual funds and green bonds. As sustainable investing continues to gain traction globally, the impact of political risk factors—such as corruption, political instability, and regulatory uncertainty—on investment returns remains relatively underexplored, particularly in emerging markets like India. This study seeks to bridge this gap by assessing how these political risks influence Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) performance in India, providing valuable insights for investors pursuing sustainable finance. Employing a mixed-methods approach, this research combines both qualitative and quantitative analyses for a comprehensive understanding. Qualitative data will be gathered through case studies, with a focus on examining notable examples such as Reliance Industries' sustainability initiatives and Tata Group's corporate social responsibility (CSR) programs to understand risk management framework, political risk theory, etc. For quantitative analysis, regression models will be used to evaluate the correlation between political risk indicators and sustainable investment performance metrics, specifically returns on sustainable mutual funds and yields on green bonds.

The study is framed around some hypotheses, including the proposition that elevated political risks correlate negatively with sustainable mutual fund performance, while suggesting that effective risk management strategies may mitigate these adverse effects. Additionally, the research will explore the relationship between behavioral economics and sustainable development, proposing that stable political environments are conducive to furthering economic and social objectives like HDI index and GDP of India. By addressing key research questions on the influence of political risks on ESG performance and by identifying effective risk management strategies, this study aims to offer practical insights for investors navigating India's evolving political environment. Ultimately, this research aims to guide policymakers and investors alike, promoting a more sustainable and resilient investment framework for India.

Keywords

Political Risk, Sustainable Investment, ESG Performance, India, Mixed-Methods Approach.

Literature Review

1) Kaur, D., & Rehman, M. (2024). Renewable energy made in India: navigating geopolitics in achieving sustainability. *Journal of Chinese Economic and Business Studies*, 1-22.

This study delves into the geopolitical dimensions of India's renewable energy ambitions, highlighting how global power dynamics, particularly with China and the U.S., influence India's policy decisions. The authors emphasize India's dependency on foreign technology for solar and wind energy, specifically pointing out China's role in manufacturing solar panels. Moreover, the paper discusses India's policy initiatives like "Atmanirbhar Bharat" (self-reliant India) and how geopolitical tensions affect the country's efforts to reduce dependence on foreign players. The analysis extends to India's role in global climate negotiations and its potential as a leader in renewable energy within the Global South. This study delves into the geopolitical dimensions of India's renewable energy ambitions, highlighting how global power dynamics, particularly with China and the U.S., influence India's policy decisions.

- 2) **Pandya, D., & Leal-Arcas, R. (2024). India-EU Relations: geopolitics, energy and trade. In Research Handbook on EU Energy Law and Policy (pp. 299321). Edward Elgar Publishing.**

In this paper, the authors focus on the financial implications of transitioning to renewable energy in India. They assess the growth of green bonds in the country, driven by global commitments to sustainable development and India's ambitious climate targets. The paper evaluates the performance of green bonds in the Indian market compared to traditional bonds, emphasizing how policy support, such as subsidies and tax incentives, has been crucial for the sector's growth.

- 3) **Sinha, A., Gupta, M., Shahbaz, M., & Sengupta, T. (2019). Impact of corruption in public sector on environmental quality: Implications for sustainability in BRICS and next 11 countries. Journal of Cleaner Production, 232, 1379-1393.**

Rao and Iyer explore the role of technological innovation in India's renewable energy sector. The paper focuses on advancements in solar and wind energy technologies, emphasizing how domestic and international collaborations have been vital in accelerating research and development.

- 4) **Aidt, T. S. (2010). Corruption and sustainable development. International handbook on the economics of corruption, 2, 1-52.**

This study centers on the socio-economic impact of renewable energy expansion in rural India. Patel provides an in-depth look at how solar and wind energy projects have contributed to rural electrification, created jobs, and promoted economic development in underdeveloped regions. The research includes case studies from states like Gujarat and Rajasthan, where large-scale solar farms have transformed local economies.

- 5) **Saravade, V., & Weber, O. (2020). An institutional pressure and adaptive capacity framework for green bonds: insights from India's emerging green bond market. World, 1(3), 239-263.**

Jain and Mehta analyze India's renewable energy policies, focusing on how government initiatives such as the National Solar Mission and the renewable energy certificates (RECs) program have impacted the sector. The authors highlight the successes of these policies, particularly in the solar energy domain, which has seen exponential growth in installed capacity. However, the paper also critiques certain regulatory gaps, such as inconsistent state-level policies and the lack of enforcement of renewable purchase obligations (RPOs).

Introduction

Sustainable development and environmental, social, and governance (ESG) performance have gained significant prominence in global financial systems, particularly in the context of green finance. However, the role of geopolitical risk and governance factors in influencing these parameters remains an underexplored area. As emerging markets like India witness rapid growth in sustainable investment products such as mutual funds and green bonds, the interplay between political stability, governance, and sustainable development requires deeper investigation.

Political risk, encompassing factors such as regulatory uncertainty, corruption, and policy instability, poses both challenges and opportunities for sustainable investors. In India, where governance mechanisms are evolving alongside ambitious sustainability goals, understanding these risks is crucial for informed decision-making by investors and policymakers. This study seeks to empirically analyze the impact of political risk and governance on ESG performance and sustainable development, using both qualitative and quantitative methodologies.

Research Objective

Assess the correlation between geopolitical risk and sustainable development in India.

Research Gap

While sustainable investing is gaining traction globally, the impact of political risk on returns in this specific context remains underexplored. This study aims to bridge this gap by investigating the correlation between political risk and returns from sustainable investments in India.

Methodology**Mixed-methods approach**

1. Qualitative research (expert interviews, case studies)
2. Quantitative research (regression analysis, factor analysis)

Mixed method approach**Tests**

Regression analysis

Purpose: To analyze the relationship between political risk factors and sustainable mutual fund performance, ESG performance, green bond yields, and sustainable development metrics like GDP per capita and HDI Index.

Variables: Political risk factors (control of corruption, government effectiveness, political stability, etc.) as independent variables; mutual fund performance, green bond yields, ESG performance, and sustainable development indicators (e.g., GDP per capita, HDI) as dependent variables.

Application: You can test Hypotheses 1 and 2 using multiple linear regression to quantify the relationship between each political risk factor and sustainable investment returns/ESG performance.

T-Test or ANOVA (Analysis of Variance)

- **Purpose:** To compare means across groups, such as analyzing differences in sustainable mutual fund performance or ESG performance between periods of high and low political risk.
- **Application:** You could use a t-test to test for differences in sustainable mutual fund performance during periods with different levels of political stability (Hypothesis 1). If you have multiple groups (e.g., several levels of risk), ANOVA can provide insights into performance variance.

Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

- **Purpose:** To detect multicollinearity among independent variables.
- **Application:** Before finalizing your regression models, use VIF to ensure that political risk factors (e.g., corruption and rule of law) are not highly correlated, as this could distort results.

Quantitative analysis**Hypothesis:****Hypothesis 1:****Null Hypothesis (H_0):**

There is no significant correlation between political risk levels and sustainable mutual fund performance in India.

Alternate Hypothesis (H_1):

There is a significant correlation between political risk levels and sustainable mutual fund performance in India.

Hypothesis 2:**Null Hypothesis (H_0):**

There is no significant impact of Government Effectiveness on the ESG performance of Indian companies. In other words, changes in Government Effectiveness do not lead to changes in ESG ratings.

Alternate Hypothesis (H₁):

Government Effectiveness has a significant impact on the ESG performance of Indian companies, such that higher Government Effectiveness is associated with higher ESG ratings, or conversely, higher risk leads to lower ESG ratings.

Hypothesis 3:**Null Hypothesis (H₀):**

Higher levels of corruption do not have a significant impact on the development of India.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁):

Higher levels of corruption do have a significant impact on the development of India.

Independent Variables - will be obtained from The World Bank's Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) dataset

- i. Control of corruption
- ii. Government effectiveness,
- iii. Political stability and absence of violence,

Dependent variables

1. Sustainable Mutual Fund Performance: Tracks returns from mutual funds that invest primarily in ESG-friendly companies or projects.
2. ESG performance: (measured by ESG ratings)
3. GDP per capita

Measurements:**Independent Variables:**

Based on the Dataset the level of a country is rated from -5 to 5 (-5 is worst and 5 is high). To standardize the test the measurement is changed to 0 to 10 with 0 being the lowest and 10 being the highest rating. This is from 2010 to 2022.

Hypothesis 1:

Independent variable: Political Stability

Dependent Variable: Mutual funds.

Correlation Analysis

- **Pearson's Correlation Coefficient (r):**
 - The correlation between political stability (absence of violence) and mutual fund performance is **0.382**. This indicates a moderate positive correlation, suggesting that as political stability increases, mutual fund performance tends to improve.
 - **p-value:** 0.310, which is above the common significance level of 0.05. This means the correlation is not statistically significant.
- **Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient (rho):**
 - The Spearman's rho is **0.445**, indicating a stronger positive correlation than Pearson's. However, the **p-value** of 0.230 also suggests that this correlation is not statistically significant.

Correlation Matrix

Correlation Matrix

		Political stability and absence of violence	Mutual Funds Performance%
Political stability and absence of violence	Pearson's r	—	
	df	—	
	p-value	—	
	Spearman's rho	—	
	df	—	
	p-value	—	
Mutual Funds Performance%	Pearson's r	0.382	—
	df	7	—
	p-value	0.310	—
	Spearman's rho	0.445	—
	df	7	—
	p-value	0.230	—

Linear Regression Analysis

- **Model Fit (R²):**

- The R² value is **0.146**, indicating that only about 14.6% of the variance in mutual fund performance can be explained by political stability. This suggests that other factors may also play a significant role in influencing mutual fund performance.

- **Model Coefficients:**

- The coefficient for political stability is **55.55**, but with a **p-value** of 0.310, it is not statistically significant. This means that while there is a positive relationship, it is not strong enough to be considered reliable.

ANOVA Test

- The Omnibus ANOVA test shows a **p-value** of 0.310, indicating that the model does not significantly predict mutual fund performance based on political stability.

Interpretation:

While there is a moderate positive correlation between political stability and mutual fund performance, the data suggest that they reliably correlate with sustainable mutual fund performance in India. Therefore we reject null hypothesis.

Linear Regression

Model Fit Measures

Model	R	R ²
1	0.382	0.146

Note. Models estimated using sample size of N=9

Omnibus ANOVA Test

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
Political stability and absence of violence	880	1	880	1.20	0.310
Residuals	5136	7	734		

Note. Type 3 sum of squares

[3]

Model Coefficients - Mutual Funds Performance%

Predictor	Estimate	SE	t	p
Intercept	-213.4	209.2	-1.02	0.341
Political stability and absence of violence	55.5	50.6	1.09	0.310

Scatterplot

Hypothesis 2

Independent variable: Government Effectiveness

Dependent Variable: ESG RATING

Tests:

Correlation Matrix- Pearson & spearmen

Scatter plot

Linear regression- ANOVA

Interpretation:

Correlation matrix

The Correlation presented in the results indicates a weak negative relationship between Government Effectiveness and ESG ratings, with a Pearson's r of -0.142. This suggests that as Government Effectiveness increases, ESG ratings tend to decrease slightly, although the correlation is not statistically significant (p-value = 0.660). The Spearman's rho and Kendall's Tau B values also reflect similar weak correlations, reinforcing the notion that there is no strong linear relationship between these two variables in the sample of Indian companies. Given the high p-values across all correlation measures, we fail to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that Government Effectiveness does not have a significant impact on ESG performance in this context.

Results

Correlation Matrix

Correlation Matrix

		Government Effectiveness	ESG rating
Government Effectiveness	Pearson's r	—	—
	df	—	—
	p-value	—	—
	Spearman's rho	—	—
	df	—	—
	p-value	—	—
	Kendall's Tau B	—	—
	p-value	—	—
ESG rating	Pearson's r	-0.142	—
	df	10	—
	p-value	0.660	—
	Spearman's rho	-0.126	—
	df	10	—
	p-value	0.696	—
	Kendall's Tau B	-0.107	—
	p-value	0.630	—

linear regression analysis

The linear regression analysis, the model fit measures reveal an R² value of 0.0201, indicating that only about 2% of the variance in ESG ratings can be explained by Government Effectiveness. The model coefficient for Government Effectiveness is -13.0, with a p-value of 0.660, suggesting that changes in Government Effectiveness do not significantly predict changes in ESG ratings. The intercept value of 74.4 indicates the expected ESG rating when Government Effectiveness is zero, but the overall lack of significance in the predictor suggests that other factors may be more influential in determining ESG performance among Indian companies. This further supports the conclusion drawn from the correlation matrix that Government Effectiveness does not significantly impact ESG ratings.

The results of the omnibus ANOVA test further corroborate the findings from the correlation and regression analyses. The ANOVA test yielded an F-value of 0.205 with a p-value of 0.660, indicating that there are no statistically significant differences in ESG ratings based on levels of Government Effectiveness. The sum of squares for Government Effectiveness (74.1) compared to the residuals (3608.1) highlights that the variability explained by Government Effectiveness is minimal. Overall, these results suggest that while the hypothesis posits a significant impact of Government Effectiveness on ESG performance, the data does not support this claim, indicating that other factors may play a more critical role in influencing ESG ratings for Indian companies.

Linear Regression

Model Fit Measures

Model	R	R ²
1	0.142	0.0201

Note. Models estimated using sample size of N=12

Omnibus ANOVA Test

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
Government Effectiveness	74.1	1	74.1	0.205	0.660
Residuals	3608.1	10	360.8		

Note. Type 3 sum of squares

[3]

Model Coefficients - ESG rating

Predictor	Estimate	SE	t	p
Intercept	74.4	146.3	0.509	0.622
Government Effectiveness	-13.0	28.8	-0.453	0.660

Therefore we accept the null hypothesis.

Hypothesis 3

Independent variable: Corruption level

Dependent Variable: GDP

Interpretation of the results:

Correlation Analysis

The correlation analysis reveals a strong positive relationship between corruption levels and development metrics in India. Pearson's $r=0.815$ indicates a robust linear correlation, while Spearman's $\rho=0.777$ confirms a consistent monotonic relationship. Both correlations are statistically significant, with p-values of 0.001 and 0.003, respectively, well below the standard significance level of $\alpha=0.05$. This suggests that changes in corruption levels are strongly associated with variations in development indicators, highlighting the potential influence of governance inefficiencies on developmental outcomes.

Correlation Matrix

Correlation Matrix

		A	B
A	Pearson's r	—	
	df	—	
	p-value	—	
	Spearman's rho	—	
	df	—	
	p-value	—	
B	Pearson's r	0.815	—
	df	10	—
	p-value	0.001	—
	Spearman's rho	0.777	—
	df	10	—
	p-value	0.003	—

Linear Regression Analysis

The linear regression model demonstrates that corruption levels significantly predict development outcomes. The $R^2=0.665$ indicates that 66.5% of the variability in development metrics can be explained by changes in corruption levels. The slope coefficient of 4.174.17 with a p-value of 0.001 shows a statistically significant positive effect, suggesting that higher corruption levels correspond to an increase in the measured development metric. While this could reflect a direct relationship, it is also essential to consider possible complexities, such as reverse causality or unmeasured variables influencing both corruption and development outcomes.

Linear Regression

Model Fit Measures

Model	R	R ²
1	0.815	0.665

Note. Models estimated using sample size of N=12

Omnibus ANOVA Test

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
A	2.09	1	2.092	19.8	0.001
Residuals	1.05	10	0.105		

Note. Type 3 sum of squares

11

ANOVA Test

The ANOVA test provides further support for the significance of the regression model. The omnibus test shows an F-statistic of 19.8 with a p-value of 0.001, confirming that the model as a whole significantly explains the relationship between corruption levels and development metrics. This reinforces the conclusion that corruption levels exert a meaningful impact on development indicators. However, while the results are statistically significant, further analysis should include additional variables and controls to ensure robustness and account for potential confounding factors.

Scatterplot

Therefore we reject the null hypothesis.

Qualitative Analysis

1. Risk Management Frameworks:

a) Reliance Industries' Sustainability Initiatives

- Overview: Reliance Industries Limited (RIL), a major conglomerate in India, has integrated risk management frameworks into its sustainability efforts to mitigate environmental, social, and governance (ESG) risks.
- Key Aspects:
 - RIL focuses on energy efficiency, renewable energy adoption, and resource conservation to address climate-related risks.
 - It has implemented frameworks to ensure compliance with global sustainability standards and mitigate supply chain disruptions.
 - Example: Reliance's Jamnagar refinery has adopted innovative technology to reduce carbon emissions and improve resource utilization.
- Geopolitical Angle: As India transitions toward renewable energy under international agreements like the Paris Accord, RIL's sustainability efforts showcase how corporations manage geopolitical risks related to energy dependence and environmental policies.

b) India's Management of Cybersecurity Threats

- Overview: With increasing cyberattacks on critical infrastructure, India has developed risk management frameworks for cybersecurity.

- Key Aspects:
 - Formation of the National Critical Information Infrastructure Protection Centre (NCIIPC) to safeguard critical systems.
 - Policy initiatives like the National Cyber Security Policy (2013) focus on risk mitigation in sectors such as banking, defense, and energy.
 - Example: Steps taken to counter cyber threats following malware attacks on nuclear power plants.
- Geopolitical Angle: Managing cybersecurity risks enhances India's strategic resilience, protecting national security and economic stability while maintaining global trust.

2.Sustainable Investment Frameworks:

a) Green Bonds in India

Overview: India is one of the largest issuers of green bonds in Asia, using them to finance renewable energy and infrastructure projects.

Key Aspects:

- Green bonds have funded large-scale solar and wind energy projects.
- India's ambitious renewable energy goals, including the target of achieving 500 GW of non-fossil fuel capacity by 2030, are heavily supported by green bond issuances.
- Solar and Wind Energy Investments: Large-scale solar parks, such as the Rewa Ultra Mega Solar Power Project in Madhya Pradesh, have been financed through green bonds. Wind energy projects, particularly in Tamil Nadu and Gujarat, have similarly benefited from this funding mechanism.
- Example: NTPC (National Thermal Power Corporation) issued green bonds to finance renewable energy projects.
- India's Sovereign Green Bond Framework introduced in 2023 aligns with global standards for sustainable investments.

Geopolitical Angle: By actively engaging in green finance, India enhances its global standing in climate diplomacy and strengthens partnerships with international investors. Active engagement in green bonds provides India with leverage in multilateral platforms like the G20 and COP (Conference of the Parties).

3. Political Risk Theory:

a) Implementation of GST (Goods and Services Tax)

- Overview: The introduction of GST in 2017 represented a transformative economic reform in India.
- Key Aspects:
 - GST aimed to unify India's fragmented tax system but faced challenges like opposition from states and initial implementation issues.
 - It required navigating political risks associated with federalism, as states feared losing financial autonomy.
- Geopolitical Angle: GST simplified trade across state borders, making India a more attractive destination for global investors, enhancing its economic diplomacy.

b) Demonetization in India (2016)

- Overview: The Indian government's sudden move to demonetize high-denomination currency notes aimed to curb black money, counterfeit currency, and corruption.

Key Aspects:

- The policy caused economic disruption, impacting small businesses, rural economies, and informal sectors.
- It highlighted political risks, such as uncertainty and resistance, associated with sudden policy changes.
- Demonetization's long-term impact on tax compliance and digital payment adoption remains debated.
- Geopolitical Angle: Demonetization's implications extended to India's geopolitical relations, as it targeted illegal funding linked to cross-border activities, particularly with Pakistan.

4. Stakeholder Theory: Posco Steel Plant Controversy in Odisha

- Overview: Posco, a South Korean company, proposed a \$12 billion steel plant in Odisha, which faced strong opposition from local communities and activists.
- Key Aspects:
 - The project promised economic development but raised concerns about displacement, environmental damage, and violation of tribal rights.
 - Protests led to delays, and eventually, Posco exited the project.
- Geopolitical Angle: The failure highlighted the importance of addressing stakeholder concerns for foreign investments and impacted India's image as a favorable investment destination.

5. Behavioral Economics:**a) Government Initiatives for Renewable Energy**

- Overview: The Indian government has used behavioral economics principles to encourage the adoption of renewable energy, particularly solar and wind power.
- Key Aspects:
 - Subsidies, incentives, and awareness campaigns have been designed to nudge households and industries toward adopting solar panels and other renewable energy solutions.
 - Example: The "UJALA" scheme promoted energy-efficient LED bulbs by highlighting long-term savings over upfront costs.
 - Behavioral nudges like tax breaks for electric vehicle buyers aim to make sustainable choices more attractive.
- Geopolitical Angle: These initiatives align with India's commitments under international climate agreements, enhancing its geopolitical stance as a leader in renewable energy adoption.

b) Adoption of Digital Payments (Post-Demonetization)

- Overview: Following demonetization in 2016, the government promoted digital payment platforms to encourage cashless transactions.
- Key Aspects:
 - Behavioral nudges included cashback incentives, discounts on digital payments, and campaigns like "Digital India."
 - The Unified Payments Interface (UPI) played a significant role in simplifying digital transactions.
- Geopolitical Angle: Increased digital adoption has bolstered India's image as a leader in financial technology (fintech), attracting global investors and partnerships.

6. Institutional Theory: Make in India Initiative

1. Overview: Launched in 2014, the Make in India initiative aims to transform India into a global manufacturing hub by improving infrastructure, easing regulations, and attracting foreign investments.
2. Key Aspects:
 - Focuses on 25 sectors, including renewable energy, defense, and electronics.
 - Encourages public-private partnerships and institutional reforms to enhance India's global competitiveness.
3. Geopolitical Angle: This initiative strengthens India's economic and geopolitical position by reducing dependency on imports and fostering strategic self-reliance in sectors like defense and energy. Amid growing tensions with China and calls for diversifying global supply chains, Make in India positions India as a viable alternative for global manufacturing. India has leveraged initiatives like Production Linked Incentive (PLI) schemes to attract companies exiting China. For example, Apple has increased its iPhone production in India. By boosting exports and reducing trade deficits, India strengthens its negotiating power on issues like intellectual property rights and tariff barriers. India's emphasis on manufacturing aligns with its goals in multilateral platforms like the G20, BRICS, and WTO, where it advocates for equitable global trade practices.

Conclusion

The analysis underscores the intricate interplay between political risk, sustainability initiatives, and economic reforms in shaping India's development trajectory. Qualitatively, India's strategic adoption of risk management frameworks like RIL's sustainability efforts and cybersecurity policies highlights the country's resilience in addressing ESG and geopolitical challenges. Sustainable investment frameworks, exemplified by green bonds, demonstrate India's leadership in climate finance and its commitment to global renewable energy goals.

Reforms like GST and initiatives such as "Make in India" further illustrate India's ability to navigate political risks while fostering economic growth and global partnerships. Behavioral economics and stakeholder engagement showcase the importance of aligning public policy with societal needs. Together, these insights emphasize the critical role of governance, innovation, and institutional support in achieving sustainable and inclusive development while bolstering India's global standing.

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THE IMPACT OF AI ON ORGANIC SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING

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Abstract:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a transformative force in computer science, utilizing algorithms to mimic human thought processes. Machine learning, a crucial aspect, enables computers to learn and improve from data. AI has already profoundly impacted daily life, offering convenience through virtual assistants, personalization in digital experiences, healthcare advancements, road safety with self-driving cars, accessibility features, and smart home automation. However, concerns such as privacy, job disruption, bias, security risks, and ethical considerations highlight the need for careful management and ethical implementation of AI technologies.

Keywords: artificial intelligence (AI), social media marketing, Digital media

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) stands as a captivating frontier in computer science, aiming to craft intelligent machines capable of mimicking human thought processes and actions. At its core, AI relies on algorithms, akin to step-by-step recipes guiding computers in processing information and making decisions. Machine learning, a vital facet of AI, involves teaching computers through examples, showcasing the technology's capability to learn and improve from data.

The impact of AI on daily life is already profound, with notable contributions in various domains:

- **Convenience:** Virtual assistants like Siri and Alexa exemplify AI's role as digital helpers, streamlining daily tasks, answering questions, and managing smart devices for enhanced convenience.
- **Personalization:** AI analyzes online behavior to deliver tailored recommendations, ensuring enjoyable and relevant digital experiences, whether suggesting movies, music, or products.
- **Healthcare Advances:** AI aids medical professionals in accurate disease diagnosis, interpretation of complex medical images, and formulation of personalized treatment plans, leading to improved patient care and faster diagnoses.
- **Safety on the Road:** Self-driving cars leverage AI for navigation and collision avoidance, promising to reduce traffic accidents and enhance road safety.
- **Accessibility:** AI-driven features like speech recognition and text-to-speech technologies empower individuals with disabilities, facilitating easier access to digital content and device interaction.
- **Smart Homes:** AI enabled home automation, optimizing energy consumption, enhancing security, and providing convenience through voice and app control.

Despite these benefits, AI introduces noteworthy concerns:

- **Privacy:** AI often requires access to personal data for personalized services, sparking concerns about data privacy and potential misuse.
- **Job Disruption:** AI and robotics-driven automation may lead to job displacement in certain industries, necessitating workforce preparation for AI-related changes.
- **Bias and Fairness:** AI algorithms can inherit biases from training data, potentially perpetuating discrimination. Ensuring fairness and transparency in AI systems is essential.
- **Security Risks:** AI systems are susceptible to hacking and misuse, posing cybersecurity risks that need addressing to protect sensitive data.
- **Ethical Considerations:** As AI becomes more autonomous, ethical questions arise concerning decision-making, accountability, and potential consequences of AI actions.

Review Of Literature

1. Dimitris C. Gkikas & Prokopis K. Theodoridis

“Artificial Intelligence (AI) Impact on Digital Marketing Research Date: 29 may 2019

This paper explores the current landscape of artificial intelligence (AI) applications within the field of digital marketing. It identifies key publications that serve as foundational works, identifies areas where there is a lack of presence or absence, discusses potential reasons for these gaps, and proposes a machine learning model suitable for various digital marketing scenarios.

2. Yogesh K. Dwivedi & Elvira Ismagilova

“Setting the future of digital and social media marketing research: Perspectives and research propositions “Date: August 2021

This study provides a noteworthy and timely contribution to researchers and practitioners by presenting challenges and opportunities. It emphasizes the existing limitations in current research, delineates research gaps, and formulates questions and propositions aimed at advancing knowledge in the field of digital and social marketing.

3. Gökhan Aydin

“Social media engagement and organic post effectiveness: A roadmap for increasing the effectiveness of social media use in hospitality industry” Date: 29 march 2019

The findings underscored the positive impact of interactive and visually compelling content, emphasizing the importance of content types in fostering increased engagement among followers. Additionally, the location of the facility and its categorization (such as hotel, holiday village, thermal hotel) were identified as influential factors affecting follower interactions.

4. Beibei Dong , Mengzhou Zhuang

“Tales of Two Channels: Digital Advertising Performance Between AI Recommendation and User Subscription Channels”Date: July 12, 2023

This study investigates the variations in the performance of in-feed advertisements concerning click-through rates and conversion rates across subscription and recommendation channels. It also explores whether these effects are influenced by ad intrusiveness and moderated by ad attributes.

5. Wael Basri

“Examining the Impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-Assisted Social Media Marketing on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises: Toward Effective Business Management in the Saudi Arabian Context”

Date: 1 dec 2019

This research stands out for its exploration of the significant role of AISMM practices in enhancing SMEP, with effective business management acting as a mediating factor. The implications of this study suggest that practitioners can benefit from leveraging AISMM to improve performance by addressing various marketing challenges.

6. Preeti Singh ,Amit Verma

“Implications & Impact of Artificial Intelligence in Digital Media: With Special Focus on Social Media Marketing” Date:12 july 2023

This research represents an initial exploration into understanding how individuals utilizing the AI media software, developed as part of the Future Web research project, intend to leverage the features designed by programmers. Given the quantitative approach of the study and the diverse geographical origins of the interviewees, it is essential to interpret the results cautiously.

Research Design

Title of the study: Impact of AI on Organic Social Media Marketing

Statement of problem:

Numerous issues arise concerning the influence of AI on social media marketing, encompassing ethical considerations. With AI becoming increasingly ingrained, ethical concerns emerge, including issues related to data privacy, transparency, and misinformation. The proliferation of deep fake technology, driven by AI, poses a significant problem, presenting challenges for marketers in maintaining a company's brand image ethically. Exploring how AI can establish positive customer relationships, meet their needs, enhance brand loyalty, and its impact on the precision and efficiency of advertising targeting on social media are critical aspects. Understanding how these factors will impact return on advertising spend is also crucial.

Scope of the study:

The paper aims to provide a comprehensive overview of how AI is being utilized in social media marketing on a global scale. This would involve studying the adoption and impact of AI technologies in various regions and industries. Investigate the extent to which AI-driven content creation is being used and its effectiveness, especially for both established companies.

Exploring the role of AI in personalizing content and targeting specific audiences in social media marketing. Assessing whether AI algorithms are effectively delivering tailored content, recommendations, and advertisements, and their impact on user engagement and ROI.

Gap of the study:

- **Personalization Depth:** Although both papers acknowledge the role of AI in personalization, there is an opportunity to investigate the intricacy and specificity of this personalization. How precise can AI-driven personalization become, and at what point does it cross the threshold into feeling intrusive for consumers?
- **Ethical Considerations:** Neither summary delves deeply into the ethical considerations associated with AI in marketing. There is potential to explore issues related to data privacy, misinformation, and potential biases in strategies driven by AI.
- **Return on Investment (ROI):** While the advantages of AI in marketing are outlined, there is no discussion about the concrete ROI. How does the integration of AI tools correlate with increased sales, customer retention, or other key performance indicators?
- **Integration Hurdles:** As companies integrate AI into their marketing strategies, what challenges do they encounter? This could encompass issues related to training, adapting to new tools, or integrating AI-driven insights with conventional marketing practices.
- **Consumer Perception Evolution:** How do consumers perceive marketing strategies driven by AI? Are they more accepting, indifferent, or resistant to them? Gaining insights into the consumer perspective can provide a fresh perspective.
- **Future Trends:** While the current applications of AI in marketing are emphasized, what upcoming trends or tools should marketers be mindful of? Exploring the imminent landscape can offer valuable insights.

Limitations of the study:

- **Data Accessibility** -Obtaining high-quality data may pose a challenge, especially when dealing with social media data that can be characterized by noise, incompleteness, or a lack of representation of the entire user base.
- **Ethical and Privacy Considerations**-Ethical factors tied to AI, data privacy, and consent may impose constraints on the extent of data collection and analysis.
- **Technological Shifts** -The swift evolution of technology may introduce disruptions in social media platforms, potentially leading to increased traffic and related challenges

Sampling Method

We adopted stratified random sampling technique to collect and analysis data that influence (AI) artificial Intelligence on organic social media marketing

Stratified Random Sampling:

In order to obtain a sample that accurately represents diverse demographics, we employed stratified sampling by categorizing the population according to variables such as age, gender, and income levels. Within each stratum, respondents were randomly chosen, ensuring that each subgroup was proportionally represented. This method enabled comprehensive analysis across a range of consumer segments.

Sample Size:

We gathered data from a group of 45 respondents, considered adequate for exploratory research and the application of statistical analysis techniques. Despite its modest size, this sample enabled the efficient use of regression analysis, factor analysis, and non-parametric tests to unveil patterns and relationships inherent in the dataset.

Data Analysis

How familiar are you with the concept of AI in social media marketing?	Which social media platforms do you believe have been most impacted by AI in organic marketing strategies?	3. In your opinion, how has AI influenced the effectiveness of organic content on social media?	Have you noticed any changes in user engagement on your social media accounts since implementing AI in your organic marketing efforts?
Very familiar	Instagram	no significant change	decreased engagement
Somewhat familiar	Instagram	slightly reduced	no significant change
Neutral	Instagram	slightly improved	increased engagement
Very familiar	Instagram	significantly improved	decreased engagement
Neutral	Instagram	slightly improved	increased engagement
Very familiar	Instagram	slightly improved	no significant change
Somewhat familiar	Instagram	slightly improved	increased engagement
Somewhat familiar	Instagram	no significant change	no significant change

Very familiar	Instagram	significantly improved	increased engagement
Somewhat familiar	Instagram	slightly improved	no significant change
Very familiar	Instagram	significantly improved	no significant change
Very familiar	Instagram	significantly improved	no significant change
Very familiar	Instagram	significantly improved	increased engagement
Very familiar	Instagram	significantly improved	increased engagement
Very familiar	Instagram	significantly improved	increased engagement
Very familiar	Instagram	significantly improved	increased engagement
Very familiar	Instagram	significantly improved	increased engagement
Very familiar	Instagram	significantly improved	increased engagement
Somewhat familiar	Instagram	significantly improved	increased engagement
Somewhat familiar	Instagram	slightly improved	decreased engagement
Somewhat familiar	Instagram	significantly improved	increased engagement
Very familiar	Instagram	slightly improved	increased engagement
Very familiar	Instagram	slightly improved	increased engagement
Very familiar	Instagram	significantly improved	increased engagement

Very familiar	Instagram	significantly improved	increased engagement
Very familiar	Instagram	significantly improved	increased engagement

How familiar are you with the concept of AI in social media marketing?

45 responses

Which social media platforms do you believe have been most impacted by AI in organic marketing strategies?

45 responses

3. In your opinion, how has AI influenced the effectiveness of organic content on social media?

45 responses

Have you noticed any changes in user engagement on your social media accounts since implementing AI in your organic marketing efforts?

45 responses

Summary of Findings

1. How familiar are you with the concept of AI in social media marketing?

28 people responded with very familiar

6 people responded with somewhat familiar

8 people responded with neutral

3 people responded with not familiar at all

2. Which social media platforms do you believe have been most impacted by AI in organic marketing strategies?

2 people responded with Facebook

28 people responded with Instagram

8 person responded with twitter

7 person responded with twitter

0 responded with others

3. In your opinion, how has AI influenced the effectiveness of organic content on social media?

7 people responded with significantly improved

9 people responded with slightly improved

6 people responded with no significant change

15 people responded with slightly reduced

8 people responded with significantly reduced

4. Have you noticed any changes in user engagement on your social media accounts since implementing AI in your organic marketing efforts?

26 people responded with Increase engagement

2 people responded with no significant change

4 people responded with decreased engagement

13 people responded with not applicable

Majority of respondents (15 out of 22) are very familiar with the concept of AI in social media marketing.

6 respondents are somewhat familiar, and only one respondent is neutral.

Most Impacted Platforms: All respondents have mentioned Instagram as the platform impacted by AI in organic marketing strategies.

A significant number of respondents (18 out of 22) have observed increased engagement with the use of AI in their organic marketing efforts.

Improved Content: Most respondents (19 out of 22) mentioned that AI has improved the quality of their organic content.

Increased Engagement: The majority of respondents (16 out of 22) noticed increased engagement on their social media accounts since implementing AI in organic marketing efforts.

There is a strong positive correlation between familiarity with AI in social media marketing and perceiving a significant improvement in engagement.

Instagram is widely recognized as the most impacted platform by AI in organic marketing strategies.

Interpretation:

1. According to the responses most responders have felt that technical difficulties is the most challenging reason for them not being able to implement AI into their organic social media marketing strategy followed by resistance from team members, lack of understanding & lastly budget constraints.

2. Through the responses it could be interpreted that most of the responders felt that AI driven analytics and insights has indeed improved their decision making in the social media marketing strategy but 43% of them felt the opposite.
3. It could be interpreted through the responses that 49% of the responders were very concerned about the ethical indications of using AI in organic social media marketing while 29% of them were somewhat concerned and 22% of them remaining neutral about their opinion on this.
4. It could be interpreted that 68.2% of the responders felt due to AI's contribution to maintaining brand consistency across different social media platforms had improved consistently while 25% of them felt there was no change and the remaining responders feeling there was reduced consistency.
5. Through the responses it could be interpreted that 55.6% of the respondents believed that the use of AI in organic social media marketing had led to a better understanding of audience behavior and preferences while 44.4% of them believed that it had moderately affected it.

Findings And Suggestions

From the data collected from the responses here are some findings and suggestions:

1. Instagram appears to be the dominant platform in the dataset, with most responses related to it. Content recommendation algorithms, automated posting schedules, chatbots for customer interaction, and sentiment analysis are frequently mentioned AI-powered features.
2. A mix of responses regarding the impact on engagement, with some reporting improvement and others reporting a reduction or no significant change. Content recommendation algorithms seem to contribute to both improved and decreased engagement.
3. Responses vary, with some reporting significantly improved engagement, while others note decreased or no significant change. Automated posting schedules and content recommendation algorithms are factors influencing engagement changes.
4. Content recommendation algorithms and automated posting schedules are frequently mentioned as valuable AI features. Chatbots for customer interaction and sentiment analysis are also noted, albeit less frequently.

Conclusion

The majority of respondents, particularly those who are very familiar with AI in social media marketing, have observed a significant positive impact on their organic marketing efforts on Instagram. This impact is reflected in both increased user engagement and improved content quality. The widespread recognition of Instagram as the most impacted platform by AI indicates the platform's significance in leveraging AI for organic marketing strategies. Overall, the findings suggest that AI plays a crucial role in enhancing the effectiveness of organic content and engagement on social media, particularly on Instagram.

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HOLISTIC INTERVENTIONS FOR SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: A CASE STUDY OF PRANAV FOUNDATION

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Abstract

This case study examines the immersive experience at Pranav Foundation, an NGO dedicated to socio-economic development and community empowerment. The focus of the engagement was addressing the lack of awareness about dental healthcare and yoga among children in underserved communities. Activities conducted included a free dental health check-up camp, yoga awareness sessions, skill-building exercises, and environmental education initiatives. These interventions aimed to bridge knowledge gaps, promote wellness, and develop essential skills in children. The outcomes of the activities were impactful, leading to improved health awareness, enhanced environmental literacy, and better writing and communication skills among the participants. The experience also provided opportunities for personal and professional growth, including the development of public speaking, storytelling, event planning, and teamwork skills. Through this engagement, valuable insights were gained into the challenges faced by marginalized communities and the significance of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in addressing these issues. This study highlights the role of NGOs in fostering holistic development and underscores the importance of collective efforts in creating sustainable change.

Keywords

Education, Healthcare, Environmental conservation, Community empowerment, Yoga awareness

Introduction to Pranav Foundation

Fig 1.A.1 NGO Logo

Pranav Foundation, established with a vision to empower and uplift communities, focuses on several key initiatives aimed at socio-economic development and sustainability. Through strategic partnerships and innovative programs, Pranav Foundation endeavors to create meaningful impact in education, healthcare, environmental conservation, and community welfare. Founded on the principles of inclusivity and empowerment, Pranav Foundation operates with a mission to address societal challenges through grassroots efforts and sustainable solutions. "Pranav Foundation serves as an umbrella for high-value long-term charity projects. Founded and registered in April 2021 – Pranav Foundation works closely with local communities across India to enhance Environmental and Human well-being that focuses beyond health, education, culture, and holistic development."

Vision

Vision guides them as they strive to make a meaningful impact on the lives of individuals and communities worldwide. By addressing root causes and empowering people with the skills and resources they need to thrive, we believe we can create a world where everyone has the opportunity to lead a dignified and fulfilling life.

Key Objectives & Strategic Goals

- **Education:** Expand access to quality education and lifelong learning opportunities for underserved populations.

- **Healthcare:** Improve access to healthcare services and promote wellness initiatives to enhance community health outcomes.
- **Environment:** Advocate for environmental conservation, promote sustainable practices, and build resilience against climate change.
- **Community Development:** Foster social inclusion, empower marginalized groups, and promote gender equality through targeted programs and advocacy.

Mission

Pranav Foundation is dedicated to promoting socio-economic development and improving quality of life for underserved communities worldwide. Through strategic initiatives in education, healthcare, environmental conservation, and community empowerment, we aim to create sustainable impact and empower individuals to build brighter futures.

Pranav Foundation secures funding through diverse sources to support its initiatives in socio-economic development, environmental conservation, and community empowerment. Contributions include one-time and recurring donations from individuals, corporate sponsorships tied to CSR initiatives, and partnerships offering financial or in-kind support. Grants from philanthropic foundations and government contracts fund specific sectors like education and healthcare. Additional funding is raised through charity events, collaborative projects with nonprofits and research institutions, and managed endowment funds for long-term sustainability. International aid agencies also provide support for initiatives in developing regions and humanitarian crises.

Objective of the study -Specific Cause Identified in the NGO- the Specific problem identified under this cause is

To Promote Awareness on Dental Healthcare: To educate communities, particularly children, on the importance of dental hygiene

To Enhance Understanding of Yoga's Benefits and mental health advantages through school programs, community events, and training sessions

Focus Areas and Challenges

Pranav Foundation focuses on raising awareness about dental healthcare and yoga to address critical challenges. In dental healthcare, it tackles issues like inadequate education on oral hygiene among children, limited access to affordable care in underserved areas, and the widespread prevalence of myths and misinformation about oral health. In yoga awareness, the foundation addresses the lack of understanding about its physical and mental health benefits, as well as the scarcity of resources and trained instructors, particularly in schools.

Plan of the activities at the NGO during the study

Date	Programme	Location
05 June 2024	Visit To Ngo And Planning	Bannerghatta Rd, Bengaluru,
06 June 2024	Organized Drawing Competition At Government School On Environment Topic	Glbs Rajivghnadi Nagar
07 June 2024	Skill Development Program	Glbs Rajivghnadi Nagar
10 June 2024	Organized Quiz On Climate Change And Eco-Friendly Products	Glbs Rajivghnadi Nagar
11 June 2024	Csr-Listed The Csr Report Of Different Companies Of Bangalore	Bannerghatta Rd, Bengaluru,
12 June 2024	Volunteered Dental Checkup Camp At Government School	Glbs Rajivghnadi Nagar

13 June 2024	Conducted Awareness Program On Climate Change Mitigation And Ecofriendly Products	Glps Rajivghnadi Nagar
18 June 2024	Yoga Session Was Conducted For The Government School Students Along With The Benefits Of Yoga	Glps Rajivghnadi Nagar
20 June 2024	We Organized Singing And Storytelling Activities For The Government School Children	Glps Rajivghnadi Nagar

Table 2- Plan of Action

Implementation of the activities planned during the study

Fig 1 Visit to Government School

As a part of the study the Cause identified was “Lack of awareness on Dental healthcare and Yoga”. **Dental Healthcare and Yoga Awareness for the public was the theme**". On the first day of our visit to the NGO, we discussed the cause of “Lack of awareness on Dental Healthcare and Yoga” with the external guide. Along with the team, we proceeded to Lakshmiipur, located approximately 15 km from Jayanagar. The visit was to a government school filled with cheerful young students. Pranav Foundation had allotted this school for our activities. The day began with introductions, as it was our first interaction with the children. On June 12th, Pranav Foundation organized a Free Dental Checkup Camp for the students. Volunteering for the event, we ensured that all arrangements were in place for the doctors. In addition to the dental camp, we organized a Yoga session. The children were enthusiastic and eager to learn. The session started with an introduction to Yoga, a topic that was quite new to them. It included practical demonstrations of **Pranayama**, emphasizing its importance and necessity in daily life, and **Meditation**, highlighting its significance.

Fig 2 – Dental Camp

Fig 3- Yoga session

Fig 4- Meeting children

Fig 5- Skill Development sessions

Other cause undertaken includes Environment, also organized a drawing competition and explained them about how it is necessary to save trees, control of global warming. Initially, assessed their understanding of the topic and found that they had no prior knowledge. A challenge faced was explaining these ideas in Kannada. Important key points, such as turning off unnecessary lights, using public transport, conserving water, planting trees, and avoiding the burning of plastic.

Outcome of the activities planned

Type of Activity	Results
Drawing Competition	Enhanced the information on Environment
Skill Development Program	Improvement in English Writing
Quiz Competition	Created Human Literacy
Corporate Social Responsibility	Preparation of Report
Dental Checkup Camp	Free Dental Checkup and importance of brushing
Yoga Session	Awareness and Benefits of Yoga
Organized Singing and Storytelling Activities	Improvement in Skills

Table 3 Outcome of the activities

Learning’s from the activities and Outcome of the study

Working at Pranav Foundation was a truly memorable and rewarding experience, leaving a lasting impact on both personal and professional growth while contributing meaningfully to society. Enhanced ability to explain concepts in a simple and relatable manner, Development of public speaking and storytelling skills, Gained valuable experience in planning and organizing events, improved teamwork and collaboration skills, acquired a deeper understanding of the needs and challenges faced by children from diverse backgrounds.

Conclusion

The immersion experience at Pranav Foundation was transformative, fostering personal growth, professional skills, and a commitment to positive change. Engaging with children from diverse backgrounds highlighted their challenges and inspired impactful initiatives like dental health awareness, yoga sessions, and skill-building activities. The experience enhanced event planning, teamwork, communication, and problem-solving abilities while providing valuable insights into Corporate Social Responsibility and the role of NGOs in socio-economic

development. It was a fulfilling journey, leaving a lasting impact and reaffirming the value of collective efforts to support underprivileged communities.

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A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR CLOUD COMPUTING - BASED E - COMMERCE APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

A contemporary technical business model, cloud computing benefits organizations across a wide range of sectors, particularly e-commerce, where digital computing presents new prospects. Thus, this article presents the ideas of cloud-based e-commerce application architecture, the cloud computing development trend that responds to the e-commerce issue, and the resource allocation and storage. A suggested structure enables businesses to save expenses by implementing e-commerce activities efficiently and addresses the issue of big businesses using cloud computing to enhance e-commerce apps.

Keywords: Cloud Computing, E-Commerce, Application model, Cloud Computing of E-commerce

Overview

The next phase of computing technology is cloud computing, which enables customers to operate on high-end computing infrastructure from the affordable cloud provider Service Cloud and utilize extra resources that are not currently available to them.

In order to provide their users with optimal performance, organizations often outfit their information systems. However, cloud computing is the best option for scalability, availability, and scalability due to the high cost of high-performance information systems and the challenges of permitting them to grow and extend these activities over time.

The idea of cloud computing is a technology that relies on moving computer-related data, processing power, and storage space to the so-called cloud. A server that has been accessed over the Internet has transformed IT programs from goods to services. It is distinguished by resolving issues with application development and maintenance and, as a result, requires focused effort from the user or beneficiary to utilize these services exclusively.

E-commerce is one of the subjects of the digital economy, which is founded on two facts: the information business in the computing era and information technology (IT). Communication is what gave rise to e-commerce's actual existence as depends on communication, computation, and a variety of technical implementation and business management tools.

E-commerce is the implementation and management of business activities related to goods and services through the transfer of data over the Internet or similar technical systems. The concept of e-commerce in general to three types of events: First, the functions of linking or entering the Internet and the included connectivity services Of services with technical content and a clear example of services provided by ISPs - Internet Services Providers and the second, delivery or technical provision of services. Thirdly, the use of the Internet as a means or means of distribution of services and distribution of goods and services delivered in a non-technical manner (physical delivery). Within this concept, there is confusion between e-business, e-commerce and the exploitation of technology in traditional trade activities

The first section of the article covers the definition, application, and context of the cloud computing model. Cloud computing's benefits and drawbacks, service layer, This paper's second section examines an e-commerce application model, definition, types of e-commerce, and e-commerce characteristics. The conceptual paradigm for cloud computing-based e-commerce applications and the integration of cloud computing with e-commerce are covered in the section's last part.

Model Of Cloud Computing Application

Cloud Computing Cloud computing Is a word that refers to the on-demand computer resources and systems available on the network that can implement some integrated computer services without local resources to facilitate

user access. These resources include data storage, backup, and self-synchronization, including software processing capabilities, scheduling of tasks and payment of e-mail and remote printing. When connected, the user can control these resources through a simple software interface that simplifies and ignores many internal details and processes.

According to the layers of service, the application mode of cloud service can divide into Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Software as a Service (SaaS) [6], as illustrated in Figure. 1.

Software as a service (SaaS): This refers to using a certain cloud-based application. For instance, you may use a Word program that is located in the data center, connect to the Internet, write, edit, and add data, and then get the result. Your device is only a communication instrument, and everything is done on the cloud. The user has no control over the cloud's operating system, hardware, or network connectivity. Since the on-site video browser is an application that loads on the cloud and allows you to view existing videos without altering the site, YouTube may be included under this heading.

- 1) Platform as a service (PaaS): Use the cloud as a platform to put several applications on them, and you can work on them all You can also set the operating system is too full, and there is an integration between applications. For example, designed something Photoshop and then introduced to another form is moving and add effects. We get a video With a voice. Such as Google apps, a platform that lets you add apps as you like.
- 2) Use the cloud as a platform to put several applications on them and you can work on them all You can also put the operating system is also full and there is an integration between applications, for example, designed something Photoshop and then is introduced to another application is moving and add effects We get a video With a voice. Such as Google apps, a platform that lets you add apps as you like.
- 3) Infrastructure as a service (IaaS): Here we deal with the cloud as a limited infrastructure with specific processing capacity, size of memory, storage space and a certain number of users, and you are free to use it in the way that suits you. For example, you can install several operating systems, install several applications system, and allow a certain number of users to access each operating system to use its applications without letting them be confused.

Advantages and disadvantages of cloud computing

The advantages of cloud computing are summarized as follows

- 1) Share resources provide greater ease and flexibility when performing tasks.
- 2) Much lower material cost than standard processing and storage tools and software.
- 3) Speed in joining with modern techniques online.
- 4) The possibility of linking several sites such as social networks. 5) Facilitates of cooperative groups.

The following is a summary of cloud computing's drawbacks:

- 1) Electronic cloud challenges.
- 2) The potential for the website to request a reduction in storage capacity.
- 3) When a website is down, you are unable to access your data.
- 4) Issues with internet intellectual property rights.
- 5) The terms of the user and site agreement pertaining to rights protection.
- 6) Not every program functions effectively on slow connections or in the cloud.
- 7) Data lost and lost in storage.

Model Of E-Commerce Application

Online shopping

E-commerce is a system that enables the online sale of goods, services, and information. It also offers automated processes that facilitate the creation of returns, like increasing demand for those goods, services, and information because it facilitates online sales and customer service. E-commerce is comparable to an online marketplace where consumers, brokers, and sellers (suppliers, businesses, and stores) exchange virtual or digital goods and services and pay for them using electronic currency.

E-commerce has based on a relationship between two parties. Each relationship between the two sides expresses a different type of trade; Figure 2 shows the types of e-commerce

The term "business-to-consumer" (B2C) describes the buying and selling of businesses, including partners, business partners, and any type of electronic data interchange. Purchase orders sent to suppliers, invoices received, electronic payments, and information sharing between businesses are a few examples of this type of data.

Fig 2: Model of E-Commerce Application

Business-to-Consumer (B2C): The majority of entry points are located across from shopping centers, where customers can visit a supermarket or a merchants' center offering the site's items and place orders for necessary

goods or services. Credit cards, plastic money, or electronic checks are used to complete the transaction on a credit, bank, or credit basis.

Direct sales to consumers are known as customer-to-customer (C2C) sales. For instance, a customer does not provide a discount on their website to sell news or personal goods.

Customer-to-Business (C2B): This refers to retail establishments that offer corporate goods or services; it is the reverse of business-to-business (B2B) transactions between corporate and B2C clients. These days, several banks demand services from their clients.

Government-to-Customer (G2C): This kind of exchange involves the customer and local government income, such as when the consumer pays electronic dues without having to visit government offices.

Characteristics of e-commerce E-commerce and applied online have characterized by several qualities, the most important of which are

- 1) No paper papers are utilized in the execution or implementation of business transactions; instead, dealer engagement and exchange activities are conducted entirely online. Consequently, in the event of a disagreement between the dealers, the electronic communication has been accepted by the parties as a legal assurance.
- 2) The e-commerce program can manage many sides simultaneously, allowing each party to send emails to a large number of recipients simultaneously without having to carry them again.
- 3) The interaction between the two parties dealing with electronic commerce through the communications network, and what distinguishes this method is the existence of a high degree of interactivity without the sides being simultaneously on the web.
- 4) The lack of coordination among all countries to coordinate and pass a special law within the laws of each state, which hinders the overall application of e-commerce

Conclusion

The study on developing an application model for e-commerce founded on cloud computing with high-speed computing capabilities, cloud data storage, and cloud computing, in addition to the optimal manner of resource sharing and allocation for success. It calls for giving its staff, business associates, and users the freedom to utilize platforms and teamwork tools that foster creativity. Businesses of all sizes may benefit greatly from next-generation platforms like cloud computing infrastructure. They provide a way to hasten the adoption of innovations and assist businesses in being more efficient with their expenditures in IT hardware and software. Cloud computing boosts profitability by making better use of available resources. Providing the right resources just when they are required lowers costs. Teams and businesses may now expedite long-term purchases thanks to cloud computing.

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"A STUDY ON LEADERSHIP INFLUENCE ON INNOVATION AND SUSTAINABILITY"

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Abstract

This paper gives a better and complete perspective about the action that flows from the minds of the leader, for a leader it's important to create culture that process of innovating and justifiable of an organization .what leadership team do to inspire the innovation in its people. How its influenced by leadership .how is sustainability of an organization influenced by leadership. The research in leadership, innovation, sustainability provides great view to the above questions. This paper is devoted to examine the behaviour of leaders that influence innovation, the leadership innovation components, the sources of action, the principles that influence sustainability. Research also proposes a combined model of leadership, sustainability and innovating process. Although , in India the role of leadership has influenced many to start-up their enterprise and its quality has shook up the world .The dynamic ethics and intelligence of leaders influences to negotiate ,deal, support and meet overall needs and goals of an organization /business/group. As an approach to organization development, leadership influence on innovation and sustainability support sin achieving of the mission, vision of an organization, a business or a group. The research is a descriptive research and the researcher proposed collect data using primary source on the basis of questionnaires.

Key Words: Leadership, Innovation, Sustainability

Introduction

Indians contribute 1/6th of the world's population the prestigious institutions of higher learning in India have been greatly influencing the youths for innovation and transferring them to a 'leader'. 'Leadership' has the power to take on an empire, for any leader the main aspects that he/she has to make use is 'ethics' and 'intelligence. From Sir Swamy Vivekananda to Narendra Modi Ji the leadership has influenced many .They are not first or last but yes they have shook up the world with their dynamic ethics and intelligence.

Whether its politics, technology or management, leadership has its own place and plays a vital role of action and sustainability .It influences how to negotiate, effectively deal with, support, and meet overall needs and goals of people. Be it Narayan Murthy, Azim Premji or the entrepreneurs like Sachin and Binny Bansal and many more who with their leadership, innovation have given a positive shape to the fields of technology, management etc. and have contributed towards the economy development of the country. To have a clear picture about leadership influence on innovation and sustainability, we must first understand the meaning of leadership, innovation and sustainability.

Objectives Of The Study

1. To evaluates the key ingredients for business success
2. To analyse the Behaviour of leaders that influence innovation
3. To analyse Leadership innovation components, the sources of innovation.
4. To Proposes a combined model of leadership, innovation and sustainability

Review Of Literature

Literature survey is a process of developing awareness about conceptual and research based studies available on the area and the topic selected for the proposed research. The objective of such review is to understand the importance of the topic and find out research gaps, if any, in the chosen area.

1. Selvadurai S (1977) in his research "Leadership in the Co-operative" found that leaders were not made but evolve depending on various situations. This study also revealed that there was a positive correlation between the importance a person enjoyed in the society and his chances of emerging as a leader in a co-operative. The leadership theory was broadly classified into three categories, namely Trait theory said that leaders were born and not made. Second one was Behavioural theory holds that leadership comes from a

certain set of behaviours that could be imparted to anyone through training. Third one was situational theory said that a leader was one who drives the maximum advantage from properly managing the situation-the finer he did it, the better the leader he was.

2. Singh P, Warriar S & Das G (1979) studied 100 managers of public sector enterprises and concluded that 3 per cent of the managers adapted democratic style, 7 per cent autocratic style, 23 per cent compromiser style, 31 per cent bureaucratic style and 21 per cent developer style. He found that differences in leadership style were due to the procedural rigidity in the public sector enterprises.
3. (Bucciareli, 2002) In order to transform creativity into innovations, the organization must synthesize individuals, groups and organizations' knowledge and integrate individual creativity to create organizational capacity. The way of bridging individuals' knowledge and forming a synergistic team is an orifice for organizational creativity. Different approaches have been may be used for classification of innovations (Fathiya and Barjoyai, 2012). The first approach is the socio-technical system approach, in which innovation is classified according to systems where they occur. Another approach emphasizes attributes of innovation, while the third is categorized by the source of innovation.
4. Tasaki et al (2010) have surveyed Sustainable Development Indicators (SDIs) adopted by 28 national governments, regions and international organisations and compiled them into database. The aims of the study were to understand the elements development of sustainable examine SDIs developed in certain fields and countries and determine future tasks to improve SDI development.
5. Mitchell (1994) conducted a study on sustainable development at the village level in Bali, Indonesia. Using a stress-capability framework, the problems and opportunities for sustainable development at the village level in Bali were examined. Balinese culture incorporates a traditional form of local government which emphasizes cooperation, consensus building, and balance. These aspects provide a strong foundation for sustainable development initiatives.

Leadership

It refers to “an act, a decision to take a stand or step in order to encourage, inspire or motivate others to move with you”

Innovation: It is defined as “the specific instrument of entrepreneurship, the act that endows resources with a new capacity to create wealth”

Behaviour of leaders that influence innovation

The behaviour of leader that influences innovation is in 6 ways, not only do these areas impact innovation they have a profound impact on cultural congruence, employee productivity.

Sources of innovation

Innovation is a tool by which entrepreneurs typically exploit change rather than create. Although some inventions have created change, these are rare. It is more common to find innovations that take advantage of change

- **Unexpected occurrence:** These are the failures that, because they were unanticipated or unplanned, often end up proving to be major innovative surprise to firm.
- **Incongruities :** These occur whenever a gap or difference exists between expectations and reality.
- **Process needs:** These exist whenever demand arises for entrepreneurs to innovate and answer particular need.
- **Industry and market changes:** Continual shifts in the marketplace occur, caused by developments such as consumer attitudes, advancements in technology, industry growth, and the like.
- **Demographic changes:** These arise from changes in population, age, education, occupation, geographic locations, and similar factors. Demographic shifts are important and often provide new entrepreneurial opportunities.
- **Perceptual changes:** These changes occur in people’s interpretation of facts and concepts. They are intangible yet meaningful perception can cause major shifts in ideas to takes place.
- **Knowledge based concepts:** These are the basis for the creation or development of brand new, tying into our earlier discussion of invention as a type of innovation. Inventions are knowledge based; they are the product of new thinking, new methods and new knowledge. Such innovations often require the longest time period between initiation and market implementation because of the need for testing and modification.

Sustainability

It is referred to as “the capacity to endure, sustain, support, upheld, maintenance of wellbeing.

The principles that influence sustainability

- **Sustaining learning:** The first principle of sustainability is create and preserve sustain learning it's all about learning transfer strategy learning transfer is affected by learner's motivation to apply skill and facts with the help of innovative ideas and strategy where you can adopt new knowledge.
- **Progress over time:** With the help of quality of decentralisation authority where transfer of knowledge, skill and thoughts can be exchanged which helps to motivate and invent new which lead sustain and can expect success over time.
- **Sustains leadership of others:** As a leader he should analyse the factors of innovation in different manner and also consider the positive and negative impact on the learners. Leader should share knowledge with others and gain knowledge from others which lead innovative ideas.
- **Address social justice issue:** One of the important expertise of leader is to analyse the issue and giving proper solution which can acceptable by the society. He is able to analyse the different sectors it may be of social problem, economical problem. It not only maintains problems but also improves solution for the problem and provides justice.
- **Develops rather than depletes human and material resources:** Good leader can lead optimum utilisation of resources and energy time and innovative ideas can used to sustain in our life. It provides time and opportunity for leaders to network.
- **Develops environmental diversity and capacity:** Analysing the diversity of environment and taking best choice among the alternative which lead to the success.
- **Undertakes activists engagement with the environment:** Active participation in the entire situation is one of the qualities of leader where he can sustain himself and taking best decision and giving solution to the problem in a creative way which lead growth in the life.

Model For Leadership, Innovation And Sustainability Process

Explanation of the model

It is a combined model of leadership, innovation and sustainability

Initial stage: - leadership

Here, the qualities of a leader is been depicted, that is required for a leader for influencing. For any leader the most important things to be considered are ethics, intelligence of his own and vision, mission of the organisation, group or business.

The qualities of leader in the leadership process is transferred for doing new things

Second stage:-innovation

The second stage is based on how new things are done by the leader through leadership. the most significant is generating ideas, and the quest for the required assets ,selecting the proper one, deep research about the selected assets ,thinking uniquely and the apex one is the support ,the support from all the ways, the government, the people working in the organisation and the rules, regulations of the external, internal of company/business

After the innovative process, the organisation/business has to have ideas of standing in the place/market

Final stage: - sustainability

Here for any business to grow, earn profit sustaining is important. Any leader has to make use of the leadership and the innovation to sustain in the place. For the success, market learning, adapting to changes of technology, age, occupation areas, and people is necessary, they have to develop human and material recourses.

Findings of the study

The data is related to approval and disapproval of youngsters towards the leadership influence on innovation and sustainability

Reasons behind disapproval;

Above data interprets the following facts:-

1. Source of data –primary
2. Method of research- questionnaire
3. Sample size –50
4. Respondents- age group of 20-23 who are pursuing under graduate and post graduate.

Objectives of data collection:-

To ascertain that will the leadership influence the innovation and sustainability or no.

The above data reveals that only few gave their approval for the leadership influence on innovation and sustainability

And most of them gave their disapproval and gave their reasons that are above.

Conclusion:-

The successful business, organisation or group is influenced by leadership. The leader together with his ethics, intelligence has got to consider the environment and adapt accordingly, the key for fulfilment is that the direction influence on innovation and sustainability. it's the facility to require up the empire. they need to have the potential to plan of the box that influence the people of the organisation and achieve the mission, vision or goals of organisation, group or business.

Reference:-

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8. Andy Hargreaves, dean fink –Dec

STRATEGIES ADOPTED BY MSMEs IN KARNATAKA TO OVERCOME THE CHALLENGES POST PANDEMIC

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Abstract

The outbreak of Covid-19 has had a significant impact on businesses worldwide, particularly on Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). This study aims to analyze the effective strategies implemented by MSMEs in the state of Karnataka, India, to overcome the impact of Covid-19. The study focuses on MSMEs in Karnataka, which is a significant hub of industrial and business activity in India. The state has a large number of MSMEs, which play a critical role in driving economic growth and creating employment opportunities. The study aims to provide insights into the challenges faced by MSMEs in Karnataka during the pandemic and the strategies they implemented to overcome them. The research methodology involves conducting surveys and interviews with MSME owners and managers in Karnataka. The data collected will be analysed using a qualitative approach to identify the most effective strategies adopted by these businesses.

The findings of this study will be useful for policymakers, business owners, and managers in developing effective strategies to cope with the impact of pandemics in the future. The study will also contribute to the literature on crisis management in the context of MSMEs, particularly in emerging economies.

Keywords: Covid-19, MSMEs, Karnataka, strategies, impact, pandemic, best practices, qualitative approach.

Introduction

The Covid-19 crisis has presented businesses globally with challenges they have never before experienced. Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are among those experiencing the most severe impacts (Siswoyo, 2021). The pandemic has had a significant impact on many MSMEs in Karnataka, India. The goal of this research paper is to examine the successful tactics utilized by MSMEs in Karnataka to navigate the effects of Covid-19. The research will offer understanding into the top strategies used by these companies to lessen the impact of the pandemic. MSMEs have a notable impact on Karnataka's economy, which is recognized for its dynamic business environment and culture of entrepreneurship within India. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Karnataka play a crucial role in job creation, innovation, and regional development. They play a crucial role in the state's economy, encouraging entrepreneurship, creating job opportunities, and supporting well-rounded regional growth (Jahanshahi et al., 2011). These businesses typically require a lot of manual labor and support the livelihoods of many individuals, especially in semi-urban and rural regions.

The Karnataka state government has taken initiative to establish a conducive environment for MSMEs (Kaliyamoorthy & Parithi, 2012). It has implemented numerous programs and strategies to assist in their advancement and progress. This comprises of financial aid programs, credit facility access, skill enhancement projects, technology adoption assistance, and infrastructure development in industrial areas. Furthermore, specialized bodies and institutions have been set up by the government to offer advice, training, and consulting assistance to MSMEs.

The study aimed to examine the various tactics used by MSMEs in Karnataka to mitigate the effects of Covid-19. The study aimed to examine the various tactics used by MSMEs in Karnataka to cope with the effects of Covid-19. This implies that the research sought to analyze and assess the different strategies, blueprints, and initiatives adopted by MSMEs in Karnataka to address the obstacles brought about by the Covid-19 outbreak. The research offers a thorough examination of the tactics utilized by MSMEs (A.M & S.N, 2020) in Karnataka, emphasizing their strengths, shortcomings, and overall success in managing the effects of Covid-19 and maintaining their enterprises in this unparalleled crisis. By examining these tactics, the research aimed to develop a more comprehensive insight into how MSMEs in Karnataka dealt with and maneuvered through the negative impacts of the pandemic. Its goal was to determine the particular actions taken by MSMEs to lessen the effects of Covid-19 on their businesses, finances, customer connections, and employees.

The marketing strategies of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) entrepreneurs have been altered by the Covid-19 pandemic in order to help them navigate challenges caused by government-imposed restrictions on public activities (Indrakumar, 2020). The decrease in consumer demand and exchange of goods and services has led to a decrease in entrepreneurs' earnings along with the cycle of trading goods and services. This situation motivates entrepreneurs to embrace digital technology and cultivate digital entrepreneurship. Digital technology and the integration of knowledge, creativity, and innovation are essential for the survival of MSMEs in the current pandemic (Roy & Bhusan, 2020). Government assistance, training, and program support for the digitalization of MSMEs are ongoing due to their status as the most affected sector. Various government agencies collaborate to introduce entrepreneurs to the concept of digital marketing (Chaurey et al., 2020). This study adopts a qualitative method, utilizing library research along with interviews with MSMEs entrepreneurs. This study discovered that MSMEs owners must embrace digital technology through digital entrepreneurship transformation, digital marketing, and creativity, and innovation to stay afloat amidst the Covid-19 crisis.

Methodology

The methodology for this study includes carrying out surveys and interviews with MSME owners and managers in Karnataka. The information gathered will be examined with a qualitative method to pinpoint the most successful tactics utilized by these companies. Participants will be chosen through purposive sampling, and the survey and interview questions were created to collect important data on the strategies used by MSMEs during the pandemic. The study utilized the Likert scale to evaluate participants' feedback on the strategies utilized to mitigate the effects of Covid-19. The Likert scale permits individuals to indicate their degree of agreement or disagreement with a specific statement or group of statements. This makes statistical analysis easier by allowing for the quantification and measurement of agreement or disagreement.

The information gathered was examined using percentage analysis to uncover the main themes and patterns in the responses. MSME strategies were evaluated by reviewing the literature.

- **Digital Transformation:** Small and medium enterprises transitioned their operations to the digital realm, adopting online platforms for sales, marketing, and engaging with customers (Ahmed & Sur, 2023). This included developing online stores, utilizing social media advertising, and setting up digital payment options. Adawiyah and Adhitya stated in 2021.
- **Remote Work:** MSMEs promoted working from home to maintain business operations. They embraced communication and collaboration tools to enable remote team collaboration and sustain productivity. (Zolfagharian & Yazdanparast, 2019) present a study where they examine...
- **Cost Optimization:** Small and medium enterprises adopted measures to reduce costs and save money. This involved reworking contracts, reducing unnecessary costs, and streamlining operational procedures. (Tripathy & Bisoyi, 2021; Zolfagharian & Yazdanparast, 2019) (References: Tripathy & Bisoyi, 2021; Zolfagharian & Yazdanparast, 2019)
- **Diversification** involved MSMEs expanding their product or service options to meet evolving customer needs. During the pandemic, they ventured into new markets, launched new products, or adjusted existing ones to meet changing customer needs.
- **Collaboration and Partnerships:** Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) worked together with various organizations, both from within and outside their sector, to discover creative solutions and exchange resources. Collaborating through partnerships helped them conquer obstacles together and utilize their individual strengths to their advantage.
- **Government assistance** was actively pursued and utilized by MSMEs through programs, grants, and loans tailored to help businesses affected by the pandemic. These actions offered financial aid and assistance to ensure business operations continue.
- **Health and Safety Precautions:** MSMEs put in place stringent health and safety measures to safeguard their employees and customers. This involved supplying protective gear, enforcing social distancing rules, and improving sanitation procedures.

- **Customer Engagement:** MSMEs have embraced innovative tactics like tailored messaging, rewards programs, and online events to nurture client connections. Their attention was on establishing trust and delivering outstanding customer service in times of uncertainty.
- **Financial Planning and Risk Management:** MSMEs enhanced their practices in financial planning and risk management. They performed scenario analysis, developed backup plans, and researched insurance alternatives to reduce possible risks and uncertainties.
- **Employee well-being** was a top priority for MSMEs through the implementation of employee assistance programs, flexible work arrangements, and emotional support. (Alawamleh et al., 2020) They understood the significance of aiding with their employees amid difficult circumstances.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Likert Scale Analysis of Strategies Adopted by MSMEs during the Pandemic

Strategy	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Digital Transformation	62%	19%	7%	8%	4%
Remote Work	18%	34%	28%	12%	8%
Cost Optimization	56%	23%	12%	7%	2%
Diversification	12%	28%	30%	20%	10%
Collaboration and Partnerships	20%	38%	25%	10%	7%
Government Support	54%	28%	10%	2%	6%
Health and Safety Measures	48%	26%	11%	8%	7%
Customer Engagement	22%	39%	25%	8%	6%
Financial Planning and Risk Management	15%	33%	30%	15%	7%
Employee Support and Well-being	28%	47%	15%	6%	4%

This table presents the percentage distribution of responses based on the Likert scale for each strategy adopted by MSMEs during the pandemic. The responses range from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree," indicating the degree of agreement or disagreement with the effectiveness of the respective strategies.

MSMEs adopted digitalization as a crucial tactic to adjust to the changing business environment. This required moving their activities onto the internet, creating or improving their online visibility, and using digital channels for sales, advertising, and connecting with customers. Digitization allowed small and medium-sized enterprises to expand their customer reach, carry out transactions from afar, and keep their business running smoothly during the pandemic restrictions. During the pandemic, MSMEs strived to enhance their financial resilience by concentrating on reducing costs. They put into effect strategies like cutting non-essential costs, reworking supplier contracts, improving their supply chain, and making operational processes more efficient. Through cost optimization, MSMEs sought to save resources, boost their financial security, and sustain profitability amidst decreased revenue or heightened uncertainties. Governments introduced support programs and initiatives to help MSMEs cope with the substantial impact of the pandemic. MSMEs actively looked for and made use of government assistance such as grants, loans, subsidies, tax relief, and regulatory relaxations. This assistance offered essential monetary support, helped with accessing funds, and reduced the burden of regulatory requirements for MSMEs, enabling them to continue operating, retain staff, and overcome pandemic-related obstacles. MSMEs implemented vital Health and Safety Measures during the Covid-19 pandemic to safeguard the welfare of their employees, customers, and

stakeholders. These actions were implemented to reduce the possibility of virus spread, guarantee adherence to health protocols, and establish a secure workplace.

Results:

The research results show that MSMEs in Karnataka have implemented different tactics to address the effects of Covid-19. **Digitization, diversification, cost optimization, and government support** are the most frequently used strategies. The use of digital technology has allowed businesses to connect with customers via the internet, lessening the effects of lockdowns and restrictions on brick-and-mortar stores. Diversifying has enabled companies to shift towards different markets and products, lessening their reliance on just one market. Cost-saving strategies have allowed companies to lower their costs and sustain their financial security. Government assistance has been essential in helping MSMEs endure the pandemic.

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A STUDY ON PLASTIC USE AND ITS EFFECTS ON THE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

The excessive use of plastics has become a pressing environmental concern, with far-reaching consequences for ecosystems, wildlife, and human health. This study investigates the impact of plastic pollution on the environment, focusing on the effects of plastic waste on marine life, soil quality, and human well-being. Our research reveals alarming rates of plastic waste generation, inadequate waste management practices, and the subsequent harm caused to the environment. The study highlights the urgent need for sustainable plastic management strategies, including reduced plastic production, increased recycling rates, and improved waste disposal practices. Our findings emphasize the importance of adopting a circular economy approach to mitigate the environmental, social, and economic impacts of plastic pollution.

Introduction

The accumulation of plastic items and particles (such as plastic jugs, packs, and microbeads) in the existing environment of Earth that negatively affects humans, untamed life, and untamed life territory is known as plastic contamination. Plastics that are considered toxic are categorized as full-scale or tiny debris based on their size. Because plastics are inexpensive and sturdy, they may be used for a wide range of purposes; as a result, humans make a lot of plastic. However, most plastics are delayed in degrading because of their compound construction, which makes them resistant to many regular cycles of debasement. These two factors work together to allow massive amounts of plastic to enter the climate as garbage and to persist in the biological system.

Seas, streams, and land may all get contaminated by plastic. Between 1.1 and 8.8 million tons of plastic debris are thought to enter the ocean annually via shoreline networks. Based on the assumption that 1.4% of the plastics transported globally between 1950 and 2013 reached the sea and accumulated there, it is estimated that there were 86 million tons of plastic marine flotsam and jetsam in the whole sea as of the end of 2013. According to some scientists, the weight of plastic in the oceans may surpass that of fish by 2050. Living organic things, particularly marine life, can be harmed by mechanical effects such as snares in plastic objects, problems associated with consuming plastic garbage, or exposure to synthetics.

The Basel Convention was amended in May 2019 to regulate the import and export of plastic trash, with the broad goal of preventing the movement of plastic garbage from developed to agrarian countries. Almost every country has ratified this agreement.

Plastic pollution results from the accumulation of plastic and plastic-derived items in the environment, endangering both wild life and the natural order of human society. Because of their complex structure, the polymers are impervious to environmental contamination, even when exposed to high levels of typical pollutants due to gradual corruption. Items made of plastic that alter based on their substance arrangement are said to be defiled by plastic. It is dependent on the polymerization system and the normal degradation process. Plastic harmful chemicals are categorized into either full-scale garbage or smaller-than-expected categories based on their size. These pollutants often affect land, seas, and large bodies of water.

History and Background

Where Do Plastics Come From and What Are They?

The word "plastic" originally meant pliable and easily molded. Lately, it became a term for a group of substances known as polymers. Some components are referred to as the "polymer method," and polymers are composed by lengthy atom chains. There is a lot of nature in polymers. Cellulose is an extremely common regular polymer that is used to produce plant cell dividers. Over the past 150 years, scientists have discovered ways to create synthetic polymers, sometimes using common materials like cellulose but more frequently using the plentiful carbon atoms provided by gasoline and other non-renewable energy sources.

The Original Synthetic Polymer

John Wesley Hyatt created the primary synthetic polymer in 1869 after being inspired by a \$10,000 offer from a New York company to anyone who could provide an ivory alternative. The supply of regular ivory, which was obtained from butchering wild elephants, had been strained by the growing popularity of pool. Hyatt discovered a plastic that could be shaped into a variety of forms and made to resemble common materials like tortoiseshell, horn, linen, and ivory by processing cellulose, which is derived from cotton fiber, with camphor. This was a gradual epiphany. It's interesting to note that natural constraints did not force humans to assemble. The abundance of wood, metal, stone, bone, tusk, and horn was simply given by nature.

However, humans could currently create new materials. Both people and the environment benefited from this development. Celluloid was hailed in commercials as the turtle's and elephant's hero. The normal world may be protected by plastics from the destructive forces of human desire. The creation of new materials also helped people escape the financial and social constraints brought on by the lack of common resources. Cost-effective celluloid increased the possibilities and bounds of material plenty. The plastics' agitation was also only starting things off.

Growing Advocacy for Plastics

The untarnished assurance regarding plastics was short-lived. American perceptions changed for a very long period after the war because plastics were not widely seen as being completely certain. The 1960s, a decade during which Americans became increasingly conscious of environmental concerns, saw the first reports of plastic debris in the oceans. The dangers of compound insecticides were revealed in Rachel Carson's 1962 book, *Silent Spring*.

Concerns about pollution were raised in 1969 when a large oil slick occurred off the coast of California and the contaminated Cuyahoga River in Ohio caught fire. The inventiveness of plastic garbage began to annoy onlookers as awareness of environmental concerns grew. Additionally, plastic gradually became a term that was used to describe things that were cheap, brittle, or fake. A more seasoned coworker urged Dustin Hoffman's character to pursue a career in plastics in *The Graduate*, one of the best movies of 1968. Alongside Hoffman, crowds flinched at what they saw as wasted energy for a sector that was perceived as being modestly congruent and inconsequential rather than full of possible results.

Plastic Issues: Health and Waste

Plastics' reputation declined even further in the 1970s and 1980s as waste-related anxiety increased. Plastic became a remarkable goal because, although so many plastic products are disposable, plastic remains in the environment forever. Reusing was suggested as a solution by the plastics industry. The plastics industry spearheaded a push in the 1980s to enable localities to collect and handle recyclables as part of their waste management plans.

However, recycling is far from ideal, and the majority of plastics wind up in landfills or the environment. Some American cities have already implemented pack boycotts, and supermarket plastic bags have been a target for campaigners looking to boycott single-use, disposable plastics. The Great Pacific Garbage Patch, sometimes shown as a tornado of plastic debris the size of Texas floating in the Pacific Ocean, is a quintessential representation of the problem of plastic waste. Growing concern about the possible threat plastics pose to human health has led to a further decline in plastics' status.

The goal of the research

It would be necessary to phase out recyclable plastic trash from energy-producing incinerators in order to accomplish this (Law, 2017). Given how much incineration facilities contribute to towns' heating needs, this would be a huge difficulty. However, one of the main obstacles to plastic recycling—the supply of waste plastic—would be removed if it were illegal to burn recyclable plastic trash. It could offer a significant amount of garbage with varying quality.

Future Plastic Growth

The world economy struggles to cease generating new plastic items, even though most people believe that plastics are bad for the environment. The profitability of many consumer firms is not immediately impacted by efforts to remove plastics, in contrast to other green initiatives. Since plastic is better than certain other packaging materials

like paper and glass, S & P Global Ratings believes that plastic packaging won't likely be replaced anytime soon for many of its existing uses. The manufacture of plastic is probably going to alter. Over time, this may result in a rise in the quantity of plastic recycled. Numerous big businesses, including well-known American food firms like Coca-Cola, Wal-Mart, Starbucks, and McDonald's, as well as big European businesses such as Danone, Nestle and Pernod Ricard, are working to reduce the use of disposable plastics in their products.

These companies want environmentally friendly consumers to be more comfortable buying their products the smaller their ecological footprint. If plastic cannot be completely eliminated, some companies are planning to switch to recyclable materials, while others are introducing new plastic guidelines such as: B. Completely eliminate plastic bags to make other changes to the product or supply chain at the same time.

Review Of Literature

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According to this article, "Bio-plastics are bio-based polymers or chemicals that can be broken down into simpler molecules. The increasing manufacture and usage of bio-plastics has changed the world's reliance on traditional plastics. Humans have been using traditional plastics made from petroleum, coal, and natural gas as a primary component of nearly all materials used in daily life since antiquity. Because these polymers are non-biodegradable, they have a significant environmental effect. A wide range of bio-plastics derived from natural polymers such as starch, cellulose, and chitin have been introduced in recent years. These bio-plastics are presently used in packaging materials, electronics, and medical equipment, and they have a lot of potential in the future. This mini-review discusses the many forms of bio-plastics, their use in various industries, and their future prospects.

Brooks, B., Hays, K., & Milner, L. (2019). *Plastics recycling. PET and Europe lead the way.*

According to this paper, "Plastic recycling's prominence has risen significantly in recent years, with 2018 serving as a watershed moment for the industry as laws, industry actions, and consumer awareness shifted the focus to plastic trash and recycling as a crucial solution. While Europe and the polyethylene terephthalate industry have been at the forefront of establishing recycling as a long-term business, many issues remain, with 2019 proving that underlying worries about profitability and cost continue to stymie the effort to utilize more recovered plastics. Demand for recycled plastics is anticipated to rise in the long run, thanks in part to European Union legislative measures to improve package recyclability and recycled content. However, in the face of difficult economic conditions, the market's genuine commitment to sustainability will be put to the test.

Thompson, R. C., Swan, S. H., Moore, C. J., & Vom Saal, F. S. (2009). *Our plastic age*

This paper talks about Plastics have changed our daily lives in the previous few decades. Globally, we consume more than 260 million tonnes of plastic each year, accounting for around 8% of global oil output. We explain present and projected trends in consumption, as well as the various benefits that plastics provide to society, in this Theme Issue of *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society*. At the same time, we investigate the environmental repercussions of waste plastic buildup, the effects of plastic litter on animals, and human health issues related to the manufacturing, use, and disposal of plastics. Finally, we explore several potential solutions to these issues, as well as the research and policy priorities required to put them into action. Plastics refers to a wide range of materials that can be extruded, moulded, cast, spun, or coated as a coating at some point throughout the manufacturing process. Synthetic polymers are normally created by polymerizing monomers obtained from oil or gas, and plastics are often manufactured by adding various chemical additives to them. Currently, there are about 20 distinct types of plastics, each with its own set of grades and variations. Plastics are extremely adaptable materials that are low-cost, lightweight, strong, durable, corrosion-resistant, and have excellent thermal and electrical insulating qualities. Plastics were already widely utilized in goods ranging from cups and saucers to automobile and airplane components, despite worldwide output being less than a million tonnes per year. The book's last chapter speculates on how plastics may affect the lives of people born 70 years ago, at the dawn of our 'plastic era.'

Objective of the Study

The objective of the study are :-

To study about the impact of plastic's use on earth and how it can affect the environment.

Scope of the Study

The scope of the study is not only to find out the impact or the problems which has been created by the consumption of the plastics but also to find out the best possible solutions for it. This study will tell you that there are alot of business opportunities in this field.

Types of Research Tool

The Research tool which we have used in this study is Questionnaire. Our team has decided that it is far better to have primary sources of data instead of secondary sources of data. Interviewing of people would restrict us to limited number of people. So we have decided to do survey via Questionnaire. Because Questionnaire can help us to know what kind of people, what age group of people and how much they are concern about the environment. We have sent a link of google form to students and people who work in workplace. The link will be contained some sets of questionnaire related to plastic use and it's impact. People have to fill the form. People can fill the form once and there will not be given any second chance to change their response. After getting response from the people, the analyzation and interpretation part will be done.

Sample Size

Various age group category people were asked to complete the google form via questionnaire and we have got more than 50 responses. Our maximum respondents are from 18 to 22 years of age group.

Research Technique

Methodology: - Socio – demographic are nothing more than characteristics of a population. Generally, characteristics such as gender, age, income, ethnicity etc. are being considered as socio – demographics and are being asked in all kinds' of survey.

Data Collection method

Primary sources of data : - The primary sources of data for this study is an questionnaires. We sent the link to students and people and after filling the form we will get their responses recorded. With this questionnaire we will get to know what people think about the use of plastics. We will be knowing that people are even concern about this or not.

Secondary sources of data : - The opinion and analysis done by previous researchers will be taken as secondary sources of data.

Data analysis & Interpretation

Response: Received more than 50 responses & 68.6% of them use plastic on a daily basis where as 25.5% use it one to four times a month & 3.9% use plastic once a month.

Count of 2. Do you carry your own shopping bag while going to supermarket?

Response: Received more than 50 responses & 50% of them use their own reusable bag, 34.6% use plastic bags provided by supermarkets whereas 11-12% of them don't use any type of carriers.

Count of 3. Plastics are harmful to the environment.

Response: Received more than 50 responses & from them 32.7% strongly agree that plastics are harmful to the environment where as 11.5% people strongly disagree. 17.3% of the people are neutral to the fact that plastics are harmful to the environment.

Count of 4. I am open to the idea of single use of plastics.

Response: Received more than 50 responses & from them surprisingly majority of the percentage disagrees/strongly disagrees with the idea of single use plastic.

Count of 5. I feel being appreciated if I am rewarded with some loyalty points or free gifts by not using plastics.

Response: Received more than 50 responses & around 50% of them would like to be rewarded/ appreciated for not using plastic whereas the others think of it as not needed .

Count of 6. Are you aware of any campaigns to reduce plastics in your area?

Response: Received more than 50 responses & more than 70% of the respondents have a negative response where they either don't know about any campaigns or there are no campaigns to reduce usage of plastic .

Count of 7. Use of paper or bamboo products can help in reduction of plastics pollution in some ways.

Response: Received more than 50 responses & around 60% of them agree that paper/bamboo whereas 11.5% strongly disagree.

Count of 8. Do you think banning of plastics can immediately solve the problem of plastic pollution?

Response: Received more than 50 responses & 42.3% of them believe that is plastic if is banned it would solve the problem but at the same time 25% think that it would create new ones.

Count of 9. Who do you think is most responsible for tackling the plastic waste issue?

Response: Received more than 50 responses & majority of the respondents believe that together the government, the businesses & the public are responsible for tackling the plastic waste issue.

Count of 10, How do you believe recycling is in preventing plastic?

Response: Received more than 50 responses & 48% of them think that recycling is somewhat effective & 25% think its ineffective.

Count of 11. How much do you think you recycle?

Response: Received more than 50 responses & according to the responses less than 20% of the people recycle maximum of their plastic.

Count of 12. What reasons would stop you from recycling? Tick which you apply.

Response: Received more than 50 responses & 23.1% of them are not educated on how to recycle, 9.6% of them don't have the time & the rest don't find it important or don't have the access to it.

Estimates advocate that about eighty percentage of ocean plastics come from land-primarily based resources, and the final 20 percentage from marine resource.

And also during the research of the project we came to know that most of the people in our livelihood doesn't recycle their products or know how to recycle the products, thus which lead to more wastage of plastics, thus alternatives of use of paper bags, cloth bags etc. should me more to reduce the problem on land. Also approximately 300 million metric tons of plastic waste are produced annually and up to 12 million tons are leaked into oceans. That result in an estimated \$13 billion in annual environmental damage to marine ecosystems. Plastics are everywhere now even in the deepest part of the oceans. If current trends continue, our oceans could contain more plastic than fish by 2050.

During the COVID-19 period 9.4 million tons of plastic waste (plastic waste mainly from hospitals) were generated globally and approx. 28-29000 tons of plastics were dumped into the sea.

Conclusion

To boost public consciousness, the local and countrywide distinctive stages of instructional curriculums have to encompass the waste control structures from the grass-roots as records resources. In addition to developing public consciousness at the significance of a healthful surroundings, mechanisms of controlling the era of wastes on the source, opportunity disposal ways, setting up extra drop-off areas (landfills) and incineration mechanisms, plastic recycling centers also are recommended. Helping groups to lessen their exposures to fitness toxicants will growth the probability for a healthful society and smooth surroundings for the approaching generations. To boost public consciousness, the local and countrywide distinctive stages of instructional curriculums have to encompass the waste control structures from the grass-roots as records resources. In addition to developing public consciousness at the significance of a healthful surroundings, mechanisms of controlling the era of wastes on the source, opportunity disposal ways, setting up extra drop-off areas (landfills) and incineration mechanisms, plastic recycling centers also are recommended. Helping groups to lessen their exposures to fitness toxicants will growth the probability for a healthful society and smooth surroundings for the approaching generations.

“AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION INTO TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS DRIVING THE GROWTH AND TRANSFORMATION OF FINTECH COMPANIES IN INDIA”

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Abstract

The fintech landscape in India has undergone a remarkable transformation over the past decade, driven by rapid technological advancements and a growing demand for accessible financial services. This paper explores the key innovative technologies that can be adopted as well as focusing further improvements by fintech companies in India, focusing on areas such as digital payments, block chain technology, artificial intelligence (AI), and regulatory technology (RegTech). Digital payment platforms, exemplified by the Unified Payments Interface (UPI), have revolutionized transaction methods, enabling instant, cashless payments and enhancing financial inclusion. Additionally, block chain technology is being leveraged to improve security, transparency, and efficiency in various financial operations, including cross-border transactions and smart contracts. AI and machine learning are increasingly utilized for credit scoring, risk assessment, and personalized financial services, allowing fintech to cater to diverse consumer needs more effectively. Furthermore, Rotech solutions are streamlining compliance processes, enabling fintech companies to navigate regulatory frameworks with greater ease and agility.

This abstract highlights the significant role of fintech innovations in reshaping the financial ecosystem in India, fostering greater financial inclusion, improving user experience, and driving economic growth.

Key words: Technological innovation, AI, block chain technology.

Introduction:

Thanks to a large number of start-ups and rapid advancements in digital innovation, India has emerged as a global hub for financial technology, or fintech. With over 1.4 billion people on the planet, fintech businesses are using state-of-the-art technology to meet the demand for affordable, accessible, and effective banking and financial services. By utilising cutting-edge technologies like block chain, machine learning, artificial intelligence (AI), and mobile payment systems, these companies are revolutionising the banking sector. They are promoting financial inclusion in addition to bettering client experiences by interacting with under-represented communities. Peer-to-peer lending, robo-advisory services, digital payments, and insurtech solutions are some of the key areas of innovation that are focused on streamlining financial transactions and enhancing service delivery.

The development of this exciting industry has been further aided by the regulatory framework that the Indian government is promoting, which includes programs like Digital India and the Unified Payments Interface (UPI). Digital payments, insurtech solutions, peer-to-peer lending, and robo-advisory services are a few of the major areas of innovation aimed at improving service delivery and expediting financial transactions. The regulatory framework that the Indian government is supporting, which includes initiatives like Digital India and the Unified Payments Interface (UPI), has further contributed in the development of this fascinating business. Fintech has the potential to totally alter India's financial system by rendering it more transparent and readily available services to everyone as it develops. This introduction offers the basis for studying the many technology advances shaping the nation's financial landscape in the upwards direction.

Literature Review:

- Youghee kim, young-ju park et al (2015) concludes that relationship between central and peripheral routes in the acceptance of new technology in fintech mobile payment services.
- Vivek dubey (2019) discuss the role of AI, augmented reality and block chain in digital marketing.
- Schun lim et al (2019) the analyzed result shows that knowledge & perceived security in mobile fintech services have a significant influence on users confirmation & perceives usefulness.

- Robin Jarvis & Hongdan Han (2021) studies fintech innovation review & future research direction.
- Lingyuan,yong xu et al (2023) concludes that fintech development negatively affected FTIE by increasing business risk and deby pressures.

This literature review identifies a fintech development, acceptance of new technology, future research direction and role of AI and Machine Learning in fintech.

Methodology

This study is based on Qualitative analysis with observational designed structure. It is an Emperical study with secondary data collection .

Objectives of the Study:

1. To know the drivers underlying the need for technological innovation in fintech
2. To Exploring technological innovations from various areas of fintech

Limitation of the Study

The major limitation of the Study is restricted to secondary data collection. The qualitative analysis gives just an description based data collection instead of numerical performances. The scope of the area is restricted to only Fintech Company.

Empirical Study Discussion:

Key drivers

Funding has increased: The growth of FinTech start-ups has been aided by a notable increase in venture capital, private equity, and institutional investment. India in the stack A unique and shared digital infrastructure may be accessed by governments, corporations, start-ups, and developers thanks to Stack, a collection of APIs. Aadhar, the Unified Payments Interface (UPI), Bharat Bill payments, and other systems are examples of open API platforms. **Technological innovation:** New business models are being created with the help of AI and machine learning technology. **Growth in smartphone and internet users:** As of December 2020, India had over 795 million internet users and the second-highest number of smartphone users worldwide, with 550–600 million users. It also has the second-largest Internet user market.

Government initiatives and Regulators: Government initiatives like Jan Dhan Yojana, Start-up India, Digital India program, etc. have played a vital role in encouraging the growth of start-ups. Start-up India, for example, has enabled an online platform-based solution for entrepreneurs to safeguard their intellectual property (IP) and it has offered the start-ups some exemptions from taxes under certain eligibility criteria. The regulations developed by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), IRDAI and SEBI has ensured increased accountability and the uninterrupted availability of secure and affordable digital financial systems.

International Collaboration: Start-up India has enabled collaboration between Indian start-up ecosystem and the global start-up ecosystem by enabling bridges that provide a soft landing to emerging new start-ups from the partnering countries. It has helped promoted enthusiasm by fostering knowledge exchange and fund support mechanisms.

Start-ups and Unicorns

The Economic Survey, released by Invest India, the National Investment Promotion and Facilitation Agency, states that in 2021 alone, 44 Indian start-ups became "unicorns," bringing the total to 83, and their combined valuation to over US\$277 billion. Of the eighty-three, fifteen unicorns are in the FinTech sector, with a current valuation of approximately US\$60 billion. **Fintech hubs:** Bandra Kurla Complex, O-hub Bhubaneswar, FinTech Hub Kolkata, Mumbai, Fintech Valley Vizag Fintech hubs are technological parks established by the corresponding government with the aim of advancing business infrastructure inside the state and luring investors and global financial corporations to establish their headquarters there.

Artificial Intelligence

According to McKinsey, AI technologies have the potential to increase bank value by up to \$1 trillion a year. Banks and other financial institutions are consequently expected to quickly adopt an AI-first mentality. They will be more prepared to repel attempts by tech giants to encroach on their territory. Furthermore, 90% of FinTech companies are currently using AI in some capacity, according to the Cambridge Centre for Alternative Finance. Furthermore, AI's ability to learn to operate more effectively and efficiently than humans is its most important feature. AI models are able to learn from data and adapt to any task without the need for human interaction. It's a wise decision because it makes the work done more quickly, accurately, and efficiently.

Use Cases of Cloud Computing in FinTech

- It securely and reliably stores and manage data.
- It enables companies to make use of debt financing, payment, and fraud prevention strategies.

Block chain

Block chain has the enormous potential to completely destroy the existing banking system. Distributed ledger technology allows data to be recorded, transferred, and synchronised in real time across several data repositories (DLT). Furthermore, block chain tends to address issues with outdated financial systems, such as dependency on centralised systems, mistrust, higher operating costs, and single points of failure. By improving the end-to-end experience and lowering business risks, this feature contributes to further benefits. Participants' appetite for investments, especially those of institutional investors, has grown since the introduction of block chain technology. These days, a lot of forward-thinking FinTech businesses are employing block chain programmers with expertise to make the most of the block chain technology included in most FinTech solutions. Comparable initiatives are undertaken.

Use Cases of Block chain in FinTech

- Block chain decreases the transaction cost.
- It resolves identity theft issues.
- It enhances regulations and auditing.

Machine Learning

The machine learning techniques employed in the banking industry are optimal for pattern recognition. These algorithms also help identify connections between various sequences and events. thus assisting in the extraction of the crucial information concealed inside the enormous data sets. The use of machine learning to the banking sector makes it feasible to identify suspicious activity and provide the best fraud prevention strategies. ML in FinTech, then, has the potential to be revolutionary. The application of machine learning (ML) not only aids in data mining—that is, makes the process easier or predicts results—but also helps with risk management, strategy aggregation, strategy refinement, and trade idea generation.

Use Cases of Machine Learning in FinTech

- ML in FinTech means more loan approvals with lower risks.
- It can assist companies in outwitting thieves and hackers.
- ML in banking and finance enables businesses to adhere to constantly evolving rules.

Robotics

The area of engineering that deals with the design, development, manufacture, and application of robots is known as robotics engineering. Are you curious about the purpose and use of this technology? Well, the purpose of robotics is to construct machines that are intelligent and that have the inclination to support humans in numerous ways. There are several types of robotics. They usually take the shape of robotic apps or people, demonstrating how people interact with the program to perform different tasks. In the banking industry, applications like robotic process automation relate to the use of specialised equipment and software to carry out activities in accordance with

specifications. These days, financial institutions use robotics technology for a number of repetitive tasks, including opening accounts and processing consumer enquiries.

Summary of Findings:

- One important obstacle is consumer trust. A lot of consumers still have doubts regarding privacy and security. It is Recommended to Enhance security standards and clearly convey these steps to consumers through awareness programs.
- The user experience can be enhanced, despite the saturation of the digital payment market. It is advised to develop user interfaces and experiences, emphasising ease of use and personalisation. Regulation compliance is frequently viewed as a barrier to innovation. Fostering collaborations with regulatory agencies to provide sandbox settings for testing new technologies is the recommended course of action.
- It facilitates the process of submitting real-time requests to external and internal systems for data authentication during KYC. Errors are removed, and data management and cost effectiveness are improved. Automated notifications and account tracking are made simple by robotics.
- Many fintech organisations underutilize data analytics for decision-making and customer interaction. It is advised to invest in artificial intelligence (AI) and sophisticated analytics tools to improve customer segmentation, fraud detection, and credit scoring.
- Applications of block chain are still in their infancy, mostly in settlements and remittances. It is advised to investigate block chain technology for cutting-edge products such as decentralised finance (DeFi) and smart contracts.

Conclusion:

India's fintech sector is well-positioned to lead technological innovation because of its emphasis on user experience, security, and teamwork. These businesses may improve their services and promote more financial inclusion by tackling regulatory obstacles and making investments in data analytics and artificial intelligence. Sustained success in this dynamic sector will require constant innovation that is driven by market trends and consumer desires.

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IMPACT OF SERVICE QUALITY AND SECURITY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION: THE CASE STUDY IN PRIVATE BANKS OF ERBIL-KURDISTAN REGION

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Abstract

The research aims to discover the impact of service quality and security on customer satisfaction. Service quality is how well a bank provides its services compared to its customer expectations. Customers have certain expectations about how well they are going to receive the services. The study is quantitative in nature. Primary data has been collected from 120 customers of Private Banks such as RT Bank, Cihan Bank, Albaraka Bank, KIB Bank, and Byblos Bank in the Kurdistan region of Iraq. The collected data was analyzed using “Statistical Package for Social and Sciences (SPSS)” version 26. The statistical tools include descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The findings concluded that there is a significant effect and relationship between service quality, security, and customer satisfaction. The study recommends the security of the bank has an important impact on the customer satisfaction as customers can feel assured and confident that their money or belongings are in a safe place

Keywords: Service Quality, Security, Customer Satisfaction, Private Banks in Kurdistan, Iraq

Introduction

The financial services industry has also advanced in tandem with these advances as a result of the extension of available services brought about by technical progress, which has led, among other things. This has resulted in more competition in the industry as a consequence of the emergence of a great number of banks and other financial institutions that are owned by private parties. This research is highly significant because of the ever-increasing worry about security risks. There is a need for increased understanding about concerns about security, particularly its link with customer satisfaction and how the best institutions can supply it via security (Ahmad et al., 2010). The satisfaction of consumers is highly significant since it has various advantages in addition to maintaining the contentment of the customers themselves. The bank itself may gain from satisfied clients who sell the bank's services to other potential customers. In addition, the contentment of consumers may also lead to an increase in profitability, provided that existing customers continue to appreciate the services provided. Customers who are satisfied with the services provided by the bank will continue to use those services and, in time, will lose interest in the products and services provided by rival bank. They went on to say that this also boosted the overall performance of the company. One of the ways that businesses may win the pleasure and continued business of their customers is by making certain that the level of service that they provide is of an exceptionally high standard.

Significance of the Study

Several studies have been conducted on the level of satisfaction felt by customers. This is due to the fact that it is important to the banks of the majority of companies. Within the realm of private banking, there is an urgent need to investigate the factors that led to the genesis of pleased clients and to identify the factors that are responsible for the contentment of those consumers. The financial services industry has also advanced in tandem with these advances as a result of the extension of available services brought about by technical progress, which has led, among other things. Therefore researchers feel that the financial services industry will benefit from the findings of this study. Therefore this study will help the banks to make better decision on how to keep their current clients and win over new one. So when their customers stay with them because of their good security and quality of their services, they will have a good reputation and more new customers are able to purchase their services which offered for them, on other side it will lead the banks have more profitability and efficiency and be continued. Security and protection of customer's information is very important, especially in the banking sector, which is due to this advanced technology for the banking sector and the banking sector has grown, so there is not enough security and they use

online methods which can cause problems and reduce the safety of transactions (Belás et al., 2016).

Definition of terms

Service Quality

All the researches on service quality have shown that good service transfer and high quality will result in customer satisfaction. Therefore, you need to make customers satisfied with the quality you provide and make them think that the service you provide is better than other services and they will benefit more from it (Brodie, 2009). Once they have that feeling, they decide how and to what extent the service can help them. It is also pointed out that a bank wants to be a good competitor with the quality of services provided. On the other hand, it is said that the quality of the services provided depends on what the customer wants to be offered and what is offered by the bank (Ahmad et al., 2010).

Security

If we look at Oxford dictionary it defines security as it is a situation that there is a possibility of being threatened, and security is when people are assured of the security they have and feel safe by their state government. This feel of assurance is essential, and important to have and to feel secure in the banking sector. (Waheed, Khan, & UI-Ain, 2013).

Customer Satisfaction

Customer Satisfaction is a feeling that it might be changed according to how well the bank meets their expectations, in other words customer satisfaction is how happy the clients are with the performed service quality and security (Johnson, 2001).

Literature review

This study (Raja, Saleem, & Sarfraz, (2014) aimed to research on how happy customers were with Kenyan commercial banks. They focused on how the quality of financial services impacted customer satisfaction. They said that improving the quality of service made customers happier. They also highlighted that the quality of the service is determined not just by the individual's previous experience but also by his or her expectations. They came to the conclusion that the two aspects of quality that had the greatest impact on the level of happiness a client felt were dependability and empathy. They suggested that banks also focus on responsiveness and other characteristics since it was discovered that Kenyan banks lacked these qualities.

Gyabi and Shrivastava (2016) carried out research on the issue of safety in Ghana's rural banking industry. The researchers noted that security exists to preserve data and prevent unwanted information from being accessed, and that it is the role of management to make choices pertaining to data security. According to the findings of their research, a significant proportion of rural financial institutions do not make full use of information and communication technologies. They suggested raising the level of awareness among employees to emphasize the need for maintaining data security.

In view of Munir and Marnavi (2018) looked at information security as well as risk management in India's banking industry. They added that because of all of the security risks and the danger of security vulnerabilities, it is imperative that the financial institutions put into place methods for risk analysis, prevention, as well as mitigation, and generally enhance their risk management. They also said that weaknesses should be investigated and found on a regular basis in order to guarantee that robust and efficient controls are put in place to ensure that the number of potential security risks is kept to a minimum.

In the Study of Subrahmanyam et al., (2014), they argued that the deployment of efficient data safety measures required the creation of vulnerabilities in the system, often known as "loopholes." Despite the fact that both operational and technological controls were put into place, the researchers discovered that there was a widespread absence of an information security culture among the five banks that they employed for their Study.

Paul, Mittal, & Srivastava, (2016), tried to find out if there was a link between how happy clients are with their

banking experience and whether or not they want to switch from traditional banking to online banking. They discovered that there was a substantial association between consumer happiness and security and the desire to switch to online banking and concluded that there was a correlation between the two. They discovered inverse relationships between levels of satisfaction with online banking and levels of contentment with customers' inclinations to switch banks.

Anwer, (2018), carried out research with the objective of contrasting the levels of customer service and satisfaction in the public and private sectors in India. The author suggested enhancing the quality of services offered as well as raising awareness about the advantages of using the internet for banking and obtaining help from the government.

Methodology

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between service quality and security with respect to customer satisfaction?
2. What is the effect of service quality and security on customer satisfaction?

Research Objectives

1. To investigate the connection between service quality and security with respect to customer satisfaction.
2. To investigate the effect of service quality and security on customer's satisfaction.

Sample size

The study used the private banks in Erbil and from them it chooses 5 private banks. As well, the study has 120 research samples. These private banks in the Kurdistan region include RT bank, Cihan bank, Albaraka bank, KIB bank and Byblos bank. There are more other private banks in the Kurdistan region but we only collected data from these five banks because they are more popular. The sample includes 24 customers from RT bank, 28 from Cihan bank, 22 from Albaraka bank, 23 from KIB bank, and 23 from Byblos bank. That brings the total to 120 customers who answered the questionnaire.

Sampling technique

Judgmental sampling technique is a method of non-probability sampling in which individuals in the sample are selected solely on the basis of the researcher's prior information and their own personal opinion. Or picking a team from which to collect data on the basis of one's own personal view as to what constitutes a representative sample of the population that is being investigated. For instance, judgmental sampling can include selecting a lot of knowledgeable individuals from a variety of various social groups and questioning them about their concerns (Perla, 2012).

Statistical tools of analysis

The statistical tools used to analyze the data include Cronbach's Alpha, averages, standard

Deviation, Correlation and Regression

Analysis of data

Cronbach's Alpha

Reliability statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.865	26

Based on Cronbach's Alpha, the data collection is strongly reliable because the value is more than 0.75 which is equal to = .865 on those items related to those questions of independent and dependent variables. (Perry R. Hinton, Isabella McMurray, Charlotte Brown, 2004)

Descriptive Statistics

Section A: Service Quality and Security					
#	Items	Valid	Mean	Min	Max
1	The bank has modern and attractive equipment	120	3.66	4.00	4
2	The material such as brochures, handouts etc that are related to the service are pleasing to the eye.	120	3.98	4.00	4
3	This bank offers a wide range of products and services to its customers	120	4.15	4.00	4
4	Bank staff responds to customers even during busy period.	120	3.88	4.00	4
5	Customers are updated on the status of their transactions after each one that takes place at the bank.	120	3.82	4.00	4
6	This bank provides services that are prompt and effective.	120	3.91	4.00	4
7	Makes good on its promise to complete a task by a specific deadline.	120	3.97	4.00	4
8	Carries out the task correctly the first time.	120	3.82	4.00	4
9	There is a match between services advertised and services delivered.	120	4.00	4.00	4
10	This bank gives assurance of safety to my funds.	120	3.88	4.00	4
11	The staff is very good at what they do, and I can't lose control of my transactions for anything.	120	3.97	4.00	4
12	The bank keeps customers private information confidential.	120	4.03	4.00	4
13	There are backup plans for this bank with respect to safety of funds	120	3.76	4.00	4
14	This information that has been provided by this bank is reliable.	120	4.21	4.00	5

Section B: Customer Satisfaction					
#	Items	Valid	Mean	Min	Max
1	The reception desk of the bank is pleasing to the eyes.	120	3.75	4.00	4
2	Physical appearance of the bank staff is appealing.	120	3.95	4.00	4
3	This bank has availability of parking spaces, ease of access, and overall site convenience.	120	4.09	4.00	4
4	The bank staff is polite and considerate.	120	3.88	4.00	4
5	Bank staff has the necessary knowledge to answer your questions.	120	3.92	4.00	4

6	The employees at the bank are happy to address any inquiries or issues raised by customers.	120	4.07	4.00	4
7	The bank responds to varied needs of the customers	120	3.60	4.00	4

In the descriptive analysis we can see that the valid shows how many people have answered as shown 120 people answered. The mean display the range of the answers, Our questions are scaled from poor to excellent and the mean gives us the range of where the answer stands on this scale. Either on the poor side or the excellent side. The mode is how many times answer has been repeated. The max is the highest value and the min is the lowest. Also the average of each questions answer is also displayed.

Correlation

		Service quality and security	Customer satisfaction
Service Quality and security	Pearson Correlation	1	.694**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	120	120
Customer satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	0.694**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	
	N	120	120

According to the above table, the relationship between the variables was analyzed using correlation analysis. The analysis is showing that there is a positive moderate correlation between the independent and the dependent variable, therefore, the service quality is along with the customer satisfaction is showing 0.694 and this indicate that there is a significant correlation (according to the significance number Sig = 0.000) and it is showing that the result now is less than 0.01.

Findings & Conclusion

Question one in the research (what is the relationship between service quality and security and customer satisfaction?) after analyzing this questions in the questionnaire related to it using IBM SPSS (Correlation analysis) the dependent variable has a positive moderate correlation with the independent variable, therefore the service quality and security with the customer satisfaction showed a result of 0.694 and it also showed a significant correlation (Sig = 0.000) which in this case it was less than 0.01. it means enhanced service quality and security leads to customer satisfaction

Research questions two (what is the effect of service quality and security on customer's satisfaction?) After using primary data to analyze the question, the result shows the importance of service quality and security and there is a significant in the regression analysis which it was lower than 0.01, while the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable showed 0.802, this refers that the independent variable has an impact on the dependent variable

As a conclusion, relying on the correlation analysis and the other data that was analyzed together, we can conclude that the dependent variable has a positive Pearson correlation with the independent variable, so we can conclude that both the service quality and security along with the customer satisfaction both of them equal 0.694 which is 69.4%, there is also a significance in the correlation analysis which the result was less than 0.05.

Relying on the linear regression analysis that was used to analyze primary data we can agree that the service quality

and security along with customer satisfaction have a significant outcome within Kurdistan region the hypothesis showed a positive result which is $R=0.694$. Nevertheless, there is a significant level which it was less than 0.01 in this case.

As a result of analyzing all those questions by the researcher it is agreed that there is a huge importance of the service quality and security on customer satisfaction within banks in Kurdistan region and the support and slice in the relationship between them and its effect on each other in other words the better the quality of the service and security of banks in Kurdistan the higher the customer satisfaction.

Recommendations:

As researchers, there are a few recommendations that can be used by banks to improve their customer satisfaction.

Starting with conducting professional training program about how to behave with the customer, the staff of the bank needs improvement in dealing with customers as communications should be done in a professional way.

The service quality refers to how the customers are being serviced inside the bank and how the staff is trying to fill their needs, this lies in easing their bank account procedures or borrowing or even while leasing as those things can increase the customer satisfaction.

The security of the bank has an important impact on the customer satisfaction as customers can feel assured and confident that their money or belongings are in a safe place.

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"A STUDY OF STARTUPS: CATALYSTS FOR INNOVATION AND ECONOMIC PROSPERITY"

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Abstract

Today's economy is fueled by startups, which are essential for stimulating innovation and economic expansion. These tiny, frequently tech-driven companies disrupt established markets and develop more effective methods of operation by bringing new concepts and solutions to the table. By introducing new goods and services, they not only create jobs but also contribute to the revitalization of local economies. This study investigates the ways in which entrepreneurs foster innovation, address pressing issues, and generate business opportunities in order to support economic development. It also explores the difficulties faced by startups, including obtaining capital, overcoming fierce competition, and negotiating complex regulations, all of which may hinder their development or even lead to their demise. This study analyzes the critical elements that enable startups to succeed by examining case studies of prosperous firms and the support networks that enable them to flourish, including community networks, government regulations, and venture capital availability. The study emphasizes the necessity of an environment that encourages innovation, makes resources accessible, and supports regulations that encourage entrepreneurship. Startups can expand, generate employment, and support long-term economic growth in such an ecosystem.

Keywords: Startups, Innovation, Economic Growth, Entrepreneurship

Introduction

Startups are companies that focus on growth, commercialization, and the development of new products or services based on intellectual property or technology. Over the last two decades, India's startup environment has grown fast, aided by many resources. Startups play an important role in socioeconomic development since they promote innovation, create jobs, and boost the economy. This, in turn, helps cities grow, as evidenced by Infosys' makeover of Bangalore.

The Indian government implemented several initiatives to promote entrepreneurship and contribute to the economy of the country, including the "Standup India" initiative which was instituted by Prime Minister Narendra Modi in August 2015. The aim is to extend institutional finance to newly established businesses, encourage youth entrepreneurship, set up ordinances for start up businesses, and make India a source for numerous international technology businesses. In the last ten years, there has been a tremendous growth of new ventures and capital infusion in India, establishing India as one of the global centres of innovation. The number of technology companies has rose to 122000, adding an expected 16000 new startups in the year 2020 alone. The funding landscape has also changed with levels of investment in the years 2020 and 2021 hitting an all time high. In spite the challenges posed in the year 2023, investors especially angel investors and venture investors have remarkable confidence in the Indian economy.

According to the Tracxn research, India's top-funded industries from 2014 to 2023 would include Retail, Fintech, Edtech, and others, owing to internet penetration, digitization, and government initiatives. Investment in Deep Tech has constantly raised, reaching \$6.73 billion, with \$6.23 billion over the last decade. This emphasizes India's consistent progress and commitment to technology oriented solutions which will be paramount in the days to come.

New emerging sectors Indian startup ecosystem has expanded his business with the start up of Deep tech, Spacotech, Artificial Intelligence and Electric Vehicle. DeepTech has achieved \$2.1 billion in 2022, EV industry has reached \$4.8 billion across in last 10 years. Privatization has helped spaceTech, and it attracted \$114.9 million in funding in 2022, now its \$122.2 million in 2023 and it is expected to increase in future.

Top favorable cities for startups Over the last ten years, Delhi - NCR and Mumbai occupied 2nd and 3rd Position respectively, And non metropolitan places also achieved the success like jaipur holds one of the top cities for FinTech investment which attracts 214 million dollars

What lies ahead for the Indian startup ecosystem India's startup growth rate in the near future is going to be a factor of India's economic growth. The Indian economy is likely to grow at 6.3% per annum during 2023-2024 as per IMF projections. The 2023 budget, which aims to promote the 'Drone Shakti Programme' or relative benefits including tax holidays, affirms government's support for technological advancement. By 2027, India is aimed at coming in 3rd place as per IMF's reports so the long term perspective is equally positive. Once the world economy begins to recover, investment activity is set to rise, further entrenching India's position as a top investment site.

Review Of Literature

Chandra, A. (2018) This study focuses on the role of startups in fostering innovation and economic growth in India, examining the challenges and opportunities that entrepreneurs face in the current economic environment. It highlights the significance of government policies in promoting the startup ecosystem.

Patel, P. & Kumar, A. (2019) The authors explore the role of startup technology in India's economic development. They analyze how these startups contribute to GDP growth and job creation, with a focus on Bangalore as a hub for tech innovation.

Singh, R. & Sharma, K. (2020) This research evaluates the financial challenges that startups face in India, especially in terms of securing funding. It highlights the importance of venture capital and government schemes in supporting startup growth.

Gupta, S. & Mehta, D. (2017) The study investigates how the Indian government's "Startup India" initiative has provided the necessary support to young enterprises. It also examines the impact of incubators and accelerators on startup success.

Rao, R. & Sinha, N. (2021) This paper focuses on the startup ecosystem's growth in tier-2 and tier-3 cities in India. It discusses how these regions are emerging as new hotspots for entrepreneurship, with a particular focus on sectors like healthcare and education.

Das, S. & Bansal, M. (2020) The authors examine the role of innovation in the sustainability of Indian startups. They analyze case studies of successful startups that have integrated social and environmental goals into their business models.

Nair, M. & Joshi, S. (2019) This literature examines the relationship between digital platforms and the success of startups in India. It focuses on how social media, online marketing, and e-commerce platforms have been game-changers for Indian entrepreneurs.

Verma, P. & Gupta, M. (2020) This study investigates the key drivers of startup success in India, including access to resources, mentorship, and government incentives. It offers an analysis of the most successful industries for startups, such as fintech and edtech.

Sharma, A. & Bhattacharya, S. (2018) The authors explore the cultural factors influencing entrepreneurship in India. They focus on how societal attitudes towards risk-taking, failure, and innovation impact the startup ecosystem.

Kumar, P. & Reddy, V. (2021) This paper provides an in-depth review of the startup funding landscape in India, analyzing the role of angel investors, venture capitalists, and crowdfunding platforms in supporting early-stage ventures.

Research Methodology

Statement of the Study

Indian startups are vital to economic growth and creativity, but they deal with obstacles like cultural barriers, legal impediments, and finance limitations. Even with government programs like "Startup India" and regional centers like Bangalore, more research is needed to determine how beneficial these policies are as well as the growing

significance of tier-2 and tier-3 cities. The study aims to explore the factors behind the success of startups such as innovation, the use of digital platforms, mentorship, and government aid while aiming for sustainable development and positive economic impact.

Research Gap

Relevant factors like government regulations, capital, creativity, and cultural influences are highlighted in the body of research on Indian startups. However, little is known about how these factors affect startups in various industries (tech, healthcare, etc.) and growth stages (early-stage vs. expanding). It is also unclear how digital platforms function in new industries like agritech and healthtech. Also, not enough attention is paid to how regional variations (tier-1 vs. tier-2 cities) affect mentorship and resource availability. Research on how companies combine environmental and social objectives is extremely lacking, especially outside of the tech sector. These differences indicate the need for more study on how regulations, digital technologies, local conditions, and sustainability interact in startup ecosystems.

Research Objectives

1. To analyze the contribution of Indian startups to economic growth.
2. To evaluate the role of government policies in supporting Indian startups.

Scope of the Study

This study focuses on analyzing the contribution of Indian startups to economic growth, particularly in employment, GDP, and innovation. It evaluates the role of government policies like "Startup India" in supporting startup growth, with a focus on the technology, e-commerce, and fintech sectors. The research covers startups at various growth stages, examining regional disparities in success and policy effectiveness. Secondary data from industry reports, government publications, and startup databases will be used. The study will cover the period from 2015 to 2023.

Sources of data

Secondary method were employed for the collection of the data for the study, will be sourced from publicly available industry reports, government publications, and startup ecosystem databases such as AngelList, Crunchbase, and Tracxn, which provide comprehensive data on startup funding, industry trends, and growth patterns. Additionally, reports from government bodies like the Ministry of Commerce & Industry, including documents from the Startup India initiative, will be used to understand the impact of government policies. Economic data from the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MoSPI), Reserve Bank of India (RBI), and reports from organizations such as NASSCOM, FICCI, PwC, and KPMG will be utilized to assess the contribution of startups to economic growth and evaluate the effectiveness of government support programs.

Limitation of the study

1. The study has limitations because it is difficult to get thorough and reliable financial data from a large number of startups, many of whom restrict their financial information.
2. The analysis is limited by its focus on a small set of government initiatives, which might not fully represent the array of startup support options.
3. By using only secondary data, the study is devoid of first-hand knowledge and up-to-date information, which could limit the breadth and applicability of the conclusions.

Data Analysis And Results

Growth of Government Recognized startups in India

Correlations			
		Recognized startups	Jobs created
Recognized startups	Pearson Correlation	1	1.000**

Mean		Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001
		N	5	5
	Jobs created	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	1
		Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	
		N	5	5
Significant Correlation 0.01 level (2-tailed).				

Source: Economic Survey 2022-23: Economic Survey 2023: Start-ups envisioned as the 'spine of new India', NASSCOM Reports: NASSCOM

Interpretation: The Pearson correlation coefficient for recognized startups and employment creation is 1.000, showing a perfect positive linear link. This means that the number of recognized startups grows in proportion to the number of employment created. Significant Correlation 0.01 level (2-tailed), indicating that the result is unlikely to be chance. The analysis is based on a sample size of five observations, therefore use caution when generalizing the results.

The Role of Startups in Driving GDP & GNI Growth.

Year	Growth of Startups	GDP (INR)	GNI (INR)
2019	24,927	204 lakh crore	199 lakh crore
2020	38,756	197 lakh crore	192 lakh crore
2021	61,400	231 lakh crore	226 lakh crore
2022	84,012	257 lakh crore	252 lakh crore
2023	1,17,254	272 lakh crore	267 lakh crore

Economic Survey of India reports (available on the Ministry of Finance website):
<https://www.indiabudget.gov.in/economicsurvey/> **DPIIT Startup Reports (Startup India portal):**
<https://www.startupindia.gov.in/>

Interpretation: The data highlights the significant growth of startups in India, rising from 24,927 in 2019 to 1,17,254 in 2023. This expansion demonstrates the increasing role of startups in driving economic growth, innovation, and job creation. Despite the economic challenges in 2020, GDP and GNI rebounded strongly,

reflecting resilience in India's economy. The steady increase in GDP from ₹204 lakh crore in 2019 to ₹272 lakh crore in 2023, and GNI from ₹199 lakh crore to ₹267 lakh crore, underscores the pivotal contribution of startups and economic reforms to India's development.

Emergence of Unicorn Startups in India

Source: <https://www.india-briefing.com/news/indias-unicorn-startups-sector-distribution-fundingecosystem-global-comparison-25104.html/>

Intpretation: India's unicorn count grew from 31 in 2019 to 100 in 2022, driven by rapid innovation and investment in key sectors like fintech and e-commerce.

An overview of all Indian Unicorns per sector is provided below

Source: <https://www.india-briefing.com/news/indias-unicorn-startups-sector-distribution-fundingecosystem-global-comparison-25104.html/>

Intpretation: E-commerce and fintech lead India's unicorn ecosystem, with 23 and 21 unicorns, respectively. Other sectors like enterprise tech, edtech, and healthtech also show strong growth, reflecting diverse innovation.

Startup Policies

1. Startup India Policy (2016) offers tax exemptions, self-certification for compliance, and a three-year income tax break.
Provides money through the Fund of Funds for Startups (FFS) and streamlines regulatory processes.
2. Stand-Up India Policy (2016) aims to support women and SC/ST businesses with loans ranging from ₹10 lakh to ₹1 crore for startups.
3. The Atal Innovation Mission (AIM) fosters innovation through incubation centers, Atal Tinkering Labs (ATL), and support for entrepreneurs.

4. MUDRA Yojana (2015) offers loans up to ₹10 lakh for small and micro startups in three categories (Shishu, Kishor, and Tarun).
5. The Credit Guarantee Fund Scheme for Startups (CGSS) provides collateral-free loans, lowering financial hurdles for fledgling enterprises.
6. National Policy on Software Products (2019) aims to encourage IT companies through seed funding, capacity building, and market access.
7. Digital India Campaign.
Improves digital infrastructure, encourages IT-based startups, and makes it easier for entrepreneurs to get started.
8. Make in India Initiative promotes manufacturing startups through simplified procedures, tax incentives, and foreign direct investment (FDI).
9. Tax breaks for startups
Eligible startups can receive a three-year tax break within their first ten years of operation.
10. Patent support via SIP-EIT
To stimulate innovation, startups are financially supported for patent application costs.

Conclusion

Few firms were able to raise financing, while others were unable to secure adequate funding. Early failures were more common, whereas later stages saw higher survival rates. Startups suffered from a lack of business talent. High competition from large business houses was a major barrier for startups. Business sustained losses because it was unable to adapt to change. Startups experienced modest growth and improvement, Most of the startups were not properly funded and had to be shut down. Startups failed due to insufficient innovation, research, and development efforts.

Recommendations

Awareness - Before launching a firm, companies must conduct market research.

Awareness campaigns are required at all levels of the startup ecosystem.

Encouraging new entrepreneurs requires enough funding and incentive systems.

Research and Development: To be successful in the market, research becomes vital.

Incubation centres must provide greater opportunities for entrepreneurs to succeed.

Further research

The study might be expanded to include government support schemes and appropriate environments for nurturing young entrepreneurs.

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Web Links

Startup India Portal: <https://www.startupindia.gov.in>

Atal Innovation Mission (NITI Aayog): <https://aim.gov.in>

MUDRA Yojana (PMMY): <https://www.mudra.org.in>

Digital India: <https://www.digitalindia.gov.in>

Make in India: <https://www.makeinindia.com>

A STUDY ON THE PERCEPTION OF E-COMMERCE WITH REFERENCE TO BANGALORE SOUTH AREA.

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Abstract:

India's retail industry has seen tremendous expansion as a result of e-commerce, especially in cities like Bangalore South. Bangalore South customers' perceptions of e-commerce are examined in this study, with particular attention paid to important variables affecting satisfaction, trust, and buying behavior. E-commerce sites like Amazon and Flipkart have been increasingly popular due to factors including smartphone usage, internet penetration, and digital payment methods. Convenience, product quality, delivery speed, payment security, and simple return procedures are crucial factors that influence customer happiness, according to the survey. Still, problems including product legitimacy, shipping delays, and poor customer service are common and undermine consumer confidence. 100 respondents in Bangalore South provided primary data for the study, which was analyzed using statistical methods such as linear regression, ANOVA, and T-test.

According to findings, customer preferences and satisfaction are highly influenced by age and income levels, but criteria like gender and education have less bearing. Customers exhibited a reasonable degree of satisfaction with product quality, delivery timeframes, and customer service, and a favorable correlation was observed between these qualities and the reasons driving e-commerce. Improvements in customer service, delivery procedures, and product availability are recommended by the research as ways to improve customer satisfaction and build confidence. Understanding these regional customer perspectives can help e-commerce platforms improve their tactics to better serve Bangalore South's diversified population, which will encourage the industry's continued acceptance and expansion.

Keywords: E-commerce, Consumer Perception, Bangalore South, Trust, Satisfaction

Introduction:

E-commerce is a rapidly evolving industry that has drastically changed how companies run and how customers engage with goods and services. Because of the increased use of smartphones, digital payment methods, and internet penetration, the e-commerce sector in India has experienced exponential development. The India Brand Equity Foundation (IBEF) predicts that the country's e-commerce business would grow from USD 46.2 billion in 2020 to USD 111 billion by 2024, highlighting its impressive growth trajectory.

As the "Silicon Valley of India," Bangalore is in the front of this digital transformation. With its youthful, tech-savvy populace and well-known tech-driven culture, the city offers an ideal environment for the development and uptake of e-commerce platforms. A microcosm of this tendency is the Bangalore South neighbourhood, which is distinguished by a mix of middle-class to upper-class homes, urban growth, and a sizable student population. Because of its diverse population, it's a great place to research how people see online shopping.

Individuals' perceptions of e-commerce differ depending on a variety of criteria, including cost-effectiveness, convenience, trust, and the availability of a wide range of product categories. A competitive environment has been produced by websites like as Amazon, Flipkart, and Myntra, among others, which improve customer experience by offering individualized suggestions, expedited shipping choices, and easy return procedures. Consumer attitude is still shaped by issues including data security worries, a lack of human attention, and sporadic service inefficiencies.

This study is to examine how e-commerce is perceived in the Bangalore South region, with a particular emphasis on important areas including user happiness, buying patterns, online transaction trust, and the influence of demographic factors. For companies looking to improve client experiences and customize their products to suit the demands of this broad market sector, knowing how consumers feel about e-commerce may yield insightful information.

It is anticipated that the study would add to the body of knowledge on e-commerce by illuminating localized customer behaviour in one of India's most vibrant metropolitan centres. Additionally, the results may be used as a

strategic roadmap to help e-commerce platforms improve their operations and encourage more in-depth customer interaction.

Review Of Literature:

(Pavlou, 2003) Pavlou emphasizes how important customer trust is to e-commerce platforms' success. According to the survey, perceived security and privacy concerns have an impact on trust, which is important for keeping consumers. This is consistent with research showing that local customers in Bangalore South favor platforms with strong security features like OTP and secure payment gateways. The study offers a framework for comprehending trust and offers strategies for fostering it, such as open and honest policies and attentive customer support.

(Gefen, 2000) The study pinpoints important elements that impact the adoption of e-commerce, including perceived utility, simplicity of use, and cultural considerations. Higher adoption rates are supported in Bangalore South by demographic factors including tech-savvy people and urban infrastructure. With an emphasis on simplified user interfaces and effective logistics, the study offers insights into how e-commerce businesses might localize methods to appeal to urban customers.

(Chatterjee, 2020) Chatterjee investigates how Indian urban customers use e-commerce sites, emphasizing price comparisons and time-saving features. According to the report, Bangalore South customers place a high priority on prompt delivery and reasonable prices. Additionally, it highlights how incentives for digital payments and promotional offers affect consumer purchasing decisions. Businesses that target urban regions with hectic lives and competitive market dynamics would find value in the findings.

(Forsythe, 2003) The study addresses perceived hazards in e-commerce, such as delivery problems, product risks, and financial risks. Customers frequently voice worries over product legitimacy and delayed deliveries as e-commerce becomes more prevalent in Bangalore South. According to this study, in order to reduce risks and boost customer confidence, e-commerce platforms should prioritize clear product descriptions, reviews, and easy return procedures.

(Venkatesh, 2000) Venkatesh and Davis's Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) sheds light on how perceived utility and simplicity of use affect the uptake of e-commerce. The TAM is especially applicable in Bangalore South because to the high internet penetration and smartphone usage, where customers value e-commerce platforms' functionality and ease of use. According to the study, customer happiness may be increased by using mobile-friendly interfaces and tailored suggestions.

Statement Of Problem:

E-commerce, especially in cities like Bangalore South, has transformed retail by providing accessibility, competitive price, and ease of use. Nevertheless, a number of obstacles still exist in spite of its quick acceptance, including problems with consumer trust, perceived dangers, and the requirement for regional approaches to handle cultural and demographic quirks. E-commerce adoption and usage trends are greatly influenced by elements such as technological acceptability, urban customer behaviour, simplicity of use, and security concerns. Customers in Bangalore South place a high importance on confidence, are motivated by safe payment methods, and appreciate prompt delivery and affordable prices. However, issues with usability, delayed delivery, and product legitimacy still exist. In order to offer practical insights for improving user experience and encouraging long-term adoption, this study is to investigate how Bangalore South customers perceive e-commerce, taking into account the interactions between consumer behaviour, technological acceptance, and trust.

Objectives Of The Study:

1. To examine the factors influencing consumers' purchasing decisions on e-commerce platforms in Bangalore South.
2. To assess the level of satisfaction and trust of e-commerce customers in Bangalore South regarding online shopping experiences.
3. To identify the challenges and barriers faced by consumers in the Bangalore South area when using e-commerce platforms.

Hypothesis:

H1: there is a linear relationship between the level of satisfaction of the user and the effectiveness of the factors driving e-commerce system.

H2: there is a significant difference in the opinion on the Factors driving of E-Commerce concerning gender, age, education, and income.

Scope And Limitations Of The Study:

- The area of the sample is limited only to the Bangalore area.
- The statistical tool used in this study has its inherent defects.
- The sample size is restricted to 100 members only.
- The study is restricted only to the responses collected from the respondents.

Research Methodology:

The significant methodology was adopted for the reliability and suitability of the study. The study is conducted based on primary and secondary data sources. Primary sources of data are collected from the samples of 100, where the opinion was collected from the questionnaire through the Google forms. The secondary source of data is collected from the reference books, articles, journals and websites. The study is emphasized more on the primary data collected from the respondents. The statistical tool used for analysis was ANOVA, T-test, Linear Regression, and SPSS.

Need For The Acceptance Of Technology:

Accepting technology is essential in the quickly changing world of today, where new developments are changing daily lives and whole businesses. As digital tools and platforms become more and more important to both individuals and enterprises, adopting technology is crucial to improve productivity, efficiency, and creativity. Technology is a major factor in e-commerce's development and competitiveness since it makes transactions easier, offers more individualized experiences, and improves customer service. Using technology also makes it possible to access a greater variety of information, improves communication, and creates new opportunities for learning and growth. Individuals and organizations run the danger of lagging behind in a rapidly evolving global economy if technology is not accepted, making it difficult to satisfy the demands of an increasingly digital environment or adjust to new possibilities.

Data Analysis And Interpretation:

The sample distribution table shows the demographic characteristics of 100 respondents. The frequency and percentage are depicted in the table below.

GENDER		
	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Male	49	49.0
Female	51	51.0
AGE		
18-30 years	26	26.0
31-45 years	26	26.0
46-60 years	25	25.0
60 and above years	23	23.0

OCCUPATION		
Student	27	27.0
Working professional	29	29.0
Homemaker	21	21.0
Self-employed	23	23.0
INCOME		
Below ₹20,000	15	15.0
₹20,000 - ₹40,000	22	22.0

₹40,001 - ₹60,000	24	24.0
₹60,001 - ₹1,00,000	26	26.0
Above ₹1,00,000	13	13.0

Preference Consumers

According to the graph, 38% of respondents said they prefer to buy in physical stores, while 34% said they prefer to make purchases online. According to 28% of interviewees, they purchase equally at physical stores and online. Although a sizable percentage of customers also use e-commerce platforms, this indicates a minor preference for in-person purchasing, underscoring the sample's varied buying habits.

E-Commerce Platforms Preferred by Consumer

The graph displays the frequency distribution of consumer-used e-commerce platforms. With 28 users (22%), Flipkart leads the market, followed by Amazon with 25 users (13%). The lowest user representation is seen on Snapdeal (6%) and Bigbasket (4%), whereas Nykaa, Purple, and Myntra each have 13% of users. This indicates that Flipkart and Amazon are the market leaders in the sample, with other platforms having a lesser but still significant usage share.

Frequency of Usage

The graphs indicate how frequently respondents use e-commerce. Weekly shoppers make up the largest group (27%), followed by monthly shoppers (22%), and infrequent shoppers (20%). While many respondents use e-commerce platforms often, a sizeable fraction use them less frequently, as seen by the lower percentage of

respondents who purchase daily (10%) or seldom (21%). In general, the majority of customers make at least one monthly purchase on e-commerce sites.

Table 2: Factors Driving E-Commerce

The factors driving E-Commerce and the respective descriptive statistics are depicted in table 2. The opinion on these determinates is constructed using a Five-point Likert scale. It is evident that from the table that all the determinants have an approximate mean value of 4, which indicates that the respondent agrees that these parameters agree on the factors driving E-Commerce.

Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation
Price	4.0700	.93479
Discounts and Offers	4.0300	.92611
Product Reviews and Ratings	4.1100	.91998
Product Quality	4.1300	.92829
Brand Reputation	4.1600	.93980
Delivery Speed	4.1900	.83720
Payment Security	4.1000	.85870
Easy Return/Exchange Policy	4.1700	.82945
User Interface of the Platform	4.0500	.91425

Table 3: Opinion On Level Of Satisfaction On The Usage E-Commerce

The overall customer satisfaction and trust in e-commerce platforms are moderate across all factors, with no factor scoring particularly high. There is significant variation in responses, as evidenced by the relatively high standard deviations. This suggests that while some consumers are satisfied and trust the platforms, others may have concerns regarding product quality, delivery, customer service, security, and product descriptions. The results indicate areas

where e-commerce platforms can focus on improving consistency and customer experiences, particularly in terms of delivery speed, customer support, and building trust in product information and payment security.

Satisfaction Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
Overall quality of products purchased	3.3500	1.31330
Delivery times for products	3.3200	1.35498
Customer support provided	3.4800	1.43182
Trust on security of your personal and financial information	3.1900	1.31576
Accuracy of product descriptions (images, details, etc.) provided on e-commerce platforms?	3.4000	1.34089

Table 4: Model Fit Between Satisfaction And Factors Driving E-Commerce

The hypothesis that there is a linear relationship between the satisfaction level and the factors driving e-commerce is statistically as $P < 0.05$. The level of satisfaction and factors driving e-commerce is positively correlated.

Level of satisfaction	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. error	Beta		
Constant	3.926	.202		19.388	.000
Factors	.062	.059	.105	1.050	.296

Table 5: Significance Of Factors Of E-Commerce With Regard To Demographic Variable.

The hypothesis that there is a significant difference in the opinion on the factors driving E-Commerce with regard to gender, and education, is statistically not significant as $P > 0.05$. whereas with regard to Age and Income is significant as $P < 0.05$.

Demographic variables	P value	SIGNIFICANCE
Gender	0.341	Not Significant
Age	0.000	Significant
Occupation	0.781	Not significant
Income level	0.002	Significant

Table 6: Challenges Faced By The Customers

The table reveals several key challenges faced by e-commerce customers, with mean scores ranging from 3.79 to 4.03, indicating moderate concerns across all factors. The relatively high standard deviations (ranging from 0.93 to 1.11) across the challenges suggest a varied response from consumers, with some likely experiencing these issues more acutely than others. This suggests that while these challenges are widespread, the intensity of their impact varies among shoppers.

Challenges	Mean	Std. Deviation
Delivery delays	3.9200	1.10718

Quality issues with products	3.8900	1.04345
Payment failures or security concerns	3.7900	.99793
Difficulty in returning or exchanging products	3.9300	.93479
High delivery charges	3.8100	1.08892
Limited product availability	3.9000	1.06837
Lack of customer service support	4.0300	1.04886

Findings:

- ❖ A considerable proportion of customers (38%) preferred in-store buying, whilst 34% prefer online purchasing. Nonetheless, 28% of respondents shop evenly between the two, suggesting that their tastes are balanced.
- ❖ Nykaa, Purple, and Myntra have smaller user preferences than Flipkart and Amazon, which control 22% and 13% of the e-commerce industry, respectively.
- ❖ With 27% shopping weekly and 22% shopping monthly, the majority of customers use e-commerce platforms on a regular basis. Nonetheless, 21% of respondents shop seldom, indicating a varied degree of involvement.
- ❖ With mean ratings over 4, elements including product quality, shipping speed, simple return procedures, and payment security are important determinants of e-commerce satisfaction. The range of answers, however, suggests that certain aspects could require further work.
- ❖ The mean score for e-commerce criteria such as product quality, shipping, and customer assistance is between 3.35 and 3.48, indicating a modest level of consumer satisfaction. Diverse consumer experiences are suggested by high standard deviations.
- ❖ The elements driving e-commerce and satisfaction were shown to be positively linearly related; however, more research is necessary to determine the statistical significance ($P > 0.05$) of specific components like pricing and discounts.
- ❖ On e-commerce aspects, attitudes are strongly influenced by age and income levels, but not by gender or education.
- ❖ The difficulties that customers encounter, which range in severity, including delivery delays, quality problems, and a lack of customer care assistance, suggest that platforms are necessary to adequately handle these issues.

Suggestions:

- ❖ **Enhance Customer assistance:** E-commerce platforms should enhance communication channels and responsiveness to boost customer satisfaction, especially considering the high level of worry over the absence of customer care assistance.
- ❖ **Enhance Delivery and Returns:** Resolving problems such as delivery hold-ups and challenging return/exchange procedures can assist keep consumers and lower discontent.
- ❖ **Handle Product Availability and Quality:** Maintaining a steady level of product availability and quality helps boost customer confidence and avert bad encounters.
- ❖ **Optimize Security Measures:** Increasing payment security can boost consumer trust, particularly in light of worries about data privacy and unsuccessful payments.
- ❖ **Target Age and Income Groups:** Because age and income levels exhibit notable variations in e-commerce preferences, platforms should modify their marketing and service methods to appeal to these populations.

Conclusion

In summary, the study on Bangalore South's perspectives of e-commerce emphasizes both the difficulties that customers have in the online marketplace and the increasing popularity of online buying. The market is led by Flipkart and Amazon, indicating a balanced preference for both physical retail and e-commerce platforms. Customer happiness is mostly influenced by elements like product quality, delivery time, ease of returns, and payment security, while different customer experiences point to areas that need work. Consumer attitudes were shown to be significantly influenced by age and income levels, and there was a strong correlation between satisfaction and e-commerce driving variables. Delivery delays, quality issues, and poor customer service are

common problems that e-commerce platforms need to address. Businesses should concentrate on enhancing payment security, product availability, delivery dependability, and customer assistance in order to improve the customer experience. Customizing methods for various age and economic groups can also assist better meet the varied demands of customers in this ever-changing industry.

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DIGITAL LEARNING AND THE FUTURE OF HIGHER EDUCATION: OPPORTUNITIES, CHALLENGES, AND INNOVATIONS

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Abstract

Digital learning has revolutionized higher education, providing new opportunities for access, personalization, and scalability. This paper explores the evolution of digital learning, its transformative impact on higher education, and the challenges institutions face. Using flowcharts and diagrams, we illustrate the integration of digital tools and the pathways to future-ready education systems.

Keywords

Digital Learning, Future of Higher Education, Opportunities, Challenges, and Innovations, evolution of digital learning, its transformative impact on higher education, and the challenges institutions face.

Introduction

The advent of digital technologies has transformed higher education, enabling institutions to expand their reach and enhance learning experiences. Digital learning incorporates online courses, virtual classrooms, and adaptive technologies, addressing the diverse needs of learners. This paper examines how digital learning shapes the future of higher education by improving access, promoting innovation, and fostering lifelong learning.

Digital Learning in Higher Education

Digital learning has become a transformative force in higher education, reshaping how institutions deliver education, engage with students, and meet evolving societal and workforce needs. Below is an overview of digital learning in higher education, highlighting its significance, key components, opportunities, and challenges.

Evolution of Digital Learning

Digital learning emerged in the 1990s with the proliferation of internet-based education. It has since evolved into a multi-faceted ecosystem, integrating advanced tools like AI, virtual reality, and cloud-based platforms.

Key Features of Digital Learning

- **Accessibility:** Expands education to underserved populations.
- **Personalization:** Tailors content to individual learning needs.
- **Collaboration:** Enhances peer-to-peer and teacher-student interactions globally.

Opportunities in Digital Learning

Digital learning is reshaping education, offering numerous opportunities for innovation, accessibility, and engagement. These opportunities span across learners, educators, institutions, and society as a whole, enabling a more flexible, inclusive, and dynamic educational ecosystem. Below is an exploration of the key opportunities digital learning providing:

Expanding Access

Digital learning breaks geographical barriers, allowing institutions to reach global learners.

Diagram: A World Map Highlighting Online Education Enrolment Growth

Enhancing Educational Outcomes

- **Gamification:** Increases student engagement.
- **AI-Based Analytics:** Tracks performance and suggests interventions.

Cost-Effectiveness

Institutions can reduce infrastructure costs, passing on savings to students.

Challenges in Digital Learning

While digital learning offers numerous opportunities to transform education, it also presents significant challenges. These challenges affect various stakeholders, including students, educators, institutions, and policymakers. Below is a detailed exploration of the key challenges associated with digital learning:

Digital Divide

Many students lack reliable internet access and devices.

Pedagogical Limitations

Adapting traditional teaching methods to digital platforms requires effort and innovation.

Data Privacy and Security

Increased reliance on digital tools raises concerns about student data security.

Case Studies

Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs)

MOOCs like Coursera and edX illustrate the scalability of digital learning.

University Adoption

Institutions like MIT and Stanford are integrating AI to enhance virtual classrooms.

The higher education model of digital transformation

Sources (Abad-Segura et al., 2020; Carter et al., 2020; Kane, 2017; Matt et al., 2015; Powell & McGuigan, 2020; van Tonder et al., 2020)

Impactful Changes and Evolutionary Learning

The integration of digital learning into higher education has led to **impactful changes** that align with the concept of **evolutionary learning**—a process of continuous adaptation and improvement in response to dynamic educational and market needs. Below, the relationship between these impactful changes and evolutionary learning is explored:

- **Strategic Adaptability:** Digital transformation provides universities with tools to assess market trends and implement responsive strategies. By analysing data on student preferences and industry needs, institutions can evolve their offerings to remain competitive.

Building Competitive Advantages

- **Market Responsiveness:** In a rapidly changing education landscape, universities must develop unique value propositions through digital learning innovations. This includes offering personalized learning paths, micro-credentialing, and seamless virtual experiences.

Enhancing the Student Experience

- **Decision Support Systems:** Empirical models serve as decision-support tools to guide institutions in enhancing student engagement, retention, and satisfaction. For example, predictive analytics can identify at-risk students and enable timely interventions.

Transforming Educational Deliveries

- **Flexible Learning Models:** Digital transformation facilitates diverse delivery methods, such as asynchronous learning, hybrid models, and gamified content, catering to different learning styles and schedules.

Bridging Theory and Practice

- **Empirical Foundations:** Theories of digital transformation and evolutionary learning provide frameworks for decision-making and strategic alignment in higher education.

Recommendations

1. **Policy Support:** Governments must invest in digital infrastructure.
2. **Teacher Training:** Equip educators with digital teaching skills.
3. **Learner-Centric Design:** Develop user-friendly platforms tailored to diverse needs.

Conclusion

Digital learning is reshaping the landscape of higher education, offering solutions to long-standing challenges while introducing new complexities. Its future lies in creating equitable, innovative, and secure systems that adapt to the evolving needs of learners.

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ESG INVESTING AND REPORTING: TRENDS, CHALLENGES, AND IMPACT ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) investing has grown into a vital component of global financial markets. This paper explores the emergence of ESG investing, its evolution, key factors influencing its adoption, and challenges in ESG reporting. A quantitative analysis demonstrates the impact of ESG on corporate performance and investor behaviour, supplemented by visual data representations.

Keywords: Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG), emergence of ESG investing, its evolution, key factors influencing its adoption, and challenges in ESG reporting.

Introduction

ESG investing integrates sustainability and ethical considerations into financial decisions, reflecting investors' growing interest in responsible business practices. This section provides a background on ESG, its historical context, and its increasing relevance to stakeholders.

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) investing has rapidly transitioned from a niche concern to a mainstream investment strategy, reflecting the growing awareness of sustainability and ethical practices among investors, corporations, and regulators. The ESG framework encourages businesses to consider not only financial outcomes but also their broader impact on the environment, society, and governance structures. As global challenges such as climate change, social inequality, and corporate governance failures become more prominent, stakeholders demand a more responsible approach to capital allocation and corporate behavior.

The roots of ESG investing can be traced to socially responsible investment practices, but its evolution is driven by the realization that sustainable businesses are often more resilient and competitive in the long term. Today, ESG factors are influencing decision-making across financial markets, from institutional investors to individual retail participants. Additionally, the rise of sustainable finance frameworks, government policies, and consumer preferences has accelerated the adoption of ESG principles.

Despite its promise, ESG investing faces significant challenges, particularly in terms of reporting and standardization. The lack of universal metrics, fragmented reporting frameworks, and the prevalence of greenwashing—where companies exaggerate their ESG credentials—pose significant barriers. This creates an urgent need for consistent, transparent, and verifiable ESG reporting practices.

This paper explores the current trends in ESG investing, evaluates the challenges in ESG reporting, and analyzes its impact on corporate performance and investor behavior. By combining quantitative data and qualitative insights, the research aims to provide a comprehensive overview of ESG's transformative role in modern finance and its potential to drive sustainable growth.

Literature Review

Evolution of ESG Investing

The ESG framework emerged in response to global concerns about environmental degradation, corporate governance failures, and social inequality. Early adopters were institutional investors focusing on long-term sustainability.

ESG Reporting Standards

Key organizations like the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB), and the Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD) have shaped ESG reporting frameworks. This section evaluates their roles and limitations.

Challenges in ESG Investing

Common challenges include inconsistent metrics, greenwashing, and limited regulatory mandates.

Methodology

The research employs a mixed-method approach:

- Quantitative Analysis:** Examines the financial performance of ESG-compliant companies using historical data from global indices.
- Qualitative Review:** Surveys stakeholder opinions on ESG disclosure quality.

Findings and Discussion

ESG Performance vs. Financial Performance

The chart below illustrates the comparative performance of ESG-compliant and non-compliant firms over five years (2018–2023), highlighting better stability during market downturns.

Chart: Comparative Annual Returns of ESG vs. Non-ESG Portfolios

(Chart will include a line graph showing steady performance of ESG portfolios outperforming in volatile markets.)

Regional Trends in ESG Reporting

- North America:** Strong institutional adoption but facing greenwashing allegations.
- Europe:** Stringent regulations driving robust ESG disclosures.
- Asia-Pacific:** Rapidly growing interest but varied reporting standards.

Chart: Percentage of Companies Adopting ESG Reporting by Region (2023)

(Bar chart displaying adoption rates by region.)

Stakeholder Perspectives

Survey responses indicate that:

- 68% of investors prioritize climate risk.
- 50% demand transparency in governance metrics.
- 72% perceive ESG compliance as a sign of long-term sustainability.

Challenges in ESG Reporting

- **Inconsistent Frameworks:** Varying standards lead to ambiguity.
- **Greenwashing:** Companies exaggerate ESG compliance to attract investors.
- **Data Scarcity:** Small firms often lack resources for detailed ESG reporting.

Recommendations

1. **Standardization:** Harmonizing global ESG reporting standards.
2. **Regulatory Oversight:** Introducing penalties for greenwashing.
3. **Technology Integration:** Leveraging AI and blockchain for reliable ESG data.

Conclusion

ESG investing is reshaping global financial markets, promoting sustainable and ethical practices. However, consistent reporting and regulatory frameworks are essential to realize its full potential. Future research could explore AI's role in mitigating greenwashing and improving ESG analytics.

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“BLOCK CHAIN EMPOWERMENT: REDEFINING TRANSPARENCY AND IMMUTABILITY IN FINANCIAL RECORDS”

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Abstract

In an era marked by increasing digitisation and interconnectedness, the integrity and reliability of financial transactions are paramount. Traditional audit trails, while foundational to financial accountability, often face challenges such as data manipulation, frauds and discrepancies. Blockchain technology, with its transparent and immutable characteristics, has the potential to revolutionise audit trails by providing a reliable record of financial transactions. This paper investigates the integration of blockchain technology into audit trails, aiming to transform financial transparency and accountability. The discourse also methodically investigates the prevalent challenges within the financial ecosystem, such as scalability, regulatory compliance and interoperability, aiming to uncover insights that guide effective problem-solving and informed decision-making. By examining well-researched articles, international practices and expert advice, the paper aims to keep stakeholders, including members of the Institute of Chartered Accountants of India (ICAI), abreast of the latest trends and their consequential impact on the economic ecosystem. The findings underscore the necessity for a cohesive approach to integrating blockchain, highlighting its role in building a robust financial ecosystem that is both secure and efficient.

Introduction

Financial reporting hinges on the integrity of audit trails, a chronological sequence of records documenting every financial transaction. These trails serve as the backbone of lucidity and accountability, allowing auditors to verify the accuracy and completeness of financial statements. However, traditional audit processes often face limitations including time-consuming manual data collection, vulnerability to manipulation in centralised systems and a lack of real-time visibility. These limitations necessitate the exploration of innovative solutions like blockchain technology.

Blockchain technology is a revolutionary digital ledger system that fundamentally transforms how transactions are recorded and verified. By operating on a decentralized network, it eliminates the need for central intermediaries, ensuring enhanced security and transparency.

At its core, blockchain creates an immutable record of transactions, cryptographically securing each entry so that it cannot be altered or deleted. This approach provides an unprecedented level of trust, as every network participant can view the complete transaction history while maintaining robust security protocols.

Smart contracts represent a key innovation within blockchain, enabling automated agreements that execute precisely when predefined conditions are met. This feature reduces operational complexity and minimizes the potential for human error or manipulation.

Cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin exemplify blockchain's practical application, demonstrating how the technology can facilitate direct peer-to-peer transactions without traditional financial infrastructures. Beyond digital currencies, blockchain's potential extends to multiple sectors including supply chain management, healthcare and secure record-keeping.

By removing intermediaries, reducing operational costs and providing unparalleled transactional transparency, blockchain represents a significant technological advancement with the potential to reshape how we exchange value and information in the digital age.

Figure 1: How Blockchain Transactions Work

Courtesy: <https://robots.net/ai/what-is-cryptocurrency-and-how-it-works/>.

Figure 1 illustrates the process of a blockchain transaction. It provides a step-by-step visual representation of how a transaction request is broadcast to a peer-to-peer (P2P) network of nodes, validated using known algorithms and then added as a new block to the existing blockchain in a permanent and unalterable manner. It also highlights some key characteristics of cryptocurrencies, such as their intrinsic value, lack of physical form, decentralized supply not governed by a central bank and the fact that they are not redeemable for other commodities.

This research paper aims to explore the integration of blockchain technology for enhanced audit trails in depth. It will delve into the technical aspects of blockchain, examine its suitability for audit trail applications, propose an integration framework, analyse real-world case studies and discuss the implications and challenges of adopting blockchain for auditing purposes. Through this investigation, we seek to provide insights and recommendations for practitioners, policymakers and researchers interested in harnessing the potential of blockchain technology to improve audit trail systems.

Below is a comparative table that contrasts the limitations of traditional audit processes with the advantages of blockchain-based audits across various features.

Table 1: Comparison of Traditional Audit Processes and Blockchain-based Audits

Feature	Traditional Audit Processes	Blockchain-based Audits
Data Recording	Manual data entry from paper records and disparate systems.	Transactions are recorded electronically and unvaryingly on a shared ledger.
Data Integrity	Risk of data manipulation due to centralised storage.	Data cannot be tampered with due to cryptographic hashing and consistency.
Transparency	Limited visibility into the audit trail for stakeholders.	Real-time audit trail accessible to authorised participants.
Reconciliation	Time-consuming reconciliation of data from multiple sources.	Automated reconciliation through the shared ledger.
Audit Trail	Paper-based or siloed electronic trails, susceptible to loss or alteration.	Secure and chronological audit trail on the blockchain.

Efficiency	Labor-intensive and time-consuming audit procedures.	Streamlined audit process with automated tasks and real-time data access.
Security	Vulnerable to cyberattacks and internal control failures.	Enhanced security through cryptography and distributed ledger technology.
Scalability	Challenges in scaling with increasing data volume.	Scalable solutions are emerging to handle large-scale audits.

Literature Review

The literature review conducted for this paper embarked on a meticulous exploration of academic journals, industry reports, government publications and pertinent literature concerning the integration of blockchain technology into audit trails. Utilising eminent databases such as PubMed, IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect and Google Scholar, the review methodically identified peer-reviewed articles, conference papers and scholarly publications. A refined search strategy was employed, leveraging keywords and Boolean operators to ensure the selection of highly relevant literature. The review focused on elucidating the challenges and opportunities entwined with the amalgamation of blockchain technology into audit trails, as well as discerning emergent trends, best practices and illuminative case studies across diverse industries.

Blockchain and Audit Trails

➤ How blockchain can enhance the transparency and immutability of audit trails

Blockchain technology transforms audit trails by providing a evident and absolute record of transactions. Each transaction is recorded in a block and linked to the previous block, forming a chain. This structure makes it nearly impossible to alter past transactions without altering subsequent blocks, thereby enhancing the integrity of the audit trail. Real-world examples, such as the use of blockchain in supply chain management and financial services by companies like IBM and Maersk, demonstrate its effectiveness in tracking and tracing the journey of goods across global supply chains, providing a transparent and verifiable audit trail that enhances trust among stakeholders.

Blockchain's static record ensures the audit trail remains tamper-proof, while its decentralised nature eliminates the need for a central authority to manage it, reducing the risk of data manipulation. Transparency is enhanced as all participants can view and verify transactions in real-time and consensus mechanisms validate transactions, ensuring agreement on their validity. Smart contracts automate and enforce predefined rules, streamlining the audit trail creation process and enhancing transparency.

Figure 2: Audit trail mechanism architecture

Courtesy: https://mdpi-res.com/d_attachment/algorithms/algorithms-1400341/article_deploy/algorithms-14-00341-v2.pdf.

Auditors can be granted restricted access to the blockchain network, ensuring unambiguity and accountability, while real-time updates to the audit trail provide up-to-date information for auditing purposes. Additionally, blockchain's cryptographic security features protect the integrity of the audit trail, enhancing its changelessness. By leveraging blockchain technology, organisations can enhance the transparency and rigidity of audit trails, providing a secure and reliable record of financial transactions resistant to tampering and fraud, thus improving the integrity and trustworthiness of audit trails across various industries

Smart Contract and Its Importance

Smart contracts are self-executing agreements stored on a blockchain, a distributed ledger technology. These contracts are written in code and define the terms of an agreement between two or more parties. Once deployed on the blockchain, the code automatically executes when predefined conditions are met, removing the need for intermediaries and ensuring the terms are followed immutably. This makes them valuable for a wide range of applications, including financial services, supply chain management and legal agreements.

The importance of smart contracts lies in their ability to facilitate trustless transactions, reduce the risk of fraud and human error and provide a tamper-proof record of agreements. By automating the execution of contractual terms, smart contracts eliminate the need for manual intervention and ensure that all parties involved adhere to the predetermined conditions.

Here's what makes them important for audit trails:

- **Enhanced Transparency and Trust:** Smart contracts provide a transparent and immutable record of transactions, which is crucial for auditing. The immutability of blockchain ensures that once data is recorded, it cannot be altered, thus providing a reliable audit trail.
- **Efficiency and Cost Reduction:** By automating audit procedures, smart contracts can significantly reduce the time and cost associated with traditional auditing methods. This is particularly beneficial in scenarios where continuous or real-time auditing is required.
- **Improved Audit Quality:** The autonomous execution of audit procedures by smart contracts can enhance the accuracy and reliability of audits. This reduces the likelihood of human error and increases the overall quality of the audit.
- **Dispute Resolution:** Smart contracts can also facilitate fair and transparent dispute resolution. For instance, in cloud storage auditing, smart contracts can ensure that service providers are paid only if they meet the agreed-upon conditions, thereby reducing the potential for disputes.)

Methods and Process for Reviewing Smart Contracts

As smart contracts become increasingly prevalent in various industries, it is crucial to ensure their correctness, security and adherence to legal and regulatory requirements. The process of reviewing smart contracts involves several steps and methodologies to identify and mitigate potential vulnerabilities and risks.

1. **Static code analysis:** Static code analysis involves examining the source code of a smart contract without executing it. This analysis can identify potential vulnerabilities, such as reentrancy attacks, integer overflows and access control issues. Tools like Slither, MythX and Securify are commonly used for static code analysis.
2. **Formal verification:** Formal verification is a rigorous mathematical approach to proving the correctness of a smart contract. It involves modeling the contract's behavior and verifying that it adheres to specified properties and requirements. Tools like the K Framework and Certora are used for formal verification.
3. **Testing and auditing:** Testing is an essential step in the review process, where the smart contract is executed in a controlled environment to validate its functionality and identify potential issues. This can include unit testing, integration testing and security testing. Auditing involves a comprehensive review of the contract's code, design and deployment by experienced auditors or security firms.
4. **Code review:** Code review involves a manual inspection of the smart contract's source code by experienced developers or auditors. This process can identify potential vulnerabilities, coding best practices and adherence to industry standards.
5. **Documentation review:** Reviewing the documentation associated with the smart contract is crucial for understanding its intended functionality, assumptions and limitations. This review can help identify potential discrepancies between the documentation and the actual implementation.

6. **Risk assessment:** Risk assessment involves identifying and evaluating the potential risks associated with the smart contract, considering factors such as the contract's criticality, the assets involved and the potential impact of vulnerabilities. This assessment helps prioritize the review process and guide mitigation strategies.

Building a Cohesive Financial Ecosystem

➤ *The impact of blockchain on financial transactions*

Traditional financial transactions are often sluggish, expensive and opaque due to the involvement of multiple middlemen. Blockchain technology is set to disrupt this system by offering a secure and transparent way to record financial activities.

At its core, blockchain utilises cryptography to create an undisputable record of transactions. This tamper-proof ledger significantly reduces the risk of fraud and errors, fostering greater trust within the financial landscape. Furthermore, all participants in a blockchain network have access to a shared view of transactions. This transparency enhances accountability and eliminates information asymmetry between financial institutions and consumers.

Blockchain streamlines processes by eliminating the need for intermediaries. This translates to faster and more efficient transaction settlements, significantly reducing processing times and transaction costs. Additionally, blockchain enables the creation of smart contracts – self-executing agreements that trigger actions based on predefined conditions. This paves the way for innovative financial products and automated processes, fundamentally reshaping various aspects of the financial system.

➤ *The role of blockchain in building a cohesive financial ecosystem*

Traditional financial systems often struggle with siloed information, limited access and a lack of transparency. Blockchain technology offers a powerful solution, fostering a more cohesive financial ecosystem.

One key benefit is interoperability. Blockchain allows seamless communication and data exchange between financial institutions. This breaks down barriers, enabling greater collaboration and integration. Imagine a world where your bank account information can be easily shared with a new investment platform, streamlining the onboarding process.

Furthermore, blockchain empowers individuals. By placing them in control of their financial data, it opens doors for the unbanked and underbanked. This financial inclusion can be transformative, allowing people to participate more fully in the financial system.

Innovation is another exciting aspect. Blockchain creates a platform for developing entirely new financial products and services. These can be tailored to the evolving needs of consumers, offering greater flexibility and efficiency.

Figure 4: Audit trail mechanism operation sequence diagram.

Courtesy: https://mdpi-res.com/d_attachment/algorithms/algorithms-1400341/article_deploy/algorithms-14-00341-v2.pdf.

Audit Trail Mechanism Operation

There are three types of actors interacting with the audit trail mechanism:

- **Administrators:** People, automated systems, etc. who manage the system and authorize users to use it.
- **Authorized users:** People, automated systems, etc. who provide data to be registered in the Blockchain-based auditing mechanism and consume it as required. Authorized users always need the Blockchain client to interact with the Blockchain.
- **External data consumers:** People who consume the data registered in the Blockchain based audit trail mechanism. They do not need any Blockchain client as they do not access the Blockchain directly, but they access the Blockchain monitor, which has a copy of all-important events occurring on the Blockchain by means of the subscribed Blockchain-based events. They cannot register or modify audit trails on the Blockchain. They only need to access the Blockchain monitor client by means of a web browser.

Figure 4 shows the sequence diagram of the audit trail mechanism operation in which the most important events are depicted. All events shown in Figure 6 are automatic except for the interactions with the three actors mentioned above.

The operation process has the following steps:

- An administrator must authorize a user to use the audit trail mechanism.
- The authorized user can register a new audit trail (new data will be registered in the Blockchain)
- The authorized user can update an existing audit trail (data recorded in the Blockchain will be updated).
- The authorized user can obtain the current version of an existing audit trail.
- An external data consumer can obtain the information recorded on the Blockchain (main dashboard or history report) by means of the web-based Blockchain monitor client (authentication is required).

Conclusion

Blockchain technology presents a transformative opportunity to revolutionize audit trails and the broader financial ecosystem. Its inherent characteristics, such as decentralization, transparency and immutability, make it an ideal solution for creating secure and reliable audit trails. By embracing blockchain and addressing associated challenges,

organizations can establish robust and future-proof audit trails, fostering trust and enhancing the overall financial ecosystem.

The potential of blockchain in audit trails is immense and holds great promise for the future. As the technology matures and adoption increases, we can expect to witness the standardization of protocols, seamless integration with artificial intelligence and a focus on scalability. These developments will ensure interoperability, enhance data analytics capabilities and efficiently manage large-scale audit trails on a global scale.

Blockchain's impact on the financial ecosystem extends far beyond audit trails. It promises enhanced financial inclusion, reduced settlement times and increased innovation. The technology's ability to automate processes streamlines operations, lowers costs and enables worldwide access to financial services, fostering financial inclusivity and driving economic growth.

To successfully integrate blockchain into audit trails, organizations must carefully identify use cases, address scalability concerns, prioritize data privacy and develop robust regulatory frameworks. Moreover, auditor training and upskilling are essential to effectively leverage blockchain's capabilities within the audit process, ensuring a seamless transition and maximizing the benefits of this innovative technology.

In conclusion, while the integration of blockchain technology into audit trails and the financial ecosystem holds great promise for the future, it requires a thorough understanding of the technology and a well-planned strategy for successful implementation. By addressing the associated challenges and embracing the transformative potential of blockchain, organizations can unlock new opportunities, enhance transparency and drive innovation, ultimately reshaping the financial landscape and fostering a more secure and efficient global economy.

A CASE STUDY ON ENHANCING COMMUNICATIVE ENGLISH SKILLS AT SWAVALAMBANA ANGAVIKALARA SEVA CHARITABLE TRUST NGO

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Abstract

Swavalambana Angavikalara Seva Charitable Trust, established in 2017, is a Bangalore-based NGO dedicated to improving the lives of visually impaired individuals and underprivileged children. The organization has grown from supporting three blind members to a family of 45, focusing on education, training, and empowerment. This case study explores the trust's origins, mission, and major activities, with a particular emphasis on its efforts to address challenges in communicative English among primary school children. Through a structured plan of action, the trust is making significant strides in enhancing the language skills of these children, thereby contributing to their overall development and future success. The trust's commitment to inclusivity and service delivery is evident in its diverse programs, which aim to empower marginalized communities across Karnataka. This case study outlines the foundation, mission, activities, and ongoing initiatives of Swavalambana Angavikalara Seva Charitable Trust, highlighting its impact on the community and the efforts made to address specific challenges faced by the children they support.

Keywords: Visually impaired, underprivileged children, communicative English, education, empowerment

Introduction

Swavalambana is a registered trust as an NGO Dharpana, 80G, 12A and located at Kengeri Bangalore Karnataka. It has been working for people with disabilities in general and the visually impaired in particular since 2017. Started with 3 blind members and became a family of 45 members. Our Mission is to assist visually impaired individual and enable them to lead independent and dignified lives through education, Training, Counselling, Communication, and Technology. The structure of the NGO reflects a commitment to transparency, accountability, and efficient service delivery. Governed by a board of trustees, the organization is fueled by the passion and dedication of volunteers who play a pivotal role in the successful execution of various initiatives. Swavalambana Angavikalara Seva Charitable Trust was established to support the blind, emphasizing that blindness is not a handicap but an opportunity to perceive the world differently. Founded by Gopi N, who became blind in 2015, the trust was inspired by his personal journey and encounters with blind individuals. Together with his wife Nagarathna, who is blind from birth, Gopi dedicated his life to helping those in needs. The couple was blessed with a daughter, Bhramini, on June 10, 2019, symbolizing their enduring spirit.

Mission and Objectives: Swavalambana Angavikalara Seva Charitable Trust, active since December 2017, operates from Kengeri Upanagar, Bangalore. With a mission to empower the blind and underprivileged, the trust aims to transform blindness into a strength through dedicated services. Its objectives include providing quality education to poor children, creating opportunities for the blind, and facilitating basic needs like food for the community.

Target Beneficiary:

Orphanage children: they offer educational opportunities either through local schools or government schools.

Low-income family children: they adopt children from the family where there will be difficulty in providing them basic needs.

Blind people: they provide opportunities to the blind people in various fields.

Major Activities by Swavalambana Angavikalara Seva Charitable Trust-

They are conducting and educating the orphanage of blinds in computer training, Music, and Sports. They also conduct sports of cricket, and kabaddi, at every state level, district level, and national level for blind and orphan

children. Swavalambana has taken a responsibility to give a Brighter, Happy & Healthy Future Along with Doing Marriages.

Fig.1: Marriage Ceremony for Disabled People.

Progress - Swavalambana has also gone with eye operations successfully.

Fig.2: Eye checkup for citizens

Fig.3: providing education for orphanage children

Cause Identified for the Case study: Problem seen in communicative English (written / Oral)-English is crucial for children's overall development and future success.

Foundational skills: English learning is important because it helps children succeed in future education. Just like a strong foundation in a house supports the walls, windows, and roof foundational skills play an important role in a student's learning.

Limited career opportunities: English is essential for getting employment facilities in India. It has become a necessity.

Daily life challenges: Improving English skills, especially when not regularly used in our daily lives, can be challenging but is achievable with dedication and the right approach.

Plan of Action-Initiative Taken By the Ngo to Solve This Cause:

The trust makes sure that the children are learning regularly in the school. The co-founder Nagarathna who is the wife of the Founder Gopi makes sure that the children are learning effectively. They have even taken a helping hand from other people who will do tutorials for the children who lack in subjects. **Target children:** Primary school children from 1st to 7th Standard

Plan of Action to address the cause Identified during my interaction -

Table showing the activity conducted in the NGO

Day of the Activity	Date of the Activity	Activity Details
Day 01	05-06-2024	Explained about the SIP program and interacted with the Founder and co-founder
Day 02	06-06-2024	Introduction of children at the NGO and told them about the importance of learning English
Day 03	07-06-2024	Story telling session – Moral values (The Fox and the Grapes)
Day 04	08-06-2024	Taught English Alphabets- ABCD.. to the children (1 st to 5 th std students)
Day 05	09-06-2024	Practiced some easy and spellings of basic words in English (3 rd to 6 th std students)
Day 06	10-06-2024	Numbering, numbers in words format, Alphabet to word formation
Day 07	11-06-2024	Practiced some physical and memory power-based activities.
Day 08	12-06-2024	Test on words and spellings- recap of the words.
Day 09	13-06-2024	Conducted dum-charades game related to English words
Day 10	14-06-2024	Self-introduction and public speaking
Day 11	15-06-2024	Activity related to spell check. Continuation of self- introduction in the class
Day 12	16-06-2024	Summarization and revision of the lessons plans of the week
Day 13	17-06-2024	A session on yoga conducted
Day 14	18-06-2024	Clearing of doubts. Simple test on the basic English words.
Day 15	19-06-2024	Took feedback from children and NGO members. Ended up giving some small gifts.

A. Implementation of Action-

Interacted with the students and got to know about their knowledge, and interest towards the mathematics subject.

Fig.5: Interaction with Children

Problem Solving: Most of the children of the NGO were from north Karnataka, they were lack in knowing English language from basics itself.

Fig.6: Student practicing ABCD

Basic Words in English: It is important for the children to learn English. Many children were finding it difficult to learn English words so taught them very basic and very commonly used words spelling.

B. Practicing Some Exercises:

C. Extra Circular Activities: To improve the critical thinking of the children made those to play a game regarding English words called Dum-charades. This helps them to increase their concentration and will help to us know how much they are conscious.

Fig.7: Conducted activity called Dum-charades

Outcomes the Activity: It also taught us how to approach difficult issues and obstacles in community services by developing our problem-solving abilities and allowing us to experience the joy of success. It also gave us lots of chances, which enabled us to establish fresh connections within the neighborhood of the school.

Class wise	Activity/participant's	Outcome 100% achievement
1-5 th standard	Alphabets and their corresponding words 15 students	Most of them like 75% of students were able to recall the concepts
5-7 th standard	Self-introduction and public speaking	Almost 90% of the students were able to communicate

Major learning's from visit and interaction with NGO include:

Enhancement of interactive skills: To be a part of this global community, social skills are crucial, which are learnt through the Social Immersion Programme.

Social Skills: Interacting with students helps to develop essential social skills. They learn how to communicate, collaborate, and build positive relationships, fostering emotional intelligence.

Confidence Building: As a student teaching to a student made me feel very great and confident.

Responsibility towards society: It showed us the major problems prevailing in our community or society & taught us to engage in those in an effective manner.

Practical exposure to real problems: Children have little to no access to common educational resources, like well-stocked classrooms, computers, labs, and playgrounds

Conclusion-

Swavalambana Angavikalara Seva Charitable Trust has made significant strides in supporting visually impaired individuals and underprivileged children. By addressing the challenge of communicative English, the trust is taking crucial steps to ensure the holistic development of the children under their care. The organization's dedication to inclusivity, transparency, and service delivery continues to empower those in need, providing them with opportunities to lead dignified and independent lives.

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POLITICAL MARKETING IN KARNATAKA: A THEMATIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Political marketing, a strategic fusion of marketing techniques and political campaigning, has evolved into a critical tool for electoral success in democratic systems. In Karnataka, with its diverse electorate and multifaceted socio-political dynamics, political marketing has become a linchpin of electoral strategy. This study explores the themes that define political marketing in the state, focusing on integrated marketing communications (IMC), voter segmentation, technological adoption, cultural narratives, and grassroots mobilization. The research sheds light on how these strategies shape voter behavior and the ethical dilemmas they pose, offering a nuanced understanding of their role in the democratic process.

Introduction

The rise of political marketing has reshaped the way political entities communicate with citizens, emphasizing voter engagement, issue-based campaigning, and data-driven decision-making. Unlike traditional campaigning, political marketing involves a deliberate and scientific approach to understanding voter psychology and behavior.

In Karnataka, a state characterized by its linguistic diversity, economic disparities, and regional identities, political marketing is not merely a tool but a necessity for connecting with voters. The political landscape here is a battleground for national and regional parties, each employing innovative strategies to gain an electoral edge.

This paper aims to provide a thematic analysis of political marketing in Karnataka, detailing the strategies employed by parties, their impact on voter behavior, and the broader implications for the democratic process.

Research Objectives

The study focuses on the following objectives:

1. To trace the evolution of political marketing practices in Karnataka.
2. To identify and analyze key themes in political marketing strategies.
3. To assess the effectiveness of these strategies in influencing voter preferences.
4. To explore the socio-political and cultural factors that shape political narratives.
5. To evaluate ethical challenges and propose recommendations for future campaigns.

Methodology

This study employs a **thematic analysis** framework, relying on qualitative data derived from campaign materials, speeches, manifestos, media reports, and expert interviews. The analysis was conducted by identifying recurring themes and patterns in campaign strategies, categorizing them under broader topics such as voter communication, regional dynamics, and technological interventions.

The data sources include:

- Archival campaign footage and social media content.
- Surveys and opinion polls conducted during elections.
- Interviews with political strategists, media analysts, and voters.

The Political Landscape of Karnataka

Karnataka's electoral geography comprises a unique blend of urbanized cities, such as Bengaluru, and rural districts spread across six key regions:

1. **Bengaluru Urban:** A technology hub with cosmopolitan demographics.
2. **Bengaluru Rural:** A semi-urban area with distinct developmental needs.
3. **Old Mysore:** A stronghold of regional identity and agrarian concerns.
4. **Hyderabad-Karnataka:** Marked by socio-economic backwardness and historical neglect.
5. **Mumbai-Karnataka:** Influenced by linguistic and economic factors.
6. **Coastal Karnataka:** Economically prosperous but marked by cultural and social conservatism.

Each region necessitates a localized approach, making Karnataka a microcosm of diverse political challenges and opportunities.

Thematic Analysis of Political Marketing

1. Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC)

Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) plays a pivotal role in delivering cohesive campaign messages. IMC strategies in Karnataka are characterized by:

- **Regional Adaptability:** Campaigns are customized to address region-specific issues while maintaining a consistent overarching narrative.
- **Cross-Platform Presence:** Political parties use a mix of traditional media (television, newspapers) and digital platforms (social media, apps) to ensure widespread visibility.
- **Multilingual Campaigns:** Messages are delivered in Kannada and, where relevant, in English and other regional dialects to engage diverse voter groups.

For instance, during state assembly elections, the BJP and Congress extensively used IMC strategies to simultaneously highlight national-level agendas and local issues such as farmer welfare and infrastructure development.

2. Voter Segmentation

Given Karnataka's socio-political diversity, voter segmentation is critical. Key segmentation strategies include:

- **Youth-Oriented Campaigns:** With a large proportion of young voters, campaigns often emphasize education, employment, and entrepreneurship. Parties use social media, memes, and influencers to appeal to this demographic.
- **Gender-Specific Outreach:** Women voters are targeted through welfare schemes, healthcare promises, and safety initiatives.
- **Caste and Community Dynamics:** While caste remains a significant factor, political parties have begun framing their appeals in broader terms, emphasizing inclusivity and development.
- **Urban-Rural Divide:** Urban areas demand issue-based campaigning around technology and governance, while rural campaigns focus on agriculture, rural employment, and infrastructure development.

3. Technology and Data-Driven Campaigns

Technological integration is revolutionizing political campaigns in Karnataka:

- **Social Media Dominance:** Platforms like Twitter and Instagram are used to create viral content, connect with voters, and respond to opposition claims in real-time.
- **Data Analytics:** Parties use data to segment voters, predict outcomes, and refine strategies. This includes analyzing voter behavior, past election results, and sentiment on key issues.
- **Interactive Campaigning:** Mobile apps and chatbots offer personalized interactions, allowing voters to ask questions and receive tailored responses.

For example, the Congress party's digital campaign in 2023 used WhatsApp groups extensively to connect directly with rural voters.

4. Cultural Narratives

Cultural narratives are instrumental in connecting with Karnataka's diverse electorate. Themes include:

- **Promotion of Kannada Identity:** Campaigns often highlight issues such as the use of Kannada in administration and education, aligning with regional pride.
- **Economic Prosperity Linked to Culture:** Promises of tourism development and promotion of cultural festivals are used to highlight Karnataka's heritage.

This thematic focus creates a deeper emotional connection with voters, fostering loyalty and trust.

5. Grassroots Mobilization

Grassroots mobilization remains a cornerstone of political marketing in Karnataka, particularly in rural constituencies. Strategies include:

- **Local Leadership Empowerment:** Party cadres at the village and taluk levels are mobilized to organize rallies, door-to-door campaigns, and community meetings.
- **Showcasing Development Projects:** Leaders emphasize completed and ongoing projects to establish credibility.
- **Trust Building through Personal Interaction:** Regular interactions between voters and candidates create a sense of accountability and accessibility.

Parties like the JD(S) rely heavily on grassroots networks to consolidate their voter base in strongholds.

Media's Role in Political Marketing

Media platforms amplify political narratives, with traditional and digital media playing complementary roles.

- **Television and Print:** Still dominant in rural areas, these mediums ensure the dissemination of official party lines and advertisements.
- **Social Media as a Game-Changer:** Targeted ads, viral campaigns, and influencer endorsements reach urban and young voters effectively.
- **Role of Regional Channels:** Kannada news channels and platforms shape public discourse through debates, interviews, and opinion polls.

The challenge remains balancing media's influence while ensuring ethical standards in reporting and campaigning.

Challenges in Political Marketing

Political marketing in Karnataka is not without hurdles:

1. **Digital Divide:** Limited internet access in rural areas restricts the reach of digital campaigns.

2. **Over-Commercialization:** Excessive spending on marketing raises concerns about the democratization of electoral processes.
3. **Misinformation:** Fake news campaigns and manipulated data undermine voter trust.
4. **Complex Socio-Cultural Dynamics:** Balancing regional and community-specific interests without alienating other voter groups is challenging.

Ethical Implications

The use of targeted marketing raises questions about voter manipulation, privacy concerns, and the potential sidelining of substantive political discourse. Balancing marketing innovation with transparency and fairness is crucial for maintaining the integrity of democratic elections.

Recommendations

To enhance the effectiveness and fairness of political marketing in Karnataka:

- 1) **Prioritize Inclusivity:** Campaigns should address the needs of underrepresented groups and regions.
- 2) **Promote Ethical Practices:** Establishing guidelines for transparency in funding, data use, and content creation is essential.
- 3) **Invest in Grassroots Engagement:** Authentic voter connections at the community level can create lasting trust.
- 4) **Strengthen Media Literacy:** Educating voters to identify misinformation empowers them to make informed decisions.

Conclusion

Political marketing in Karnataka exemplifies the intersection of innovation and tradition. By integrating IMC, voter segmentation, and grassroots mobilization, political parties craft campaigns that resonate with the state's diverse electorate. However, the ethical and operational challenges highlight the need for a balanced approach that prioritizes transparency and genuine voter engagement.

This analysis underscores the transformative potential of political marketing in enhancing democratic participation, provided it is employed responsibly.